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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

(accepted papers)

4

Prominent and least studied – Theorizing reputational risk in the supply chain

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Reputational risks are less commonly studied in PSM research, yet they are said to be amongst the most material for a company. This paper aims to improve the conceptualization of reputational risks and contribute to the development of risk management theory. Reputational risk is found to be multi-faceted, impactful, and sizable when considered in a supply chain context. A reputational risk can rapidly work its way up and down the extended supply chain with spillover effects and reputational borrowing. Industry effects and profiles in the supply chain are among the contingencies to consider when quantifying the duration and intensity of reputational damages.

Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience

A Maturity Framework for Enhancing End-to-End Supply Chain Visibility: A Systematic Literature Review and Extended Resource-Based View.

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Abstract

In an increasingly complex and interconnected global economy, the demand for achieving end-to-end (E2E) supply chain visibility (SCV) has grown significantly, as it is crucial for driving sustainable growth and resilience. The ramifications of the increasing global supply chain disruptions, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, atrocious natural disasters, and escalating geopolitical conflicts around the world, have heightened the pressure on supply chain managers where they can no longer focus on internal operations or supply-side efficiencies. Organizations must reconfigure their supply chain structures and strategies to maintain a competitive edge, ensuring seamless technological integration across the entire supply chain. Ultimately, it is essential for companies to achieve a comprehensive understanding of E2ESCV capabilities and to manage processes collaboratively and mitigate risks, creating greater value for all ecosystem partners. Following the abductive approach and qualitative strategy, this research adopted a systematic literature review (SLR) to identify the compartments of E2ESCV. The content analysis results have led to the development of an E2ESCV maturity framework, providing valuable guidance for supply chain managers and PSM professionals to enhance end-to-end visibility, improve decision-making, and strengthen the collaborative supply chain.

Introduction

Achieving end-to-end supply chain visibility (E2ESCV) has been a longstanding challenge, with information flows often fragmented and limited. The loss of visibility and control over long distances in chains creates inefficiencies and increased risks. This issue is compounded by the interdependence of supply chain ecosystems, making collaboration and data sharing across entities difficult.

In recent years, modern supply chain management focuses on integrating advanced technologies and collaborative platforms to enhance visibility in critical areas, such as sales and operations planning (S&OP). However, achieving E2ESCV requires more than a single platform; it needs a combination of technologies that create a control towers like in the supply chains to have real-time data visibility and identify risks in advance which optimise effective decision-making for overall supply chain performance.

Companies attempting to achieve unprecedented levels of visibility, therefore, need to break through internal boundaries and apply a holistic E2ESCV maturity framework to achieve ecosystem synchronisation.

Methodology

This study follows the abductive approach and qualitative strategy, adopting systematic literature review (SLR) to explore the key characteristics, enablers, and barriers to achieve E2ESCV. The SLR provides comprehensive and rigorous overview of existing research, as well as identify gaps and synthesise insights. The selections of key parameters were determined, including Language (English), Publication period (the last 10 years), Subject Areas (Engineering/ Business, Management and Accounting / Computer Science), and Literature type (Journal, and Book chapter). The key words were constructed for search strings and search engines to indicate the location of the studies as follows: "Supply chain visibility", "Supply chain transparency", "End-to-end visibility", "Information sharing", "Digitisation", "Digitalisation, and "Industry 4.0". The Boolean search strings were then used in the selected search engine databases to establish the search criteria, which helped the author locate the scope finding and evaluate the contributing literature to answer the research questions. The SLR used three main academic research databases, including ABI/INFORM Global or ProQuest (260 articles), Scopus (260 articles), and Web of Science (246 articles) to cover as much literature as possible to provide a comprehensive systematic review. Through the structured of screening and evaluation process, 98 articles were selected for full-text content analyses and synthesis, providing the foundation for the development of an E2ESCV maturity framework.

Findings

The content analysis revealed three main dimensions critical to develop a E2ESCV maturity framework: key characteristics, enablers, and barriers. The **key characteristics** identified 16 attributes which can be grouped into four main characteristics: Visibility, Control, Connectivity, and Automation. 'Visibility' is the first step towards enhancing data visibility and accessibility along with real-time monitoring on products and events across cross-functional activities, 'Control' capabilities refer to the ability to analyse risks and control supply chain processes which may work collaboratively with closed-tier ecosystem partners.. 'Connectivity' refers to the ability to tailor the bridges between different processes and systems with external partners through the facilitation of digital technologies. Finally, 'Automation' refers to stage that all the processes and systems are fully synchronised and fully adopted of advanced technologies. These key characteristics imply the evolution stages of achieving E2ESCV, which can be referred to as the **maturity stages**. The **key enablers** can be classified into four main groups, namely People, Process, Technology, and Data. Companies need to prioritise and achieve these four enablers to achieve each maturity level and progress forward to achieve E2ESCV. The **challenges** identified and comprised into six groups, namely social and culture, business process, information utilisation, technology maturity, structure, and legal. These challenges will be taken into consideration and evaluated the impact at each maturity level to help practitioners provide the proactive strategies in order to streamline the SCCT implementation process

Development of the E2ESCV concept and maturity framework

The findings from the SLR analysis were instrumental in developing the E2ESCV maturity framework, which proposed as a standard guideline for understanding the different requirements at each stage and to assess and enhance their visibility capabilities to structure a roadmap from basic transparency to fully integrated, real-time visibility, offering practical guidance for supply chain managers seeking to mitigate risks and drive sustainable performance.

Since implementing E2ESCV typically expands from an inside-out implementation, where companies initial assess the readiness of their internal operations and identify the requirements to achieve the expected goal level. Therefore, each maturity level is underpinned by the four key antecedents (People,

Process, Technology, Data) - alongside the six identified challenges of E2ESCV had been contributed in this framework for a more comprehensive assessment.

Some characteristics can be developed in each construct at each maturity level based on the sub-dimensions of the associated constructs. For instance, “**People**” dimension is related to inter-organisational collaboration, trust relationships, top management support, culture adaption, and skill and knowledge. Thus, at the stage of “**visibility**” maturity level, these sub-dimensions are very poor, which implies a lack of skills and knowledge, high operational silos, representing low in trust relationships and closed organisational culture. It related to the corresponding dimensions of “**process**” to have low collaboration and coordination between operational functions and a basic level of “**technology**” that enables information sharing and communication between internal functions and partially shares “**data**” among a few closed relationship partners.

The ultimate level of E2ESCV maturity is “automation”, where the characteristics are completely opposite from the initial stage of “visibility” level. At this level, the “people” dimension implies high collaborative support and coordination between different entities across the extending supply chain network through a high level of inter-organisational trust where “processes” are connected, providing a unified view of the whole supply chain operations across the global, and “technology” implies the well synchronisation of a system-of-systems, while “data” can be openly accessed, shared, and processed to create a new shared value among supply chain ecosystems. In between these two levels, there are other two maturity stages that represent the collective improvements towards the advanced levels. These are “control” and “connectivity” maturity levels, which are also based on the key antecedent dimensions. Consequently, the characteristics of each maturity level are developed in this manner as the collective goals, while each dimension of key antecedents is representing as the characteristic’s conductor.

The framework proposed herein provides clear definitions of the underlying constructs and a robustness of how the constructs were developed sequentially. The characteristics at each level facilitate a clear understanding of how they build interrelated relationship. As a result, this framework makes it possible for SC managers who interested in improving E2ESCV understand how E2ESCV maturity strategy could be developed.

Conclusion

This study not only identifies the scope of E2ESCV capabilities but also proposes a conceptual framework to help businesses progress towards achieving synchronised connectivity and enhancing visibility across the entire supply chains. The analysis, based on a systematic review of 98 papers, establishes core constructs necessary for developing an effective E2ESCV framework. This framework serve as a valuable self-assessment tool for companies, helping them evaluate their current readiness and identify areas for improvement. The integration of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and digital twins, along with effective data-sharing strategies, present promising avenues for future research on upscaling businesses towards E2ESCV. Overall, the continuous development and application of the E2ESCV framework will enhance PSM practices, enabling businesses to meet the evolving demands of global supply chains.

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 11. Digital

6

Buyer ownership and supplier sustainability-oriented innovation.

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This study investigates how buyer ownership structure influences supplier risk-taking, sustainability goals, and adoption of sustainability-oriented innovation (SOI), in agri-food supply chains. Using expected utility theory and transaction cost economics, we analyze data from Dutch arable farms through logit and ordinal regressions. While buyer ownership does not significantly affect SOI or risk-taking, cooperatives demonstrate higher sustainability goals. Additionally, a positive correlation between risk-taking and SOI is identified. Our findings contribute to the existing literature on supply chain sustainability and offer insights for practitioners and policymakers on promoting SOI and advancing sustainability goals in agri-food supply chains.

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.), 10. Purchasing innovation

A Network Approach to Scope 3 Emissions

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

Scope 3 emissions account for the majority of a company's greenhouse gas emissions. Despite their oversized representation in a company's emissions profile, data quality and coverage issues make Scope 3 accounting a convoluted exercise. This paper makes several contributions. First, we develop a methodology that uses Scope 1 and 2 emissions, as well as mathematical properties of complex networks, to estimate a company's upstream and downstream emissions. Second, we present an analytical framework to assess errors that occur when the assumptions of our model do not hold. Third, we derive a second version of our model that adds flexibility to the data requirements needed in the first derivation of our model. Finally, we apply our model to a sample of production networks, contrasting results from our calculations with Scope 3 emissions figures reported by companies in our sample.

Our model is constructed under the reasoning that, in a closed economy, a company's indirect emissions result from the direct emissions of clients, partners, and suppliers in the supply chain. As a result, calculating indirect emissions can be reframed as a question of attribution of direct emissions in a client-supplier network. This fact informs the two assumptions needed for constructing our model: First, we assume that we have complete knowledge of business-to-business (B2B) transactions among firms in a client-supplier network. Second, we assume that we observe all Scope 1 and 2 emissions of the companies in this network. We argue that combining the information embedded in the structure of B2B transactions with emissions data can provide a reasonable estimation of a company's supply chain emissions.

This initial derivation of our model represents the ideal case where transaction network data and environmental data are fully available. For this reason, we refer to this as the *Full Information* scenario. Unfortunately, the conditions for this scenario are seldom achieved in practice. Because of this, we introduce an error analysis formula that quantifies the error for indirect emissions accounting when our assumptions are no longer valid. The breakdown of our assumptions also motivates a second, less strict version of the model. In this second version, we relax the requirement of knowing the values of all B2B transactions between companies. Instead, this requirement is simplified to a binary Yes or No indicator of whether two companies are engaged in a commercial transaction.

Two main implications arise from this change of definition. In the *Full Information* scenario, the B2B transaction data was used to assign the weight to each client (supplier) represented in a company's downstream (upstream) emissions. Since the information on B2B data is replaced by a binary indicator, this will result in all clients (suppliers) receiving an equal weight in our calculations. Because of this equal weighting, we refer to this case as the *Naïve Scenario*. On the other hand, since client and supplier disclosure data is much more ubiquitous than B2B transaction values, this change results in a considerable expansion in the number of companies in our sample of production network data.

In the final sections of our paper, we present results from an empirical application of our methodology on two datasets: FactSet Supply Chain Relationships for production network data and Trucost for data on Scope 1, 2, and 3 emissions. Our sample includes company data from 2010 until 2021 and produces two main results. First, we find a very high correlation when comparing the results of the *Full Information* and *Naïve* scenarios. This result has important implications since it indicates that the more flexible, applicable, *Naïve* scenario provides a reasonable estimate for the more robust *Full Information* scenario. Second, we apply the *Naïve* model to our complete sample. When comparing these results to the reported Scope 3 figures in Trucost, our calculations generate larger estimates in more than 60% of instances. Because of the high correlation between both scenarios, this 60% figure may indicate that the more accurate *Full Information* scenario might produce a similar result.

The increasing relevance of Scope 3 emissions in the transition to a sustainable economy clashes with the high logistical and economic costs required to measure Scope 3 emissions. These costs represent a major challenge for firms, investors, and regulators, and the challenges in measuring these emissions may require that methodological contributions be developed in order to tackle this complex task. This paper aims to make a methodological contribution that standardizes the data required to calculate value chain emissions. These data are more readily available to businesses, which can be retroactively applied to assess the evolution in Scope 3 over time and which produces results that are comparable across different companies.

Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 5. Supplier selection

Quantity at the expense of quality: A comparative perspective of “Technical” and “arm-chair” stakeholders and the management of periodic road maintenance of community roadworks contract projects in DLGs in Uganda: A qualitative Analysis of results

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The qualitative study addresses the interface between technical and roadusers' personnel (the “arm-chair” auditors) in addressing varying stakeholder opinions regarding the quality of community roadworks and the efforts in minimising procurement performance expectations gap, from a stakeholder's perspective, creating a trade-off. The scarcity of roadworks resources has led to massive customisations of road designs, thus affecting quality of output, yet at the same time roadusers are demanding quality roads. The trade-off arises when customisation focuses on more volume, amidst better quality roads, which could not be balanced. The study was guided by the research question: How do the different stakeholders with different needs, interests and expectations, perceive and interpret the quality and volume of completed roadworks contracts and expenditures in District Local Governments (DLG) in Uganda? Findings indicate that despite efforts by technical personnel in executing high volume of community roadworks, the roadusers feel they are not highly satisfied with the quality and this mix of quantity -quality trade-off has created mixed reactions in the minds of stakeholders. The implications of this study clearly show that despite the technical personnel's perception that the “arm-chair” auditors' opinions might be grossly wrong, their subjective opinions must also be respected in order to have a wholistic community roadworks acceptance.

Paper topic

13. Public procurement, 1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 17. Sustainability - social

11

Brokering organisations and supplier diversity – achieving a morally incentivised approach to procurement

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Summary: Supplier diversity (SD) is a growing research area yet dominated by US and silo studies of key areas, e.g. gender or disability. Data from three extensive narrative interviews with leading brokering firms working in the UK, show that although brokering firms have a key role in supporting greater diversity in both buying and supplier firms through education, training and mentorship, challenges include existing corporate processes, translation of programmes beyond US contexts and digital-media/AI barriers in reaching other diverse businesses. Positively, corporate buyers are assessed by brokering organisations as being ethically or morally incentivised in supporting SD.

Paper topic

17. Sustainability - social, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 5. Supplier selection

Multi-criteria optimization: Integrating order quantity and supplier selection toward resilient supply chain management

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Supply chain management (SCM) has evolved drastically over the last few years, becoming more complex as SC managers increasingly realize that maximizing profit does not equate to the most satisfactory result. Part of its complexity is reflected in the trade-offs that are inherent to SC managers' decisions, from classical weighting strategies (between service level optimization versus cost reduction, for example) to more subtle issues such as the possibility of a bullwhip effect as a resulting impact of their orders to their suppliers' forecasts. Alongside the problem of order-quantity decision-making, also lies the dilemma of supplier selection, since purchasers must address a variety of additional trade-offs encompassing operational factors (e.g., cost lead time and reliability) and an increasing trend of environmental concerns (such as carbon footprint) As a result, decision-making within the SCM domain cannot be accounted for by merely human intuition, thus calling for the support of additional methods based on distinguished areas of decision theory. On the one hand, the inherent trade-offs within the multitude of relevant variables call for multi-criteria decision-making. On the other hand, the domain is far too complex to be resolved without intensive computational support and the active search for a robust set of data-driven solutions to provide ever-so-important resilience to supply chains.

Within recent literature, robust optimization is defined as the optimization technique that deals with uncertain variables by only looking at intervals without a need for further distributional information. This way the method can produce results irrespective of the true underlying distribution that generates the data. Robust optimization offers the advantage of computational tractability compared to alternative scenario generation methods. Its independence from demand distribution assumptions makes the robust optimization approach well-suited for inventory control applications under demand uncertainty. However classic models do not account for the inherent complexity of supply chain management, to better suit this demand the stochastic programming modeling of uncertainty can be enhanced by integrating the interaction between optimization decisions and the process of information discovery. Thus, decision-dependent uncertainty can be used as the main optimization model employed. Decision-dependent uncertainty consists of a class of problems where decisions are optimized over a time horizon under uncertainty, and such decisions influence the time of information discovery for a subset of the uncertain parameters. In other words, it is akin to a robust optimization problem approach where a series of sequential decisions affect not only one another but also the uncertainty surrounding the next decision. Various SCM factors such as cash flow, stock levels, machinery capacity, workforce,

and logistics are inherently decision-dependent, despite this, decision-dependent uncertainty has rarely been used in SCM problems.

From the seldom uses of decision-dependent uncertainty within the supply chain literature, some impressive results were obtained regarding resilience, in a problem of supply chain design, where the uncertainty was constrained by the decisions of where the location of the facilities should be and their optimal capacity. Selecting resilience as the objective function, the formulation proved efficient in reducing the bullwhip effect.

Despite all its benefits, robust optimization has inherent limitations for the supply chain domain, due to the various trade-offs present in any individual optimization variable selected to be optimized for be it profit, cost, service level, resilience, or any other, it is impossible to capture results where the trade-offs would be seen as more aligned with the company goals, this is the main problem of applying mono-criteria decision-making techniques and sets of constraints for unacceptable outcomes in the remaining relevant factors.

The supply chain management endeavor is concerned with multiple diverging aspects, and therefore trade-offs are inherent to its nature, multi-criteria decision-making is extremely effective in dealing with trade-offs. Therefore, a multi-criteria approach makes itself a solid candidate to assist as decision support for supply chain management decisions. Applying a multi-criteria approach consists of basically two steps, first, the relevant criteria must be defined and weighted, and the second step is about defining the ranking algorithm, thus the most satisfactory alternative can be selected by simply intuiting the data. However, there are some limitations to this approach, despite usually being computationally efficient, the more modern methods such as Viktor improve their robustness by the inclusion of more alternatives the method itself cannot create the alternatives nor integrate the consequences of certain choices, and how that interferes with the criteria, in other words, it depends on the information inputted to generate scenarios, therefore the method cannot guarantee optimality in its satisfaction function, there is a lack of capacity to capture the optimal satisfactory solution.

Note that both areas are extremely complementary, the directional optimization and capability to generate the input for derivative criteria is present in decision-dependent uncertainty robust optimization, and the trade-offs are properly dealt with using multi-criteria decision-making. The combination of these approaches, however, is far from trivial.

This paper proposes multi-criteria optimization (MCO), a novel concept for improving resilience along a supply chain, by combining multi-criteria decision-making with robust optimization. In addition, we designed a framework that encompasses MCO to support SC managers in their purchasing decisions.

An important step in any multicriteria approach is to normalize the scale of its variables, however, once introduced to an optimization model the same variables cannot be used as a normalizing component due to their everchanging values within the code.

As a solution for the integration, the framework for multi-criteria optimization proposes a sequential solution, sub-sets of optimization problems will be run to find the maximum and minimum values of each criterion by having them as the objective function. Once the extremes are defined the real problem can be implemented using the output of the weighting algorithm as the objective function for the final robust optimization problem, this way scenarios can be generated efficiently, dealing with the

complexity and trade-offs of supply chain management. This enables the optimization for multi-criteria satisfaction, therefore generating robust solutions optimized for the company's strategic goals.

Despite the mostly theoretical and model-heavy presentation so far, the application is extremely practical as will be demonstrated by the three situations addressed by the framework: Order quantity problems, supplier selection problems, and overall satisfaction.

Order quantity decisions are the most direct application, by using the uncertainty associated with the demand and the relevant criteria such as profit, cost, service level, on-time delivery, cash flow, and the bullwhip effect. Supplier selection is an ever-growing concern of purchasers, this activity is far from trivial, since there are concerns that go beyond expected lead time and cost, it is crucial to consider the reliability of the delivery and the environmental impact as well (with proxies such as carbon footprint), this new optimization technique allows for the optimization aiming for the maximum satisfaction considering the weight given to each criterion.

The interesting contribution of these two analyses is the decision-dependent nature of how they affect one another, an agent could select the supplier first, with criteria such as lead time, cost, carbon footprint, and reliability to further decide how much to order or decide on the order quantity to then decide on the supplier composition to fulfill it. Therefore, the problems are intertwined and in theory, should be solved simultaneously until the optimal or most satisfactory solution can be reached iteratively, using the solution of the previous iteration of one problem as the basis for the next iteration of the second problem alternating the objective function. The problems are intertwined, the cost is determined by the supplier selection solution and the order quantity to be distributed among the suppliers comes from the order quantity solution, thus overall satisfaction can be calculated by solving the best pairwise solution of both sub-problems (order quantity, supplier selection)

Once the three previous problems are structured it is possible to solve the use of the framework to model the interactions between entities within the supply chain, by giving each entity its own set of preferences and decision problems iteratively in a decision-dependent way contributing to a methodology for resilient supply chain design that thanks to the application of robust optimization allows for despite the lack of information sharing.

This work is a novel framework for a new methodology of robust optimization to aid the decision-making process of purchasers and supply chain managers and assist in a more realistic and robust supply chain design, by having a satisfaction-driven approach for a decision support system. This new framework aims to integrate the complexities and trade-offs inherent to SCM to the resilient contributions of a robust optimization solution, essentially the MCO allows for the solution that generates the most overall satisfaction for each member of the supply chain, this creates a possibility of simulation of the entire supply chain from any node if the preferences of the client and criteria of the competitors are known. This work will clarify how these advantages are possible, opening the way for future fully integrated implementation.

Paper topic

5. Supplier selection, 18. Risk and resilience, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Micro-Level Perspective on Blockchain Adoption: A Fuzzy Cognitive Map Analysis of Motivations

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Purpose/Aim: This study shows the mental models of individual actors in their decision making when facing blockchain adoption. It covers their perceptions, beliefs, and attitudes, focusing on their decision-making processes and motivations.

Design/Scope/Methodology: Through qualitative interviews with 23 upstream actors and 11 downstream individual actors in Europe, the study explores the cognitive shifts, prioritizing and underlying reasons driving initial adoption decisions. Data analysis was conducted using Atlas.ti software, followed by the development of a Fuzzy Cognitive Map (FCM) to visualize the interconnected factors influencing individual decision-making processes.

Theoretical framework used: Institutional Isomorphism was combined with a Grounded Theory approach.

Paper topic

11. Digital, 10. Purchasing innovation, 3. Purchasing organisation

How to balance sustainability and risk in supply chain management: a manufacturing perspective

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Summary: After the pandemic, risk and sustainability have received greater attention from business managers, government policy makers, experts and scholars in the supply chain field. For many companies, the simultaneous avoidance of risk and pursuit of sustainability are emerging as interconnected business goals, and have become increasingly entangled and complex. How to evaluate and balance the nexus between risk and sustainability in company strategic decision-making has become an urgent problem to be solved. This study aims to investigate the implementation of risk initiatives and sustainability initiatives in companies, and their impact on corporate performance. In order to assess how companies are approaching sustainability and risk in supply chain management, this study conducts a cross-sectional study of Chinese manufacturing companies. Interviews and a survey are conducted to explore how sustainability and risk practices may be related, and impact on corporate performance.

Keywords: Supply chain risk management, Sustainable supply chain management, Supply chain performance.

Submission category: Working paper

Purpose

'Inequalities keep growing. The climate crisis continues to escalate. Biodiversity loss is accelerating. Progress towards gender equality remains disappointing. And conflicts in Ukraine, Gaza, Sudan and beyond have left an unprecedented 120 million forcibly displaced people worldwide'.

--António Guterres (UN, 2024)

According to The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2024 released by the United Nations (UN), only 17% of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are on track, geopolitical tensions and growing climate chaos are impacting global sustainable development (UN, 2024). From the UN's perspective, the earth's environment and all mankind's development are facing multiple crises, and it is urgent to achieve the 17 SDGs. However, from the perspective of governments, the political demands of countries and individuals also need to be considered. The same is true for companies that are regulated by

national laws and regulations. Companies need to consider the requirements of laws, regulations and public opinion for sustainable development, but they also need to consider their own interests.

In recent years, manufacturing globalization has gradually occurred, and during this process, the scale and scope of supply chains of many companies have been expanding (Kumar et al., 2018). Larger, more complex supply chain systems will inevitably bring a variety of risks, which will affect the operational continuity of the organization and the supply stability of goods and services (Jordan & Bak, 2016), and ultimately affect the profitability and development of the company itself.

For companies, risks in supply chains arise for different reasons, recent examples at the macro level include geopolitical crises (Bednarski et al., 2023), or diseases and epidemics (Kumar et al., 2021; Majumdar et al., 2020; Soyer et al., 2023). In order to deal with these different risks, companies often need to develop a systematic risk management system to reduce the impact of risks on the achievement of business objectives. Often corporate risk and sustainability initiatives tend to go hand in hand. For example, large companies must undertake certain sustainability initiatives to meet legal and regulatory requirements, which may also lead to increased risks for the company. How to balance the coupling relationship between sustainable and risk initiatives within the company seems to have become an urgent problem to be solved.

SSCM and SCRM research have developed as two independent research fields, and more recently studies are emerging that investigate their intersection (Fattahi et al., 2021; He et al., 2021; Mukherjee et al., 2023; Rajesh, 2019). This study contributes to this nascent body of research by drawing on the concepts of the triple bottom and risk management to better understand how sustainability and risk initiatives might impact on one another. The study explores how the strategic decision makers of companies view sustainability and risk management, and what practices are adopted by companies to achieve SDGs. In this study, the research questions are as follows:

- How do manufacturing firms use sustainability initiatives to implement supply chain performance objectives?
- How do manufacturing firms use supply chain risk initiatives to implement supply chain performance objectives?
- How do manufacturing firms balance supply chain risk measures and sustainable development measures in practice?

Method

This study aims to conduct a qualitative multi-case study using a sample of large manufacturing companies in China for data collection and analysis. Twenty five supply chain managers from Chinese manufacturing companies have been invited to participate in semi-structured interviews, data collection is ongoing and to date ten managers have been interviewed. These interviews explore sustainable development and risk management in the supply chain. The interviews are recorded, assuring the anonymity of participants. The interview recordings are then transcribed into text files, and summaries are offered to participants to enhance reliability and validity (Halldorsson & Aastrup, 2003). The transcripts are then coded, and subject to abductive thematic analysis using NVivo, simultaneously adopting codes from the literature and allowing codes to emerge from the data. The analysis process will be iterative, until there is a saturation of themes (Bowen, 2008; Francis et al., 2010).

Findings

The findings will elucidate some current mainstream views of supply chain managers in China. Looking across the data, thematic comparisons will be made between different manufacturing sectors, and between different sustainability and risk initiatives, as well as the factors affecting supply chain strategies (e.g. company size, product offerings etc). The findings will assess the risk and sustainability initiatives of manufacturing companies, and the coupling phenomenon between the two. The results are expected to illuminate the ways in which manufacturing companies can balance supply chain sustainability risk goals. The results will reveal strategies formulated by business managers and provide insights and recommendations for the practicability of such strategies.

Relevance

Both SSCM and SCRM have been subject to academic investigation, and have been widely used in the daily operation and supply chain management process of companies. But the intersection between the two has received limited attention to date. Therefore, this study will attempt to fill the research gap in this area and improve the consistency between risk management goals and SDGs. This qualitative study aims to develop a conceptual model, that will be tested in a subsequent survey, leading to theoretical advancement at the nexus of SSCM and SCRM. For companies, this study will help stakeholders to better understand the challenges facing companies. It will provide supply chain managers with insights into more sustainable and robust strategies, and which specific practices could be adopted in the future to meet sustainability goals, reduce supply chain risk and internal friction, and improve competitiveness and performance.

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Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience, 17. Sustainability - social, 16. Sustainability - environmental

Are monitoring and incentives the only answers to the buyer agency problem? The use of supply brokers in complex infrastructure developments

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Key words

Agency theory, Prime contractor, brokers, complex infrastructure, construction

Purpose

In Purchasing and supply management agency theory has been applied to dealing with aberrant behaviour by the supplier. Grounded in high volume and continuous industries, typically manufacturing, such studies have led the literature to focus on Buyer remedies, namely monitoring and incentives (Spina *et al.*, 2016; Maestrini *et al.*, 2018). Amortised over the length or scale of a continuous relationship these sunk costs are recovered through more effective Buyer alignment of the original equipment suppliers with the buyers' goals.

But what if relationship continuity is absent? What if original equipment suppliers (OEMs) do not see value in a continuous relationship and are happy with arm's length transactional contracts that chop and change and do not follow the Buyer, crucially not featuring any shadow of the future or of the past? Monitoring and incentives remedies would be extremely time and resource consuming for a one-off transaction.

Literature-to-date has focused on the more visible Client-Prime contractor relationship in complex infrastructure developments (Nikulina and Wynstra, 2022; Santos and Cabral, 2022; Forster *et al.*, 2024). To advance our argument we develop the under-discussed Prime contractor buying role. In purchasing and supply the Prime role is parallel but not analogous to, that of the more well-known first tier supplier in continuous purchasing (Wihelm *et al.*, 2016).

Design/methodology/approach

Observations and 34 semi-structured interviews are conducted in various engineering projects in the global power plant construction sector. Interview questions are informed by theoretical insights to investigate the nature and solutions of goal incongruence (Saam, 2007; Rossetti and Choi, 2008) and information asymmetry (Eisenhardt, 1989; Saam, 2007) between prime contractors and OEMs.

Findings

Whilst working as a buyer in complex infrastructure projects, where some supply relationships are transactional and suppliers are essentially nomadic and independent, a different buyer remedy was observed. Instead of applying monitoring or incentive mechanisms themselves, prime contractors purposefully adopt supply brokers to address their agency problems with suppliers. Supply brokers take the “unwanted” piecemeal orders from OEM suppliers on behalf of the Prime and offer extra services such as invitation to bid preparation and recommendations for alternative OEM suppliers that meet the Prime’s standard. In addition, supply brokers monitor equipment manufacturers’ production schedules, provide clarity over technical designs and expedite deliveries.

Relevant/contribution

Our contribution is not to wider generalisability but to highlight a specific, perhaps even unique set of purchasing characteristics, which introduce the little addressed issue of the roles supply brokers can play in supply management. We propose that at least in some complex infrastructure eco-systems, supply brokers are unacknowledged talent, an essential but unheralded link in the value creation process whose roles enable the Prime to focus on its core procurement talent capabilities.

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Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.), 2. PSM strategy

MRO category management in procurement to increase availability: A case study in the oil and gas sector

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This study explores the impact of category management on MRO procurement within a leading Brazilian oil and gas company. By applying the Kraljic Matrix and prioritizing strategic procurement levers - demand consolidation, price evaluation, process automation, and supplier relationship management - the company achieved significant improvements: a 22% increase in contracted items, a 13% rise in buyer productivity, and a 36% backlog reduction. The findings highlight how structured category management enhances MRO availability and procurement efficiency, contributing to operational resilience.

Paper topic

4. Category management

A mission to gather every tender and contract: a case study of Spend Network's AI enabled public procurement data

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Key words

Global procurement data, service, product, professional service firm, action research

Purpose

It is conventional in IPSEERA to present research on purchasing or procurement as a functional activity. This research study reports on a firm whose business model is to sell Government procurements (tenders) systemised by AI. This is very different to work to-date that focuses on automating PSM operational processes (Meyer and Henke, 2023); equipping the procurement process with AI-based solutions (Guida, Caniato, Moretto and Ronchi, 2023); or 'A focus on how the adoption of digital technologies in purchasing impacts its organization, processes, and capabilities' (Spreitzenbarth, Bode and Stuckenschmidt, 2024).

Professional Service Firms (PSFs) provide clients with services not available in house. Procurement PSFs would be a niche within this industry, but Artificial Intelligence (AI) is facilitating their emergence. This study is a case study of the evolution of a machine learning/AI enabled procurement PSF. The service they provide is access to a global collection of curated public procurement tenders, scrapped/harvested from government procurement sites all around the world. In effect having a "free good" (publicly available data) at the heart of the business, where the business adds value is the scale and scope of its data, how it cleans and packages (curates) that data, and how that data is marketed. This contrasts with other PSFs, even those using AI where professional expertise (e.g. specialist lawyers or accountants, leads the offer). In combination these features of the business model justify a single case study approach, which suggests that AI technology appears to be driving a product informed service as an emergent Procurement PSF business model.

Design/methodology/approach

This study presents a single organisation case study observed across 18 months, conducted by a practitioner and academic team. A case study was adopted due to the lack of previous work in this area (Harju, Schaefer, Hallikas and Kahkonen, 2024). The organisation varies in size across this time frame from a micro to a small to medium sized (SME). It is an action research (Meehan, Touboulis and Walker, 2016; Coughlan and Coughlan, 2002) based project, an intervention intended to improve the performance of the firm. Observations include a committee meeting every three months.

As we are reporting on a very small digital entity we adopt a theoretical frame combining dynamic capabilities and business model innovation. Dynamic Capabilities (DC), is a term first coined by David Teece et al in 1997, building on Leonard-Barton's 1992 theory of 'core' capabilities. DC theory, however, is more a reflection of what a business *does*, rather than what it *has* (e.g. its resources, as previously captured in the resource based view of the firm - RBV), or how it is *organised / structured* (e.g. its functional areas), in order to help it achieve competitive advantage; the dynamic prefix stressing the importance of continuous renewal and innovation. DCs, when implemented lead to new business models (BMs). Recent studies link the two (DCs and BMs) frames (Ibarra, et al 2020; Heider et al, 2020: Chirumalla, 2021; Randhawa et al, 2020), and how one feeds the other.

Finding

We observe a transition from a complex service offering to a more tangible product like offering, an evolving transition that is moving the business from effectively a farmer of procurement data to a more chef like role. We report on AI enabled output that we propose will, in the long term change government procurement and undoubtedly be adopted where possible in the private sector.

Relevant/contribution

Our contribution is a treatment of the use of AI procurement divergent to previous work that we are aware of. Paradoxically we observe a procurement business moving from primarily offering a service to primarily offering a product. We observe the evolution of a procurement based PSF, whose challenges resonate with existing SME literature (the "liability of smallness" (Freeman, Carroll & Hannan, 1983), but whose output could disrupt current procurement practices most noticeably through its potential to identify corrupt procurement practices. This study reports on a new form of talent in the procurement space, bringing something new and practice led to the academic study of procurement and ready to jostle with existing procurement academic talent for attention.

Acknowledgements

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Paper topic

13. Public procurement, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.), 2. PSM strategy

‘Like drinking water after being in the desert’: Social-Symbolic Work of Procurement Professionals in driving Sustainable Procurement.

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Purpose

Sustainable procurement aims to strategically embed environmental, social, and economic considerations into purchasing decisions to minimise negative impacts and generate positive outcomes across the entire supply chain (Meehan and Bryde, 2011). Recent studies have argued that procurement professionals can play a pivotal role in sustainable procurement by acting as change makers and implementers within their organisations (Knight et al., 2019; Luzzini et al., 2024). However, individual-level perspectives on their agency remain limited and under-documented (Villena, 2019). The study examines how procurement professionals use their agency to change procurement functions and incorporate sustainability. It draws on the notion of social-symbolic work which refers to the ‘purposeful, reflexive efforts of individuals, collective actors and networks of actors to shape social symbolic objects’ (Lawrence and Suddaby, 2019, p.31). Where a social symbolic object is considered ‘a combination of discursive, relational, and material elements that constitute a meaningful pattern in a social system’ (Lawrence & Phillips, 2019 p.24). In this study, we examine procurement as the social-symbolic object where the discursive elements encompass the language and narratives related to purchasing. The relational elements pertain to the networks of relationships between procurement professionals, suppliers, internal departments, and regulatory bodies. Lastly, the material elements include the tools, technologies, policies, and procedures that enable procurement activities.

Design/Methodology/Approach

We adopted a theoretical sampling approach (Glaser & Strauss, 1967; Strauss & Corbin, 1990) by identifying procurement professionals engaged in sustainability initiatives or with sustainability as part of their role, including those who had previously held such roles across various sectors. To capture individuals demonstrating agency and commitment to change, we recruited participants from a globally recognised bottom-up initiative promoting sustainable procurement practices. We contacted 117 procurement professionals via LinkedIn who are members of this initiative, and 31 agreed to participate. An additional 5 participants were recruited through snowball sampling, resulting in a total of 36

participants. The interviews were conducted between June and August 2024. In addition to the interviews, the first author attended 15 meetings, webinars, and conferences organised by global initiative between October 2023 and September 2024, where procurement professionals openly shared their journeys and experiences. Notes were taken throughout to aid in the analysis. Furthermore, we analysed secondary data by reviewing over 20 episodes from multiple podcasts centred on sustainable procurement, where professionals shared detailed narratives. These diverse data sources provided rich and in-depth insights into the evolving practices and actions involved in driving sustainable procurement. The Gioia method (Gioia et al., 2013) was used to rigorously analyse the data by identifying first order codes, second order themes and third order aggregate dimensions.

Findings

Our study reveals that embedding sustainability in procurement involves shaping multiple social-symbolic objects: the practice of procurement itself and the identities of the professionals within it. Procurement professionals engage in three intertwined forms of social-symbolic work: *practice work*, *legitimacy work*, and *identity work*.

- *Practice work* encompasses efforts to reshape procurement processes through developing tools, frameworks, and sustainability-oriented metrics that help institutionalise sustainable practices.
- *Legitimacy work* involves framing sustainability as an organisational priority, crafting narratives and building support that anchor these practices within the organisation's strategic objectives.

Together, these forms constitute in a broader category of *organisational work* as they are focused on changing the operational and functional aspects of procurement within the firm.

However, our study reveals that *identity work* operates at the personal level, thereby constituting a form of *self-work*. This self-work is crucial, as it involves procurement professionals actively reshaping their identities in line with sustainability principles through two interconnected processes: identity alignment and identity projection.

- Identity alignment involves these procurement professionals integrating personal beliefs about sustainability into professional practices
- Identity projection, where professionals actively shape how they are perceived as sustainability champions within their organisations.

Through this self-work, procurement professionals do more than implement sustainable practices as they internalise and redefine their professional identities to embody sustainability.

Furthermore, this study reveals that these forms of work are not isolated; they are conducted simultaneously, creating a dynamic interplay that drives both sustainable procurement practices and the transformation of professional identities. This interconnectedness demonstrates how systemic change in procurement can be enacted, as aligning organisational practices with individual values creates a reinforcing cycle where each strengthens and extends the influence of the other. Through this interplay, procurement professionals move beyond simply implementing sustainability; they embody it, positioning themselves as pivotal agents of change and building a foundation for enduring, sustainable practices within the firm.

Practical implications

The study provides important practical implications for procurement leaders and organisations seeking to foster sustainable procurement. For procurement professionals, the findings underscore the importance of aligning personal values with professional responsibilities to create meaningful and lasting change. By understanding how self-work and organisational work interact, procurement professionals can more effectively leverage their roles to advance sustainability within their organisations. For organisations, the findings emphasise the need for firms to support sustainability initiatives stemming from traditionally functional departments such as procurement. Senior management (i.e. Chief Executive Officers, Vice Presidents and Board of Directors etc) can play a key role in supporting procurement professionals by providing resources, developing supportive policies, and recognising the efforts of individuals who are driving sustainability. The study's findings suggest that procurement professionals need the flexibility to shape their roles to reflect sustainability values. Firms can support this by providing opportunities for procurement professionals to engage in sustainability projects, take on emergent roles, and build legitimacy for sustainable procurement within the organisation. This can help in creating a culture where sustainability is viewed as an integral part of procurement rather than an add-on or compliance requirement.

Relevance/Contribution

This research aims to make threefold contributions. Firstly, shed light on sustainable purchasing and supply management literature by taking an individual level perspective which has often been overlooked (Villena, 2019; Walker et al., 2012), we demonstrate how the individual values of procurement professionals serve as a motivation to drive changes within the procurement. Secondly, scholarly debate on the strategic role of purchasing and supply management in systemic change and addressing global challenges (Knight et al., 2022; Luzzini et al., 2024) by adopting a social symbolic work lens, we show how procurement professionals can act with intentionality to transform their organisations procurement practices to have sustainability embedded while simultaneously transforming their professional identity (Ellram et al., 2020). Lastly, we contribute to the literature on the social-symbolic perspective by demonstrating how different forms of social-symbolic work are combined (Lawrence & Phillips, 2019). We found that while procurement professionals engaged in various forms of organisational work (i.e. practice work and legitimacy work), they also undertook self-identity work thereby constructing sustainable procurement as a strategic practice and, in the process, reshaping their professional identities.

Keywords: Sustainability, Purchasing and Supply Management, Social-symbolic work, Procurement Identity

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Paper topic

2. PSM strategy, 17. Sustainability - social, 16. Sustainability - environmental

Risk Mitigation in Project Contracting through the AWP Methodology

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Practitioner Paper

Abstract/summary

Author keywords:

1. Risk Management
2. Contracting Strategies
3. Advanced Work Packaging (AWP)
4. Electromechanical and civil services

Abstract

Research has been conducted about advantages and challenges for supply chain partnering (SCP) in some specific large spend and complex sectors. In recent years, the management of capital goods projects has faced significant challenges, with many objectives not being met (IPA, 2024). The lack of comprehensive conceptual and practical frameworks still hinders a detailed and systemic understanding of integration within project-based supply chains (Venselaar, Gruis & Verhoeven, 2015).

The interest of partnering and supply chain integration (SCI) has increased in various industries, but there is still a lack of comprehensive conceptual and practical frameworks that enable both a detailed and systemic understanding of integration in project-based supply chains (Eriksson, 2015).

As a consequence, there are procurement challenges to be addressed, and proposed techniques include integrating parallel engineering, employing lean building procedures, and forming strategic partnerships. To mitigate procurement uncertainties and enhance supply chain integration, it is essential to develop robust inter-organizational communication, coordination, and collaboration (Huang and Li, 2024).

Although new methodologies have been developed to reverse this scenario, consistent adherence to these practices throughout all project phases is essential to ensure risk mitigation and increase efficiency (Hamdi, 2013).

In 2009, the Construction Industry Institute (CII), initiated a Research Team (RT) aiming to develop an executable model of enhanced work packaging based not only on Work Face Planning but also on other industry work packaging practices (Hamdi, 2013). The team developed a lifecycle execution model for

work packaging with an emphasis on field implementation (Meeks, 2011). The advanced vision and practices of work packaging was defined as Advanced Work Packaging (AWP) methodology. It has shown significant benefits in control and efficiency, increasing predictability, reducing rework, and improving financial indicators in projects (The Construction Industry Institute, 2013).

The essence of AWP is conveyed in the Figure 1. The figure shows two main overlapping parts of the Advanced Work Packaging lifecycle: the Front End Engineering Design (FEED) part along with the Detailed Engineering (DE) phase from one side and the WorkFace planning (WFP) part from the other side.

Figure 1 : Advanced Work Packaging model (Hamdi, 2013)

This work addresses risks in contracting electromechanical and civil services, highlighting challenges and techniques to mitigate them. Different types of contracts and best practices for risk control are discussed, from the planning phase through to execution, with a practical approach. The work also explores the request for proposal (RFP) phases, highlighting how scope understanding, quantitative and qualitative analysis, and management processes can influence successful contracting and risk mitigation.

Design/methodology/approach

The approach in this work is based on professional reports and lessons learned from experience in large-scale projects. Data was collected through autoethnographic research, with direct observations on client and contractor successes and failures, which enabled the development of practical strategies to mitigate risks in contracting electromechanical and civil services. The study draws on practical experience in applying these strategies, associated with the AWP methodology, to increase efficiency and mitigate risks throughout the project life cycle (IPA, 2024; The Construction Industry Institute, 2013).

Findings

Supply chain integration remains underutilized in the sector. As mentioned by Huang and Li (2024), adopting these methods is crucial for enhancing procurement management in this sector. These strategies aim to optimize procurement methods, increase efficiency, and effectively manage the inherent complexities of a project management. The application of AWP in construction projects, combined with practical risk mitigation strategies from the contracting phase, can lead to up to a 25% increase in productivity and a reduction of up to 10% in total installation cost. Lessons learned also emphasize the importance of choosing the right type of contract and conducting a detailed analysis of proposals (RFP), ensuring better control over costs, schedule, and quality.

Relevance/contribution

This work adds to the studies on AWP (The Construction Industry Institute, 2013) with a practical approach based on lessons learned in the context of risk management and resilience in construction projects, through autoethnography. Based on direct observations and experience accumulated in capital-intensive projects, this work provides a holistic view of AWP and its application in the initial

phases of the project, offering practical insights for contractors and clients on how to improve predictability and control in their operations. As a conclusion, continuous research and adaptation are vital for advancing the global engineering contracting sector, they will empower stakeholders to enhance their strategic competencies, adapt to evolving trends, and build a more resilient and efficient global infrastructure system. This way the industry can drive sustainable progress and achieve long-term success in an increasingly complex and dynamic global market.

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Independent Project Analysis (IPA) **Site-Based Capital Projects Improvement Journey—A Case Study Timeline** consulta realizada 24/10/2024 em <https://www.ipaglobal.com/resources/case-studies/site-based-capital-projects-improvement-journey-a-case-study-timeline/>

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Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience

How can online retailers collaborate with supply chain partners to facilitate knowledge exchange in digital platforms: from the perspective of relational view

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Introduction

Digital platforms have grown rapidly in recent years (Zhou et al., 2023). These platforms improve online retailers' operational performance by expanding market share (Chen et al., 2020) and facilitating communication, tracking, and connectivity (Jovanovic et al., 2022). Consequently, many retailers have joined digital platforms, such as Amazon, eBay, and Alibaba, to gain a competitive advantage (Cenamor et al., 2019; Shi et al., 2021). In this research, digital platforms are defined as those operating under an agency selling model, which bridge the links between online retailers and customers. For the purposes of this research, online retailers comprise third-party resellers and manufacturers. Despite the many advantages of participating in digital platforms, online retailers frequently encounter operational challenges, including customer satisfaction, cost control, and inventory management (Qin and Liu, 2022).

Supply chain collaboration has been shown to be essential for successful implementation on digital platforms (Golicic et al., 2002). Although the benefits of supply chain collaboration are widely recognised in the literature (Ralston et al., 2017), early research on digital platforms primarily focused on changes in distribution channels and the downward pressure on market prices (Johnson and Whang, 2002). Nevertheless, research on supply chain collaboration from the perspective of online retailers remains limited (Dragomirov, 2020). This lack of understanding often leads to uncertainty for many online retailers in managing collaborative relationships with supply chain partners within digital platforms (Cenamor, 2021; Siraj et al., 2020). Accordingly, this study aims to explore how online retailers can collaborate with supply chain partners when engaging with digital platforms. The supply chain partners considered in this research are primarily composed of product suppliers and logistics service providers.

Underpinning theory

Since the key factors of online retailers' supply chain collaboration identified in prior literature align with the main concepts of the relational view, this research adopts the relational view as a valuable

theoretical lens to study how collaborative relationships are transformed within digital platforms. As a branch of the resource-based view (RBV), the relational view suggests that firms achieve a competitive advantage through inter-firm relationships (Dyer and Singh, 1998). Relational benefits arise from the interconnected activities of supply chain partners (Möller, 2006). There are four determinants within the relational view: (1) investments in relation-specific assets; (2) substantial knowledge exchange; (3) complementary resources and capabilities; and (4) effective governance (Dyer and Singh, 1998). From this perspective, firms may enhance inter-organisational relationships by investing in mutually beneficial assets, information, and resource capabilities, or by employing more effective governance mechanisms (Dyer and Singh, 1998). Accordingly, this research applies the relational view theory to explain how online retailers collaborate with supply chain partners to address challenges stemming from engagement with digital platforms.

Methodology

To address the research questions, this study adopted an exploratory qualitative research approach. The study employed semi-structured interviews as the primary data collection method to gain deeper insights into the practical perspectives of online retailers regarding supply chain collaboration. The interview participants were managers who had experience with digital platforms, all based in China. To select participants capable of providing valuable insights, the study developed a set of desired characteristics, and twenty companies meeting these criteria voluntarily participated. The interviews were conducted in three main formats: face-to-face, by telephone, or through WeChat video. Furthermore, this study employed both content and thematic analysis to examine the collected data.

Findings and analysis

This research found that complementary resources and capabilities are the primary drivers for initiating and sustaining collaborative relationships over time. Accordingly, the data suggest that if partnerships are to be initiated, firms should assess the potential for integrating partners' capabilities. This assessment enables partners to evaluate the additional value that the partnership can generate and capture. In practice, this evaluation process continues throughout the relationship and encompasses three relational perspectives: evaluating the benefits of integrating the provider's resources and capabilities; ensuring that partners' offerings meet specific requirements for various products or services; and combining supply chain partners' resources and capabilities to support business development.

Knowledge-sharing processes and routines are essential to facilitate data collection between online retailers and their supply chain partners. The findings of this research confirm that these routines are not limited to conventional meetings but can also be facilitated digitally. Two key themes emerged from the respondent data analysis regarding knowledge sharing and utilisation. The first theme emphasises the need for enhanced transparency in knowledge-sharing. The second suggests that partners should apply this knowledge collaboratively to develop processes for data and knowledge utilisation.

When complementary resources and capabilities, and knowledge sharing routines are present, this research found that online retailers and their partners are inclined to realize the full potential of their partnership through investing in relation-specific assets. Two main themes were highlighted by the study's respondents on this subject: (1) investment in technology, and (2) the investment in human resource. Partners are likely to jointly invest in building information systems for data sharing.

Additionally, in order to ensure the agreed collaborative contents are provided smoothly, online retailers need to assign dedicated staff to manage collaborative relationship.

For successful collaboration, partners should agree on mechanisms to govern their partnerships. This research found that greater emphasis is placed on contractual governance mechanisms as the collaborative relationship evolves. This shift is natural, as contractual terms change over time, leading to more efficient and effective governance mechanisms. The findings show that partnerships often begin with a highly contractual governance approach and subsequently progress to a transitional governance phase as the relationship matures.

Discussion and contribution

This study aimed to investigate how online retailers collaborate with supply chain partners to tackle the challenges posed by digital platforms from the relational view (RV) perspective. It examined issues related to complementary resources and capabilities, specific-asset investment, knowledge-sharing routines, and governance mechanisms that impact supply chain collaboration. Complementary resources and capabilities were the main triggers for initiating and sustaining collaborative relationships over time. When complementary resources and capabilities and information-sharing routines are present, online retailers must invest in and engage with the relationship accordingly. Furthermore, the data analysis suggests that approaches to partnership governance need to be transformed to become more efficient in order to fully leverage the potential of advanced collaboration.

This research contributes to the field of digital platforms by examining online retailers' implementation from a supply chain perspective; it fills a gap, as very limited research has sought to investigate the elements constituting supply chain collaboration from the perspective of the relational view. Through the relational view, which posits that sound resources, capabilities, knowledge-sharing routines and governance enable online retailers to perform effectively and efficiently with their supply chain partners, this research contributes to existing theory by demonstrating that supply chain collaboration functions as a solution to tackle challenges arising from digital platforms. Regarding practical contributions, the findings provide online retailers with guidance on managing their interactions with supply chain partners and on managing their relation-specific assets to effectively support supply chain collaboration and tackle challenges arising from digital platforms.

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Paper topic

11. Digital, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Is Sustainable Public Procurement promoting Sustainability-Oriented Innovation? A systematic literature review.

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This systematic literature review investigates the intersection of Sustainable Public Procurement (SPP) and Sustainability-Oriented Innovation (SOI) within the context of global value chains (GVCs). As governments worldwide strive to meet environmental and social objectives, SPP serves as a strategic tool to influence market behaviour and drive innovation (Adjei-Bamfo et al., 2023; Yu et al., 2023). This study aims to systematically review the literature on SPP and its relationship with SOI, focusing on the dynamics within global value chains (GVCs). By synthesizing existing research, we seek to identify trends, gaps, and opportunities for future inquiry.

The study adopts literature published from 2000 to 2023, focusing on peer-reviewed articles that explore how SPP practices can stimulate SOI that aligns with sustainability objectives. The review is motivated by the increasing recognition of the role of public sector purchasing in driving environmental and social sustainability, particularly in light of global challenges such as climate change, resource depletion, and social inequality (Ghisetti, 2017).

The methodology employed in this review is multifaceted, incorporating text mining and thematic analysis to synthesize findings from a diverse corpus of 73 academic texts in Business, Management, Engineering Management, Accounting or Economics, selected considering the journals and the authors' relevance to the topic. The use of text mining techniques facilitates the extraction, cleaning, and processing of large volumes of information, allowing for a structured analysis of keywords and themes that emerge from the literature. This approach not only streamlines the analysis process but also provides valuable insights into the conceptual structure of the research field. By employing thematic analysis, the study identifies the key themes associated to each SOI and group them into one of the four GVC categories elaborated by integrating the GVC-oriented policies adopted in De Marchi & Alford (2022) with the innovation concepts in GVC embraced in Ambos et al. (2021). This novel elaboration also provides a conceptual framework capturing the evaluation of SOI in a GVC perspective which can potentially inspiring further studies.

The findings are multiple and span from systematic findings to the final proposal of a conceptual framework. The text analysis identifies various streams of SOI that are influenced by SPP practices. These include technological innovations, such as eco-design and digital solutions, as well as non-

technological innovations that encompass social and organizational dimensions (Adjei-Bamfo et al., 2019, 2023; Al Nuaimi, Khan, et al., 2021; Al Nuaimi, Singh, et al., 2021; Al Nuaimi & Khan, 2019; Rainville, 2017; Yu et al., 2023). The analysis reveals that while there is a growing body of literature on the technological aspects of innovation, there remains a notable gap in understanding the social and organizational factors that facilitate or hinder the implementation of sustainable practices in public procurement. The thematic analysis highlights the importance of upgrading in the value creation along the chain: firms can engage in various forms of it, such as improving machinery, workforce training, and introducing new product lines. These innovations allow firms to move up the value chain, transitioning from low-value activities to higher-value ones, capturing more value from their participation (Ambos et al., 2021). However, to upgrade, collaboration and stakeholder engagement are the keys. Effective partnerships among public authorities, private sector actors, and civil society organizations are essential for co-creating innovative solutions that meet sustainability goals. The literature suggests that collaborative approaches not only enhance the effectiveness of procurement practices but also contribute to building a culture of innovation within public institutions. Finally, the review emphasizes the need for coherent policy alignment at local, national, and international levels to create an enabling a global environment for SPP and SOI.

In terms of practical implications, the findings of this review provide valuable insights for policymakers, practitioners, and researchers interested in advancing sustainable procurement practices. By understanding the mechanisms through which SPP can stimulate SOI, stakeholders can design more effective procurement strategies that not only achieve cost savings but also deliver social and environmental benefits. The review advocates for the integration of sustainability criteria into procurement processes, encouraging public authorities to prioritize suppliers that demonstrate a commitment to innovation and sustainability. The insights gained from this review not only advance academic discourse but also offer practical guidance for stakeholders seeking to navigate the complexities of sustainable procurement in an increasingly interconnected world.

The study concludes by identifying several avenues for future research. It calls for more empirical studies that explore the impact of SPP on SOI across different sectors and contexts. Additionally, there is a need for research that investigates the barriers and enablers of implementing sustainable procurement practices, particularly in developing countries where resources and capacities may be limited. The review also suggests that future studies should consider the role of digital technologies in enhancing the effectiveness of SPP and facilitating innovation.

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Paper topic

13. Public procurement, 16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social

Exploring Supplier's compensatory Responses to Price Concessions: A Working Paper

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

While a substantial body of research in supply chain management (SCM) and negotiation has focused on buyer strategies to secure price concessions from suppliers, the subsequent supplier compensatory responses to these concessions remains a relatively understudied area. This oversight has significant implications for supply chain performance, as buyer-initiated price reductions can trigger negative supplier reactions, such as reduced quality, delayed deliveries, or decreased cooperation. This study aims to fill this gap by expanding on the work of Carnovale et al. (2019), one of the few empirical investigations of supplier compensatory actions. The research of Carnovale et al. (2019) revealed how suppliers might respond by adjusting quality, service, and R&D investments. Their study was primarily deductive, meaning that the variables included in the analysis were predetermined by the limitations of their dataset obtained from a market research company. Thus, the current study will take a more exploratory approach. The aim of this study is threefold is to validate the findings of Carnovale's original study in the context of the current economic and political landscape, explore how recent economic and political factors influence supplier responses to price concessions and identify new moderators that may affect supplier reactions to price concessions. The main research questions of this study are as follows:

1. To what extent do suppliers' responses to price concessions align with the findings of Carnovale's (2019) study in a simulated environment reflecting the economic and political disruptions of the past seven years?
1. How do economic and political factors, as simulated in the game, influence supplier responses to price concessions?
2. Are there additional moderators, beyond those identified by Carnovale, that significantly affect supplier reactions to price concessions in this simulated environment?

We will use a mixed methods approach to answer those questions. First, we will conduct semi-structured interviews with experts to explore a wider range of potential supplier responses. Second, we will use a scenario-based experiment to simulate the economic and political disruptions of the past seven years. The findings from the qualitative interviews will be used to refine the design of the scenario-based experiment, ensuring that the scenarios are realistic, relevant, and capture the complexity of real-world supply chain relationships.

Methodology

The experiment will be developed to simulate seven years of economic and political disruptions, mirroring the key events and trends of the past decade. It will consist of seven rounds, each representing a year, with varying economic and political conditions. Participants will assume the role of suppliers and make decisions regarding their responses to price concessions within the context of each round's economic and political environment. After each round, participants will complete a survey assessing their reactions to price concessions, considering the prevailing economic and political conditions. The survey will include measures of supplier characteristics, economic factors (e.g., GDP, inflation), political factors (e.g., government policies, geopolitical events), and potential moderators identified in previous research.

Expected Outcomes

The study will provide insights into the generalizability of Carnovale's findings in a dynamic and simulated environment. Additionally, we expect to identify how economic and political disruptions influence supplier responses to price concessions. Finally, we aim to discover additional factors that can significantly affect supplier reactions to price concessions in the context of economic and political uncertainty.

Keywords: Buyer-Supplier relationship, Price concessions, price reduction pressure

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 7. Negotiation and contracting

Importance of Supply Chain Management in Execution of International Construction Projects

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Summary

This working paper explores the significance of supply chain management (SCM) in international construction projects, specifically focusing on how contractual obligations influence the supply chain performance. The research highlights critical gaps in existing literature, particularly the lack of tailored managerial insights and the challenges posed by fragmented transactions and poor coordination. Utilizing a qualitative approach, semi-structured interviews will be conducted with stakeholders from Azerbaijani construction companies involved in international projects. The aim of this research is to investigate the impact of contractual requirements on SCM within construction projects, with the goal of providing guidance for practitioners involved in international projects.

Keywords

Supply chain management, international construction projects, contractual obligations, supplier selection

Submission category: Working paper (WP)

Literature Review

In the rapidly evolving landscape of the global construction industry, effective supply chain management (SCM) has emerged as a crucial factor for the successful execution of international construction projects. This working paper focuses on the intricate relationship between contractual obligations and the selection and performance evaluation of suppliers within the context of projects financed by International Financial Institutions (IFIs) such as the Asian Development Bank (ADB), the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), the World Bank, and the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA). The research aims to address gaps in the existing literature, particularly regarding the lack of tailored managerial guidance that addresses the complexities of supply chain integration in specific project contexts.

The literature review identifies several key areas of focus within supply chain management (SCM) and project management. First, it emphasizes the importance of integrating supply chains into project management, highlighting the necessity for cohesive collaboration among stakeholders to enhance efficiency and align project objectives. It draws on the work of Erikson et al. (2023), who analyze how project complexity necessitates enhanced coordination among various parties involved. The integration of multi-disciplinary information and the role of tools like Building Information Modeling (BIM) are also discussed, underscoring their potential to facilitate smoother collaboration and operational efficiency.

Secondly, the review addresses the critical area of supply chain risk management in construction projects. It articulates the challenges associated with managing supply chain risks, particularly in international contexts, drawing on studies by Shishehgarhaneh et al. (2024) and Koc and Gurgun (2020). These studies propose comprehensive frameworks for risk assessment and mitigation, providing valuable insights into effective strategies for managing risks in complex construction environments. Their findings reveal the importance of proactive strategies and innovative approaches, such as the robust optimization model (Hsu et al., 2019) for modular construction, which offers a pathway to circumvent operational uncertainties and enhance project success.

Another focal point is the significance of material supply and inventory management. Al-Aidrous et al. (2022) highlight the detrimental impact of ineffective inventory systems on project execution, emphasizing the need for robust frameworks to manage materials effectively. Awaad et al. (2024) contribute to this discussion by proposing a material supply chain framework specific to road construction, further illustrating the critical role of strategic monitoring in avoiding project delays and cost overruns.

The selection of suppliers and coordination of their performance is examined as a key challenge in the construction industry. The application of the Supply Chain Operations Reference (SCOR) model (Pan et al., 2010) serves as a foundation for understanding and evaluating supplier performance, while Chen et al. (2018) highlight the potential for mathematical modeling to optimize resource allocation and enhance project efficiency. These insights underscore the need for a systematic approach to supplier selection that aligns with project goals.

Despite these advancements in SCM literature, the review uncovers persistent research gaps. Notably, the need for practical insights tailored to specific project contexts remains largely unmet. Additionally, there is a lack of exploration into the dynamic roles of supply chain participants and the complexities they encounter throughout the integration process. This underscores the necessity for further research that addresses the evolving nature of supply chains and the contextual nuances that impact project success. Despite advancements in supply chain management strategies, there is an ongoing need for seamless coordination and collaboration between project scheduling and supplier selection to enhance project outcomes.

International construction projects financed by IFIs are being implemented and regulated based on FIDIC Multilateral Development Bank (MDB) Contract. The previous literature has paid insufficient attention to the contractual obligations of all stakeholders during project implementation or the impact of stringent contractual requirements on supply chain management.

To bridge these gaps, this working paper poses the research question: *“How do the contractual obligations outlined in international construction contracts influence the selection and performance evaluation criteria for suppliers within the supply chain?”*

Research Methods

The research methodology is anchored in qualitative analysis, employing semi-structured interviews to collect insights from key stakeholders involved in international construction projects. It is related to the experiences people have encountered with the subject that is being explored (Groenewald, 2004) and allows us to understand better the real-world events and human interactions associated with them. The semi-structured interview guide will be prepared, and data collected will be analyzed by using thematic analysis. The target audience includes project managers, supply chain managers, contractors, and suppliers from Azerbaijan construction companies executing projects abroad, as well as relevant professionals from foreign companies working in Azerbaijan. This approach enables an in-depth examination of the challenges practitioners encounter in managing supply chains in complex international contexts.

Semi-structured interviews enable participants to share their experiences and perspectives on supply chain management, facilitating a rich understanding of the intricacies involved. The flexibility of this method allows researchers to probe deeper into respondents' answers, uncovering innovative strategies and best practices employed in the field (McIntosh and Morse, 2015). The interpretive research paradigm used in this study emphasizes the role of participant experiences in understanding supply chain dynamics.

The sampling method for participant selection is purposive, ensuring that individuals with relevant expertise and experience are chosen to provide valuable insights into the challenges of SCM in international construction. Purposive sampling method relies on the researcher's judgment when identifying and selecting the individuals, cases, or events that can provide the best information to achieve the study's objectives (Palinkas et al., 2015). Approximately 20-25 interviews will be conducted, adhering to the principle of theoretical saturation, where data collection continues until no new information emerges. This approach is essential for identifying key themes and relationships within the qualitative data collected.

Conclusion

The findings from this research are anticipated to shed light on the critical challenges faced by construction companies in managing supply chains during international projects. By understanding the impact of contractual obligations on supplier selection and performance evaluation, the research aims to provide actionable insights that can enhance decision-making for project managers and supply chain professionals. The study also seeks to contribute to the broader discourse on construction SCM by offering recommendations for improved coordination, collaboration, and overall project success.

Ultimately, this research emphasizes the interconnectedness of various factors within the realm of supply chain management in international construction projects. By addressing the identified gaps in literature and offering a nuanced understanding of the challenges faced by practitioners, it aims to pave the way for future research in the field. The insights from this study are expected to be valuable to both academia and industry professionals navigating the complexities of supply chain management in a globalized construction landscape.

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Paper topic

14. Project procurement, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 5. Supplier selection

Effects of Internet of Things Implementation on Supplier Organizational Capability: Is technological implementation always beneficial to Green Innovation?

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Effects of Internet of Things Implementation on Supplier Organisational Capability: Is technological implementation always beneficial to Green Innovation?

Keywords: Internet of Things, Supplier Organisational Capabilities, Resource Flexibility, Human Resource Flexibility, Green Innovation Performance

Research Motivation

As digital technology advances profoundly transform the global manufacturing landscape, the Internet of Things (IoT) is increasingly recognised as a pivotal enabler for manufacturers to attain a competitive edge and sustainable development. The supply chain management literature has demonstrated the crucial role of IoT in enabling agility, visibility, tracking and information sharing to facilitate shared activities in areas such as supply chain processes and demand prediction.

However, this stream tends to emphasise the perspective of the buying firms, focusing on operational issues of product and information flows. Consequently, the question of the positioning of IoT technologies in relation to other elements of the supply network remains largely unanswered. In other words, most previous studies have considered IoT as operational entities rather than as components interwoven with the fabric of the relationships between the supply chain parties and the value creation process. Therefore, despite gathering substantial attention from the academic community in its practical application within the manufacturing sector, the implementation of IoT on supplier involvement practices and its impact on supplier capabilities from the upstream supply chain remains unclear.

Drawing on Capability Approach Theory, this study intends to reveal the implementation of IoT in supplier involvement practices and its impact on supplier organisational capabilities, especially by actively leveraging the data collection/sharing functions obtained from smart connected devices and the data analytic functionalities within the IoT platform layer to enhance suppliers' material resource flexibility and human resource flexibility. Moreover, this study plans to delve further into whether supplier organisational capabilities influenced by IoT that demonstrate both material resource flexibility and human resource flexibility can enhance the key aspects of green innovation performance - specifically, green product innovation performance and green process innovation performance.

Research Aims and Questions

This study seeks to deviate from previous work by highlighting the impact of IoT implementations on suppliers' organisational capabilities and their impact on green innovation performance. The first research objective of this study is to investigate the impact of IoT implementation resources, represented by the platform layers of IoT architecture, on supplier organisational capabilities. The second research objective is to examine the impact of potential supplier organisational capabilities on green innovation performance.

To achieve the research aims and objectives, this research tends to investigate:

RQ1: How is IoT implemented in supplier involvement practices?

RQ2: To what extent does IoT influence and strengthen supplier organisational capabilities?

RQ3: How can green innovation performance be generated and improved from supplier organisational capabilities?

Research Hypothesis Development

IoT Data Exchange and Supplier Organisational Capability

The level of information exchange during IoT implementation is believed to increase the organisational flexibility of suppliers. In addition, information exchange plays a vital role in robust supplier management. This exchange of information facilitates the resolution of suppliers' cross-business processes, such as resourcing flexibility and staff redeployment, if they increase exchange levels, such as inventory, production, order, delivery, and demand forecasting. Similarly, it requires emphasising that sharing production costs, technical knowledge, and schedules between suppliers and buyer firms is critical for suppliers to reconfigure their resources quickly and cost-effectively and respond flexibly to changing market conditions. Suppliers operating in high-uncertainty environments, especially in the post-pandemic period, can gain greater material resource and human resource flexibility through effective internal and external information exchange. In turn, effective flexibility is expected to positively impact innovation performance. Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed in this study:

Hypothesis H1a: There is a positive relationship between IoT data exchange and material resource flexibility.

Hypothesis H1b: There is a positive relationship between IoT data exchange and human resource flexibility.

IoT Data Processing and Supplier Capability

Accurate data analytics sharing between organisations will positively impact system performance and enhance the organisation's capability to react flexibly to market change. The quality of data analytics affects the performance of supplier operational activities such as forecasting buyer firm's demand, logistics planning, and production planning. The higher the quality of data analytics, the more flexible the supplier will be in responding to the changing needs of the buyer firm in real-time. A higher level of data analysis by suppliers through IoT technology also facilitates suppliers' flexibility in material resource reallocation and human reorganisation in the case of demand uncertainty, thus improving the performance of both suppliers and buyer firms. Based on the above discussion, the hypotheses of this study are as follows:

Hypothesis H2a: There is a positive relationship between IoT data processing and resource flexibility.

Hypothesis H2b: There is a positive relationship between IoT data processing and human resource flexibility.

Supplier Organisation Flexibility and Green Innovation Performance

Green innovation is essentially a product of green improvement activity based on existing knowledge, resources, and technologies. With increased organisational flexibility, suppliers can make minor adjustments to cope with uncertainties in the internal and external environments. When there is a shortage of certain material resources or insufficient human resources in green innovation activities, suppliers can quickly utilise other similar material resources and reorganise staffing to ensure the continuity of the innovation process. Therefore, improving material resource flexibility and human resource flexibility can facilitate suppliers' rapid adaptation to changes in buyer firms' green needs during the green innovation process. Thereby, this study hypothesises:

Hypothesis H3: There is a positive relationship between material resource flexibility and green innovation performance.

Hypothesis H4: There is a positive relationship between human resource flexibility and green innovation performance.

Research Framework Development

The research model of this study consists of five potential constructs: IoT data exchange, IoT data processing, material resource flexibility, human resource flexibility, and green innovation performance, which including green product innovation performance and green process innovation performance. Each

of the hypothesised relationships represented is theorised as positive and direct in the research model. Implementing IoT in supplier involvement practices is the prerequisite in the theoretical model, while data exchange and data processing are represented simultaneously. It is also hypothesised that the implementation of IoT and the structure of key supplier capabilities can influence suppliers' green innovation performance.

Research Method

This study utilises the survey data collected from approximately 300 Chinese component manufacturers to examine the proposed research model and hypotheses.

In the data analysis phase, this study employs hierarchical regression analysis and the bootstrapping method to test the hypotheses. Additionally, confirmatory factor analysis is utilised to ensure the fidelity of the measurement scales. A structural equation model is used to assess the robustness of the research framework.

Findings and Contribution

The results show that IoT implementation significantly improves the capability of suppliers to effectively align human and manufacturing resources, thus contributing to green product and process innovation performance.

This study presents a novel approach that integrates IoT technology with supplier involvement activities for empirical studies in operation and supply chain management. Using the capability approach theory, this study contributes to the literature on IoT implementation and green innovation on the supplier side, as well as to research focusing on technology implementation impacts on supplier organisational capabilities within supplier involvement practices.

More specifically, this study generates theoretical insights regarding the impacts of IoT application on human resource flexibility within supplier organisations, as human factors and cultural dynamics are consistently pivotal to organisations' technological application and innovative activities. The findings also add to understanding the interplay between suppliers and buying firms.

Additionally, this study contributes to providing novel guidelines for component manufacturing firms to enhance the IoT implementation levels, and also assists buying firms in giving them new practical insights for their supplier involvement activities.

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 11. Digital, 16. Sustainability - environmental

The Impact of Hyper-Local Disruptions on Supply Chain Plasticity: The Moderating Role of Centrality and Clustering

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The Impact of Hyper-Local Disruptions on Supply Chain Plasticity: The Moderating Role of Centrality and Clustering

Supply chain plasticity is the ability of a supply chain to rapidly and effectively adapt to environmental changes (Zinn & Goldsby, 2019). It is a critical capability for businesses in today's dynamic and unpredictable world (Hughes et al., 2022). Hyper-local supply chain disruptions, such as natural disasters, political unrest, and social unrest, that impacts individual supply chain sites can have a significant impact on business operations, causing delays, shortages, and increased costs (Guntuka et al., 2023). To mitigate these risks, businesses need to develop supply chains that are plastic, or adaptable.

One key aspect of supply chain plasticity is response time, defined as the ability of businesses to respond effectively to disruptions (Hughes et al., 2022; Falcone et al., 2022). Response time in supply chain plasticity is crucial since reflects a business's ability to react swiftly and effectively to disruptions, which is essential in today's dynamic and competitive environment (Doshi & Tang, 2012). A quick response minimizes disruption impact, reduces downtime, and preserves customer trust, ultimately mitigating financial losses. Importantly, businesses can take proactive measures to enhance the plasticity of their supply chains. This includes diversifying their supplier base to reduce dependence on a single source, which can help ensure a steady flow of goods even if one supplier is affected by a disruption. However, existing literature has not yet explored when firms prioritize response time and how they implement strategies to enhance it.

This study investigates the impact of hyper-local disruptions on supply chain plasticity. It also examines the moderating role of centrality and clustering in the relationship between disruption severity and response time. The theoretical foundation for this study is based on the resource-based view of the firm and the network perspective on supply chain management (Lockett et al., 2009; Carnovale & Yeniyurt, 2015). Based on these theoretical foundations, the following hypotheses are developed:

- H1: The response time of the focal firm increases with the severity of hyper-local disruptions to a certain point, and declines after that point resulting in a curvilinear relationship between the disruption severity and the focal firm's response time to the disruption.
- H2: Focal firm's centrality moderates the relationship between the hyper-local disruption's severity and response time to the disruption where the inverse U relationship between severity and response time is weaker at lower levels of centrality, while the relationship is stronger at higher levels of centrality, thus steepening the inverse-U curve.
- H3: Focal firm's clustering moderates the relationship between the hyper-local disruption's severity and response time to the disruption where the inverse U relationship between severity and response time is stronger at lower levels of clustering, while the relationship is weaker at higher levels of centrality, thus flattening the inverse-U curve.

To test our hypotheses, we partnered with a Silicon Valley based end-to-end supply chain risk management solutions provider, Resilinc. Corp (Guntuka et al., 2023; Boyson et al., 2022). Resilinc. Corp was founded in 2010 by former Cisco supply chain practitioners and technology experts. This firm maps the entire supply chain of its customers drilling down to supplier, site, product, and part level data in one centralized system and actively monitors 24x7, any human-made or natural disaster events that take place at their customer's and the customer's supplier sites that have a potential to disrupt the firm's operations. This unique dataset enables us to construct the supply chain network of different firms with a novel level of precision to the extent of our knowledge has not been previously done in the supply chain/operations literature. The data will be analyzed using a variety of statistical methods, including regression analysis.

Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 2. PSM strategy

DRIVING ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT: EXPLORING RESERVATION SCHEMES AND INDIGENOUS FIRM ENGAGEMENT IN ROAD INFRASTRUCTURE DEVELOPMENT IN UGANDA

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This study investigates the role of reservation schemes in driving economic empowerment through indigenous firm engagement in road infrastructure development in Uganda. Reservation schemes are policies and mechanisms that allocate specific procurement opportunities to certain groups, promoting inclusivity, economic empowerment, and fair competition by ensuring underrepresented businesses have access to government contracts. Data from 37 local construction firms in Kampala was collected via cross-sectional surveys, employing qualitative and quantitative methods. Regression analysis reveals a statistically significant effect of reservation schemes on local firm engagement, with increased reservation thresholds and contractual requirements positively influencing participation by 38.5%. Recommendations include stringent monitoring by the Public Procurement and Disposal of Assets Authority (PPDA), ongoing sensitization programs for local contractors, tailored subcontracting arrangements, and addressing barriers to participation such as timely payments.

Paper topic

13. Public procurement

Quantifying and reducing the environmental impact of medical disposables: an analysis of purchasing data in Dutch Academic Medical Centers

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Introduction

The healthcare sector has a significant environmental impact, with the Dutch healthcare system alone responsible for 7.3% of the national carbon footprint (Friedericy et al., 2021, Steenmeijer et al, 2022). Medical devices and equipment contribute to 6% of this total, equivalent to 11 million tons of carbon emissions (Gupta Strategists, 2019), while in England even 15% was reported (Tennison et al, 2021). Additionally, healthcare activities account for 4% of the country's waste and 13% of its consumption of critical raw materials, including metals and minerals (Steenmeijer et al, 2022). A substantial portion of this environmental burden comes from single-use medical disposables (Conrardy et al., 2010). These disposables, ranging from synthetic rubber or nitrile gloves to more complex items made from multiple materials. Commonly used materials include plastics, textiles, electronics and metals, which contribute variably to the environmental burden depending on their composition and disposal methods. In particular, the production of electronics and metals demands large quantities of raw materials, and energy, further exacerbating their environmental footprint (Le et al., 2020). The widespread use of these products not only depletes resources but also generates significant greenhouse gas emissions and waste. However, current data on the usage and environmental impact of medical disposables are largely based on Environmentally Extended Input Output Analyses (EEIOA). In that top-down method, financial spending is linked to (carbon) emission factors. This yields only global estimates, offering limited insight into the physical quantities of materials consumed. Therefore, this information cannot be used to inform decision makers in hospitals on material flows in their facility.

To overcome the limitations of EEIOA approaches, in this study we analyzed actual procurement data of medical disposables from Dutch university medical centers (UMCs) and manually classified this data, enabling us to calculate environmental impact based on physical units (e.g., the number of items per product) rather than solely financial figures. This approach provides a more accurate representation of the actual volume of materials consumed, as financial data alone can give a distorted view due to price variations or economies of scale. By using physical units, we were able to more precisely estimate which products contribute the most to environmental burden and where the greatest sustainability gains could be achieved. Thereby our study addresses a critical gap by providing a comprehensive analysis of medical disposables used across multiple healthcare settings (Mang et al., 2023). This broader perspective is essential to prioritize impactful interventions that can swiftly reduce raw material use and waste production on a sector-wide scale. While a shift toward reusable alternatives presents a significant opportunity, it also requires careful consideration of operational changes within hospital

workflows. Such transitions may involve substantial time and resources, highlighting the need for strategic planning and targeted implementation support to facilitate sustainable practices effectively. To support such investments, obtaining accurate data on the scale of medical disposable use is essential. The aggregated data on the volumes and environmental impacts of these disposables, as used in our study, can help identify which products should be prioritized for reduction to achieve significant environmental benefits quickly.

The goal of this research project is to identify the 50 medical disposable products with the highest estimated environmental impact currently used in Dutch University Medical Centers (UMCs) and to assess the feasibility of reducing this impact in the short term for around 20 of these products. The methodology involves a detailed analysis of purchasing data from these UMCs, complemented by prioritization and formulation of recommendations through focus group discussions.

Methodology

Our study employed a mixed-method approach that combined quantitative procurement data analysis with qualitative insights from focus groups. In the quantitative phase, we gathered procurement data from six of the seven Dutch UMCs, focusing on disposable medical products ordered in quantities over 1,000 units, as well as the top 50 products by cost (calculated as price multiplied by quantity). Each product was manually classified according to its primary material composition and designated as either disposable or reusable. This classification allowed us to directly analyze physical units, providing a more accurate reflection of disposable consumption. After categorization, we analyzed the data to identify the most frequently ordered disposables and those with the highest environmental impact potential, based on material type and usage patterns.

To complement this quantitative data, we conducted two rounds of focus group sessions with healthcare professionals from various hospitals and departments, including physicians, infection prevention, logistics, and waste management. The first round aimed to establish initial insights on feasible replacements and waste-reduction strategies, while the second round focused on validating and refining these initial findings. Focus group participants evaluated each disposable item for its potential to switch to reusable alternatives, reduce use through behavior change, or improve recycling efforts (based on the R-ladder framework). Discussions also highlighted challenges, such as infection control, the durability of reusable items, and the infrastructure required for recycling and reuse. These qualitative insights informed the development of a shortlist of most impactful and actionable medical disposables, supported with short- and long-term recommendations, structured around the feasibility of each intervention within the hospital setting.

Results

The environmental impact assessment of the longlist of 50 items highlights significant variability in CO₂-equivalent emissions across different product categories. The top 50 items, ranked by estimated CO₂-footprint, demonstrate the substantial environmental footprint of commonly used medical disposables. The highest impact was observed in syringes without needles, with an estimated 1.1 kt of CO₂-eq for 16.1 million units ordered. Other high-impact items included oxygen sensors (0.5 kt CO₂-eq), non-sterile gloves (0.5 kt CO₂-eq), and skin cleansing wipes (0.5 kt CO₂-eq). While non-sterile gloves were ordered in large quantities (38.2 million units), their per-unit environmental impact was relatively lower compared to items like oxygen sensors or baby bottles, which have higher per-unit impacts.

The focus group sessions resulted in a shortlist of 22 high-impact disposable products for which sustainable alternatives were deemed feasible, categorized by recommended interventions for short-

and long-term implementation. Disposable items identified as candidates for reusable alternatives included surgical gowns, protective gowns, and certain trays, where infrastructure allowed for collection and reprocessing. Products for which reusable options were deemed unfeasible due to hygiene or logistical challenges included items like bandages, swabs, and needles. In these cases, focus group participants emphasized the potential for minimizing overuse (refuse/reduce), such as by using a single gauze for blood collection or IV insertion instead of multiple gauzes, as well as opportunities for improved recycling infrastructure, particularly for items like urine collection bags and infusion lines. Additionally, the focus groups identified significant discrepancies in disposable product usage rates across UMCs, suggesting an opportunity for optimization through standardized usage practices.

A full overview of the quantities and impact of the top 50 items, as well as the recommendations related to the 22 shortlist items is available.

Discussion and conclusions

The findings reveal both the environmental impact of disposable medical products and significant variation in usage patterns across hospitals, offering valuable insights to inform hospital-level sustainability strategies. Focus group discussions highlighted the importance of internal communication and knowledge sharing about sustainable practices, emphasizing that coordinated purchasing efforts across hospitals could substantially influence suppliers to adopt more sustainable product practices. These prioritized, actionable interventions, if implemented on a national level, have the potential to significantly contribute to the Dutch Green Deal's goal of halving raw material consumption by 2030.

This study extends current sustainability research by providing a comprehensive, sector-wide view of disposable product use in healthcare, addressing a crucial gap in the literature. By using actual procurement data and physical unit measurements rather than financial proxies, our approach enhances the accuracy of environmental impact estimates and allows for more precise, targeted recommendations. Key insights from this data-driven analysis identify high-impact disposables—such as surgical and protective gowns—as priority areas for reuse initiatives, while proposing strategies for products that lack reusable alternatives, such as minimizing overuse and improving recycling practices.

Recommendations emerging from our findings advocate for multi-institutional collaboration, both in knowledge sharing and collective purchasing strategies, to exert greater influence on suppliers for sustainable product innovation. Implementing reusable alternatives or recycling systems often requires structural changes in hospital workflows, and hospital management must invest in logistics, infrastructure, and training to enable these shifts. Beyond healthcare, this study contributes to the broader purchasing and supply chain management literature by demonstrating how coordinated purchasing strategies can amplify bargaining power, prompting suppliers to adopt sustainability practices that benefit the entire supply chain. Additionally, integrating supplier relationship management within sustainability initiatives proves essential, as suppliers' willingness to adapt to demand for sustainable options is critical for systemic change. Together, these findings offer a scalable model for promoting sustainability across sectors reliant on disposables.

Paper topic

16. Sustainability – environmental

Resource sharing and joint knowledge creation: Mechanisms through which collaborative culture stimulates innovation in buyer-supplier dyads

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Resource sharing and joint knowledge creation: Mechanisms through which collaborative culture stimulates innovation in buyer-supplier dyads.

Keywords: collaborative culture, innovation, joint knowledge creation, resource sharing

Abstract

There is a broad agreement on the effect of national and organisational cultures on innovation. However, the nexus between collaborative culture and innovation in buyer-supplier relationships has remained unexplored. Hence, even though the effect of collaborative culture on innovation in buyer-supplier relationships can be inferred from the effect of national culture and organisational culture on innovation, empirical evidence is required to validate this theoretical inference (Ma, et al., 2023). Additionally, the mechanisms through which the inference between collaborative culture and innovation occurs remains a metaphoric black box that needs unravelling.

The literature on the effects of culture on innovation suggests that culture will lead to innovation when it enables key organisational activities (Shehzad et al., 2023). Similarly, we believe that a collaborative culture should trigger some key inter-organisational activities and practices that help enable innovation – “the extent to which a firm works jointly with its supply chain partners in introducing new processes, products or services” (Cao & Zhang, 2013, p. 79).

Accordingly, we propose a network of adjacent mechanisms through which collaborative culture contributes to innovation in buyer-supplier relationships by proposing two mediating variables – resource sharing and joint knowledge creation. Resource sharing, which denotes “the process of leveraging assets and making asset investments amongst supply chain partners” (Cao & Zhang, 2013, p. 64) and joint knowledge creation, which denotes “the extent to which supply chain partners develop a

better understanding of and response to the market and competitive environment by working together” (Cao & Zhang, 2013, p. 67).

Our research framework links collaborative culture, collaborative practices and innovation. Limited studies exist on the collaborative culture and innovation nexus (Acquah, 2023; Yang et al., 2018). We, through this paper, contribute to the literature by not only establishing the impact of collaborative culture on innovation, but also by empirically identifying and validating the mechanisms through which collaborative culture enhances innovation in buyer-supplier relationships.

Prior research highlights the need to investigate how collaborative cultural activities can drive collaborative practices such as resource sharing and joint knowledge creation (Acquah et al., 2021; Nguyen et al., 2022). Moreover, there is a need for a more nuanced understanding of the effects of resource-sharing behaviours and joint knowledge creation. (Le et al., 2020). Additionally, collaborative culture has been identified as a critical enabler in joint knowledge-creation activities (Yang et al., 2018), while previous empirical studies have not fully explained the collaborative cultural innovation mechanisms through resource sharing and joint knowledge-creation (Awan et al., 2013). Our paper purports to fill these gaps by addressing the following research questions: RQ1. Does collaborative culture directly contribute to enhancing innovation in buyer-supplier relationships? RQ2. Do resource sharing and joint knowledge creation mediate the effects of collaborative culture on innovation in buyer-supplier relationships?

In this quantitative study, we apply structural equation modelling to a unique sample of 166 supply chain participants in Ghana’s downstream petroleum sector. This unique sample comprises bulk oil distributors, oil marketing companies and Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) marketing companies. Our results indicate that innovation increases with high levels of collaborative culture. Also, even though joint knowledge creation mediated the effects of collaborative culture on innovation, resource sharing is not a mechanism through which collaborative culture enhances innovation in buyer-supplier relationships. A combination of collaborative cultural behaviours such as long-term orientation, power symmetry, uncertainty avoidance and collectivism promote innovation amongst supply chain partners.

We contribute to the conversation by offering empirical insights not only on how collaborative culture amongst supply chain partners helps promote innovation but also underscoring the complex mechanisms through which collaborative activities enhance innovation in supply chain dyads. Further, the study extends our understanding of collaborative culture by validating resource sharing as a mediator of the effect of collaborative culture on innovation while modelling collaborative culture as a higher-order construct related to resource sharing and joint knowledge creation.

Practically, we provide insights to managers on how to boost business performance through investment in collaborative cultural building activities in a way that facilitates resource sharing and joint knowledge creation in supply chain dyads.

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Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 10. Purchasing innovation, 2. PSM strategy

Case study AI in purchasing: AI-driven offer comparison

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Practitioner Paper

Abstract/summary

Motivation and Problem Statement

There is a widespread consensus regarding the transformative potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on the future of work and work processes, particularly in the field of purchasing. While academics and practitioners have discussed this potential, there remains a scarcity of literature and dialogue surrounding the implementation of pilot projects that utilize AI in purchasing (Allal-Chérif et al., 2021; Meyer and Henke, 2023; Schulze-Horn et al., 2020; Spreitzenbarth et al., 2024).

This paper presents a case study detailing the implementation of a pilot project aimed at introducing an AI solution in purchasing. Specifically, we developed and piloted a Generative AI (GenAI) tool designed for comparing offers. The case study outlines the selection of the use case, the organization of the pilot, and the challenges encountered throughout the process.

A significant challenge for purchasing departments is taking the initial steps on their AI journey. This involves translating the apparent potential of AI into concrete use cases and securing company resources for pilot projects by demonstrating tangible benefits. Purchasing departments often find themselves competing with other business areas, such as marketing, which may already be more advanced in using AI (Constant et al., 2022, S. 2).

The motivation for this paper is to deepen the understanding of AI pilot projects in purchasing. It is essential not only to discuss potential benefits and barriers but also to share experiences from actual pilot projects. Currently, Generative AI is at the "peak of inflated expectations" phase of the Gartner Hype Cycle (Gartner, 2023), making it crucial to gain insights during this phase to foster positive momentum.

Methodology

This paper is structured into two methodological sections. The first section presents a literature review of AI applications in purchasing. Thereby a comprehensive landscape of valuable AI implementations within purchasing processes is established. This literature review incorporates both scholarly articles and white papers from consulting firms.

The second methodological section details the execution of an AI pilot project, presented as a case study. This case study is designed in a holistic single-case design and was conducted from April to June 2024 (Yin, 2018). It encompasses the selection of the AI application offer comparison and the implementation of the AI solution in a pilot project in the purchasing department of a company in the HVAC industry.

The case study addresses the challenges of the pilot project AI-driven offer comparison, evaluates the benefits of the use case, and outlines the subsequent steps following the pilot phase.

Findings

The findings from the case study are discussed in relation to three key questions:

1. How was the GenAI solution implemented during the pilot phase?
2. What challenges were encountered during the pilot phase?
3. How can the GenAI solution be scaled beyond the pilot phase?

1. How was the GenAI solution implemented during the pilot phase?

The AI tool was developed through several iterations. The iterative process involved loading two offers from different suppliers into the AI tool for a tender. Ten evaluation criteria were defined to analyze the offers via prompts. The AI tool then assessed the degree of fulfillment of the two offers against these criteria, assigning a score from zero to four. For each score, the tool provided a brief explanation of the evaluation.

The ratings generated by the AI tool were subsequently compared with those of the buyers. In cases of significant discrepancies, an iteration was conducted, during which the prompts for specific categories were modified. The technical implementation of the GenAI pilot project was executed on Microsoft Azure, utilizing Azure OpenAI. The front end of the tool was developed using PowerApps.

2. What challenges were faced during the pilot phase?

During the pilot phase, it became evident that the precision of the evaluation criteria prompts significantly impacted the quality of the results. Crafting these prompts required a detailed description of each of the ten criteria, which was relatively time-consuming. The pilot project focused on a material group from indirect purchasing, and the prompts were tailored specifically to this material. Other material groups would necessitate customized prompts.

Another challenge was the limited information available to the AI tool, which was restricted to the two offer documents. In practice, however, supplier relationships and the buyer's prior experiences with suppliers may also be relevant. Additional information, such as insights gained from phone calls or queries, could not be incorporated into the AI tool's evaluation.

3. How can the GenAI solution be scaled beyond the pilot phase?

The challenge of customizing prompts for different material groups could be addressed by creating a library of predefined prompts. This would reduce the customization effort required for new tenders, as an existing prompt set for a specific material group could serve as a foundation.

The goal of the GenAI pilot is not to completely transfer the task of offer analysis from the buyer to the AI tool, but rather to provide optimal support to the buyer. For instance, the AI tool could offer an initial assessment (preliminary evaluation) of the offers, allowing the buyer to focus on a detailed analysis of only the top three offers identified by the AI tool. Additionally, the buyer could leverage the AI tool to quickly identify the main differences between various offers.

Relevance

AI solutions are poised to revolutionize purchasing by transforming tasks, work processes, and required skills. The opportunities presented by Generative AI are substantial, as applications can be implemented more easily, yielding impressive results.

Collaborative discussions on specific AI use cases in purchasing make the topic more tangible for both academia and practice. This level of detail is essential for identifying challenges and collaboratively developing solutions. To date, there are few comprehensive descriptions of AI pilot projects in purchasing that go beyond merely listing potential applications. This paper aims to bridge that gap and serve as a foundation for further discussion and exchange.

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Paper topic

11. Digital, 2. PSM strategy, 8. P2P, sourcing analysis

35

Retrospection of healthcare procurement on the COVID-19 pandemic Preparedness for future disruptions

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed critical vulnerabilities in healthcare systems, particularly in procurement and preparedness for supply chain disruptions. Hospitals were crucial in responding to these disruptions, and purchasing experts were at the core of the turmoil. This study addresses the main barriers and best practices for developing hospital preparedness plans. A case study research was conducted, including 15 interviews with purchasing experts in German hospitals. This paper provides a roadmap based on best practices designed to support hospitals in strengthening their preparedness plans. We attempt to raise awareness of the lack of preparedness plans in hospitals from a procurement perspective.

Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

Financialization in procurement: practices and consequences

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

Financialization affects the procurement area of organizations, influencing their strategies. In this context, this study aims to identify the consequences and practices of financialization within the procurement area. Through a systematic literature review and content analysis, we uncovered a set of thirteen consequences of financialization in procurement, mostly detrimental to company and society in the long term. Additionally, we identify thirty practices for shareholder value maximization, related to costs and assets reduction and increase in revenue and goodwill. These practices and consequences are arranged in a conceptual framework, leading into two propositions, with managerial and theoretical implications.

Paper topic

2. PSM strategy, 3. Purchasing organisation, 19. Supply chain finance

When buyer dependence becomes a vendor lock-in: a critical incident study

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Open University, Heerlen, Netherlands

Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

Organizations rely on transactions and relationships with suppliers to ensure their survival, which always brings certain levels of buyer dependency. Dependency as such is not problematic, although excessive buyer dependence can take the form of a vendor lock-in with many risks and disadvantages for buying companies. It is therefore remarkable that limited research has been conducted on vendor lock-ins. To address this gap, we used the Critical Incident Technique to study the experiences of Dutch manufacturing managers. A total number of 28 thick descriptions were found, detailing critical circumstances that triggered the emergence of vendor lock-in situations. Analysis of the interview data resulted in a comprehensive overview of vendor lock-in types.

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Adopting servant leadership in purchasing and supply management: principles, opportunities, best practices, and challenges

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Business performance – whether understood in terms of profits, value creation, resilience, or sustainability – increasingly relies on the quality and stability of relationships with external partners, especially strategic suppliers (Ali & al. 2024; Poissonnier & al., 2024). The recognition, consultation, integration, and valorization of these suppliers is essential to enable successful innovation and jointly obtain decisive competitive advantages (Allal-Chérif & al., 2022). Furthermore, collaborative, inclusive, and responsible purchasing approaches give meaning and well-being to purchasing professions, long plagued by cost-killing practices (Silva & Ruel, 2022). Other companies have even more original and moral practices by seeking to respond to the needs of their suppliers as a priority. They adopt principles of servant leadership such as: prioritizing ethics before profit, honoring and empowering others, being humble and trusting, and demonstrating empathy and stewardship (Spears & Lawrence, 2016). However, the literature on the adoption of servant leadership theory by purchasing and supply management is only emerging. It therefore seems essential to us to fill this gap by characterizing the opportunities, best practices, and associated limitations.

This article answers the following research question: to what extent can servant leadership theory be applied to the field of purchasing and supply management? We offer recommendations resulting from an analysis of the very rich literature on servant leadership and its transposition to purchasing contexts different from those originally described by Greenleaf (2007) such as marketing (Zarei & al., 2022) or teaching (Hays, 2008). The literature review reveals all the benefits of servant leadership in its different applications in an interorganizational context (Gutierrez-Broncano & al., 2024; Urrila & Eva, 2024), without forgetting to mention the associated limitations (Nichols & al. 2020; Canavesi & Minelli, 2022). This article draws on an in-depth longitudinal case study of a multinational industrial company that has adopted servant leadership within its various departments, including purchasing, for around ten years. The data was collected as part of discussions within a research chair, during semi-directive interviews, and following non-participant observation. Servant leadership helps reduce buyer turnover and build loyalty because they work in a healthier environment, are subject to much less pressure, and receive recognition other than simple bonuses. It also helps build loyalty and integrate suppliers as extensions of the company because their expertise is recognized, their creativity is unleashed, and their performance is rewarded. However, the application of servant leadership in purchasing can also involve certain limitations that require specific adaptations.

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Paper topic

12. Ethics, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 2. PSM strategy

"What could go wrong?". Unlocking AI Potential in Supply Chain Management: Design Principles and Best Practices

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The fourth industrial revolution, widely known as Industry 4.0, is profoundly reshaping the industrial landscape through the integration of cutting-edge technologies such as cyber-physical systems, the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, and Artificial Intelligence (AI). Artificial Intelligence is a technology that aims to replicate human abilities in learning, reasoning, and self-correction. In recent years, AI has gained increasing popularity and attracted the attention of researchers and organizations due to advancements in the underlying technology, its growing applicability, and its potential to deliver significant results. The interest in this technology is so substantial that experts predict the AI market will grow tenfold within the next decade as stated in a recent article published on Forbes Advisor (Maheschwari, 2024).

Today's industrial context is characterized by a highly competitive marketplace and increasing complexity. Additionally, the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020 highlighted the weaknesses and vulnerabilities of traditional supply chain and production processes. Together with growing stakeholder demands for resilience, these challenges have accelerated the need for organizations to shift toward technology-driven paradigms. The ability of AI to enhance decision-making, reduce cycle times, and improve operational efficiency positions it as one of the most promising technologies to address operations and supply chain challenges.

Despite its transformative potential, AI adoption on an industrial scale remains limited (Armonk, 2024). Currently, the development and implementation of such technologies are primarily the domain of large organizations. Early adopters have explored the technology's potential and plan to undertake more AI projects, demonstrating its disruptive impact on organizational processes. However, implementing such projects requires significant investment in financial and human resources, as well as a strong commitment to innovation and digital transformation capabilities.

Many organizations attempting to adopt AI encounter significant challenges during implementation, leading to project failures and to limited results compared to expectations (Merhi, 2023). This creates a paradox: while AI can offer substantial benefits, its successful integration requires overcoming numerous obstacles, which often became clear and evident only when implementation fails. For this reason, some researchers have begun investigating the reasons behind AI project failures and identifying

critical success factors that practitioners should consider during the implementation process. (Merhi, 2021, 2023; Meyer & Henke, 2023).

Although some studies have tackled the topic of AI implementation effectiveness, there are still limited contributions that provide comprehensive and empirically tested guidelines to support managers and companies during this complex process. This research seeks to bridge this gap by developing a generalized framework of design principles to guide practitioners in AI system implementation in the field of operations and supply chain management.

The framework is derived based on a mixed method approach, combining a systematic literature review, which identifies the current state of knowledge on factors and guidelines for AI implementation, and the development of case studies to evaluate its potential effectiveness.

In particular, the systematic literature review identified 15 works that allowed to develop a set of 10 design principles aimed at supporting practitioners in deploying AI in supply chain processes. The framework stands out from previous works, and it not only provides practitioners with critical factors to consider, but also suggests approaches and activities, highlighting their importance, that organizations should adopt to enhance the likelihood of a successful implementation.

To validate the framework, an empirical investigation has been conducted. Specifically, three case studies have been developed in large industrial organizations. In particular, the case studies investigated implementation projects of AI solutions to support supply chain management processes, analyzing in detail the processes followed during these projects. The findings from the case studies have been compared to the proposed framework to assess its applicability and establish a hierarchy of importance for the identified design principles. In particular, we identified some implementation principles that represent necessary conditions for a successful implementation project, and others that contribute to making the implementation more effective and can reduce the duration of the implementation project.

Based on this analysis, a final framework for AI implementation is proposed, along with guidelines for its use in practical applications. In particular, the identified design principles refer to the following areas:

- Employees management
- Stakeholders' management
- Top management
- Data and infrastructure
- AI knowledge
- Post deployment
- Financial capability
- Governance and communication
- Organization's strategy
- Organization's structure

For each principle a set of proper practices have been developed, based on both the systematic literature review and the analyzed case studies, thus identifying 32 best practices.

The contribution of the work is twofold. First of all, we summarize the current knowledge on AI implementation in SCM in a structured framework that provide a reference point to any work willing to investigate this topic in further detail. Second, we provide a reference guideline for practitioners on how to tackle AI implementation, supporting innovation and anticipating relevant constraints to the first steps of the development projects.

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Paper topic

11. Digital

Supplier driven barriers to internal integration?

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Abstract

Internal integration has been shown to distinguish advanced organisations from less advanced organisations that struggle with competitive disparity. In this paper we take a closer look at dilemmas that surface in the transfer of tasks from purchase to production in Swedish forest companies and trace these integration failures to the fact that both purchasing and production departments have important supplier relationships that impact their respective perception on how to coordinate their internal work flow. We base our reasoning on a supplier relationship approach, and on previous studies on departmental integration and conflict in the area of purchasing. Empirically the paper make use of a qualitative study on the matter in four large Swedish forest organisations.

Background and purpose of the study

Division of labour into various functional “expert” areas, such as purchasing, marketing and production, has ever since the late 1700s formed a basis for much departmentalization (Crittenden et al., 1993). However, as stated by Crittenden et al. (1993, p. 299): “potential conflict exists between any of two or more business functions within an organization”, and can lead to both “interfunctional conflict and myopic functional-level decisions” (ibid.) as illustrated by a purchaser in the forest sector:

“Thus far, I have never been in conversation where there has been follow up on the planning, to make sure that it works well when it is transferred (to the other department). These aspects are not perceived as valuable.”

This statement from within a modern Swedish forest association is just one of several, from both the purchasing and production side, showing that not only is the integration between departments in forestry lacking, but there is also a general lack of focus on reaching a better integration. One of the managers at another Swedish forest association expressed, when questioned on the lack of integration between departments, that: *“It does always get fixed somehow anyway.”* As an outsider it does

however strike you as troublesome and, as a business researcher, as quite intriguing to understand: How can it be that an industry that is screaming for raw material is willing to accept so much resources leakage within their own organisation?

Integration can be defined as “the quality of the state of collaboration that exists among departments that are required to achieve unity of effort by the demands of the environment” (Lawrence & Lorsch, 1967, p. 11). It is a process of collaboration between departments with the purpose to “arrive at mutually acceptable outcomes for their organization” (Pagell, 2004, p. 460). Previous research has shown that integration is a variable that distinguishes advanced organisations from less advanced organisations that struggle with competitive disparity (Cousins et al, 2006; Ellegaard & Koch, 2012; 2014). Organizational integration has also been found to affect many performance parameters such as customer satisfaction, growth in sales and product quality, to mention just a few (Das et al, 2006; Flynn et al., 2010; Handfield et al, 2009).

This study aims at studying reasons for low integration stemming from external supplier relationships. There are quite a few studies on internal integration, but less so with a purchasing angle and even less combining the external and internal, especially with a purchasing focus. However, in a study from 2012, Ellegaard and Koch investigate the effect of internal integration on supplier resource mobilisation, and find that the buying company waste much resources trying to fix issues created by uncoordinated behaviours. They found that the purchasing function was most often left without advice for how to improve their coordination with other departments relative to suppliers. Hence, this study adds to their findings, by turning the arrow the opposite direction.

Study design and methodological considerations

In this paper we take a closer look at dilemmas that surface in the transfer from purchase to production in four Swedish forest companies and relate these dilemmas or tensions to the fact that both purchasing and production departments have important supplier relationships that impact their respective perception on how to coordinate their internal work flow. As two of the authors are part of an organisation dedicated to research on forestry, the idea behind the project and its aim was empirically problem based. We knew before the study started that there were integration issues to address in the forest sector. In order to reach insight into this type of issue we needed a qualitative method that provided enough depth and detail.

Our interpretation of the problem at hand was written up in a short typo that was then sent out to six large Swedish forest organisations (associations or private forest companies) with a question if they were interested in participation in a study on the matter. We wanted participating organisations that agreed with us on the existence of the problem statement in general terms, and that were willing to let us into their organisation to interview a number of their employees. All the approached organisations were of medium to large size both in turnover and number of employees, since size is said to amplify integration challenges. All organisations were also organised functionally, with different specialised departments along the processing chain, since a) this is a common way to organize forestry, and b) one of the challenges becomes reaching a well-functioning integration between departments.

In the next step, we interviewed top executives from four of the six organisations in order to reach an understanding of their organisational background, organisational arrangements and business models.

Knowing that there is heterogeneity facing each organisation, we also asked them to pick out two regional offices in the organisation with slightly different market conditions. During a time period of eight months in 2023, we interviewed 46 persons in total, of which 10 were interviews with top management and 11 were with managers from the purchasing or the production side, 13 of the respondents were purchasers and 10 worked on the production side of the interface. All data has then been coded and analysed based on the Gioia method (Gioia et al., 2013).

Disposition of the final paper and contributions

The paper will be structured as follows. Section 1 present the background in internal integration and lack thereof especially related to supply management and show our area of investigation. In section 2, we provide the theoretical framing of the study by a discussion of departmentalization and integration between functions paired with studies on supplier relationships as portrayed in previous research. In section 3, we describe the research design including collection of material and analysis. Section 4 presents the empirical results before the discussion is made in section 5. Finally, in section 6, we draw conclusions, show implications for management and make suggestions for future research efforts on the matter.

The study makes several contributions. Through the focus on external supplier relationships and their role in the challenge, we contribute to the supply management, purchasing and business network literature. By uncovering reasons for low integration between departments, the paper also contributes to research on operations management. While there are studies on supply chain integration (e.g. Richey et al., 2010), there are less studies that connect internal integration efforts with external relationships.

Paper topic

3. Purchasing organisation, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 20.
Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

41

Market shaping through public government procurement: Challenges and tensions

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The aim of this study is to contribute to knowledge on the shaping of markets through public government procurement. This through investigate the market shaping process and investigate tensions arising that influence this process. Empirical data consists of information from 39 semi-structured interviews with respondents from a) a large Swedish agency, b) suppliers to the agency and c) corresponding agencies in the other Nordic countries. Findings reveal challenges and tensions influencing the market shaping process belonging to four overarching themes: Procurement and Innovation, Procurement and Supplier Relationships, Procurement and Organisation, and Procurement and Value.

Paper topic

13. Public procurement

What is necessary to get Purchasers behave innovatively? Work climate or personality?

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This research examines the individual and collective factors necessary for buyers to engage in innovative behaviour, focusing on personality traits and work climate. Based on an online survey of 370 purchasers in France, this study applies necessary condition analysis to identify the traits and work climate settings that must be present for purchaser to innovatively behave. The results show that first individual personality - especially openness to experience and conscientiousness - and then a cohesion within the purchasing team play an important role. The study contributes to the purchasing and innovation management literature by emphasizing the interplay between personal and organizational influences and provides managerial insights for fostering innovation in procurement functions.

Paper topic

1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 10. Purchasing innovation

Harnessing supply chain governance mechanisms to promote resilience through supply chain collaboration

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Harnessing supply chain governance mechanisms to promote resilience through supply chain collaboration

Keywords: Supply chain resilience, supply chain collaboration, supply chain governance, small and medium sized enterprises

Abstract

Due to the increased complexity and volatility within the business environment which sometimes causes disruptions in supply chains, there has been a need to explore various mechanisms that enhance Supply chain resilience – “the ability of a supply chain to quickly anticipate, prepare, adapt and recover back normal supply chain operations after the occurrence of disruptions” (Hohenstein et al., 2015). This has become necessary for firms in emerging economies, especially for manufacturing small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). We investigate the nexus between Supply Chain Governance (SCG) and Supply Chain Resilience (SCR), with emphasis on the mediating role of Supply Chain Collaboration (SCC) in the Ghanaian manufacturing SME context. We present how governance mechanisms, specifically Rational Governance (RG) and Contractual Governance (CG), can be exploited to foster a stronger resilient supply chain in an uncertain and dynamic business environment. The significant role of governance structures in the mitigation of supply chain disruptions has been greatly emphasised by previous studies (Mabotia, 2022; Nsowah, 2022; Lin et al., 2023; Lu et al., 2024). Despite these significant findings, the mediation pathways through which supply chain governance influences supply chain resilience are still underexplored, especially in the context of emerging economies such as Ghana.

Supply chain governance, which refers to the systems, structures, and processes that an organisation uses to control its supply chain to enhance efficiency and compliance to achieve its strategic objectives, plays a critical role in fostering resilience (Tsolakis et al., 2023; Lu et al., 2024). We believe that when supply chains employ both formal (contractual) and informal (relational) governance mechanisms to regulate their supply chain, they, together with their partners, can prevent disruptions, as well as quickly

resume back to normal operations after disruption (Keller et al., 2021; Bonatto et al., 2022; Lu et al., 2023). Additionally, studies have demonstrated that incorporating governance techniques improves the resilience of supply chains by enhancing smooth flow and management of resources, maintaining standards and strategic consistency across all levels (Li et al., 2023). While there is a growing recognition of the importance of harnessing governance mechanisms in achieving resilience, there still remains a gap in understanding how its combined formal and informal mechanisms affect resilience in a resource-constrained business environment like Ghana.

Research has also shown the importance of SCC, the degree to which supply chain partners work together to effectively manage supply chain operations to achieve a common goal in enhancing resilience (Cao et al. 2010). Hence, as supply chain partners share information, jointly make decisions and manage risks together, they are able to develop a more resilient supply chain (Wadudu, 2022 & Brobbey, 2024). Also, SCC has been shown to increase supply chain partners' commitment and trust, which typically enables more robust responses to disruptions (Baah et al. 2022). While governance mechanisms are not integrally dynamic or adaptive in isolation, collaboration among supply chain partners can help bridge this gap by enabling the operationalization of governance mechanisms through framework agreements, information sharing and collective resource pooling (Jain et al., 2005; Barbieri et al., 2021). Moreover, an underlying governance system is typically required for these cooperative initiatives to be effective. Despite this, prior studies have not fully examined the mechanisms through which supply chain governance fosters the resilience of supply chains. The study argues that supply chain collaboration, is a mechanism through which relational and contractual governance influence supply chain resilience. Accordingly, the study sought to fill these gaps by answering the following research questions: RQ1. How does Supply Chain Governance Influence Supply Chain Resilience in Manufacturing SMEs in Ghana? RQ2. To what extent does Supply Chain Collaboration mediate the relationship between Supply Chain Governance and Supply Chain Resilience?

This study uses the quantitative approach to test the relationship between variables by employing the structural equation modelling technique. Data will be collected from a group of 389 small and medium-sized manufacturing companies in the Accra Metropolis of Ghana (Ghana Statistical Service report from 2016). Considering the challenges faced by SMEs in Saharan Africa, such as limited resources and unstable markets, among others, selecting Ghana as the research setting holds significant relevance. The participants in the research include supply chain managers and procurement managers working in small and medium manufacturing enterprises and staff responsible for supply chain management tasks within these enterprises.

Our study provides a robust analytical framework for understanding the interdependencies between SCG, SCC and SCR. The study also extends our knowledge of collaboration as a mechanism through which supply chain governance can enhance the resilience of firms. The study's findings, which highlight the importance of governance mechanisms, are anticipated to have a major impact on supply chain managers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders in Ghana and other emerging economies. For industrial practitioners, this study provides a clear way of achieving resilience by investing in formal and informal governance structures to enhance collaboration among supply chain partners.

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Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 12. Ethics

The critical role of Supply Chain Finance on corporate performance. The case of Startups and SMEs

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

In a global financial landscape that is characterized by a growing complexity and high levels of competition, Startups and Small and Midsize Enterprises (SMEs) encounter major financial challenges that severely affect their corporate performance and eventually jeopardize their viability. The solution to this problem comes with the application of Supply chain finance (SCF) tools, which help build a trust environment among the involved parties (buyers – suppliers - banks) and set the framework for a win-win situation through simple and fast payable processes. SCF incorporates a range of financial instruments and practices designed to enhance the working capital of firms all throughout the supply chain. For Startups and SMEs specifically the SCF tools provide access to timely funding that is critical for managing operational costs, fulfilling orders, and investing in progress initiatives. By leveraging SCF solutions such as platform financing, dynamic discounting, and reverse factoring, these companies can unlock trapped capital, reduce payment cycles, and enhance their total purchasing power. Therefore, the aim of this paper is to shed light on the crucial role that SCF plays in building resilient supply chains for Startups and SMEs, allowing them to overcome financial constraints while fostering scalability and enhancing operational resilience and competitiveness. In support of the above, various business cases from leading global industries are utilized to justify the SCF impact in the real world. The findings showcase that the role of SCF in building resilient supply chains has drastically evolved, especially in the case of SMEs, via the establishment of strong, collaborative partnerships marked by transparent sharing of timely and valuable information as well as optimizing critical business processes through automation and better terms.

Paper topic

19. Supply chain finance

Circular economy: Tensions in implementing the 10 R-principles

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This paper provides insight into tensions related to understanding and implementing CE, applying the lens of paradox theory. This research uses a combination of primary empirical data and secondary data to explore tensions to CE in practice using the 10-R circular practices. The paper develops five propositions based on the analysis of qualitative data. Among the case studies, CE practices appear to be embedded in the traditional business model where profit maximization—or something that resembles profit maximization—drives decision making. The archetypal tension of financial performance/ cost reduction shapes CE practice.

Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 10. Purchasing innovation

Beyond the contract, the future of agency theory

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This paper explores supplier challenges when delivering social value in UK public procurement contracts. We use agency theory to explore principal–agent relationships within contracts and propose expanding it to include a socio-economic logic perspective. A taxonomy of buyer–supplier relationships, shaped by differing institutional logics, is introduced to explain agency loss for non-financial outcomes. This expanded framework provides new insights of opportunities for agency gain and future market shaping, thereby challenging the extant literature’s assumption of agency loss. The paper responds to the call for more qualitative research in supply chain orientated agency theory by contributing the agent’s perspective.

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 13. Public procurement, 17. Sustainability - social

ESG Practices: Impact and Contributions of the Governance Axis in the Procurement Area – A Bibliometric Analysis

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This study examines, through a bibliometric analysis, the impact and contribution that the governance axis of ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) practices brings to the enhancement of governance in the procurement area within organizations and for their stakeholders, both internal and external.

Chen and Paulraj (2004) describe that the procurement area operates on two fronts: an external one, focused on engaging and negotiating with stakeholders outside the organization, particularly suppliers, and an internal one, focused on collaboration and interaction with the organization's stakeholders. The large number of interactions with virtually all internal and external members of the supply chain requires effective actions to guide and harmonize the agendas of each stakeholder.

Within the responsibilities of the procurement area, achieving collaboration between internal and external stakeholders results in aligning the procurement process with the organization's objectives and needs.

However, within the political arena of organizations, procurement areas face significant challenges, such as obtaining support and recognition to proactively manage procurement processes, with clearly defined functions and responsibilities aligned with the organization's objectives and strategies. This aids in empowering negotiation and reorienting the implicit interests of stakeholders, which naturally diverge from the organization's interests. For this, there is a need for an effective, transparent, and unequivocal governance structure.

In parallel, studies on ESG practices are growing and occupying a crucial position in works related to the procurement area. For example, in 2024, at the annual IPSERA meeting held in Rio de Janeiro, 47% of the accepted papers focused on procurement themes associated with ESG or sustainability. However, less than 10% of these articles addressed, even tangentially, the governance aspect, with the majority concentrating on the environmental and social dimensions (Schiele and Ribeiro 2024). The importance of ESG practices is also growing outside the academic field, as evidenced by Deloitte's 2023 CPO Survey, where ESG became the second priority for executives in the area.

Aligning procurement governance with ESG practices tends to create a mutually beneficial relationship, generating positive results for the procurement area, the organization, and the internal and external parties involved in procurement processes, thereby reinforcing and strengthening ESG practices.

Methodology

Using the Scopus and Web of Science databases, the literature was mapped to identify the main strands and evaluate research that relates to the topic directly or tangentially, seeking to identify the main lines of thought, emerging trends, opportunities, and potential gaps. The terms Supply Chain, Procurement, and Purchase were considered for obtaining articles and consolidated in this work under the term "Procurement."

The research was conducted in two rounds, the first focusing on the relationship between ESG and Procurement, and the second with a more detailed focus on the relationship between ESG and Procurement Governance. After checking the main articles found on the topic, a final selection was reached. Between the years 1997 and 2024, 6,709 articles involving (ESG and S) were found, of which 215 articles between 2009 and 2024 involve (ESG and GS), meaning only 3.2% of the articles involving (ESG and S) incorporate the governance theme in procurement, with 196 of these articles (91%) published between 2021 and 2024, demonstrating a recent growth in scientific investigation. However, these articles mostly tangentially address the focus of interest of this study; no articles centered specifically on the ESG and GS theme were located.

Findings

Through bibliometric analysis, three questions described in the formulation of the research problem were answered, indicating that:

1. Regarding the current state and trajectory of publications that relate ESG practices and governance in procurement compared to publications that relate ESG practices and procurement, current studies predominantly emphasize the environmental and social aspects of the topic, with the governance axis still being underexplored. This discrepancy is reflected in the number of authors, sources, and peer-reviewed articles that contrast the two strands, one including governance and the other not. A change in this scenario has been detected with a notable increase in ESG publications incorporating the Governance topic in recent years, indicating a promising trajectory in terms of emerging publication trends.

2. Regarding the conceptual framework of existing research between ESG and procurement governance, the structure reveals the influence of strands centered on responsibility, social and corporate performance, and the impact on financial performance, the role of social and environmental responsibility in attracting investors, and corporate responsibility. The focus of the studies appears to be predominantly external to organizations, neglecting an analysis with an internal focus on the organization and its structures.

3. Regarding the most influential publications, emerging themes, and future trends, the primary sources of citations indicate that the topic has not yet been widely discussed in the main journals of "Purchase, Supply, or Supply Chain Management." Cooperation between countries is scarce, and articles addressing the topic emphasize the importance of governance in ESG practices and the supply chain, without any specific mention of the importance of governance in the procurement area.

The examination of publications revealed the absence of an academic focus on the specific theme of this study, where the main research trends between ESG and governance highlight through four clusters:

The first, focusing on performance, provides insights into the relationship between ESG factors and company performance, as discussed in the studies of Friede et al. (2015), along with the literature on ESG, social responsibility, and corporate performance by Gillan et al. (2021).

The second, focusing on corporate social responsibility and environmental sustainability, investigates the concept of moral capital in promoting relationships with shareholders, impacting abnormal returns, and supporting the safe effect hypothesis, as discussed by Godfrey et al. (2009) and Orlitzky et al. (2003).

The third, concentrating on financial performance, examines how ESG strategies can influence financial outcomes (Atan et al., 2018), demonstrating that these strategies reduce companies' cost of capital, increase shareholder value, and require transparent disclosure practices to attract investors.

The fourth, focusing on value creation for organizations, is based on various theories, including stakeholder theory, which emphasizes the ethical duty to maximize shareholder value; trade-off theory, which recognizes the potential of ESG initiatives in reducing resource inefficiency; management theory focusing on long-term value creation by managers; and agency theory (Jensen, 1976) applied to managers involved in ESG activities for personal gain (Blundell, 1998).

The analysis of the results suggests that in current contexts, both academic and business, ESG principles, referring to the three fundamental axes – Environmental, Social, and Governance, are progressing and gaining increasing importance and, mainly, increasing effectiveness. However, the absence of an academic focus on the specific theme of this study, on one hand, may bring difficulties to addressing the research problem, but on the other hand, exposes a potential research gap, paving the way and highlighting the potential contribution and impact that this study can generate, shedding light on the absence of focus on the effective governance role of a procurement area in organizations; as well as aligning it with ESG practices and generating positive results for the procurement area, the organization, and the internal and external parties involved in procurement processes, thereby reinforcing and strengthening ESG practices.

Contribution

With the support of bibliometric analysis, the examination of current publications revealed the absence of an academic focus on the specific theme. This absence results in the difficulty of addressing the research problem but also highlights the potential value of this study's contribution, exposing a research gap and paving the way for future investigations. The emergence of articles tangential to the theme in recent years signifies a growing interest in studying the governance axis of ESG practices, particularly in organizations and supply chains.

This study sheds light on the absence of focus on the effective governance role of a procurement area in organizations, where governance, by establishing and clarifying rules in the political arena, serves as a foundation to align internal and external agendas with organizational strategy.

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Paper topic

3. Purchasing organisation, 17. Sustainability - social, 12. Ethics

51

RPA implementation & use in procurement

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This study aimed to evaluate the adoption of *Robotic Process Automation* (RPA) in procurement, covering the dimensions (1) financial, (2) processes and (3) people, during pre-implementation, implementation and post-adoption. The research method was a qualitative single case study in a Brazilian multinational company. The results indicate that: (1) the implementation was feasible; (2) the expected benefits of productivity and relief of operational load were perceived; the task characteristics and design were critical; and (3) RPA acceptance by users was perceived, related to performance, usefulness, ease of use and support. Overall, the results are consistent with the findings in the literature.

Paper topic

10. Purchasing innovation

Trust and distrust states in buyer-supplier relationships: the role of reorientation

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This study explores how trust and distrust reorientation facilitate the transition between trust/distrust states in buyer-supplier relationships (BSRs). First, using the literature, trust and distrust reorientation are conceptualized as separate, distinct processes. Hereafter, these processes are empirically investigated in the context of a BSR. This study demonstrates that a single BSR can include four archetypical trust/distrust states: low trust/low distrust, high trust/low distrust, low trust/high distrust, and high trust/high distrust. This study further demonstrates that when these states are associated with negative outcomes, trust and distrust reorientation can steer the BSR toward a more desirable state.

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Strategic thinking in purchasing and supply management (PSM): A competency-based analysis

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Despite the growing importance of strategic thinking as a critical competency in PSM, its definition, structure, and function remain unclear. Therefore, a competency-based analysis is conducted to provide a structured understanding of strategic thinking. Through a literature review, 64 cognitive competencies are identified and aggregated into ten dimensions. By applying a measurement model, the initial structure of strategic thinking is represented, facilitating subsequent concretization, specification, and validation of the formative-reflective structure.

Paper topic

1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 2. PSM strategy, 3. Purchasing organisation

Mission Impossible? Challenges to government procurement in support of the circular transition

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Introduction

The transition to a circular economy necessitates a fundamental transformation in how we take, make, use, and no-longer-dispose materials (see e.g., Benachio et al., 2020). This shift involves extending product lifecycles (i.e., slowing the loop), replacing conventional materials with more sustainable alternatives (i.e., narrowing the loop), and moving towards more and higher-value material reuse (i.e., closing the loop). Collectively, these trends aim to advance more responsible production and consumption of materials, one of the grand challenges of our time. By nature, grand challenges cannot be resolved by individual organizations alone. Instead, they require coordinated efforts across a broad spectrum of public and private stakeholders.

Government procurement in support of so-called missions (see e.g., Mazzucato, 2021) may help to mobilize networks in support of transitions. At the same time, the circular transition continues to be slower than desired, with progress towards targets waning. This calls for studying the role of the government as a central architect leveraging procurement activities to align public policy objectives with private sector capabilities and achieve sustainable outcomes (George et al., 2024), which has received limited scholarly attention to date. This paper therefore addresses the role of government, particularly their procurement, in establishing, governing and monitoring collaborative networks in support of the circular transition.

Theoretical background

The theoretical perspective adopted is that of the Mission Economy (Mazzucato, 2021), which suggests that public organizations have the ability to formulate missions that provide direction to and create unity in transitions. More specifically, government can play an active and strategic role in shaping the direction of economic and sustainable growth by setting ambitious missions to address pressing societal challenges. This involves an holistic approach to innovation involving public as well as private entities – e.g., producers and consumers, knowledge institutes, industry associations, etc. (Rong et al., 2015; Tate

et al., 2019)– that each provide different contributions to the mission in scope. The government is the ‘mission director’ that guides this innovation process by providing leadership, direction, and funding. The role for procurement is to “make” (not “fix”) the market by selecting the “willing” (not the “winners”) (Leadbeater, 2018; Nijhof et al., 2022), and to shape the scope of the partnerships, set the terms of collaboration, and define the specificity of outcomes (George et al., 2024) in public-private collaborations aimed at creating solutions, pooling resources and sharing risks. Building on this perspective, this paper specifically investigates the role of (government) procurement in driving, enabling and stimulating the circular transition. Building on Weidemann’s (2023) overview of technical, socio-cultural, institutional, and market/ economic barriers to circular economy transitions in the construction industry, we seek to identify what barriers are impeding the circular transition, and subsequently how “mission economy”-thinking could help overcome these.

Methodology

The circular transition is studied by conducting a single theory-building case study. Our research setting involves a collaborative network active in the construction industry, particularly civil engineering (i.e., soil, road and hydraulic) in the Netherlands. Construction activities in this setting pertain to e.g., road, viaducts and bridges, but also e.g. shores of ditches and rivers. We consider this empirical setting to be representative of a circular transition that is to be achieved by a collective of actors, including producers, contractors, distributors and customers.

We focus on geotextiles, a construction material that primarily consist of virgin polymers and that finds its application in several civil engineering activities such as separation, filtration, drainage, reinforcement, stability, barrier, and erosion control (Gerritsen et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2020). Making up 3.6% of the synthetics used in the Dutch construction sector and 0.5% of total synthetics use in the Netherlands (Voskamp and Retzlaff, 2022), geotextiles are expected to be more widely applied in the decades to come in order to provide safe and resilient living areas for humanity (Gerritsen et al., 2023). More environmentally-friendly alternatives are available in the form of sustainable and even bio-based geotextiles, yet their adoption has been slow. Currently, over 50% of geotextiles used in civil, road, and hydraulic engineering are incinerated end-of-life (Joustra and Van Leeuwen, 2022).

Admittedly being a fairly small category, the argument for focusing on the geotextiles supply chain is that a collaborative network has been put in place through a bottom-up approach involving producers, wholesalers, contractors, and public and private customers, which enabled collecting data from diverse actors and obtaining a comprehensive understanding of the geotextiles supply chain as it undergoes the circular transition. We conducted nine interviews, which we subsequently coded using the coding structure built from our literature review. We also attended three of the collaborative network’s bi-monthly meetings, in which we advanced and verified our emergent insights as part of the discussions on a more sustainable geotextiles supply chain, and where we also led discussion on how the circular transition could be accelerated and facilitated.

Findings

Our findings reveal that the Dutch geotextiles supply chain faces a myriad of technical, institutional, market/ economic and socio-cultural barriers in undergoing the circular transition. While procurement specifically faces barriers in all these categories, market/ economic and institutional barriers seem to particularly resonate with procurement. Examples include, but are not limited to, lacking (financial) incentives to truly promote the adoption of sustainable geotextiles (market/economic) and missing or ineffective policy (institutional) when it comes to e.g., the use of Environmental Cost Indicator calculations to award contracts.

Our findings also show that the principles underlying “mission economy”-thinking can help facilitate the transformation of the market and establish a mission-driven approach for the Dutch geotextile supply chain, particularly by intensifying public-private collaboration and share knowledge, resources and risks related to adopting innovative circular practices. We found that transformation is highly contingent upon innovation and active participation from all stakeholders. In addition to stimulating these collaborations, the government is to develop financing mechanisms that support the adoption of circular practices, and to set clear and achievable targets for collaborative networks and its individual members. Such initiatives, which closely align with “mission economy” thinking, are found to be crucial to overcoming many of the barriers currently encountered.

Contributions

This study makes two key theoretical contributions. First, it enriches the growing body of research on collaborative inter-organizational networks featuring public-private collaborations by exploring the multifaceted barriers hindering the circular transition and showing how “mission economy”-thinking may help the collaborative network to overcome these barriers and accelerate the transition to more sustainable supply chain practices. Second, we contribute to literature at the intersection of purchasing & supply management and public policy by developing theory on how procurement for missions can support collaborative networks composed of interdependent relationships between public and private actors to address “wicked” problems (Helper et al., 2021). As such, we offer valuable P&SM-based recommendations for public policy.

Managerial implications reside in the practical recommendations that are derived from this study, being the development of a consensual mission that gives direction and unity to the collaborative network, and adapt the institutional framework in support of procuring more sustainable product alternatives and hence shaping of the market. Finally, pilots are key to address remaining (technical) knowledge gaps, and experience the feasibility and effectiveness of new financial incentives and risk-sharing approaches.

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Paper topic

13. Public procurement, 16. Sustainability - environmental

Improving Performance with AI-Driven Purchasing and Supply Management Practices

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is expected to transform Purchasing and Supply Management (PSM), yet research on its practical adoption remains limited. Using Practice-Based View (PBV), this article explores how AI-driven PSM practices enhance performance in specific use cases. Through 30 interviews this study offers a comprehensive understanding of AI in PSM by identifying current and future AI use cases in various industries. The study contributes to both theory and practice by enhancing the understanding of the practice-performance links of AI-driven practices in PSM, highlighting both common and novel AI use cases, and providing insights for managers of AI adoption.

Paper topic

11. Digital, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 15. PSM theory, methodology, education

Navigating Earthquake-Induced Supply Chain Risks: A Framework for Risk Categorization and Management

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This study examines supply chain risks during and after earthquakes, focusing on both direct and indirect supply chain risks that hinder effective disaster management. Centered on the 2023 earthquakes that hit Türkiye and Syria, we conducted semi-structured interviews with 23 companies in textile, food, and automotive supply chains in Türkiye. Our findings reveal that some indirect risks significantly affect supply chains, even more than traditional supply chain risks do. We propose a framework for categorizing direct and indirect supply chain risks and identifying key pitfalls, offering a structured approach to navigate and manage earthquake-related risks and disruptions in supply chains.

Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience

Mapping Innovation roles and archetypes of purchasers - insights from French Firms (2020-2024)

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This study examines the roles and archetypes of 76 purchasing functions dedicated to innovation in French firms. Based on data from 1,233 purchasing services described from 2020 to 2024, it identifies three key archetypes of innovation-focused purchasing functions: New area (EPI2 and beyond), Category (EPI and beyond) and Transformation (support function). It reveals that purchasing's involvement extends beyond early-stage product development to broader innovation forms at different stages. Thus, this study provides insights for both practitioners and researchers in purchasing and innovation management, and avenues for further research regarding organization and training of purchasers.

Paper topic

10. Purchasing innovation, 1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 3. Purchasing organisation

Management competences for implementing resilient supply chains

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

In the last years many external events like the Russian-Ukrainian conflict, the COVID-19 pandemic and in general the increasing number of extreme weather events challenged global supply chains in a disruptive and unexpected manner. Firms had less time to react to the changing requirements within supply chains, which often resulted in delivery delays, the unexpected loss of supply capability, and ultimately in the breakdown of supply chains. The unexpected loss of supply capability is often referred to as supply shock, meaning the focal company cannot provide enough raw materials for its production processes (Kiers et al., 2022). In the past, the predominant trend in SCM was towards global sourcing and single sourcing strategies. The main advantage of globalised supply chains and the concentration on single suppliers is cost savings for the focal company. Especially a single sourcing strategy and a reduced supplier base lead to negotiation savings and less effort in buyer-supplier-communication (Van Hoek, 2021). At the same time, the limited number of suppliers leads to a high level of dependence on a few suppliers and regions and therefore to a higher risk of delivery failures due to external events.

As a consequence of disruptive events, the global orientation of supply chains and single sourcing strategies are being called into question. In this context, the literature primarily analyses strategies to build supply chain resilience when supply shocks occur. Apart from this, only a few studies focus on managers and examined the competences required to deal with resilient supply chains (Kiers et al., 2022). The main challenge for managers in these disruptive situations is that they have to make quick decisions based on a high level of information uncertainty. Accordingly, specific competences are required for the implementation of strategies to build and improve the resilience of supply chains. The research objective of this study is therefore to identify the relationship-specific conditions for building resilient supply chains and, based on this, to characterise the required management capabilities and higher-level competences of managers in SCM. For this purpose, a theoretical scenario-based model is being developed, that depicts alternative supply chain strategies in the context of resilience.

In general, supply chain resilience (SCRE) as part of supply chain risk management (SCRM) focuses on the response to disruptive and unexpected events. Therefore, resilient supply chains are designed as self-regulating systems, that automatically return to normal operation or even achieve a higher level of performance after a disruption. Furthermore, SCRE from a managerial perspective means that reactive measures are defined, which run as self-evident and automatic process supporting managers in unstructured disruptive situations. Overall, the aim of SCRE is to absorb disturbances and develop a kind

of resistance in order to maintain or restore SC performance in disruptive situations. The literature intensively analyses the changes in SCM due to disruptive events and identifies possible strategies for improving SCORE. The most popular strategies are diversification, localisation and dual sourcing. The suppliers are located in regions with different environmental conditions and therefore the probability of a possible disruption varies. With the diversification strategy, contrasting regions are included in the supplier base for reducing region-specific risks (Van Hoek, 2021). If the suppliers are located in the same region as the focal company, they face similar problems which leads to better control of supplier disruptions. Localisation describes the selection of domestic suppliers that are close to the company's own facilities. The third strategy is dual sourcing, describing the use of several suppliers for one (same) product for reasons of risk diversification. In summary, the strategies presented are in contrast to the previous trend of global and single sourcing (Kiers et al., 2022). While the contextual factors and organisational capabilities to develop and implement the strategies to improve SCORE are explained in detail in the literature, the competences and activities of management when a supply shock actually occurs are rarely examined.

Therefore, we first analyse the dimensions that determine the buyer-supplier-relationship for building resilient supply chains, based on the literature. The main challenge is to organise supplier relationships in such a way that potential disruptions can be automatically absorbed, ensuring the functionality of the entire supply chain. This places high demands on management, whose task it is to create the framework for resilient supply chains and to establish and maintain strategic partnerships with suppliers. Therefore, the first research question is:

RQ1: "Which relationship-specific conditions are required for the management of resilient supply chains?"

Especially the contract design can be expected as an important factor in managing the relationship and to define the supply performance in case of disruption. According to the transaction-cost-theory, a difference is made between various types of contractual relationships. In this context, relational-contractual-relationships are required. With this type of relationship, a reservation of the supply potential can be established as a contract specification to compensate for the possible loss of other suppliers. In addition, designing resilient supply chains needs to encourage suppliers to provide compensation for potential supply disruptions and act as backup-suppliers. Therefore, the transparent communication and relationship-management with the suppliers seems to be crucial to establish a backup-strategy (Rajae and Miloudi, 2024). Apart from this, incentive systems and exchange mechanisms or auction systems for potential supply capacities can be alternatives to contractually bound backup-suppliers. The dimensions discussed represent approaches for management to create the framework conditions for implementing resilient supply chain structures.

Managers play a key role in the implementation of relationship-specific factors and thus in the design of SCORE. The second research question focuses on the supply chain managers and examines the competences required:

RQ2: "Which capabilities do supply chain managers need to implement self-regulating, resilient systems and which higher competences do they have to complete?"

In order to answer the research questions, we developed a theoretical scenario-based model, using the example of dual sourcing and localisation as SCORE strategies, which represents a resilient supply chain and is in contrast with single sourcing as a basic strategy. This is applied as a framework in the interviews

and contributes to a better understanding of the concept of SCRE. Every model considers a supply chain with one focal company and one upstream tier consisting of one (Model A) or two (Model B) suppliers. Model A is designed as a basic model and represents the combination of global and single sourcing strategy. In this case, the focal company is only supplied by a single supplier located outside its own country. It is assumed that the supplier's environment is potentially sensitive to disruption due to environmental conditions. Model B combines dual sourcing and localisation as strategies to improve SCRE in this disruptive environment. There, the supplier base of the focal company consists of two suppliers for the same product. The aim of splitting the delivery volume is to spread the risk of a supplier shortfall, particularly if a supplier is located in an uncertain region. Both suppliers act as a kind of backup-supplier for each other. One of the suppliers is still located overseas, which reflects the advantages of globalisation and is characterised by a lower price, but also by a high vulnerability to supply chain disruptions. The second supplier is located in the manufacturer's region in order to reduce the risk due to the company's distance to the global supplier. To demonstrate the consequences of a supply shock in the models described above, we assume that an unforeseeable, external event occurs which negatively influences the deliverability of the foreign supplier. In Model A, the disruption results in a complete delivery failure. To prevent this problem, Model B has a second (local) supplier who takes over the delivery from the foreign supplier. This represents the resilience strategy in which the unexpected loss of a supplier can be compensated. To summarise, the theoretical scenario-based model provides insight into the process of implementing and managing SCRE strategies to identify the necessary competences in SCM.

We use the developed model to conduct expert interviews with supply chain managers to understand the management activities that are automatically initiated in the event of a supply shock to bring the system back to a functional state. Therefore, it is important to investigate and identify which management capabilities and competences are required in SCM to design and manage the described resilient system. This is based on our findings from the literature analysis on the relationship-specific conditions that are required for the management of resilient supply chains. Building on this, we identify the higher management competences required to implement resilient supply chains.

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Paper topic

1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 18. Risk and resilience, 7. Negotiation and contracting

Procurement as a leverage point: Navigating social sustainability risks and system dynamics in the Swedish construction sector

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Toward Ethical Procurement: A Systems Perspective on Social Sustainability in the Swedish Construction Sector

Introduction

Modern supply chains, particularly in labour-intensive sectors like construction, involve complex networks of formal and informal subcontracting, which heighten the risk of forced labour (Allain et al., 2013). Procurement often struggles with achieving transparency, particularly regarding informal workers who fall outside corporate codes of conduct. In Sweden's fragmented construction sector, which employed over 330,000 people in 2022, social sustainability issues such as labour exploitation are prevalent, especially among foreign workers (Swedish Construction Commission, 2022). Addressing these challenges requires monitoring and ethical oversight that extends across all tiers of the supply chain (Crane, 2013). Key dimensions of social sustainability in procurement include labour rights, health and safety, societal responsibility, diversity, and product responsibility (Alghababsheh and Gallear, 2021). To promote ethical procurement and mitigate social sustainability risks, procurement organizations must create transparency within supplier ecosystems, enabling the detection and management of unethical practices (Mani et al., 2018).

Procurement is encountering a systemic shift as traditional linear supply chains are increasingly replaced by dynamic business ecosystems. First conceptualized by (Moore, 1996), a business ecosystem includes focal actors, organizations, and institutions beyond traditional networks. It encompasses suppliers, distributors, outsourced partners, competitors, customers, end-users, and regulatory agencies, all of which influence the creation, delivery, and development of products or services, either directly or indirectly (Aarikka-Stenroos and Ritala, 2017). The Swedish construction sector exemplifies such an ecosystem, evolving from a traditional labour market to a complex network of diverse actors with

blurred industry boundaries. These overlapping and parallel labour market networks create ambiguity in market structures and complicate efforts to address unethical practices.

(Forrester, 1971) assertion that "social systems are multi-loop, nonlinear feedback systems" suggests that the internal structure of social systems both generates problems and contains leverage points for change. However, the belief that stricter legislation and tighter controls alone can mitigate forced labour risks often overlooks these sensitive leverage points. (Meadows, 1999) expands on Forrester's ideas, identifying leverage points as "points of power" for intervention. These range from altering parameters to fundamentally changing system rules, mindsets, or even paradigms. While superficial changes may yield limited effects, systemic interventions at deeper levels can drive more meaningful transformation.

This research applies the frameworks of Forrester (1971) and Meadows (1999) to analyse the Swedish construction sector's supplier ecosystems and identify effective leverage points for the procurement function to combat social misconduct. By developing a feedback-based knowledge framework for procurement based on (Dickson et al., 2001), the study seeks to help procurement managers to visualize and address these issues. Furthermore, aligning with (Koskela-Huotari et al., 2024), it examines the drivers and barriers procurement faces in preventing social misconduct within supplier ecosystems. Concepts such as stocks, flows, feedback loops, and mindsets will highlight systemic mechanisms contributing to unethical practices and inform potential interventions.

Research Objectives

This study aims to deepen understanding of the procurement function's critical role in mitigating social sustainability risks and promoting ethical procurement practices within Sweden's construction sector. It will explore procurement's role in supplier selection, monitoring, and collaboration to ensure ethical behaviour and safeguard human rights across supply chains and stakeholder networks. By leveraging systems thinking and empirical insights, the research seeks to clarify how procurement can effectively manage ethical sourcing and foster a socially sustainable supply base. Accordingly, the study will address the following research questions:

How can procurement promote ethical sourcing and effectively mitigate social sustainability risks within a firm's supply base?

1. What role does the procurement function play in preventing unethical practices within the supply chains of Sweden's construction sector?

Methodology

This research employs a single-case study approach to address the two primary research questions. This methodology enables an in-depth examination of procurement, social sustainability, and ethics within a real-life context, providing valuable insights into their complexities and specific nuances. A case study approach is particularly suited for exploring phenomena where boundaries between the context and the subject of study are not clearly defined (Gomm et al., 2000; Yin, 2009). Its flexibility in integrating

multiple data collection methods, as highlighted by (Eisenhardt, 1989), further supports its suitability for this study.

The selected case company, referred to as CaseCo, is one of the largest construction firms in the Nordics, with operations spanning building and infrastructure contracting, asphalt and stone materials production, and commercial property development. The study focuses on CaseCo's procurement function and its supply base, including internal and external stakeholders pertinent to procurement and sustainability. Informants will be selected based on their expertise in procurement, sustainability, and risk management, ensuring a diverse range of perspectives. Specific parts of CaseCo's supply base will be chosen for detailed analysis based on their risk profiles and involvement in complex supply chains. This targeted focus will enable a deeper exploration of ethical sourcing practices and strategies to mitigate social sustainability risks.

The research adopts an abductive approach using systematic combining (Dubois and Gadde, 2002), where the theoretical framework, empirical data collection, and case analysis evolve in tandem (Flick, 2014). This iterative and adaptive approach ensures flexibility in refining both data collection and analysis to remain aligned with emerging insights, rather than adhering to rigid, sequential phases.

Data will be collected from multiple organizational levels within CaseCo and its supply base, encompassing both business and corporate functions. Informant selection will follow Eisenhardt's (1989) principle of sufficiency, with interviews conducted until the saturation point is reached, at which no new information emerges or the coding framework ceases to evolve. Primary data sources will include qualitative interviews, company documents, government and public reports, industry studies, and online resources. Secondary data will be drawn from literature reviews and sector analyses, providing a comprehensive foundation for examining procurement and social sustainability within the construction sector.

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Paper topic

12. Ethics, 17. Sustainability - social, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

KPIs management in Brazilian Procurement Companies

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This study explores the use of procurement Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in Brazilian companies, assessing their selection, monitoring, and challenges. While literature emphasizes a shift from cost-saving metrics to value-driven indicators (e.g., innovation, sustainability, and team development), Brazilian organizations still rely on traditional KPIs. Through interviews with procurement professionals, the study identifies 47 KPIs, with savings as the most prevalent. Challenges include data integration, analytical capabilities, and system limitations. The findings highlight the need for strategic KPI frameworks and automation. Future research should investigate the transition toward comprehensive procurement performance measurement and the role of emerging technologies.

Paper topic

2. PSM strategy

63

Increase buyers' focus on employees

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

The aim of this article is to ask whether purchasing departments should give employees a more central role in the purchasing performance management system. Based on action research carried out in an international insurance company, our results show that purchasing departments place greater emphasis on supplier risk assessment (external stakeholders) than on managing the impact of risks on the company's employees (internal stakeholders). And yet, according to employees, purchasing departments should increase their awareness of risks and dysfunctions and their impact on employees' working conditions. Employees believe this would strengthen the legitimacy of purchasing departments.

Paper topic

17. Sustainability - social, 18. Risk and resilience

Procuring sustainable values in public institutions

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Summary: Public procurement serves as a strategic tool to foster innovation, sustainability, and market development. However, realizing its potential requires evaluating both procurement processes and business models to address trade-offs among diverse goals, such as social and environmental sustainability. Using vertical farms as a case study, this research explores how small business innovations are integrated into public procurement for healthcare and education. Data from interviews and documents highlight challenges in categorizing multi-purpose solutions, aligning procurement strategies, and valuing non-measurable benefits like well-being and education. Findings emphasize the need for adaptive procurement practices to support sustainability-oriented innovations and public value creation.

Introduction

Public procurement is seen as a strategic function that can, for instance, stimulate innovation, create crucial demand-side initiatives and shape market development (Malacina et al, 2022). It can also promote sustainable development if used properly (European Commission, 2020; Milios, 2017; Sönnichsen and Clement, 2019). However, public procurement officers will need to evaluate both new business models and their current procurement processes to understand and realize the potential for sustainable value creation beyond price measures. Trade-offs and conflicting priorities at various levels of strategy are present and may involve choosing between many options to achieve the same goal (Plantinga et al., 2020) or between multiple goals, such as social and environmental sustainability (Brammer and Walker, 2011). Recent research has conceptually developed the potential for value creation of public buyers through specific purchasing and supply chain practices, yet the need exists for empirical studies to better understand the tensions faced by public procurement buyers (Malacina et al, 2022; Ghisetti, 2017).

The internal issues stem from the fragmentation of functions within the procurement organization causing “silo-budgeting” where the budgetary obligation and the product's use don't align (Edler and Yeow, 2016). Additionally, one crucial component of procurement is the degree of centralization of strategic and operational activities (Patrucco, Andrea Stefano et al., 2019). The more centralized an organization is, the more its procurement team must collaborate and communicate with other divisions to plan its needs for products and services. As a result, procuring goods or services that are novel to the organization presents difficulties, since this requires organizational adaptation in terms of learning,

internal coordination, and change management to establish links across various internal stakeholders (Edler and Yeow, 2016). As new sustainable business models are introduced by small business suppliers, it's important to understand the processes around public procurement; how goods and services are valued from a three-pillar perspective and how these valuations impact purchasing decisions, and subsequently market development.

This paper explores the public procurement processes of a sustainability-oriented innovation from small business suppliers through the following research questions:

- RQ 1: What value(s) are considered by the procuring organization and how are they evaluated or measured?
- RQ 2: If the value(s) of the solution spans several categories, how is this handled during the procuring process?

In this study, vertical farms are used as an example of small business suppliers. Vertical farming, or the process of growing plants in stacked layers within either fully-controlled or semi-controlled environments, is introducing new business models in food production built on goals to create environmental and social values. It was chosen as an empirical area for several reasons. First, for its ability to grow food in untraditional environments (e.g. indoors, in cities) leading to a reduction of environment impacts including less water usage, no agricultural run-off due to the indoor environment and lower food miles as transportation is reduced or eliminated due to the hyper-local growing process (Al-Kodmany, 2018). Second, studies acknowledge the benefits of green environments on well-being especially in places where exposure to biodiversity has decreased (see e.g. Soininen et al, 2022; Detweiler et al, 2012). Lastly, vertical farming provides fresh, local produce which introduces both nutritional benefits and opportunities for growing awareness and education of food production (Kalantari et al, 2018; Specht et al, 2016). Thus, vertical farming as a case represents an interesting analytical puzzle from a public procurement perspective as it potentially spans different purchasing categories, e.g. food, infrastructure, educational tool, and holds the potential to generate different sustainable values.

Method

Empirical material was drawn from the procurement process of vertical farming solutions in healthcare and educational environments. In the Netherlands, the introduction of a vertical farming solution for the healthcare environment was investigated, while in Sweden, both healthcare and educational environments were included. To build out the two cases, semi-structured interviews with the vertical farms, healthcare staff and procurement professionals were conducted, along with a review of documents, both internal and public. Data collection was aimed at answering the above research questions.

Table 1: Respondents in the data collection

Respondents	Organization
Chef_1	School_1, Sweden
Chef_2	School_2, Sweden
Manager	Elderly care home, Sweden
Owner_1	Vertical farm supplier_1, the Netherlands
Owner_2	Vertical farm supplier_2, Sweden
Owner_3	Vertical farm supplier, Sweden
Strategic Procurement Officer	Swedish municipality

Results & discussion

The analytical framework was grounded in procurement literature, particularly for sustainability and innovation. Preliminary results from schools and elderly care homes show identified values in the following categories: food (availability, novelty, and inspiration), education and awareness (learning and increased knowledge levels), well-being and ambiance (focal point, a happening, and green space), and other values (promotion).

For both the schools included, the purchasing of the vertical farming modules was initiated directly at the school level and not via any strategic centralized procurement, e.g., the municipality. Furthermore, the purchase was not included in the traditional procuring categories. Instead, innovation funds and unused budgets were used. The chefs in the kitchens were the initiators, the champions of the solution.

Findings from the vertical farms in the elderly care homes show the challenge of multi-purpose solutions, where it was uncertain if they should be evaluated as food service or furniture. Similar challenges could be seen in the school case, where the modules were intended for educational purposes and to supplement greens in the cafeteria. This points to a potential drawback of procurement departments being structured around category management and the need for strategic alignment.

Beyond the obstacles related to category management, the cases show the potential difficulty of handling sustainability trade-offs and the complexity of evaluation criteria that do not have standardized measurements. The vertical farming modules hold the potential to generate several non-measurable values, including well-being, educational opportunities, and a closer connection to food.

This study contributes to purchasing and supply chain management by unpacking the procurement processes for sustainability-oriented innovations in public organizations. It provides a greater understanding of procurement of sustainability values and potential changes needed in purchasing management and routines in public organizations, which are essential actors in a sustainable transition.

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Paper topic

13. Public procurement, 16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social

65

Proposing a conceptual management model for digital customer-driven purchasing and supply management

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

PSM has traditionally focused on meeting internal requirements, yet a stronger alignment with end-customer demands is essential for enhancing procurement effectiveness and strategic value creation. By following a design science approach, this study proposes a conceptual management model that integrates customer-driven strategies and advanced digital technologies into PSM. Thus, the overarching architecture of the approach is described and specific tasks that outline a phased roadmap for realisation is provided. Consequently, this working paper contributes to PSM research by providing scholars and practitioners tangible means to bridge the longstanding disconnect between procurement and external customer demands.

Paper topic

2. PSM strategy, 11. Digital, 15. PSM theory, methodology, education

Impact of Social and Health Service and Supplier Market Characteristics to Public Procurement Tender Selection Criteria

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Abstract

Local governmental organisations, such as municipalities and federations of municipalities (FOM), are under increasing pressure to both reduce costs as well as ensure sufficient quality and availability of social and health care services given the aging population that is heavily increasing the demand for said services (Loprete and Mauro, 2017), and global shortage of labour in health care (Peters, 2023). These pressures often lead local governments to make and/or buy considerations in relation to the public services they offer to their citizens (Hefetz and Warner, 2012; Rodrigues et al., 2012; Petersen et al., 2015; 2018). The benefits and shortfalls of make, buy, and make-and-buy practices (later we use the term service delivery approach), have been studied in detail and recent studies suggest that the make-and-buy approach is the most common (Kauppi and Taponen, 2022). A single service delivery approach is not found to be universally cost efficient compared to the others, instead, other characteristics related to the buying organization and the population are found to be more important (Kauppi and Taponen, 2022).

While public service delivery alternatives have been examined extensively in the past, their study rarely merges with the study of public procurement, particularly when it comes to how the tendering is organized when deciding to contract out. Yet for example scoring rules used when contracting out can impact e.g., the number of bids received and the price-quality composition of the bids (Dini et al. 2006; Jääskeläinen and Tukiainen, 2019), hence ultimately determining the potential cost (dis)advantage and overall value and impact of said service delivery approach. It is thus important to understand what kind of criteria is being used when contracting out health and social care services, and what determines the selection of the criteria for services with different characteristics.

In this paper, we focus on individual service tenders in Finnish public social and health care services between 2017-2020. Our sample consists of over 400 contract award notices for tenders that are above the EU threshold. The sample is collected from TED (EU Tenders Electronic Daily) database and complemented with data collected directly from the tendering Finnish municipalities and FOMs. Using quantitative methods, we aim to understand if and how the characteristics of services in these individual tenders predict if quality has been used as an evaluation criterion in bid evaluation. Additionally, we

control for factors related to the service supplier market (such as the number of possible suppliers in the area) and to the buying organization. On top of tendering data, we aim to conduct a survey for procurement professionals and subject matter experts, where they help us categorize the specific services tendered in terms of their characteristics. This first stage of the study helps to form an understanding of current criteria usage and what potentially impacts it. In the second phase of the study, we aim to understand what the perceived ideal criteria are to be used for different service tenders in varying supplier markets, and whether they match the actual criteria used under such conditions. For this, we collect data via behavioural vignettes, asking procurement professionals the criteria they would use in tendering when presented with different typical (drawn from real cases) scenarios. This also allows us to observe, if the criterion used and the criterion ideally suggested by other procurement professionals matches. In other words, this allows us to observe, how subjective the decision on using quality as an evaluation criterion in tender evaluation is.

The goal of our research is to understand the importance of specific characteristics of services procured on how they are procured. Previous literature suggests that when services are contracted out, the way they are contracted out is important for the cost efficiency of the contracted-out services, as well as for example for the number of bidders (Jääskeläinen and Tukiainen, 2019).

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Paper topic

13. Public procurement, 5. Supplier selection, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

Ageing workforce and life-long learning in procurement: Challenges and opportunities for teaching Silver Workers to prepare for Industry 4.0

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Summary

This paper discusses the impact of an aging workforce on businesses in the European Union. It emphasizes the importance of lifelong learning and digital literacy for older employees in purchasing and supply management. Organizations should recognize the contributions of older employees and implement flexible working arrangements, health programs, and ongoing training to support their evolving needs. We conducted a quantitative survey of procurement professionals of all ages to compare silver workers and other age groups in terms of their competences. Despite the focus on traditional competencies, there might be a significant gap in training programs addressing digital and IT expertise for older workers, particularly in the context of Industry 4.0.

Keywords or phrases: procurement analytics, procurement data management, aging workforce

Paper topic

1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 12. Ethics, 11. Digital

Eco-design and environmental performance: the impact of ambidextrous orientation and the moderating role of supply chain emissions data management practices

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This study explores how ambidextrous supply chain orientations and supply chain emissions data management practices work together to drive eco-design adoption and enhance environmental performance. Drawing on the practice-based view and supply chain practice view, we investigate how sustainability-driven exploration and exploitation orientations independently influence eco-design practices and environmental performance. Survey data collected from 158 Finnish firms, analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling, reveal that exploration significantly enhances eco-design practices and environmental performance, while exploitation directly improves environmental outcomes but not eco-design practices. Furthermore, supply chain emissions data management practices amplify the impact of exploitation on environmental performance, highlighting the role of data-driven approaches in achieving sustainability through operational improvements.

Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental

Sourcing from Economically Distressed Regions: A Complexity-Paradox Perspective

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Introduction

Supplier diversity has gained increasing attention as an essential aspect of procurement strategy, aiming to integrate businesses owned by and operated by disadvantaged groups into traditional supply chains. Historically, while supplier diversity initiatives focus on demographic attributes (e.g., women-owned, minority-owned businesses), location-based supplier diversity programs emphasize sourcing from businesses in economically distressed regions. The HUBZone program by the U.S. federal government exemplifies this approach, designed to create employment and foster economic development in historically underutilized business zones (HUBZones). Despite its potential, the HUBZone program faces significant challenges in meeting its dual objectives: economic efficiency and inclusion.

Objectives and Methodology

This study investigates the paradoxical tensions and complexities inherent in location-based supplier diversity programs, using the HUBZone program as a research context. We employ a field-based qualitative approach, collecting data through interviews, focus groups, and reviews of policy documents. The study integrates two theoretical frameworks, supply chain complexity theory (Bozarth et al. 2009) and paradox theory (Smith and Lewis 2011), to offer a nuanced understanding of these programs' operational and policy challenges.

Findings

1. Paradoxical Tensions in Program Objectives

The HUBZone program is designed to simultaneously enhance inclusion by supporting diverse suppliers and achieve efficiency in procurement processes. However, these objectives often conflict, leading to paradoxical tensions. For example, measures to increase supplier inclusion—such as stringent certification requirements—can reduce operational efficiency by creating administrative burdens for both businesses and federal agencies. Similarly, the periodic redrawing of HUBZone boundaries introduces uncertainty, dissuading long-term participation by businesses.

2. Complexity in Program Implementation

The program's inherent complexity arises from its scale, heterogeneity of stakeholders, and dynamic policy environment, as discussed below:

- **Detail Complexity:** Managing a large, diverse pool of suppliers and tasks—including certification, training, and monitoring—strains resources.
- **Dynamic Complexity:** Frequent policy updates and the interactions among federal, state, and local governments exacerbate unpredictability, creating barriers for effective coordination among different stakeholders.

3. Role of Supporting Institutions

Supporting institutions play a critical role in alleviating the complexities of the HUBZone program. These organizations assist with supplier development by offering technical, financial, and workforce support. However, misaligned goals among federal agencies, supporting organizations, and HUBZone businesses often hinder progress.

Proposed Conceptual Framework

To address these challenges, we propose a conceptual framework that:

1. **Embraces Complexity:** Encourages adaptive strategies rather than simplification to accommodate the diverse needs of HUBZone businesses, and more generally of long-tail suppliers associated with supplier diversity programs.
2. **Balances Dual Objectives:** Recommends adopting an ambidextrous approach that integrates both efficiency and inclusion goals.
3. **Leverages Supporting Organizations:** Highlights the importance of multi-stakeholder collaboration in implementing supplier development practices across the supplier development lifecycle.

Theoretical and Policy Implications

The findings contribute to supplier diversity and procurement literature by highlighting the importance of location-based supplier diversity initiatives as a complement to demographic-based programs. For policymakers, the study underscores the need for tailored strategies to manage the paradoxical tensions and complexities in sourcing from businesses in economically distressed regions. By leveraging the role of supporting organizations, purchasing managers can better balance economic efficiency with inclusion objectives, fostering sustainable supplier ecosystems.

Conclusion

Location-based supplier diversity initiatives, like the HUBZone program, offer significant potential to advance equitable economic development while supporting procurement efficiency. However, their inherent complexities and paradoxical objectives necessitate innovative approaches to supplier management. This research provides actionable insights for enhancing the design and implementation

of such programs, enabling purchasing managers to contribute meaningfully to both business and societal goals.

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Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 13. Public procurement, 17. Sustainability - social

Disrupted platform-supplier relationships: e-commerce platform evolution from a supply management perspective - the case of Wish

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Extended Abstract

Digital technology has facilitated the reorganization of industries around platforms. Defined as organizational forms that facilitate the interaction of actors and resources via information technology (Wei & Pardo, 2024), digital platforms aim to integrate global supply resources by creating online marketplaces where actors who lack direct connections can interact. Digital platforms are becoming an unignorable disruptive power for the existing retail industry, blurring the lines between suppliers and retailers, shortening the distances between buyer and seller, and minimizing steps between discovery and delivery.

“Disruption” originally describes a process whereby a smaller company with fewer resources is able to successfully challenge established incumbent businesses (Christensen, 1997). To gain a competitive edge in markets traditionally dominated by local retailers and incumbent platform giants, platform entrepreneurs introduce disruptive innovations, leveraging advancements in digital technology and novel business models to drive differentiation and success in competition. Multi-sided platform business models, fueled by advanced information technology, have enabled distributed purchasing for platforms, outsourcing most value-creating activities to suppliers. Instead of owning and managing inventory, platforms facilitate interactions and focus on consumer acquisition, while merchants handle sourcing, purchasing, stocking, and fulfillment to end consumers. This mode allows platforms to extend their global reach quickly and adapt to demand fluctuations without being tied to fixed assets or high operating costs.

Mainstream disruption theory suggests that disruptive innovations are new technologies, products, or business models that typically emerge from low-end or new-market footholds that are overlooked by incumbents, which emphasizes demand-based factors as key drivers of the success or failure of disruptive innovation (Adner, 2002; Christensen, 1997) but largely neglect the critical role of the supply-based factors. Recent studies have sought to extend mainstream disruptive innovation theory to the context of platforms. Scholars have started to examine disruptive tensions that emerged on the supply side as the main reason for disruption in the video game industry (Ozalp, et al., 2018) and highlight the significance of inter-firm linkages when new entrants disrupt the established television industry

(Kumaraswamy, 2016). However, despite the deep revolution digital platforms have brought in supply networks in the setting of cross-border e-commerce, little attention has been paid to how platform-driven disruptive innovations unfold in supply networks.

By eliminating multiple layers of traditional intermediaries in the long cross-border trade process, platforms are able to offer consumers nearly bottom-line prices and unlock access to larger global markets. However, the gaps between various actors in the supply chain don't simply vanish through the creation of an e-commerce platform. Functions that were traditionally handled by intermediaries still need to be fulfilled, which calls for novel forms of integration of global resources and rethinking of relationships among global actors organized by platform owners. In such cases, existing roles, rules, and relationships within the supply network may be profoundly affected and reconfigured (Kumaraswamy et al., 2018). Therefore, a disruptor introducing its innovation into an existing supply network needs to stitch together a set of roles and rules governing the arrangements, relationships, and interdependencies (Ansari et al., 2016). As what a platform can offer to its consumers largely relies on suppliers, the dynamic of a platform is intrinsically tied to its relationships with suppliers and its ability to incentivize suppliers to mobilize and develop their supply network resources. Therefore, the disruptive platform needs the support of suppliers and other actors in the supply network who they are disrupting. Thus, how to garner the support of suppliers and managing the relationships with a sheer number of suppliers become critical challenges for platform owners as platforms continue to evolve and transcend traditionally defined industry boundaries (McIntyre and Srinivasan, 2017).

In this study, we view disruptive innovation not as a singular event or product but as a dynamic, ongoing sequence of actions and developments over time. This perspective emphasizes the stages and mechanisms by which disruption unfolds, both shaped by and, in turn, shaping the platform evolution. This paper aims to explore how digital platforms, leveraging advanced technologies and innovative business models, may disrupt the nature and dynamics of platform-supply relationships and reconfigure supply networks as platforms evolve.

In this paper, we make use of a case study of the cross-border e-commerce platform Wish to reach a better understanding of platform evolution as a process co-evolving with supplier networks, and how disruptive tensions in the supply network may disrupt the platform's sustaining development and success in competition. "*Change the way the world shops*" was the slogan of Wish, an online bazaar on mobile phones that offers a huge variety of products at rock-bottom prices directly from suppliers to end consumers. Founded in 2011 by two computer science engineers in the U.S., Wish initially targeted value-conscious consumers who were buying unbranded, less expensive alternatives. Taking advantage of its technical strength in machine learning, Wish soon became a pioneer in mobile e-commerce, winning millions of consumers by providing personalized shopping experiences and over one million suppliers by removing operational barriers. While the personal recommendation technology introduced novel ways to match demand and supply, and the marketplace business model redefined the roles and responsibilities between the platform and suppliers, the conventional way of purchasing and supply management put suppliers at higher risk under the Wish mode. Suppliers had to seek new strategies in sourcing and purchasing management. The Wish mode also indirectly disrupted the industry, fostering the emergence of new roles, new rules, new types of relationships, and novel formats of linking resources in broader supply networks.

Wish's open-door policy meant that sales were taking off, but so were quality-control problems. Wish took a series of innovations both in platform policies and automatic mechanisms to manage its supply base throughout its evolutionary process. But these changes are rarely tailored to individual suppliers

but a set of “one-size-fits-all” mechanisms designed for the whole online marketplace. This often results in heterogeneous influences on the relationships with different suppliers and unexpected complex dynamics that widespread supply networks. The two sides of the platform-supplier relationship are asymmetrical, owing to different levels and forms of investment and reactions of the two sides. Suppliers who take the majority responsibility for operation activities are closer connected to and have more direct investments in their supply network. This makes them less flexible and challenging to keep updating with frequent platform disruptive changes and rebuilding their respective relationships and networks. Moreover, while platforms rely on automated, system-driven responses to manage relationships, suppliers’ perceptions of their relationship with platforms are far more complex and nuanced, leading to the departure of a large number of suppliers. Tensions in its relationships with suppliers had persisted and continued to escalate, becoming a hidden undercurrent that gradually disrupted its long-term development trajectory. All the efforts, including several rounds of turnaround plans and transitions of CEOs that attempted to upgrade its supply base and fix the relationship with suppliers, failed to rescue Wish from the brink of survival. April 2024, Wish was sold to the Singapore-headquartered e-commerce platform Qoo10 at a 99% markdown from its peak market price in 2021.

We trace Wish's rise and decline from 2011 to 2024, with a particular focus on how the platform-supplier relationships are influenced and even disrupted by the platform’s innovative technology and measures in the supply base over time. We also examine how the broader interdependencies in the supply network may constrain a platform’s capacity to achieve disruptive innovation. In seeking how and why a platform’s proposed disruptive innovation was disrupted, we illustrate how the evolving process can be divided into five phases with different supply management modes and associated challenges for the platform in managing supplier relationships and its supply network. The findings show that while platforms can bring disruptive power to existing supply networks to reorganize the patterns of value creation, whether a platform can sustain long-term success in competition or rather be disrupted by its own weight, depends on how it could cope with the disruptive tensions in the supply network.

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Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 10. Purchasing innovation, 11. Digital

Green logistics in food supply chains

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The food industry plays a dominant role in the academic discussion about sustainability, as in developed nations emissions from the field to the plate are about 30% of total anthropogenic emissions (Planete Energie, 2023). Great attention has been paid by researchers on the carbon footprint of production (in terms of agriculture and industrial processes), since it is responsible of most of the impact (Notarnicola et al., 2017). Logistics impact is not negligible either, since transportation accounts on average for 19% of total food system emissions (European Commission, 2023). Moreover, logistics impacts also on other aspects, such as road congestion and noise pollution. Thus, interest in sustainable logistics solutions is growing, and new sustainable practices are emerging, in line with the 'Green Logistics' principles (Liu & Yuan 2012).

Green Logistics is related to making the logistics processes – including transportation, warehousing, packaging, etc. – more environmentally sustainable (Liu & Yuan 2012), and it is associated to a variety of practices, such as reverse logistics, that includes collection for refurbishing or remanufacturing, collection of used packaging, and other practices (El Ayoubi & Radmehr, 2023). Extant studies provide taxonomies of green supply chain practices that also include some green logistics solutions. However, a specific taxonomy for green logistics is missing.

A first aim of the paper is therefore to fill this gap, by classifying green logistics solutions with specific reference to food distribution. Although some practices are common with other industries, food has peculiarities (e.g. cold chain management) that require special attention. This is done through a systematic analysis of literature and grey literature, to collect all possible nuances in how practices are studied and applied.

After introducing the taxonomy, the framework is used to analyze the adoption of the identified practices through a case-based method. Multiple case studies are used to gather more precise information on the implications of green logistics solutions adopted. A multiple case study is selected, with unit of analysis identified in the logistics distribution network of the focal company and managers as key informants. The information collected comes from a triangulation of data coming from interviews, questionnaires, and publicly available reports. During the interviews, the main topics of analysis were criticalities in terms of sustainability of the food supply chains, corresponding solutions represented by green practices, and impacts of the mentioned solutions. The authors decided to focus

on the Italian Food Valley district, in the Emilia Romagna region. Italy is one of the most important countries in the food sector, and the region of Emilia Romagna is particularly interesting due to the peculiar organization of the food system, such as the high diffusion of large producers' cooperatives who have an active role in matching supply with demand. Emilia Romagna has also some of the highest concentration of products protected by designation of origin certifications (PDO, PGI and GI).

Thanks to the literature analysis, we were able to map 185 different practices, spanning across the following areas:

- **Network design:** some solutions (e.g. port centric logistics) help design the logistics network of food products in a more sustainable way;
- Infrastructures, with practices and solutions that impact the single nodes in terms of:
 1. building management, in terms of energy efficiency, use of refrigerants or water, and wastage (e.g. cogeneration);
 2. processes: the main processes considered include inventory sizing, handling, storage, waste management, and other processes (e.g. automation of processes);
 3. collaboration (e.g. sharing of spaces);
- **Distribution,** with green practices related to different types of transportation (Full Truck Load or Last Mile) and vehicles (in terms of fuel and mode). Moreover, also drivers' behavior and management (of routes and spaces) are included. Collaboration is present also in this part, with practices such as groupage;
- Packaging, with solutions that can affect material, size, and management;
- **Reverse logistics,** with solutions such as refurbishing or collecting used packaging;
- **Compensation,** which is included to have a full picture, although it is not a green practice per se and there is still an open debate in terms of actual impact.
- Others, which includes management systems, training, results monitoring, compliance to standards, strategy, collaboration, and noise pollution.

The second contribution of the paper is related to the analysis of the adoption of green practices. Case studies results show that the most applied solutions are related to transportation (mentioned by 9 companies out of 15). An interesting point to note is the limited efficiency and the high costs of electric vehicle. The practices related to warehouses and infrastructure are also applied, especially solar panels or solutions to improve the energy efficiency of the building. Automation, instead, is still perceived as an elite solution, and this could be explained by the intrinsic characteristics of the food sector in Italy, dominated by small and medium enterprises that have limited investment capacity. Packaging practices focus more on the avoidance of use of multiple materials, that makes recycling less complex, and on the reduction in the use of plastic.

Criticalities mentioned in the interviews were linked to corresponding solutions and related economic and environmental impacts. The sets of criticalities, solutions, and impacts were then classified in various categories. Category I includes practices that lead to improvements from both economic and environmental (reduction in CO₂e emissions and/or non-recyclable waste) perspectives. Category II covers solutions that worsen the economic situation but lead to energy savings and/or significant reductions in CO₂e emissions. Category III refers to solutions that show an improvement in economic performance but are accompanied by an increase in CO₂e emissions. These were mentioned during interviews as solution to some criticalities but are less relevant for the scope of the study as the

environmental impact is negative. If an impact is positive only from an environmental or economic perspective, it is assigned to Category X. Finally, in cases where criticalities were evidenced but no solution proposed, the criticality is assigned to Category O.

The strong presence of Category I and Category II solutions reflects the influence of both economic and environmental factors. Economically, companies are motivated by potential cost savings, operational efficiency improvements, and regulatory incentives. On the environmental side, there is increasing pressure from stakeholders to adopt sustainable practices.

To conclude, a causal map is presented to summarize the main environmental criticalities encountered in the food supply chain, and the most promising solutions to the problem.

The paper aims to have a twofold contribution. First, it fills a gap in the literature and provides useful hints to prioritize research activities in the field. Second, practically, it provides managers with an actionable tool to choose practices that improve the sustainability of their logistics processes. The paper is relevant to the conference scope as it relates to one of the key topics, environmental sustainability, and positions in the supply chain management subject of literature.

However, some limitations exist. Although the authors have thoroughly analyzed both scientific and grey literature, some practices may still be missing. The outcomes in terms of adoption level can be related to the peculiarities of the Emilia Romagna region. The companies that accepted to participate to interviews are probably the most sustainable and the sample suffers therefore a selection bias. Future research could focus on expanding the study to a wider sample of companies, also in other Italian or foreign regions.

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Paper topic

2. PSM strategy, 16. Sustainability - environmental, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

Adapting ProcurCompEU for Innovation in Healthcare Procurement: A Competency Framework Approach

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Practitioner Paper

Abstract/summary

Healthcare Procurement of Innovation (HPI) is increasingly recognised as a strategic lever for addressing complex challenges in healthcare while fostering technological advancements. However, it is unclear which competences HPI personnel require. The European Commission's ProcurComp^{EU} framework provides a structured competency model for public procurement, yet its applicability to innovation procurement, especially HPI, remains underexplored. This paper examines how ProcurCompEU can be adapted to address the unique demands of HPI, emphasising the need for knowledge, skills, and behaviours that facilitate supplier engagement, risk management, and long-term strategic planning. Building on the competency-based view and the Knowledge-based View (KBV), we argue that HPI professionals require a distinct set of competences that go beyond traditional cost-efficiency models. Through a literature review, this paper explores the specific competency gaps and how they can be bridged through targeted capacity-building initiatives. The ongoing empirical research includes a series of future expert interviews that could not yet be included.

Paper topic

1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

Digital product passport in the textile industry: what is the supply chain readiness?

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The textile industry is a key sector within European manufacturing, counting 143,000 companies and employing 1.3 million people (Alves et al., 2024). Nevertheless, the industry is under increasing scrutiny for its sustainability profile, due to significant environmental and social impacts along the supply chain (Stridsland et al., 2023). The industry accounts for 8-10% of global GHG emissions (Stridsland et al., 2023), generates 57 million tonnes of waste on a global scale (Gachenga, 2022) and faces poor labour standards and working conditions, especially in the upstream supply chain (Köksal et al., 2017). Textile supply chains typically include multiple tiers located across the globe, which exacerbates these problems by creating intricate relationships among suppliers and focal companies, while also decreasing transparency.

Recognising the magnitude of environmental and societal impacts of the industry, EU regulators have prioritised the textile industry within the legislative framework of the Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2024; Zhang and Seuring, 2024), drafting the EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles (European Commission, 2022). The strategy is built around six pillars: introducing mandatory eco-design requirements; stopping the destruction of unsold or returned textiles; tackling microplastics pollution; introducing information requirements and a Digital Product Passport; green claims for truly sustainable textiles; extended producer responsibility and boosting reuse and recycling of textile waste (European Commission, 2022).

The Digital Product Passport is thus a cornerstone of the EU policy for sustainable and circular textiles, expected to enable informed decision support for purchasing by sustainable customers as well as to facilitate compliance with existing and upcoming regulations (Zhang and Seuring, 2024). A digital product passport (DPP) is a “digital interface composing a certified identity of a single identifiable product by accessing the set of life cycle registrations linked to this object in order to yield insight into the sustainability and circularity characteristics, the circular value estimation, and the circular opportunities for both that product and its underlying components and materials” (van Capelleveen et al., 2023). The DPP is expected to be at the centre of a joint transition towards circularity, digitalisation and sustainability (European Commission, 2022; University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership and Wuppertal Institute, 2022), calling for a collaborative supply chain in which the exchange of data is functional to these transitions (Jensen et al., 2024).

This legislative change will induce organisations to innovate to ensure regulatory compliance (Chaudhuri et al., 2024). However, there is limited knowledge of the *a-priori* psychological, behavioural, and structural preparedness of organisations (Lokuge et al., 2019), in relation to the introduction of the DPP (Zhang and Seuring, 2024). Adapting the *a-priori* model of organisational readiness for digital innovation, this work thus aims to investigate the organisational and supply chain readiness to adopt DPP within the textile industry, contextually identifying barriers and enablers for DPP implementation.

Research on DPP is currently immature, therefore an exploratory multiple-case study research design was used. Case study research methodology was selected as the research focuses on a contemporary phenomenon, i.e. the textile supply chain implementation of the DPP, arising in a real-life context (Yin, 2003). The multiple-case study design allows to compare different case studies through a cross-case analysis, thus strengthening the external validity of the study (Gong et al., 2018). Purposive sampling was used to select the case studies, allowing the selection of relevant cases for the research objectives (Creswell, 2014). Relevant cases include organisations along multi-tier textile supply chains, as well as consortiums of organisations belonging to the industry. Data and information were collected according to a case study protocol. Primary data collection included ten semi-structured interviews and three site visits, while archival data about the organisations were collected through secondary sources including company websites, internal company documents and publicly available reports, effectively achieving data triangulation.

Preliminary results identify limited cognitive, cultural and strategic readiness at the organisational level, especially in smaller companies and in organisations located upstream in the supply chain. These companies predominantly describe DPP as an additional element of legislative compliance within the sustainability domain and question the potential distribution of value emerging from the DPP along the supply chain. Cognitive readiness is primarily hampered by limited expertise and knowledge on sustainability and circularity and secondly by limited digital knowledge. Partnership and trust are widely considered as the key enablers to successfully implement DPP along the multi-tier supply chain to limit data confidentiality risks. At the same time organisations recognise a low IT readiness at the supply chain level, especially due to fragmented IT systems, which hinder standardized exchange of data and systems interoperability.

Data to be included in the DPP is generally available across the supply chain, although some challenges were highlighted in achieving the product-level granularity of data required. The effective translation of regulatory requirements into supply chain data requirements is a critical enabler for the DPP to successfully go beyond regulatory compliance and create value. Supply chain data requirements should capture information supporting operations of all supply chain tiers, rather than being led by focal companies generated platforms, thus limiting information asymmetries. This would enable to distribute benefits across all supply chain tiers, avoiding to reinforce existing textile supply chain dynamics with unbalanced value capture favouring focal companies. Circularity information in the DPP was particularly highlighted as a critical issue, as data requirements may differ significantly depending on the positioning of organisations along the multi-tier supply chain and the circular strategy being employed. Further barriers regarding data were highlighted for parts of the supply chain located outside the EU, including concerns regarding data availability, quality and integrity, particularly for suppliers located in developing countries. Future research may expand this work by including in the study also suppliers located outside the EU jurisdiction to obtain a more nuanced understanding of the supply chain readiness for the DPP.

This work contributes to the supply chain management literature by (i) identifying barriers and enablers to the adoption of DPP during the early initiation phase of DPP implementation; (ii) expanding the theory on organisational readiness to the supply chain domain, focusing specifically on readiness of supply chains to endure legislation-induced changes targeting concurrently digital, sustainable and circular dimensions.

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Paper topic

20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.), 16. Sustainability - environmental, 11. Digital

Engagement in public procurement as drivers of circular economy: the role of companies' market orientation and supply chain collaboration

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Purpose: Engagement in Public procurement activities has been identified as a powerful driver of innovation in companies, with positive effects on their financial and sustainability performance (Adjei-Bamfo et al., 2023; Testa et al., 2016). Recently, Sun et al. (2024) demonstrated that participation in public procurement can incentivize the adoption of circular economy (CE) practices. However, several studies have identified key barriers affecting companies' participation and success in public procurement, emphasizing that both procedural and relational capabilities are critical for companies to navigate and win public tenders (Ancarani et al., 2019; Flynn & Davis, 2017). A related stream of research has investigated how strategic market orientation can help to succeed with public buyers. In particular, strategic market orientation allows firms to proactively align their internal capabilities and external market strategies to address the demands of innovation from buyers (Kibbelling et al., 2013), thus improving their ability to adapt to sustainability-driven requirements in tenders. Recently, scholars have argued that companies with a strong understanding of public sector customers' needs and expectations are more likely to succeed in procurement, highlighting the role of customers market strategic orientation in this process (Saastamoinen et al., 2020; Tammi et al., 2017). Furthermore, Sönnichsen & Clement (2020) found that supply chain collaboration significantly enhances success in circular public procurement, as cooperation among suppliers, manufacturers, and public buyers helps overcome technical and logistical challenges, fostering the adoption of CE practices (Genovese et al., 2022). Despite these advancements, little research has explored how firms' strategic market orientations can act as an enabler for public procurement participation and circular economy integration, addressing both internal alignment and external collaborative efforts. While literature has individually explored the success factors in PP participation and its role as a driver of sustainable and circular innovation (Sun et al., 2024; Saastamoinen et al., 2020), a gap remains regarding the influence of strategic market orientation on circular practices through public procurement participation. Addressing this gap, this study investigates how strategic market orientation fosters firms' engagement in public procurement, driving their transition towards a circular economy.

Design/methodology/approach: Given the heterogeneity of regulatory frameworks across European Union member states in promoting sustainability and circular economy through Green Public Procurement (GPP), this research targets firms operating in seven EU countries: Italy, Austria, Germany, Poland, Hungary, Slovenia, and Croatia. The selection of these countries accounts for varying levels of

regulatory pressure, sampling firms from countries with well-established GPP frameworks (e.g., Italy's Environmental Minimum Criteria) as well as those with emerging policies (e.g., Poland). Focusing on key sectors such as manufacturing and construction, which are heavily engaged in public procurement, this research adopts a mixed-methods approach. First, a questionnaire-based survey is designed using validated constructs from literature to measure market orientation strategies (Narver & Slater, 1990), supply chain coordination (Li et al., 2005; Chen & Paulraj, 2004), and firms' integration of circular economy practices (Corsini et al., 2024). The survey also includes control variables such as firm size, sector differences, and regulatory environment to account for confounding factors that might influence results, strengthening the validity of the findings. The questionnaire will be reviewed by practitioners from national agencies and chambers of commerce and pretested by managers in eight companies to refine potentially unclear items and reduce the risk of bias. The survey will then be translated and disseminated to a stratified sample of firms across targeted countries, with the goal of collecting up to 500 responses. Subsequently, semi-structured interviews will be conducted to gain deeper insights into the mechanisms influencing firms' participation in GPP and the adoption of circular practices. The qualitative phase will deepen emergent patterns and differences across regulatory and sectoral contexts, helping to refine and contextualize the quantitative findings. The interview protocol, informed by literature and survey results, will target managers from five firms per country until data saturation is reached.

Expected Findings: In line with previous research, both customer and competitor orientation are expected to be critical drivers of firms' engagement in public procurement, enabling alignment with public buyers' circular requirements. Participation in public procurement is expected to significantly enhance firms' integration of CE practices, as it provides opportunities to meet green and circular criteria in public tenders. In this context, we expect the regulatory context to have a significant effect as firms in countries with higher regulatory pressure on GPP may adopt CE more proactively than those in less regulated environments. Lastly, supply chain coordination is expected to play a pivotal role, since external collaboration and coordination with suppliers helps firms overcome technical and logistical challenges, boosting success in public procurement and ensuring the effective implementation of circular practices.

Theoretical contribution: The Resource Dependence Theory (RDT) offers a robust framework to explain the dynamics of firms' participation in PP and their adoption of CE practices. RDT posits that firms depend on external resources, and their success centers on their ability to strategically manage these dependencies (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978). PP represents a critical source of financial resources and legitimacy for firms, especially as governments increasingly prioritize sustainability through green and circular procurement frameworks. Two resource dependence related effects may influence firms' orientation toward public procurement as a driver of CE practices: (1) the *resource effect*, where the stable demand and low risks of public contracts empower firms to set their orientation toward public procurement (Sun et al., 2024), and (2) the *monitoring effect*, where external stakeholders, such as investors and the media, amplify attention on firms' sustainability, motivating their efforts in advancing CE when they participate in public procurement.

Originality/Value: This research addresses a gap between two distinct research streams, examining how strategic market orientation predisposes firms to participate in public procurement, thereby enhancing their integration of CE practices. Moreover, by integrating RDT with Market Orientation, this study explores how firms navigate resource dependencies while responding to market demands and competitive pressures. Together, these perspectives provide a comprehensive understanding of how firms adapt to the public demands of circular economy.

Keywords: circular economy, public procurement, strategic market orientations, supply chain coordination.

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Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 13. Public procurement

Repeated ties in buyer-supplier projects

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This study investigates the interplay between value creation and value capture of learning effects in buyer-supplier relationships. It focuses on how interproject learning effects affect supplier profitability. We analysed key performance indicators (e.g., profit, past turnover with focal buyer, past turnover with other buyers, R&D ratio, general turnover) of around 3,000 projects from a large automotive supplier. Our findings indicate that suppliers learn from repeated projects. However, the extent to which this results in higher profitability depends on whether these repeated projects are with the same buyer or with another buyer. We find that past turnover with a focal buyer in a given product group reduces the supplier's profitability. However, past turnover with other buyers shows a positive effect on the supplier's profitability. Supplier dependence shows to moderate these effects, and generally reduces the supplier's value capturing leverage. These findings provide new insights into the dynamics of value creation and value capture of learning effects in buyer-supplier relationships.

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 5. Supplier selection, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

Bridging Agile Procurement and Preferred Customer Status: A Strategic Integration

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

In today's business environment, characterized by intense competition for high-quality resources and the scarcity of strategic suppliers, the concept of the "preferred customer" has emerged as a pivotal strategic advantage for organizations. This status not only ensures stability in procurement operations but also fosters innovation, collaboration, and long-term partnerships. Nollet et al. (2012) highlight the numerous benefits of preferred customer status, including prioritized access to limited resources, enhanced collaboration in innovation, and increased operational flexibility. These advantages significantly contribute to organizational competitiveness and sustainable performance. Similarly, Hüttinger et al. (2012) emphasize that two critical determinants — customer attractiveness and supplier satisfaction — serve as precursors to achieving preferred customer status, as suppliers prioritize customers who align with their strategic objectives and contribute to their long-term success.

This working paper explores the practices and attributes in buyer-supplier relationships that promote preferred customer status in the context of strategic procurement. Using George C. Homans's Social Exchange Theory (1958) as a guiding framework, the study examines the interplay of customer attractiveness, supplier satisfaction, and strategic alignment, proposing a conceptual model that integrates these factors. Fiocca (1982) provides an early foundation by identifying the key dimensions suppliers evaluate when determining customer attractiveness, including market size, economic benefits, technological capabilities, and socio-political alignment.

The Role of Customer Attractiveness in Buyer-Supplier Relationships

Customer attractiveness represents the initial stage of relationship development, where suppliers assess potential buyers based on their value proposition. Hald et al. (2009) identify economic, relational, and technological factors as key drivers of attractiveness. Buyers that offer consistent purchasing volumes, financial stability, and opportunities for innovation are more likely to attract supplier interest. Additionally, relational attributes such as trust, cultural compatibility, and a history of reliable engagement play a pivotal role in enhancing attractiveness. These findings align with Fiocca's (1982) segmentation criteria, which suggest that suppliers evaluate buyers on multiple dimensions to determine their potential strategic fit.

In globalized supply chains, customer attractiveness is further influenced by the buyer's ability to integrate advanced technologies. Choy et al. (2002) argue that tools such as relationship management systems, augmented by artificial intelligence, enhance the precision and efficiency of supplier selection. These technologies enable buyers to communicate their value effectively, reinforcing their attractiveness to suppliers and enabling better alignment of capabilities. For example, companies using AI-driven tools report reductions in supplier selection time and increased alignment in operational goals (Choy et al., 2002).

Supplier Satisfaction: Sustaining and Strengthening Relationships

Supplier satisfaction serves as the bridge between initial attractiveness and the potential for preferred customer status. Defined by Essig and Amann (2009) as the alignment between supplier expectations and relationship outcomes, satisfaction is a critical determinant of long-term relationship stability. Buyers that consistently meet or exceed supplier expectations in operational performance, communication quality, and adherence to agreements are more likely to sustain positive interactions.

Operational excellence is a recurring theme in the literature. Nyaga et al. (2010) highlight the importance of efficient processes, such as timely payments, clear communication, and reliable delivery schedules, in fostering supplier satisfaction. Beyond these functional aspects, relational factors such as trust, loyalty, and shared objectives deepen the supplier's commitment to the buyer. Trust, in particular, reduces perceived risks and enhances collaboration, as highlighted by Christiansen and Maltz (2002), who note its role in enabling smaller buyers to secure preferential treatment despite limited economic leverage.

Preferred Customer Status: Achieving Strategic Priority

Preferred customer status represents the culmination of sustained efforts in demonstrating customer attractiveness and maintaining supplier satisfaction. This status is characterized by the supplier's willingness to prioritize the buyer in resource allocation, innovation initiatives, and operational support. Steinle and Schiele (2008) highlight the strategic advantages of preferred customer status, noting that suppliers are more likely to offer exclusive benefits, such as early access to innovations, favorable pricing, and flexible terms, to their preferred customers.

These benefits are further enhanced when buyers actively engage in collaborative practices. Moody (1992) emphasizes that early involvement in supplier projects, proactive communication, and joint problem-solving are critical practices for maintaining preferred customer status. Similarly, the strategic alignment of objectives and the creation of shared value through co-development initiatives are cited as best practices for fostering long-term supplier loyalty (Hüttinger et al., 2014).

Conceptual Model Integration

Building on insights from Social Exchange Theory and existing literature, this working paper proposes a conceptual model that integrates the stages of customer attractiveness, supplier satisfaction, and preferred customer status. The model emphasizes the progression from initial value assessment to sustained relationship management and strategic prioritization.

Key components of this model include:

1. **Economic Value:** Buyers that provide consistent purchasing volumes, profitability, and reduced transaction costs are more attractive to suppliers and likely to achieve satisfaction and preference.
2. **Relational Quality:** Trust, loyalty, and cultural alignment serve as foundational elements for deepening relationships and fostering long-term partnerships.
3. **Strategic Alignment:** Compatibility in objectives, geographical proximity, and shared innovation goals contribute to the strategic prioritization of buyers by suppliers.

By structuring these components within a dynamic framework, the model highlights the interconnected nature of buyer-supplier relationships and the deliberate actions required to achieve preferred customer status.

Research Justification and Practical Relevance

The justification for this research lies in its potential to address key challenges in modern supply chain management, where competition for strategic suppliers and high-quality resources is intensifying. Organizations that successfully position themselves as preferred customers not only secure operational stability but also gain access to critical innovations and competitive advantages.

The practical relevance of this work is underscored by its focus on structured practices that align buyer and supplier interests. Recommendations include enhancing operational efficiency, fostering trust and transparency, and leveraging technological tools to optimize supplier engagement. These practices, as supported by the literature, are instrumental in achieving the mutual benefits central to strategic procurement relationships.

Findings

Working Paper.

Relevance/contribution

Mentioned in the above Abstract.

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Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 4. Category management, 2. PSM strategy

Can contract logistics leverage reverse logistics to orchestrate the sustainability of packaging waste management? A multiple-case of Kenyan manufacturers

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This exploratory study investigates the role of contract logistics in sustainable packaging waste management. It is motivated by the apparent decoupling of a firm's economic activities from environmental and social responsibilities. Kenya provides a rich context for this undertaking owing to its idiosyncratic manner of dealing with solid waste in general. While it hosts many multinational corporations dealing in consumer goods that release tonnes of packaging materials to the market, the country is grappling with the implementation of solid waste management laws due to lack of funding, lack of support from the population, and partly emasculation by powerful multinationals that seem to resist these changes (Behuria, 2019). It seems that these legislations are symbolic rather than intentional owing to the nonchalant nature of their implementation. Granted, modest steps have been made towards sustainable waste management but the weakest link remains the manufacturers of consumer goods. For this reason, the study proposes the use of logistics service providers to take over the backward flow and disposition of post-consumer packaging products to enable focal firms achieve sustainable packaging waste management.

This proposal is informed by the debate in the literature on the efficacy of contract logistics in supply chain management. For instance, the use of contract logistics providers is considered a strategic outsourcing decision that remarkably reduces logistics costs and also helps to unlock the sustainability of a firm's reverse logistics model (Wang *et al.*, 2020). Besides, it is established that the right choice of logistics service provider enables a focal firm to gain value-added capabilities, reduced supply chain risks, robust environmental policy, smart technology, competitive advantage and proficient management of backward logistics operations, among others (Chen *et al.*, 2021). In a nutshell, the capability of contract logistics has advanced to the extent that it is likely to orchestrate sustainability within the supply chain ecosystems of their partners. In Africa, particularly, this orchestrating role of advanced logistics service providers is projected to be in the offing currently (Achola, 2024) thus informing this exploration in Kenya.

We conjecture that contract logistics can undertake the reverse logistics operations of planning, controlling, and implementing the backward flow of packaging materials and associated information from the consumer to the producer on behalf of its client, in order to recapture value or for proper disposal (Rogers and Tibben-Lembke, 1999). While Ravi and Shankar (2015) identify the strategic role of

reverse logistics in achieving operational competitiveness, Bag and Gupta (2019) and Münch *et al.* (2023) tie sustainability achievement to this very competitiveness. Therefore, we argue that reverse logistics can lead to the sustainability of post-consumer packaging waste management. This, as a matter of fact, forms the basis of our research question: *How can contract logistics leverage RL to orchestrate sustainability of packaging waste management of Kenyan FMCG industry?*

The answer to this question demonstrates how consumer goods manufacturers can streamline the efficient backward flow of their post-consumer packaging waste to address socio-ecological sustainability requirements. For this to be achieved, the investigation anchored on a mid-range theory of circular economy which advocates a departure from the linear business model to a cyclic 'cradle-to-cradle' model. Consequently, it enables the scrutiny of a firm's strategy on processes and mechanisms of sustainable post-consumer packaging waste management.

A multiple-case study approach was adopted whereupon four cases of food and beverage manufacturers were selected based on their predominant use of PET (polyethylene terephthalate) plastic and glass containers, both of which rank as the most popular packaging materials in the industry globally (Ma *et al.*, 2020). We then categorised the cases using a matched-pair design in which a set of two cases, each with a common packaging material, were compared (Eisenhardt, 2021). We further included peripheral entities such as manufacturers of the packaging materials, the producer responsibility organizations (PROs) for the respective focal firms, and a couple of logistics service providers with the intention of triangulating responses from the focal cases. A total of 15 interviews were conducted using a semi-structured interview protocol administered to senior supply chain managers and operation managers. Data was obtained in the form of interview notes since nearly all respondents refused to be audio-recorded.

We used literature to aid in the categorization of data (Locke *et al.*, 2020) leading to Gioia's style first-order codes (Gioia *et al.*, 2012) totaling to 17 in number. These were then axialized to form second-order codes by constant comparison between the initial categories (obtained from the literature) and data. A further iteration of the latter codes, upon saturation, yielded three aggregate themes: planning and coordination of packaging waste logistics; advanced capabilities of logistics service providers; and post-consumer packaging product reclamation and revalorization. The three themes were then subjected to discussion and used to answer the overarching research question.

The preliminary findings are key in giving the direction that the study takes. Upon completion, the study is likely to definitively show how pivotal contract logistics is in addressing post-consumer packaging waste management. It will have managerial implications regarding making policies bent on increasing the use of logistics service providers to plan and manage packaging waste value chains of focal firms. On the theoretical front, it reveals that logistics outsourcing can also trigger changes in the supply chain systems by setting pace on the sustainability drive of packaging waste management to erstwhile dormant manufacturers.

Keywords: Sustainability, Contract Logistics, Reverse Logistics, Packaging Waste, Manufacturers

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Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental

Supply chain resource orchestration towards regeneration: the enabling impact of collective action

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

To achieve regenerative goals within a supply chain, organizations must access, and leverage resources located inside and across supply chain boundaries. This paper examines how resources are gathered, organized and mobilized at the network level in pursuit of social-ecological regeneration using case studies of 12 B Corps. Preliminary findings highlight the different structural features and relational mechanisms that enable collective action towards regeneration. Further, the findings illustrate the importance of each of these elements through the structuring, bundling, and leveraging of collective resources in support of social-ecological regeneration.

Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental

Reconceptualizing value creation for regenerative supply chains: Elaborating the role of non-traditional actors

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

Regenerative supply chains necessitate a significant change in how organizations operate their supply chain to create value. Traditional linear supply chains operate with many assumptions about value that conflict with the principles of regeneration. We problematize the existing frames used to understand what constitutes value, and how it is created and distributed within supply chains. We reconceptualize value and propose alternative approaches to value creation and distribution in regenerative supply chains that centre non-traditional actors and recognizes the importance of social and ecological systems. Finally, we advance research principles to guide future research on regenerative value in supply chains.

Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social

Employer Attractiveness from the Purchaser's Perspective: The Case of Swedish Forestry

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Any organization's performance is dependent on its employees, which makes the organization's ability to attract and keep skilled employees crucial. The concept of employer attractiveness has been minted to describe this ability. Being perceived as attractive is important for the employer, because it influences both career choices and job choice decisions of potential employees, as well as employee retention.

A current problem within the Swedish forest sector today is recruitment of employees. Research and practice testify to work environments within forestry that often contain stress, ambiguity and lack of coordination between functions. The purpose of this paper is therefore *to study how tensions within the purchasing function in forest companies affect the perceived employer attractiveness*. The paper is based on a comparative case study with two different forest companies in Sweden. The focus of the paper is on the purchasers' view of work conditions, as well as their (critical) view on modern forestry. The study comes close to their daily work and asks not just about their opinions, but also about their working conditions and how these conditions affect the interactions with suppliers.

Paper topic

3. Purchasing organisation, 1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 2. PSM strategy

Modern Slavery in PSM: a context dependent discourse and practice

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Purpose: The growing interest in studying Modern Slavery into Purchasing and Supply Management (PSM) research brings with it theoretical confusions and overlaps. Indeed, Modern Slavery refers to “situations of exploitation that a person cannot refuse or leave because of threats, violence, coercion, deception, and/or abuse of power” (ILO, 2017, p. 9). This definition provides an overview of Modern Slavery, but it challenges PSM managers to balance cost-cutting with human rights and (at minimum) decent work, since it is a very broad idea (Caruana et al., 2021). This becomes even harder when dealing with different contexts where legislation, cultural habits and companies’ practices affect PSM initiatives. Therefore, this paper aims at reflecting on and proposing boundaries that can guide future research and practice to deal with Modern Slavery.

Methodology: In this working paper, a two stage-study was employed to reach our research aim. First, we selected the 10 top cited academic papers to identify what is the definitions used and the subsequent status quo. Complementarily, we unpacked results from four existing literature reviews published about Modern Slavery (i.e., Han et al., 2024; Ishaya et al., 2024; Strand et al., 2024; Szablewska and Kubacki, 2023). Second, a secondary data study has been developed across the six regions: Africa, Americas, Asia, Europe, Middle East and Oceania. Moving away from a North-Western perspective, we intend to explore multiple perspective of Modern Slavery in each studied region.

Findings: Preliminary results show that within top cited papers there is no consensus about Modern Slavery. Terms such as “exploitation practices” and “forced labor” are often used, in some cases as synonymous. Some of the papers simply do not use any definitions. Two main disciplines supported our comprehension of Modern Slavery in PSM, that is, supply chain management and human resources management (see Han et al., 2024). Therefore, by exploring common practices we have developed a matrix that help to understand what the level of engagement is requested in PSM. For example, child labor, often linked to Modern Slavery, can have different expectations in different global regions. While this practice is not acceptable, specific contexts help to uncover reasons why it remains alive nowadays.

Practical implications: As part of our debate, we provide a matrix to help managers to improve due diligence through a diagnosis of their practices and risks.

Originality: This study provides an understanding of Modern Slavery to avoid the *one-size-fits-all* approach. We claim that although a common comprehension of the topic is vital, the context will shape how to deal with Modern Slavery due to legal, historical and political issues, which is often overlooked in the literature (Strand et al., 2024).

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Paper topic

17. Sustainability - social, 18. Risk and resilience, 12. Ethics

91

Window, Telescopes, Mirrors, Microscopes: A Conceptual Model of Boundaries in Supply Chains

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This research explores how buying firms use boundaries in supply chain discovery, focusing on modern slavery. Boundaries guide decisions, behaviours, and roles, defining control and group identity, while distinguishing between 'us' and 'them'. While established across management fields, boundary work is underexplored in supply chain research. For modern slavery, boundaries shape what firms prioritise, and overlook. Using empirical data, we propose a conceptual model showing how boundaries influence firms' attention to ethical issues. The findings shift the discovery focus from suppliers to buyers, emphasizing how buying firms create and maintain boundaries – and modern slavery – through their discovery efforts.

Paper topic

17. Sustainability - social, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 12. Ethics

Competing for water: households and nature as Factor Market Rivals

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Keywords: Water, Factor Market Rivalry, Competition, Supply Chain, Supply Chain Management

Submission category: Working paper abstract

Introduction

Currently, two billion people worldwide lack access to clean water, while four billion individuals experience acute water scarcity for a minimum of one month annually (UN, 2024). Globally, most fresh water is divided among 410 water basins of which 22% are considered high stressed but account for 51% of water withdrawals (Hundertmark et al., 2020). Water can thus be embedded in products and services that are transferred in supply chains out of regions already suffering from water scarcity. For example, 76% of fruit water footprints stem from overseas supply chains (Hess et al., 2018).

water basins, firms and supply chains in such areas are prone to experience water scarcity and high competition for water resources. This phenomenon, competition for resources in the firm's factor market is defined as factor market rivalry (Markman et al. 2009), and as such the Factor market rivalry theory (FMR) (Ralston et al., 2022) is well suited to examine it. Previous research (e.g. Ellram et al. 2013; Ralston et al. 2017; Wiedmer and Whipple, 2022) has examined FMR focusing on the tendency of firms to not recognize all competing firms within their factor markets. In areas suffering from water scarcity, water competition can indeed arise from beyond competitors in the same product markets, namely from firms in other industries as FMR currently predicts (Ralston et al. 2017), but also from further unanticipated directions such as households and nature itself. We argue that firms cannot overlook the factor market rivalry for scarce natural resources such as water from these non-firm rivals. The role of non-firm rivals in factor markets is substantial also from the perspective of strategies that can be chosen to respond to factor market rivalry. Based on the above, our research focuses on the following questions:

1) Why do firms not anticipate water scarcity and competition in upstream supply chains?

2) How do firms respond to water scarcity and competition in upstream supply chains, when rivals include firms but also households and nature?

3) How do firm responses mitigate the impact of water scarcity and competition in upstream supply chains?

Theoretical background

We apply the Factor Market Rivalry (FMR) as a theoretical background when exploring impacts from and responses to water scarcity and competition. Table 1 summarizes the key variables of the FMR theory, and how each variable applies in our study context.

Table 1 – FMR variables in the studied context (two first columns adopted from Ralston et al., 2022)

Methodology

We first employ a secondary multi-case data analysis to explore water scarcity and competition in upstream supply chains as well as how firms respond to FMR. We focus on textile firms' cotton supply chains because of their significant water footprint (Pazdzior et al., 2017) as well as negative impact on water, other environmental factors and human rights (Abbate et al., 2024).

Based on the FMR review, this study concludes that a firm can either anticipate or not anticipate FMR over water. Additionally, while water scarcity does exist, not all firms will have experienced a water disruption event in their supply chain yet. Figure 1 displays the four states a textile firm can thus 'exist' in. In our longitudinal, secondary data analysis we will map the potential, historic path that each case company takes across the four possible states (Figure 1) during 2013 to 2024.

Figure 1 – Overview of potential states depending on firms' un-/ anticipated water rivalry and no-/ experienced water disruption event.

This study first collects relevant supply chain and water-related information for each firm, by triangulating (Jick, 1979) the CDP Water Security database, firm annual (sustainability) reports and publicly accessible firm communications as well as news articles concerning the firm's water use and water management.

The second phase of the study includes a single in-depth case study. We use the secondary data analysis to find a relevant textile sector case company.

Expected contributions

Firms may not anticipate water scarcities and competition. Consequently, firms may also not be strategically prepared to address FMR over water. Yet water scarcity is only likely to become an increasingly prevalent issue in global supply chains (Cole et al., 2022), and scarcity of other natural resources are on a similar trajectory (Bell et al, 2012). Yet, only limited research on the impacts of natural resource scarcity exists within the SCM domain (Kalaitzi et al., 2019). Hence future research analyzing mitigation strategies for resource scarcity has been called for in general (Wiedmer and Whipple, 2022) and specifically in relation to water (Cole et al., 2022). Our research focus on firm responses to water FMR provides such called for contributions. We particularly aim to explain the

dynamics of factor market competition including additional stakeholders beyond firms, namely households and nature. We hence extend the FMR theory within the water context, which is particularly relevant when considering the grand challenges that supply chains face. Adding competing voices beyond firms to resource factor markets is especially important in the context of the just transition (Karaosman et al., 2024).

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Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience, 16. Sustainability - environmental

Artificial Intelligence in Public Procurement: Understanding Challenges and Potential through Participatory System Mapping

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Summary: Amid growing expectations on the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for process improvement, several challenges prevent its adoption and exploitation to full potential. These challenges are even more relevant for the public sector where experimenting with technology poses higher risks than in a business context. This paper thus presents an analysis of the complex web of factors influencing AI adoption in public procurement processes. Through an expert study, we identified driving and hindering forces pertaining to technological, organizational, and environmental dimensions. We then analyzed their interdependencies through a novel analytical approach. The resulting system map sheds light on core aspects.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, public procurement, theory of change, TOE, expert study

Introduction and relevant literature

With AI mainstreaming, there is the risk of a public-private digital divide to grow even further. Against the prospect of higher efficiency, firms are urged to experiment and adopt emerging technological solutions. Instead, AI can prove uniquely problematic in a public sector context due to, on the one hand, the impact of potential errors (e.g., private data leaks, discrimination) and, on the other hand, the need to follow still unclear regulatory frameworks (e.g. the “AI act”). The divide seems to be widening also with respect to procurement processes. Yet, with public spending ranging between 15% and 20% of gross domestic product in most countries, is this sustainable? Under this premise, we analyze the challenges of AI adoption in support to public procurement to understand the complex interplay of factors specific to this context.

Relevant literature refers to AI in purchasing and supply management (e.g., Culot et al., 2023; Guida et al., 2023) and in particular to studies analyzing drivers and barriers (e.g., Chatterjee et

al., 2021). This is complemented by research on prior waves of digitalization and sector-specific considerations (Patrucco et al., 2017).

Methodology

Given the relative novelty of the phenomenon, this study was shaped with an exploratory intent. The research process consisted of two phases. First, we conducted a series of semi-structured interviews with experts from Europe and the US. The choice of geographies was motivated because of the similar levels of both public spending and government digitalization among the two geographical contexts, while presenting different policy orientations with respect to AI. So far, we interviewed 21 experts identified among executives working at technology providers, academics, users in public organizations, and policy advisors. We plan to carry out further interviews to better balance our sample in terms of geographies and respondent category. Questions revolved around unveiling AI potential in public procurement, barriers and drivers to adoption, and application-specific situations. The interviews were transcribed and coded according to the TOE framework.

The second phase of the project will be targeted at developing a participatory system map, adapting the method of Wilkinson et al. (2021). Specifically, the experts will be asked to assess the linkages among the various factors emerging from the analysis of the interviews through remote interactions.

Preliminary results

A series of factors emerged from our analysis as determinants of AI adoption in public procurement (see the Appendix). In terms of **technology**, it appears that technology advancements and the presence of use cases are the main drivers; however, public procurement might suffer more from the risks of AI errors and require a higher explicability of underlying analytical approaches. The presence of applications specifically targeted to the public sector is a must. From an **organization** perspective, many factors echo dynamics already highlighted for the private context (e.g., data quality and availability, change agents and digital champions). Interestingly, it seems that AI will require a redesign of processes with a likely centralization of procurement functions, despite potential drawbacks in terms of adoption speed. Finally, when considering the **environment** dimension, public opinion and the presence of policies/regulations stand out as the most relevant determinants.

Starting from the list of factors from the interviews, we analyzed the impacts and interdependencies. The map will be refined with the experts in the second phase of the project; however, it shows an interplay between the technological and environmental dimensions in driving organizational change.

Discussion and conclusion

The study provides a new perspective on the interplay between different determinants of AI adoption in public procurement. From our preliminary results, we can anticipate that some elements have a “mixed” effect (being both drivers and barriers). By analyzing these elements through system mapping, we should be able to highlight the conditions behind their actualization. This will advance current theoretical approaches to technological adoption and provide valuable input for policymaking.

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Appendix

List of factors according to the TOE framework:

Technology

- Advancements in AI capabilities
- AI technological complexity/explicability
- AI use cases beyond public procurement
- AI use cases in public procurement
- Applications suitable for public procurement
- Risks of AI-driven errors

Organization

- Benefits of using AI
- Budget allocation and funding challenges
- Centralization of procurement functions
- Change agents and digital champions
- Data quality and availability
- Digital maturity/literacy
- Employees' digital literacy
- External collaborations and partnerships
- Impact on suppliers
- Process redesign when adopting AI

- Resistance to change
- Technology deployment

Environment

- Adoption of standards and best practices
- AI and data regulation
- Application of AI beyond procurement
- Concerns of AI security and reliability
- Digital talent and AI literacy
- Fears of employees' displacement
- Funding for digitalization and AI initiatives
- International collaborations
- Legislation for transparency in public procurement
- Perceptions of AI potential and impact
- Policies to support AI development/use
- Research and knowledge availability
- Vendor ecosystem and outsourcing trends

Paper topic

13. Public procurement, 10. Purchasing innovation, 11. Digital

The sourcing strategy of British corporations before and after Brexit

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The sourcing strategy of British corporations before and after Brexit.

Introduction

The UK officially parted ways with the EU on the 31st of January 2020, after approximately four years of negotiations, challenges and business uncertainty. Overwhelmingly, everyday experience and the developing academic research (e.g., Du and Shepotylo, 2024; Du et al., 2023), suggest that, generally, the UK economy has been negatively affected by leaving the single market. For example, Du et al. (2023) found a persistent decline in UK export performance and a contraction in the variety of goods exported to the EU following the implementation of the EU-UK Trade and Cooperation Agreement. When it comes to the inward flows of goods and services, these have been adversely affected by the newly introduced tariffs, customs checks, and regulatory compliance requirements that have disrupted previously seamless supply chains. For instance, the UK chemicals sector faces heightened logistics delays and compliance costs due to divergent regulatory regimes, with 71% of companies reporting ongoing trade difficulties and 82% expressing concerns about dual regulatory uncertainties (Financial Times, 2024).

These increased lead times and costs have prompted British firms to reconsider their sourcing strategies. Many have explored reshoring and nearshoring options to mitigate risks associated with cross-border trade and regulatory uncertainties, and enhance supply chain responsiveness (Moradlou et al., 2021). The concept of “friendshoring”, which involves sourcing from countries with aligned geopolitical stances, has also gained prominence in the post-Brexit era (e.g., Charpin and Cousineau, 2024). This approach enables firms to build more resilient supply chains by engaging with partners in geopolitically stable and aligned regions.

However, despite the increasing interest in the implications of Brexit for global supply chains, there is no large-scale systematic work on whether and how British firms adapted their sourcing strategies amidst the uncertainty during the period from the 2016 referendum to the end of the ‘transition’ period (31/12/2020), and post-Brexit. This work employs longitudinal buyer-supplier (dyadic) data to address this gap and supplement related micro-level firm-based research (e.g. Moradlou et al. 2021) and macro-level studies on bilateral trade between UK and other nations (e.g. Du et al., 2023).

Theoretical scope

In this work-in-progress paper, we investigate changes in the procurement strategy of British public firms manifest through four dimensions:

- *Geographical dispersion* of the firm's supply base and spend.
- Extent of the firm's spend *concentration*.
- The firm's *dependence* (in terms of purchase spend) on suppliers from different regions (e.g., UK versus EU)
- The number of *critical suppliers* from different regions (e.g., UK versus EU)

Methodology

The timeframe of our work spans from 2012 to 2023. During this 12-year period, 'Brexit' turned from a fringe idea advocated by certain British right-wing political parties and figures to a seemingly irrevocable decision that has given rise to a 'new' business reality. As such, it should help us to holistically capture any trends in the dimensions of interest.

Data and variables

All data comes from the Supply Chain Analysis function of the Bloomberg terminal ("Bloomberg SPLC"). For a given firm, this function provides a list of all direct suppliers and customers. Bloomberg consults several sources to construct these lists, such as SEC filings, profit and loss accounts and trade news. A considerable proportion of these relationships is 'quantified', meaning that Bloomberg provides a US dollar amount (in millions) representing the value of goods or services exchanged between the companies (*REL_VALUE*), and a corresponding estimate of the bilateral financial dependence in percentage terms: for the supplier, this is the percentage of total revenues that comes from the customer (*%REVS*); for the customer, it is the percentage of total purchase spend that is allocated to the supplier (*%COGS*).

The main limitation of Bloomberg (and the SPLC function) is that it provides data almost exclusively for public firms, i.e., those listed in a stock exchange across the globe. This means that the resultant supplier lists do not include private firms like SMEs, a sector of the economy that includes approximately 99% of the businesses operating in the UK, and which appears to have been adversely affected by Brexit (British Chamber of Commerce, 2023). Yet, understanding structural changes in the relationships between large British public firms and their non-British counterparts is important for several reasons. First, a lot of these relationships are long-term strategic partnerships, and there is a lively theoretical interest in identifying the effects of geopolitical tensions and similar macro-level disruptions on such relationships (e.g., Rogers et al., 2024). Second, our interest is limited to the upstream side, and large public firms with global operations are naturally more exposed internationally for inputs than SMEs. Third, the volumes (and corresponding value of traded goods) exchanged between these firms is substantial in absolute terms, hence, changes in these can reflect significant macro-trends. Fourth, because these firms' strategic decisions can impact entire sectors or regions (e.g., Stellantis closing its Luton plant – The Guardian, 2024), it is important for policymakers to gather insight that can help them adjust policies and mitigate risks.

For all firms included in the FTSE 200 list with a 'physical' supply chain, we their suppliers' data on an annual frequency from 2012 to 2023 (31/12/2012, 31/12/2013 etc.). This resulted in hundreds of Excel

sheets (created through a combination of text analytics and manual brute force) that were merged into a multi-level dataset, wherein supplier relationships of focal British firms were observed for a maximum of 12 years. The country of origin or HQs (*COUNTRY*) for each supplier was sourced from the Orbis database. After imposing a reasonable threshold for the minimum number of quantified supplier relationships per firm (n), we ended up with a total of firms.

The next step was to appropriately aggregate the raw data and create the variables of interest at the firm-year level. Due to some missing values, we ended up with a slightly unbalanced *FIRM-YEAR* panel. All analysis is based on a sample of .

Geographical dispersion is measured by a) the number of countries with suppliers, and b) a dispersion measure of purchase spend among four regions (UK, EU, US, 'Other), based on Stock et al. (2000). *Supply base concentration* is operationalised using a) a simple Herfindahl–Hirschman index, and b) the mean %COGS allocated to Top 5 suppliers. *Dependence* on suppliers from different regions is the sum of %COGS allocated to suppliers from that region (e.g., UK), while *Critical Suppliers* from each region is the number of suppliers in the Top 10 (in terms of %COGS).

Data analysis

We only report some descriptive results. Specifically, we regress the dimensions of interest on time (operationalised as a set of dummy variables) using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and report on how the model-predicted means evolve over time.

Results and Discussion

Some emerging findings from the descriptive analysis follow.

- British corporations have (on average) reduced the geographical dispersion of their supply base and of their spend. There is a clear downward trend since 2016, despite a recent uptick.
- They also seem to have concentrated their spend to fewer and fewer suppliers, especially since 2017.
- In terms of the average dependence of British corporations for inputs on suppliers from the UK and the EU, there is no discernible trend in the data, with the average %COGS to supplier from both regions remaining relatively stable since 2016.
- The average number of critical suppliers from the two regions reveals a steady increase for EU, and a slight decrease for UK.

This preliminary descriptive analysis suggests that amidst the uncertainty and turbulence of the last decade, British corporations have developed deeper and possibly more collaborative relationships with a decreasing number of suppliers from limited locations. Although their reliance on EU suppliers for inputs has remained relatively stable, specific EU suppliers are becoming 'critical'. This might be because certain expertise and capabilities largely reside in the EU rather than at home, something that is recognised by British corporations.

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Paper topic

6. Outsourcing, offshoring, reshoring, 2. PSM strategy

How does Reshoring Benefit Manufacturing Companies? A Study of Performance Outcomes

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This study explores the performance outcomes of manufacturing reshoring through 16 interviews, with a four-dimension framework using the Eclectic Paradigm as the theoretical lens. Findings reveal efficiency-seeking advantages like improved profitability, flexibility, and production control, alongside strategic benefits such as better product quality, brand image, environmental sustainability, and positive societal impacts including job creation. Challenges, including unexpected delays, inventory level, and supplier disruptions, highlight the need for careful planning. By examining outcomes across two implementation phases, the research offers practical insights for firms and policymakers to enhance reshoring success. Future studies should explore how outcomes evolve post-implementation for deeper understanding.

Paper topic

6. Outsourcing, offshoring, reshoring

Geopolitical Disruptions and Agri-Food Resilience: Strategies from Poland's Food Supply Chain System

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The war in Ukraine has profoundly impacted global food security, economic stability, and supply chains. This paper investigates supply chain resilience strategies within Poland's agri-food industry in response to the war. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the research analyzes qualitative data from interviews and quantitative data from the Emerging Markets Information Service (EMIS) & Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAOSTAT). The study examines challenges like disrupted logistics, price volatility, and regulatory changes, evaluating the effectiveness of resilience strategies such as diversification, localized sourcing, and scenario planning. The integration of real-time analytics and predictive modeling is crucial for preparedness. Findings provide best practices for managing supply chain risks and offer recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders to enhance food system resilience amidst geopolitical uncertainty. This research contributes to a framework for mitigating vulnerabilities in global food systems.

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 18. Risk and resilience, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

SME resilience to high-impact shocks: Evidence from 15 cases in northern Europe

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This paper seeks to increase our understanding of resilience and addresses how small and medium enterprises (SMEs) maintain operations continuity when faced with high-impact shocks (i.e., crisis). The paper adopts a multiple-case study approach, including 15 SMEs. The study explains how the SMEs responded to high-impact shocks by tapping into their pre-, during, and post- crisis capital. The study suggests that SMEs use exploration and exploitation, depending on whether they are bouncing back or reorganizing and bouncing forward. This research finds that SMEs can be resilient by surviving and even realizing new business opportunities in such situations.

Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience

Sustainable building materials? Who cares. Architects' perception of sustainability attributes of flooring material in the Netherlands

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Practitioner Paper

Abstract/summary

The 12th Sustainable Development Goal (SDG 12) focuses on responsible consumption and production (UN, 2015). Addressing sustainability in the supply chains of construction materials is particularly important for meeting this goal because of its significant impact on resource use and waste management (Bellini et al., 2024; Kiani et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2022). In the European Union (EU), the construction sector is one of the largest consumers of natural resources (consuming about 50% of resources) and generates about 35% of all waste. Buildings are responsible for 40% of energy consumption and 36% of greenhouse gas emissions caused by construction work, use, renovation and demolition (EU, 2024). The construction sector thus contributes significantly to environmental impact and therefore faces a significant challenge to become more sustainable. The transition to a more sustainable construction sector is being driven by regulations such as the European Green Deal (GD), which aims to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. In addition to regulation, growing societal concerns about climate change play an important role. SDG 12 seeks a balance between economic growth and the conservation of natural resources, prompting companies to review their business processes to reduce waste and use resources more efficiently.

European flooring companies are increasingly investing in innovation and sustainability to meet stricter regulations and increasing market expectations for environmentally friendly products. An important focus here is the reduction of CO₂ emissions. To significantly reduce these emissions, there is a strong focus on recycling, ecodesign and promoting circularity. In addition, companies are encouraged to increase their transparency by publishing detailed reports on their sustainability progress (Forbo Group, 2023; Tarkett, 2023; Gerflor, 2022). Mutual competition can act as a catalyst for the acceleration of sustainable innovations (Porter & van der Linde, 1995; Lopes et al. 2022). Companies that fail in their sustainability efforts risk reputational damage, declining sales and may face legal consequences, while those that are successful can gain a competitive advantage by meeting the growing demand for sustainable products (Rosen & Kishawy, 2012; Tarnovskaya, 2023).

An important stakeholder in construction value chains are architects (Asselbergs, 2023). Architects play a pivotal role in influencing both upstream and downstream decisions—upstream by driving suppliers to innovate and prioritize attributes such as sustainability, design and cost-efficiency; downstream, through product selection, material application, and overseeing satisfaction of end-users. The role of architects must be carefully acknowledged and strategically integrated into the transitions towards a more sustainable construction industry, as they face an almost infinite number of choices in design and construction processes, ranging from functional and aesthetic to technical decisions (Michalak and Michalowski, 2021). The relevance of sustainable product attributes is increasingly important for architects in the Netherlands given the shifting regulatory landscape and consumer preferences.

But sustainability is multifaceted construct, and little is known about how architects factor various sustainability-related attributes into their decision-making process for which product to select (Camilleri et al., 2023). Employing hypothetical production evaluation techniques, in this research we examine architects' perception of flooring products. Relevant insights garnered from this approach include: 1) how sustainability attributes are considered in relation to other product attributes (e.g., functionality, cost), 2) how sustainability attributes are considered in relation to each other (e.g., upstream versus downstream carbon emissions; carbon impact versus recycled content); and 3) other relevant attributes (e.g., familiarity with specific concepts, perceptions of end-users' expectations and preferences). The validity of the study is enhanced by triangulation, combining insights from desk research with findings from semi-structured interviews. This combination of methods ensures that findings are viewed and verified from different perspectives, providing a more accurate understanding of how architects factor sustainability claims into their decision-making (Busetto et al., 2020).

Dutch architects reported high level of perceived interest from end users for sustainability-related product specifications, but differences were found between desired specifics depending on contexts (e.g., private residences versus large, publically-funded projects). Congruent with Michalak and Michalowski (2021), architects demonstrated high level of technical knowledge of sustainability-related product specifications. However, there was discrepancy in the understanding carbon impacts for the full life cycle of flooring products. Insights garnered in this research offer practical implications for promoting sustainable transitions in the European construction industry (paramount for SDG 12 and the Green Deal), as well as contributions to theoretical discussions on how the ambiguity of sustainability claims influence decision making processes of product selection.

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Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental

The impact of supply chain resilience on sustainability and financial performance: the mediating role of investments in sustainability

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

Resilience and sustainability are two critical, and sometimes conflicting, objectives for contemporary supply chains. This study examines the relationship between supply chain resilience (SCRES), sustainability, and financial performance. Based on a survey of 713 Italian firms, the study employs structural equation modeling with partial least squares to test the model. The findings reveal that SCRES positively influences sustainability performance, encompassing both environmental and social aspects, and financial performance. Furthermore, the study highlights the mediating role of sustainability investments, showing that resilient supply chains are more likely to adopt sustainable practices, which in turn positively impact both sustainability and financial performance.

Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience, 17. Sustainability - social, 16. Sustainability - environmental

Transitioning to the ecologically dominant paradigm: Inter-organizational relationships as a vehicle for change

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EADA Business School, Barcelona, Spain

Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The aim of this study is to understand how focal firms build upon inter-organizational relationships to drive positive environmental outcomes. The theoretical basis is grounded upon literature on environmental partnerships, the ecologically dominant paradigm, and the theory on planned change. The sample is composed by the 12 companies that achieved triple-A in the carbon disclosure project in 2023. Our method combines content and discourse analysis to capture the inter-organizational relationships and impacts sought, and evidence of new ways of thinking, doing and organizing that may point to a shift towards the ecologically dominant paradigm in incumbent firms and their ecosystems of action.

Paper topic

2. PSM strategy, 15. PSM theory, methodology, education, 16. Sustainability - environmental

Unveiling the Link between Supply Chain Collaboration and Competitive Advantage: The Mediation Role of Supply Chain Finance

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Keywords: *Supply chain collaboration, Supply chain finance, competitive advantage, small businesses*

Abstract

Despite being the engines of developing economies, small businesses are plagued with constraints that inhibit their progress and sustained competitiveness. This has also been heightened due to the influx of foreign products (Tsiu et al., 2024). Hence, strategies must be developed to address disruptions and fortify these small businesses' competitiveness. Competitive advantage is the ability of a business to outperform its rivals by delivering superior value to customers, achieved through cost leadership, differentiation, or enhanced responsiveness (Asare et al., 2023). Accordingly, most studies term supply chain finance as a solution for small businesses to optimise their working capital and fulfil their financing needs for the smooth functioning of their operations since it minimises risks and costs and facilitates the outperformance of competitors (Caniato et al., 2016; Hoffman, 2011; Xu et al., 2023). Supply Chain Finance (SCF) integrates financial services such as factoring, reverse factoring, and inventory financing into supply chain operations to ensure liquidity, reduce costs, and enhance operational efficiency (Huang et al., 2014).

For local small businesses operating in volatile and resource-constrained environments like Ghana, gaining competitive advantage demands that their supply chains are efficient and strategically collaborative. Due to this, it has become apparent to investigate how small businesses can integrate efforts across supply chain partners to enhance efficiency, innovation, and risk-sharing to gain resources to achieve an edge over their competitors. Supply chain collaboration refers to the strategic partnership and alignment of supply chain stakeholders to achieve shared goals through joint decision-making, resource sharing, and risk management (Baah et al., 2022). The importance of supply chain collaboration has not gone unnoticed, as studies have emphasised its role in preserving a supply chain's competitive position (Simatupang & Sridharan, 2005).

As small businesses, particularly in Ghana, face unique challenges, including constrained access to financial resources, which hampers their ability to sustain operations and leads to missed opportunities for growth, SCC can enhance operational efficiency and market responsiveness, clarify uncertainties through information sharing and helps businesses reduce certain transaction costs which serve as a drive for businesses to adopt supply chain finance solutions which will aid in achieving competitive advantage as stated by Chen et al.,2021, Jia et al.,2020 and Lu et al.,2020. Despite its significance, the circumstances and mechanisms under which supply chain collaboration can be harnessed through supply chain finance to gain competitive advantage remain underexplored in the context of small businesses in Ghana. Moreover, limited research exists on how SCF mediates the relationship between SCC and competitive advantage, leaving a critical gap in understanding how small businesses can optimise these synergies. This study argues that since supply chain collaboration can enhance and drive small businesses to partner among their supply chain partners to gain resources and outperform their competitors, then supply chain finance can mediate the relationship between supply chain collaboration and competitive advantage. In order to bridge these gaps, the study seeks to investigate the impact of supply chain collaboration on competitive advantage by exploring the mediating role of supply chain finance by answering the following research questions:

RQ1. How does supply chain collaboration influence the competitive advantage of small businesses in Ghana?

RQ2. To what extent does supply chain finance mediate the relationship between supply chain collaboration and competitive advantage?

The study uses the quantitative approach by employing the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) technique to assess the relationships between Supply Chain Collaboration, Supply Chain Finance, and competitive advantage. Data will be collected from a group of 257 small businesses in the Accra metropolis of Ghana of which was provided by Ghana Enterprise Agency, in February, 2021. The participants in the research include managers, owners and staff responsible for supply chain management tasks within the business.

The study makes significant contributions to both theory and practice. It advances academic discourse by elucidating the mediating role of SCF in the relationship between SCC and competitive advantage. Practically, the findings offer actionable insights for small businesses and policymakers. Small business managers can adopt SCF solutions to maximize the benefits of collaborative supply chain efforts, while policymakers can design financial support programs to strengthen supply chain ecosystems in emerging economies. By emphasizing the integration of SCC and SCF, the study provides a roadmap for small businesses to achieve sustainable competitive advantage in a challenging economic landscape (Tsolakis et al., 2023)

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Paper topic

19. Supply chain finance, 2. PSM strategy, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Exploring the role of supply chain ambidexterity and supply chain learning in enhancing competitive advantage

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Exploring the role of supply chain ambidexterity and supply chain learning in enhancing competitive advantage

Keywords: Competitive advantage, supply chain ambidexterity, supply chain learning, small and medium-sized enterprises

Abstract

In an increasingly complex and volatile business environment, sustaining competitive advantage has become essential for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), particularly in emerging economies like Ghana. This study investigates the roles of supply chain ambidexterity (SCA) and supply chain learning (SCL) in enhancing the competitive advantage of SMEs in Ghana. Competitive advantage, defined as the ability of a business to outperform its rivals by offering unique value, either through cost leadership, differentiation, or focus strategies (Kartiraharjo & Isfianadewi, 2021), is essential for SMEs striving to maintain a sustainable market position. Supply chain ambidexterity, the ability of a business to balance exploration and exploitation activities within supply chain operations, is a key factor that allows businesses to adapt to changing market conditions while maximising operational efficiency (Suharto, 2023; de la Lastra, Martín-Alcázar, & Sánchez-Gardey, 2022). It has been argued that small businesses that invest in exploitative practices, including process optimisation, experience operational stability and instant cost savings. Simultaneously, exploratory operations, including creating creative supply chain models, improve flexibility and agility, allowing businesses to seize new opportunities. (Patel and others, 2012; Úbeda-García et al., 2020). Despite the wide study of ambidexterity in organizational and strategic management (Zhao et al., 2021;), its application in supply chains of emerging economies is still underexplored. This leaves a gap in understanding how resource constrained firms like SMEs utilize exploitation and exploration to enhance their competitiveness. Supply chain learning, which involves acquiring, assimilating, and applying information throughout supply chain networks, enhances innovation and operational flexibility, which are vital for sustained competitive advantage (Huo et al., 2020). Studies have highlighted that supply chain learning improves performance and is an essential source of competitive advantage (Chen et al., 2023; Gurol, 2021). Businesses may

better anticipate and react to disturbances, align operations with market expectations, and enhance decision-making processes by giving learning inside their supply chains top priority.

Also, while exploration stresses creativity and adaptation, exploitation concentrates on streamlining current supply chain procedures for efficiency and cost-effectiveness. In order to bridge these two approaches, supply chain learning promotes a culture of experimentation and ongoing development (March, 1991; Raisch & Birkinshaw, 2008). Supply chain learning guarantees that insights from exploitation are recorded and utilised to improve exploration operations, and vice versa, through shared learning mechanisms like knowledge-sharing platforms, training courses, and cooperative projects (Schilke, 2014). Hence, companies with strong learning systems were better able to capitalise on the advantages of ambidexterity, increasing their ability to adapt to shifting consumer demands and market conditions. The significance of supply chain learning in promoting flexibility and creativity has been demonstrated by prior studies (Hult et al., 2003; Schilke, 2014). Nevertheless, not enough research has been done on how supply chain learning mediates the relationship between ambidexterity and competitive advantage. Filling this knowledge gap advances our comprehension of the ways in which ambidexterity might affect competitive outcomes. This study seeks to answer the following research questions: RQ1. How does supply chain ambidexterity affect competitive advantage among SMEs in Ghana? RQ2. How does supply chain learning affect the competitive advantage of SMEs in Ghana? RQ3. Does supply chain learning mediate the relationship between supply chain ambidexterity and competitive advantage in SMEs in Ghana?

The study employed a quantitative approach to evaluate the relationships between these variables by adopting the structural equation modelling technique (SEM). Data will be collected from 400 SMEs in the Accra Metropolis of Ghana (Ghana Enterprise Agency report from 2021). Given the challenges that SMEs in Sub-Saharan Africa encounter, such as globalisation pressures and restricted access to financial resources, others choose Ghana as the research setting, which holds significance. The participants in the research include supply chain managers working in small and medium-sized enterprises and staff responsible for supply chain management activities within these enterprises.

This research contributes to theory by integrating SCA and SCL into a cohesive framework that explains their synergistic impact on competitive advantage. It also offers practical implications for SMEs and policymakers, emphasising the importance of adopting ambidexterity and learning capabilities within supply chains. This study will also offer SMEs in Ghana and similar emerging markets the ability to navigate globalisation pressures and resource constraints more effectively, ultimately enhancing their competitive position and sustainability.

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Paper topic

2. PSM strategy, 10. Purchasing innovation, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Stimulating collaboration within youth care networks: The impact of public policy and procurement mechanisms

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Network collaboration holds promise for addressing youth care challenges, but its realization hinges on policy decisions due to the public nature of youth care service delivery. This study aims to explore how policy incentives strengthen collaboration and enhance outcomes in youth care. Through a two-phased qualitative study in the Netherlands, analyzing approximately 100 tenders and conducting twelve interviews across four cases, we identify twelve policy incentives and four moderating factors. Our findings underscore the pivotal role of procurement procedures and the strategic combination of policy incentives in fostering effective network collaboration within youth care.

Paper topic

13. Public procurement

Managing buyer-supplier relationships in public procurement: a systematic literature review of relational contracting in the public sector

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This study delves into the role of relational contracting in public procurement, as an alternative to conventional contracting practices. Public procurement is a vital aspect of public financial management, with a significant proportion of GDP allocated to it. Traditional contracting methods often struggle with changing contexts, resulting in incomplete contracts. The notion of relational contracting, emphasizing trust and relational governance mechanisms, has therefore garnered attention. Via a systematic literature review this study examines the drivers, barriers, outcomes, and conditions under which relational contracting occurs in public procurement. It aims to provide an overview of its utility and consolidate existing knowledge transparently, contributing to financial management and public procurement and offers avenues for further research.

Paper topic

13. Public procurement, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 15. PSM theory, methodology, education

Leveraging dynamic capabilities in public procurement: Empirical insights on driving sustainability in supply networks

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Summary

This study explores how public buying organizations use dynamic capabilities to drive sustainability in the supply network. Preliminary analysis of public tenders and interviews with actors on the buyer and supplier side of public procurement, we identify two mechanisms: relational sensing which enables early engagement and contractual adaptation allowing for flexibility. The emergence of a more flexible approach to public tendering highlights how public organizations enhance collaboration through dynamic governance. This research contributes to the understanding of public procurement as a transformative lever and offers insights for policymakers aiming to institutionalize adaptive, sustainability-driven practices.

Paper topic

13. Public procurement

Sustainable Supply Chain Finance Platform Governance: The Role of Incentives and Control

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Introduction

Sustainability is a critical focus for global supply chains, encompassing environmental, social, and economic dimensions. While supply chains account for up to 86% of global greenhouse gas emissions (Hoepner and Schneider, 2022), sustainability challenges also include labour rights, diversity, equity, inclusion, resource inefficiencies, and economic disparities among suppliers (Abbasi, 2017). Recognising these challenges, the European Parliament introduced the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive, mandating companies to exercise due diligence on human rights and environmental impacts across supply chains, with significant financial penalties and civil liability for non-compliance. This includes identifying, preventing, and mitigating adverse impacts such as human rights violations and environmental degradation.

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs), which dominate global supply chains, often face significant barriers, such as limited access to capital, low credit ratings, and resource constraints, making sustainability improvements particularly challenging (Jia et al., 2020).

Sustainable Supply Chain Finance (SSCF) has emerged as a transformative approach to tackle these challenges, integrating sustainability into Supply Chain Finance (SCF), a set of financial solutions aimed at optimizing companies' working capital (Gelsomino et al., 2016). As firms increasingly seek innovative mechanisms to enhance sustainability, SSCF has attracted significant attention. SSCF programmes are orchestrated by SCF providers, including financial institutions and financial technology providers (fintechs), which design and implement platform ecosystem governance mechanisms to align financing with sustainability goals (Song et al., 2021).

Theory Background

The term SSCF was first introduced by Tseng et al. (2019), who explored Vietnam's textile industries and noted that SSCF can facilitate a balance among the triple bottom line dimensions, yielding benefits for SCF providers in risk control and for suppliers in sustainability performance. Later, Medina et al. (2023) provided the first formal definition: *"a set of solutions incorporating sustainability practices (e.g.,*

supplier assessment, development, incentives) to support their implementation within supply chain management” (p. 14).

SSCF addresses financial barriers that hinder suppliers, particularly SMEs, from adopting sustainable practices (Zhou et al., 2018). Scholars (e.g., Jia, et al., 2020; Zhan et al., 2018) have highlighted how SCF solutions, such as reverse factoring, alleviate liquidity constraints while enhancing sustainability outcomes. Companies like Coca-Cola, PVH, Henkel, Bridgestone and Walmart have implemented SSCF programs to incentivise sustainability in their supply chains.

Current literature (e.g., Medina et al., 2023) identifies two key governance mechanisms for implementing SSCF programs. The entry-barrier mechanism restricts suppliers’ access to SCF solutions unless they meet specific sustainability criteria. In contrast, the rewarding mechanism offers lower interest rates to suppliers based on sustainability performance.

Despite these advancements, the literature on SSCF remains fragmented, with limited exploration of diverse models and mechanisms. Much of the existing research primarily emphasizes access control and reward-based incentive governance mechanisms, while offering limited exploration of other governance mechanisms (Jia et al., 2020; Medina et al., 2023). Notably, the framework proposed by Chen et al. (2022) offers a comprehensive perspective on platform ecosystem governance, categorizing mechanisms into controls and incentives. Controls not only regulate which actors are onboarded but also monitor their behaviour, evaluate outputs, and manage their interactions with competing platforms. Similarly, incentives go beyond merely offering financial rewards; they aim to enhance participation by sharing technological resources, providing information, and granting autonomy within the platform ecosystem.

There is also limited understanding of how SSCF can engage a broader base of suppliers, particularly those with low initial sustainability performance, to foster inclusive improvements across supply chains (Nguyen et al., 2023). Studies also tend to focus on specific industries or regions, limiting the generalisability of findings and leaving gaps in understanding SSCF’s broader applicability (Medina et al., 2023).

In light of these gaps, comprehensive research is needed to explore innovative SSCF mechanisms, examine their adoption across industries and regions, and analyse their implications for governance and sustainability outcomes. These objectives guided the formulation of the following research question:

How does platform ecosystem governance affect buyer and supplier engagement and sustainability in SSCF programs?

Method

Given SSCF’s innovative nature and the limited research available, we plan to adopt a multiple exploratory case study approach. This methodology is particularly suited for investigating complex, emerging phenomena where theoretical frameworks are underdeveloped, and empirical evidence is scarce. Our study will focus on governance mechanisms employed by SCF providers, including fintech companies and financial institutions operating through dedicated platforms. By examining these mechanisms, we aim to understand how SSCF programmes are structured, how participation is incentivised, and how governance aligns with sustainability goals.

Data will be collected through interviews with several actors, including SCF providers to analyse governance strategies, buyers and suppliers to explore motivations and challenges, ESG information providers to understand their contributions to SSCF solutions. To ensure diverse findings, we will include variability in the size of providers and users and the industries adopting SSCF programs. This approach will allow us to explore how contextual factors influence the adoption and effectiveness of SSCF governance mechanisms and provide insights into the scalability of SSCF models.

Preliminary findings

We have begun systematising the existing literature on SSCF by applying Chen et al. (2022) framework on platform ecosystem governance mechanisms and conducting exploratory discussions with SCF providers. Preliminary findings reveal the adoption of additional governance mechanisms in SSCF programs, extending beyond access control and reward-based incentive mechanisms.

On the incentive side, conferring autonomy allows SCF providers to empower buyers to choose ESG information providers or involve suppliers in deciding how and by whom they are assessed, fostering collaboration and inclusivity within SCF ecosystems. On the control side, particularly regarding output control, traditional models (e.g., entry-barrier and rewarding models) evaluate suppliers' sustainability performance. However, preliminary findings suggest a new model where buyers' sustainability performance toward suppliers is assessed, with suppliers benefiting from lower interest rates as buyers improve their sustainability practices.

Expected contributions

The authors aim to contribute by systematizing the existing SSCF literature using Chen et al.'s (2022) framework on platform governance mechanisms, thereby bridging SSCF research with platform ecosystem studies. This approach enables the exploration of new governance mechanisms relevant to SSCF programs.

This research seeks to examine the outcomes of these models, such as supplier participation, and to explore how industry characteristics affect the adoption of specific SSCF models. For example, the centralized structure of the automotive industry may favor more restrictive governance mechanisms, while the decentralized and fragmented nature of the food industry may be better suited to more flexible governance mechanisms.

Additionally, the study also seeks to examine the temporal evolution of these governance models, investigating shifts from less inclusive to more inclusive frameworks and identifying the drivers behind these changes—whether supplier demands, buyer requirements, or platform-scaling strategies.

Lastly, we aim to contribute to the platform ecosystem literature, where research on governance mechanisms for those who utilize the platform ecosystem (i.e., users) remains scarce, with most existing studies focusing primarily on those who add value to the platform ecosystem (i.e., complementors).

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Paper topic

19. Supply chain finance, 16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social

Cost-Based Decision-Making Under the Microscope: A Deeper Understanding of Biases in Public Project Procurement Decisions

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

Major public procurement projects often experience systematic cost deviations. While research has traditionally focused on planning-specific causes, biases in cost-based decision-making remain underexplored. Addressing this gap, this study examines how decision-makers engage with project information through 18 interviews with 29 public procurement professionals. It confirms seven of ten previously observed biases and identifies two additional biases from adjacent research disciplines that inhibit the actual use of cost information in procurement decisions. By offering new explanatory insights, this study advances research on decision biases, provides a pathway for debiasing decision-making, and underscores the critical need for a cost culture approach in public procurement.

Paper topic

3. Purchasing organisation, 13. Public procurement, 14. Project procurement

Procurement of Innovation in Healthcare Institutions: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Healthcare systems worldwide are struggling to reconcile their objectives on accessibility, service quality and cost (Naylor, 1999). The acquisition of innovations could be instrumental to balance this triple trade-off. New medical technologies are potentially more expensive than those currently available on the market but could generate significant clinical benefits, such as reduced length of stay, reduced readmission rates and shorter patient recovery times (Royle et al., 2021). Emerging technologies have also the power to shift the focus from treatment to prevention and may contribute to tackle the problem of labor shortage, that has a deleterious impact on the accessibility and the service quality offered (Barbieri et al., 2023).

Healthcare innovation is often described as a convoluted set of new clinical services and medical technologies (Askfors and Fornstedt 2018). The acquisition of innovation by the healthcare sector is an interactive process where technology (knowledge) is not solely pushed by its developers; users play a role in "pulling," orienting, or guiding the supplier market towards innovations that meet their needs (Georghiou et al., 2014). As such, innovation involves a technological development that is attractive to the market (Tao et al., 2010). It represents a link between a necessity and a solution that leads to value creation (Legenvre and Gualandris, 2018).

Most countries are adopting strategies to contain the rising costs of the healthcare sector. Since procurement costs are an important source of expenditure in the healthcare sector (Montgomery and Schneller 2007), they are instrumental in constraining increasing costs. Traditionally, healthcare organizations have chosen to purchase high volumes of medical items to reduce purchasing costs (Belotti-Pedroso et al., 2024). However, procurement strategies focused on volume result in reducing returns over time (Lichtenberger et al., 2010) and may hinder innovation and technology developments (Meehan et al., 2017).

The challenges of procurement decisions in the extremely complex organizations that are hospitals should not be underestimated (Glouberman and Mintzberg, 2002). Purchasing managers in healthcare institutions must collaborate with professionals with expertise in defining medical items' specifications that become pivotal players in the purchasing process (Belotti Pedroso et al., 2024). The rising number

of complex technologies available and their adoption challenges increase the difficulties of purchasing decisions in this context (Miniati et al. 2014).

The challenge of the acquisition of innovation by healthcare institutions can be analyzed from different angles. The first angle focuses on the interactions of the actors involved in the procurement cycle. User receptivity to the innovations proposed by the supplier market is a second angle. Finally, public policies are also a relevant angle of analysis, as governments play a key role in healthcare systems worldwide (Papanicolas, 2018). Each of these angles needs to be considered to explore the challenges and best practices of the acquisition of innovation by healthcare institutions. The purpose of this bibliometric study is to draw an integrated review of research at the intersection of innovation, procurement and healthcare to guide researchers in the procurement field interested in this topic.

Methodology

A bibliometric study involves the quantitative analysis of a substantial body of literature within a specific field, with the aim of gaining insights into the domain and identifying emerging topics (Broadus, 1987). The analysis conducted in this article adheres to a rigorous structure and methodology, commonly employed in similar studies (Fahimnia et al., 2015; Kazemi et al., 2019). Two databases were identified as the most relevant for the purpose of this bibliometric study: Web of Science and PubMed, the latter being specialized in the healthcare sector. The search query was structured as follows: (“healthcare” OR “health” OR “hospital”) AND “innovation” AND (“purchasing” OR “procurement” OR “buyer” OR “sourcing” OR “supply management”). To retrieve relevant documents, the keywords were searched within the titles, abstracts, and keywords of articles. After thoroughly reviewing the titles and abstracts from both the PubMed and Web of Science databases, we retained a final selection of 218 articles, comprising 23 articles from PubMed and 195 articles from Web of Science. Before conducting the data analysis, the selected articles were merged into a single text file. The data analysis is carried out in two stages, as outlined in previous studies (Kazemi et al., 2019). The first stage involves a quantitative and descriptive analysis conducted using the Bibexcel software. This tool enables the extraction of key information such as authors, journals, keywords, citations, and co-citations from the dataset. By running frequency-based queries, the software facilitates the identification and statistical analysis of prominent authors, journals, and keywords. The second stage utilizes Gephi software to perform a more detailed analysis. Gephi is instrumental in identifying co-citation patterns and generating a visual representation of the network through the creation of clusters, offering a deeper understanding of the relationships within the dataset (Fahimnia et al., 2015).

Preliminary Results

The final database comprises 218 articles published between 1994 and 2024. An initial peak in publication activity is observed in 2007, followed by a more significant increase in 2012 and again in 2015. From 2016 onward, the number of articles published on this topic has grown exponentially, rising from 5 articles in 2016 to more than 25 in 2024. This trend suggests that the body of literature on this subject is likely to continue expanding.

The analysis of the dataset reveals interesting insights into the disciplinary focus and institutional contributions to the literature on healthcare innovation procurement. Starting with the research areas, the most represented domain is Health Care Sciences & Services, reflecting the strong emphasis on healthcare-related topics within the database. Other prominent areas include Business & Economics, and Public, Environmental & Occupational Health. These results indicate that the subject of healthcare

innovation procurement spans multiple disciplines, combining perspectives from healthcare services, public health, and economics.

The analysis of authorship, keywords and contributing journals patterns further confirms the fragmentation of the research, as no single author, keyword or contributing journal emerges as dominant. Overall, the citation analysis demonstrates that the most impactful articles in the database are those that combine local influence, global recognition, and network centrality (PageRank).

The co-citation analysis resulted in clusters addressing challenges and research opportunities, including sustainable supply chain practices, policy frameworks, technological advancements, and their implications for healthcare systems. Building on this analysis, this research provides critical insights for scholars and practitioners, offering strategies to address contemporary challenges while outlining future research directions for advancing research on the procurement of innovation in the healthcare sector.

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Paper topic

20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.), 10. Purchasing innovation, 13. Public procurement

110

Growth Dynamics in Supply Networks: Buyer Production Growth and Its Influence on Supplier Emission Efficiency

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

Management studies tend to associate production growth with business success. However, the emphasis on growth and its perceived limitless potential sharply contrasts the urgency of responding to the climate crisis. This study examines how buyer growth impacts supplier emission efficiency within aerospace supply networks. Using temporary network data, we explore how buyer power in the supply network and supplier environmental innovativeness shape this relationship. Rooted in resource dependence theory, our findings suggest that while buyer growth can enhance supplier emissions efficiency, structural autonomy and high supplier dependence on dominant buyers negatively influence this effect.

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 16. Sustainability - environmental, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

Crisis under Control: Supply Network Emergence and Control in the Automotive Sector

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This paper investigates how emergence and control manifest in the relationship between a buying firm and its second-tier suppliers and assesses how the balance between emergence and control evolves during and after a high-impact supply network disruption. Through a case study approach, we investigate an automotive Original Equipment Manufacturer's (OEM) relationship with three second-tier supplier and map the interactions with each supplier in the context of the semiconductor crisis of 2021-2023 and post-crisis. We adopt a Complex Adaptive Systems (CAS) perspective and analyze the changes in emergence and control through the variations in strength of ties. Our findings identify and delineate the concepts of emergence and control by showing how they in the supply network and how their balance evolves under the influence of a high-impact supply network disruption. The paper offers empirically-based insights that further our understanding of how emergence and control manifest in real-life supply networks.

Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience

Building resilient supply chains: The role of PSM organisations' learning capabilities – Insights from a qualitative investigation

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Introduction

The unpredictable turbulences of recent years demonstrated the vulnerability of companies and supply chain networks. Disruptive events like the COVID-19 pandemic or the war in Ukraine change the economic world sustainably. Unpredictability, random occurrence and their impact on the material flow characterize these supply chain disruptions (Craighead et al., 2007). Their occurrence normally does not originate from single production facility failure but rather from causes on the supply network level (Kim et al., 2015). Furthermore, interconnected structures caused by the increasing complexity and dynamic in today's supply chains depict another driver for the extension and rise of risks (Hosseini et al., 2019). The purchasing and supply management (PSM) organisation manage the design and strategy of the supply chain to source products and services for the companies (Patrucco and Kähkönen, 2021). As a result, PSM departments have emerged as strategic functions in coping with the recent crisis events due to their management responsibility for the upstream supply chain (Küffner et al., 2022). PSM departments engaged in risk and crisis mitigation strategies to cope with these supply chain disruptions. One lesson organisations learned, is the need for systemic change by promoting resilient strategies beyond the traditional risk management process (Pettit et al., 2019; Wieland and Durach, 2021).

Since the early 2000s resilience has been a designated research topic under investigation in the supply chain management domain (Pettit et al., 2019). Supply chain resilience represents a capability that consists of a set of capabilities to anticipate, adapt, respond, recover, and learn (Ali et al., 2017). Establishing these capabilities increases the competitive advantage in uncertain and non-static environments in the long run (Lee, 2004). The supply-side resilience perspective refers to the PSM measures of the resilience strategy in supply chains by ensuring the continued availability of resources before, during and after a disruptive event (Pereira et al., 2020). Therefore, proactive and reactive measures conducted by organisational functions, like the PSM organisation, develop and strengthen the set of capabilities needed for resilience in supply chains (Pereira et al., 2020). Reactive measures include all activities undertaken in response to the experienced disruption based on a situational analysis (Hohenstein et al., 2015; Hollnagel, 2017). On the contrary, proactive measures prepare the supply chain for future events (Hollnagel, 2017). The impact of these proactive measures leads to direct effects (e.g. an increase in inventory) and is based on the reflection of prior experience from past situations (Thun

and Hoenig, 2011; Wieland and Wallenburg, 2012). These experiences made during a crisis can foster new organisational routines in the sense of rules, procedures, conventions, strategies and technologies or lead to new supporting organisational functions such as beliefs, basic structures, paradigms, norms, cultures and knowledge (Levitt and March, 1988). Developing knowledge from lessons learned and the organisation's value of the learning ability grounds the management of future crisis events (Ivanov, 2024). Learning is a key ability for resilience in supply chains (Pereira et al., 2020) to cope with changing market conditions, operational fluctuations or technological advances (Seville et al., 2015). Learning from crises not only involves sharing the experience of successful strategies, as a result of retrospective observations, within the company and in the supply chain (Chen et al., 2022) but also learning about improving the process, such as regaining stability after a disruptive event (Dabhilkar et al., 2016). This process underlies boundary conditions (e.g. organisational innovativeness or agility) which influence the process's outcome positively or negatively (Eryarsoy et al., 2022). However, the process of how and under what constraints the PSM organisation learns from disruptions in the supply chain has been the subject of very little research. Therefore, this working paper aims to close the research gap by answering the following research question:

How do PSM organisations learn from supply chain disruptions to enhance their resilience strategies?

Methodology

To analyse the learning ability of PSM organisations from supply chain disruption, we aim to use a qualitative approach by conducting guideline-based expert interviews to uncover the process and potential boundary factors. Thus, we focus on identifying connections between disruption types and the learning process, learning sources, formalized learning steps, triggers for adaption based on the experience, learning goals and concrete barriers or enablers for the process. The qualitative data sampling follows the principles of the Grounded Theory (GT) approach. The GT allows iterative data collection (Glaser and Strauss, 2017) by following an abductive approach switching between induction and deduction by constantly comparing the acquired data (Morse et al., 2021). The GT approach's qualification for analysing the learning capability of PSM organisations in highly complex networks lies in its potential to interpret the individual's interactions in an organisation and on the supply chain network level (Randall and Mello, 2012).

Conclusion

Based on the qualitative data sampling by interviewing PSM professionals and the currently finalized interview guidelines, this research contributes to the proactive management of resilience in supply chains. In addition, this research aims to describe the current state of the acquiring, interpreting and transforming experience of disruptions into resilience strategies and, additionally, to identify potential barriers and enablers for deriving supportive actions. This study highlights the PSM department's key position for resilient supply chains and it extends the theoretical understanding of the learning ability of PSM departments to contribute to resilience in supply chains. Furthermore, uncovering the special learning situation, its barriers and enablers during a disruption support PSM managers initiate supporting actions to improve the learning process.

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Paper topic

3. Purchasing organisation, 18. Risk and resilience, 1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences

113

Green or Lean? How Sustainability Criteria Influence Competition and ESG-driven Supplier Participation in Public Procurement

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This paper examines how integrating sustainability award criteria into public procurement affects supplier participation. Analyzing over 860,000 EU procurement tenders and linking them with Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) performance data, it investigates whether emphasizing sustainability considerations influences the number of bids received. The study reveals that adding stringent sustainability award criteria reduces supplier participation, potentially limiting competition. However, firms with higher ESG scores or environmental supply chain policies target these sustainability-focused tenders, leveraging their capabilities to gain a competitive advantage. The research highlights the need for balanced procurement strategies that promote sustainability while maintaining open and fair competition.

Paper topic

13. Public procurement, 16. Sustainability - environmental

Unlocking Silver Expertise: Redefining Workforce Training Development in Purchasing for Industry 4.0

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This study addresses the challenges of an ageing workforce in purchasing and supply management (PSM), driven by demographic shifts like rising retirement ages and declining birth rates. It focuses on “Silver Workers” (employees aged 50+), highlighting their value and the need for tailored training to meet the demands of Industry 4.0 using survey data from PSM professionals. The research contributes by deepening the understanding of the ‘Silver Workers’ concept, evaluating training methods tailored to their needs, and assessing the effectiveness of professional training programs. These insights support workforce adaptability, inclusivity, and innovation, ensuring organisations can fully leverage the expertise of a multigenerational workforce while addressing skill shortages and technological challenges.

Paper topic

1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 15. PSM theory, methodology, education

The three musketeers of coevolutionary circular design

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

The transition from a linear to a circular economy necessitates systemic changes in product design, data sharing, and material flows. This study applies a coevolutionary framework to examine how these three dimensions interact dynamically in circular economy transitions. Drawing on case studies from three industries, we analyse the mutual adaptation of product design activities, data-sharing initiatives, and material flows. By advancing the coevolutionary framework, this study provides theoretical insights into the interdependencies shaping the emergence of a circular economy. It also offers practical guidance for companies seeking to embed circularity in design and procurement strategies. Our findings inform policymakers about the importance of harmonized standards and incentives to facilitate industry-wide circular transformations.

Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 21. Special track: Regulations in shaping sustainable ecosystem change

Responding to Supply Chain Disruptions: Buffering or Bridging?

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Extended abstract:

Introduction

Supply chains have become more complex and more susceptible to risks and disruptions in recent years (Ellis et al., 2010; Harland et al., 2003). Supply chain risk management and supply chain resilience are often discussed in this context as the capability of a supply chain to prepare for and/or respond to disruptions (Adobor and McMullen, 2018; Tukamuhabwa et al., 2015). Two types of strategies organisations can employ to react to supply chain disruptions are buffering and bridging (Bode et al., 2011) identify two types of strategies that a company can employ to react to a supply chain disruption: buffering and bridging strategies. Buffering strategies are external to the relationship with a current supplier and aim to shield the company from the impact of disruptions originating in the exchange relationship with a supplier (Bode et al., 2011). Bridging strategies are initiatives in collaborating with a current supplier to increase the buyer's control over the needed resources, thereby mitigating supply chain risks.

Previous research has shown that buffering and bridging practices enhance supply chain risk management, improving the company's performance (Manhart et al., 2020). However, little research has been done on how relational attributes such as dependence and trust impact a firm's choice for bridging and buffering strategies. To address these issues, this study seeks to answer the following question: *How do trust and dependence within the supply chain relationship influence the buyer's decision to implement buffering and/or bridging strategies?*

In order to do so, we conducted a policy-capturing experiment in which expert decision makers (i.e., purchasing managers) decide on buffering and bridging strategies for different suppliers. The data collection is ongoing and will be presented at IPSERA 2025.

Literature background and hypotheses

Impact of dependence

Dependence indicates how much a company needs a specific supply chain partner based on the uniqueness of this partner and the related difficulty of finding a possible substitute (Mishra et al., 2016; Tellefsen and Thomas, 2005). In general, we expect dependence to create a necessity to engage in both buffering and bridging strategies. Buffering strategies are needed to reduce dependence by diversifying supply sources or building redundancy. Bridging strategies are critical for securing access to key suppliers by strengthening the relationship. Ergo,

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive relationship between buyer dependence and the implementation of buffering strategies.

Hypothesis 2: There is a positive relationship between buyer dependence and the implementation of bridging strategies.

Impact of trust

Trust in a supplier implies that the buyer has confidence that the supplier fulfills its promises and that the supplier engages in the relationship with genuine and positive intentions (Doney and Cannon, 1997; Ganesan, 1994). When the buyer trusts a supplier it reduces the necessity to buffer, as the buyer is confident that the supplier continues its supplies during a disruption. In situations of high trust, the buyer is more likely to invest in the relationship through bridging strategies, trusting that the supplier will be reciprocal in the collaboration efforts to reduce the effects of possible disruptions.

- *Hypothesis 3: There is a negative relationship between a buyer's trust and the implementation of buffering strategies.*
- *Hypothesis 4: There is a positive relationship between a buyer's trust and the implementation of bridging strategies.*

Impact of supplier dependence

When the supplier is dependent on the buyer's account, this generally increases the commitment of the supplier to that buyer. Buyers can be aware of such dynamics and will try to leverage these power advantages. Therefore, if a supplier is dependent on the buyer, this reduces the buyer's need to take action since the supplier is unlikely to focus its attention on other buyers. Reversely, if the supplier is independent from the buyer, the buyer needs to pro-actively take action because it is less likely that the supplier will help to diminish the disruption impact for the buyer. Thus, supplier dependence reduces the need for the buyer to engage in buffering and bridging strategies.

- *Hypothesis 5: Supplier dependence weakens the effect of buyer dependence on the implementation of buffering and bridging strategies.*
- *Hypothesis 6: Supplier dependence weakens the effect of a buyer's trust on buffering and bridging strategies.*

Methodology

Conducting a policy-capturing experiment

A policy-capturing experiment was conducted using purchasing managers at a high-tech company in the Netherlands. A policy-capturing experiment is a type of vignette study that integrates experimental and survey techniques by presenting participants with hypothetical yet realistic cases, and asking participants to make decisions in reaction to these cases (Aguinis and Bradley, 2014; Priem et al., 2011). The cases are manipulated to gain information about the variables included in the hypotheses (Qian et al., 2021). This study's two dependent variables are buffering and bridging. Buffering and bridging are operationalized based on the constructs' definitions.

The purchasing managers were presented with hypothetical suppliers, which varied on attributes that reflect our independent variables (buyer dependence, supplier dependence, and trust). Then, we asked them to decide on bridging and buffering strategies as they would in real-life in their role as purchaser. By systematically presenting the purchasing managers with combinations of our independent variables, we are able to identify the relationship between these variables and our dependent variables. Buyer dependence and buyer's trust have three levels (low, medium, high) to account for potential u-shaped effects (Bode et al., 2011), supplier dependence has two levels (low,high), even as our control variable relationship length.. This resulted in a $3^2 \times 2^2$ factorial design of 36 experimental conditions. Because this number is too high to test with each individual respondent, we use an incomplete block design to split the total amount of experimental conditions into three blocks of 12 decisions (Graham and Cable, 2001; Mellewigt et al., 2017). Multiple interactions with the high-tech company -among others for creating the case descriptions- ensured realism and face validity of the experiment.

Data analyses

The data collection is ongoing and preliminary results will be presented at IPSERA.

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Paper topic

2. PSM strategy, 18. Risk and resilience, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

117

Software Supply Chain Management: State of Play by Executing a Review of Reviews

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Summary: Software Supply Chains increasingly shape modern products like cars, integrating functionalities from global players, specialized software suppliers, and open-source developers. This study synthesizes knowledge from multiple research fields, applying a supply chain perspective to this phenomenon. A review of literature reviews consolidates fragmented research, analysing 20 articles. This study identifies current knowledge, highlights research gaps, and proposes future directions. A key finding is the recurrent need to address coordination challenges, yet established supply chain management theories and concepts remain absent, emphasizing the need for a structured approach to Software Supply Chain Management and its integration into mainstream research.

Keywords: digital, review of reviews, supply chain management, software

Paper topic

11. Digital, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 10. Purchasing innovation

The evolution of purchasing urban logistics services in the context of Low Emission Zones (LEZ): First results of an exploratory research

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The evolution of purchasing urban logistics services in the context of Low Emission Zones (LEZ): Strategic adaptation and necessary innovation

LEZs have become an essential lever in the fight against urban pollution, contributing to a significant reduction in greenhouse gas emissions and atmospheric pollutants (Coulombel et al., 2018). More than 300 LEZs have been deployed in Europe. In France, 11 LEZs have been set, each with specific regulations in terms of implementation timetable and access conditions (Paché et al., 2020). This regulatory diversity requires lead services providers (LSPs) to be highly flexible and adaptable to meet local requirements. Historically, the outsourcing of logistics activities has been part of a rationale to reduce costs and improve operational performance (Fabbe-Costes et al., 2008; Fulconis et al., 2011). However, with the integration of environmental concerns into supply chain management (SCM), purchasing criteria for logistics services must now include dimensions of sustainability and regulatory compliance. This evolution calls for a rethinking of purchasing strategies, focusing on the selection of LSPs able to meet not only traditional costs and reliability requirements, but also the strict environmental criteria imposed by LEZs (Anderson et al., 2011; Jazairy et al., 2020).

The central research question is: “How should the purchasing of urban logistics services evolve to keep pace with the constraints due to the implementation of LEZs?” More specifically, our research aims to identify the new purchasing requirements imposed by LEZ, analyze the impacts of these requirements on the selection and management of LSPs, explore the adaptation and innovation strategies needed to respond effectively to environmental and regulatory constraints, and finally propose recommendations for purchasing firms in developing sustainable partnership relationships with LSPs.

In the first part, the urban logistics panorama will be presented. The research appears quite fragmented (Allègre, 2016; Lagorio et al., 2016; Akeb et al., 2018). Based on the theory of stakeholders (Freeman, 1984) and the resource-based view theory (Wernerfelt, 1984; Hamel & Prahalad, 1990; Barney, 1991) we will demonstrate the specific character of the logistics service provider in this urban environment and the need for a stakeholder approach to ensure that these new constraints related to LEZs are considered. Urban logistics is particularly complex to buy due to the specific challenge of, on the one hand, reducing all the negative impacts and, on the other hand, offering better and faster deliveries. In

this part, a focus on a literature review on the purchase of logistics services will also be proposed. The degree of complexity of logistics services allows distinguishing two main categories: “basic logistics services” versus “advanced logistics services” (Anderson and Norrman, 2002; Selviaridis and Norrman, 2015; Large, 2017; Merminod et al., 2019). In the urban logistics context, the role given to the “urban logistics service provider” (ULSP) should be well understood in order to collaborate well with stakeholders.

In a second part, a qualitative exploratory approach will be presented, based on semi-directive interviews with eight experts from complementary fields: service provider, distributor, shippers, local authority, association, ..., all involved in sustainable urban logistics initiatives. These interviews, which lasted between an hour and an hour and a half, enabled us to gather rich and detailed data on the experts' perceptions of the specificities of urban logistics, the impact of LEZs on purchasing practices, and their expectations of LSPs. Data analysis is carried out using the thematic coding method recommended by Strauss and Corbin (1990), enabling us to identify the main emerging themes linked to changes in the purchasing of urban logistics services.

The results of this research highlight several key dimensions in the evolution of purchasing urban logistics services in the context of LEZs:

New complexity of purchasing requirements: LEZs impose strict regulations on the types of vehicles allowed, delivery schedules, and logistics flow management methods (Paché, 2020). LSPs must now invest in fleets of electric or hybrid vehicles, adopt more flexible delivery practices, and integrate technologies for tracking CO₂ emissions. This increased complexity calls for more elaborate purchasing criteria, taking into account not only LSPs' operational capacity but also their environmental commitment and capacity to innovate (Selviaridis and Spring, 2010).

Diversity and structuring of the LSP market: the urban LSP market is gradually taking shape in response to the requirements of the LEZs. Service providers are diversifying according to their ability to meet new regulatory and environmental constraints. We are seeing the emergence of LSPs specializing in green delivery solutions, such as companies using electric cargo bikes or hydrogen-powered vehicles (Anderson et al., 2011). This specialization promotes a better match between buyers' needs and LSP offerings, enabling more effective management of the constraints imposed by EPZs.

Increasing importance of sustainability criteria: sustainability criteria are becoming a priority in the purchasing process for urban logistics services. Companies are looking to partner with LSPs that demonstrate a strong commitment to reducing CO₂ emissions and adopting clean technologies (Jazairy and von Haartman, 2020). This focus on sustainability is also reinforced by government initiatives and corporate social responsibility (CSR) programs, which value environmentally-friendly logistics practices (Hartmann and de Grahl, 2011).

Collaboration and relational governance: the complexity of LEZ requirements and the diversity of players involved in urban logistics require effective relational governance between buyers and LSPs. Trusting relationships, information sharing and close collaboration are essential to ensure regulatory compliance and efficient logistics operations (Selviaridis and Norrman, 2015). Buying firms need to develop strategic partnerships with their providers, fostering a win-win approach and continuous innovation in logistics practices (Manuj et al., 2014).

Impact of economic contexts and uncertainties: economic uncertainties, such as those generated by the Covid-19 crisis, inflation, or geopolitical tensions, complicate LSPs' planning and investments in sustainable urban logistics solutions (Merminod et al., 2018). This economic instability creates a climate of uncertainty that influences companies' purchasing decisions and investment strategies towards LSPs. It therefore becomes crucial for buyers to develop flexibility in their purchasing approaches and favor relationships with LSPs able to adapt quickly to market changes.

For companies wishing to optimize the purchase of urban logistics services in an LEZ context, several practical recommendations emerge from this research: Integrate sustainability criteria into purchasing processes: ensure that LSP selection criteria include environmental performance indicators, such as CO₂ emissions, use of clean vehicles, and adoption of sustainable logistics practices (Jazairy, 2020). Develop strategic partnerships with LSPs: foster long-term collaborative relationships based on trust, information sharing, and a shared commitment to sustainability and logistics innovation (Hartmann and de Grahl, 2011).

Encourage continuous innovation: Collaborate with LSPs to develop and implement innovative logistics solutions, such as night-time deliveries, smart relay points, and emissions tracking technologies (Blanquart, 2018). Accompany investment in green technologies: provide financial and logistical support to LSPs to facilitate fleet renewal and the adoption of clean technologies, ensuring compliance with LEZ requirements (Merminod et al., 2018). Manage regulatory complexity: set up regulatory watch mechanisms to monitor changes in LEZs and adapt purchasing criteria accordingly, ensuring ongoing compliance of logistics services (Paché, 2021).

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Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.), 2. PSM strategy

120

Enabling Procurement of Innovation: Municipal Capacity Building from Policy to Practice

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This paper explores how municipalities build policy capacity to operationalise public procurement of innovation (PPI), using Wu et al.'s (2015) policy capacity framework. Based on interviews with eight senior practitioners across eight EU countries, the first findings suggest that internal capacities and organisational culture are key drivers of successful PPI operationalisation, rather than external support. Practitioners tend to view PPI instruments as means to achieve organisational goals, rather than an end in itself. Therefore, the first findings suggest that policymakers should reconsider how PPI policies and instruments are designed and communicated to better align with practitioners' point of view.

Paper topic

10. Purchasing innovation, 13. Public procurement

Who holds the keys to sustainability visibility in ASCs? Including small holder farmers in digital transitions

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Introduction

Agricultural supply chains (ASCs) have been a focus of blockchain based traceability efforts, driven by both regulations and consumer demands for sustainability transparency (Hastig and Sodhi, 2020). However, widespread adoption has been slow due to focal firms lacking the capabilities (Hastig and Sodhi, 2020) and governance issues (Goldsby and Hanisch, 2022). As purchasing organizations are faced with increased due diligence requirements, blockchain based digitalization will become an even more important tool (Heldt and Pikuleva, 2024).

Much of the produce imported to the EU comes from regions very sensitive to climate change, like Kenya, where farmers have been trying to adapt to changing growing conditions and inconsistent rainfalls particularly over the past two decades (Hennings, 2021). Safe labor conditions and fair wages are also a persistent issue in production (SOFA Team and Doss, 2011). The task of visibility through digitalization becomes more daunting in ASCs where producers in rural areas have low access to markets and separated by layers of intermediaries (Okello et al., 2012).

However, the nascency of these systems also provides an opportunity to design a more inclusive system from the start. Hastig and Sodhi (2020) identify small suppliers as key to achieving transparency. This study specifically looks at a food product that has a shorter chain between purchasing organizations and the small holder farmers that produce it, pigeon peas (Shiferaw et al., 2007). Kenya has a well-established export market to Europe and pigeon peas are Kenya's third most important legume, cultivated exclusively by small holders (Nzuma, 2020).

This study explores two questions regarding how inclusive digital systems could be designed. First, establishing the flow of information starting with producers and ending with purchasing organizations. Who is communicating what with whom? This entails investigating where the sustainability information is coming from (if any at all) and information complexities at the different tiers within the ASC.

The second regards how a pilot use case can be used to facilitate secure information transfer between the producers and purchasing organization, thereby increasing supply chain visibility. How can producers be included in the information exchange? Specifically looking at technical solutions that producers could use.

Pigeon pea market overview

Pigeon peas are a staple in Kenyan agricultural production, both for local consumption and increasing as a reliable export (Nzuma, 2020). It has been a target of development due to its resilience to changing climate, it can be grown without many resources in most regions of Kenya, which is arid and semi-arid (Snapp et al., 2003), and it supports sustainable agricultural practices (ICRISAT, nd). Pigeon peas are a particular legume of interest because of its increased planting can be grown alongside other crops which is suitable for additional income in family gardens (Shiferaw et al., 2007). Pigeon peas are completely small holder farmed, with 34% of production exported (Nzuma, 2020). Each product variation (e.g., fresh or dried) has different value chains as well depending on the pigeon pea variety, harvest time, processing needs and the consumer market (Shiferaw et al., 2007).

Aside from the opportunities that pigeon pea provides for small holder farmers, it is also a good test product for exploring the potential use of digitalizing sustainability information because there are fewer links in the chain. Pigeon pea producers have contracts directly with exporters, yielding a larger percentage of the value created than other marketing channels (Shiferaw et al., 2007). Though it is mostly grown for local consumption, it is still one of Kenya's top exported crops (Nzuma, 2020) with a high growth potential in the European market (CBI, 2023).

Information flows and sustainability visibility

While acceptance of electronic certificates required for agricultural trade increased during the pandemic, digitalizing basic documentation is still not widely adopted (Laget and Deuss, 2023). Building digital platforms for transferring basic documents between exporting firms and importing customs is a work in progress, to put it mildly. Another issue is that digital systems proposed for transparency in ASCs are primarily developed and studied from the focal firm perspective (Heldt and Pikuleva, 2024). If inclusive and transparent ASCs are to be designed, small holders are the key (Hastig and Sodhi, 2020; Heldt and Pikuleva, 2024).

The pigeon pea market is uniquely suited for a direct approach to governance because purchasing organizations do have direct access to producers (Shiferaw et al., 2007; Tachizawa and Wong, 2014). Though the supply chain still has some complexities, pigeon pea producers have a greater potential to be seen by purchasing firms due to fewer intermediaries (Nzuma, 2020).

Research goals and proposed method

Though blockchain is well studied for its potential in making ASCs transparent, its applications in regard to reporting due diligence are still being explored (Heldt and Pikuleva, 2024). The primary goal is to understand how purchasing organizations can attain visibility of sustainability related information from producers. This study is being conducted as part of a larger project where a blockchain based digital platform is being piloted for transmitting standard customs documentation for fruits and vegetables from Africa.

This study first identifies the key stakeholders who are the intended users of this digital solution. Then, what requirements should be added to the system to increase visibility of production, such as, but not limited to, documentation related to sustainability certification. Finally, exploring ways to expand usership beyond the exporter and purchaser i.e., being able to exchange information directly with producers.

Alongside reviewing existing reports from governmental agencies and NGOs regarding the pigeon pea supply chain, interviews will be conducted with digital solutions developers. This will provide the scope of what is technically possible regarding the inclusion of small holder farmers. Additional design functions will also be discussed regarding how to incorporate sustainability information within the existing framework.

Contributions summary

Though this study focuses on one particular crop in one country, it is used to illustrate how the ASC of small holder grown crops can be made more visible to purchasing organizations through digitalization. Though the pigeon pea export value chain is less complex than other products, it serves as a base case to see if the same digital solutions can be expanded to more complicated value chains. If a framework for exchanging sustainability information with small holder farmers can be created, it can be used as a template for replication and adaptation for other ASCs with a large proportion of small holder farmers.

Future research could also include how to expand this framework to other countries with similar profiles to Kenya. More research is also needed to understand how much purchaser resources and knowledge investment it would take to reach key stakeholders via established and trusted groups (e.g., NGOs and trade organizations).

Keywords: agriculture supply chains, sustainability, visibility, digitalization

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Paper topic

11. Digital, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.), 17. Sustainability - social

Integrating insect-based foods into sustainable supply chains: Overcoming consumer barriers.

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Global disruptions, such as the COVID-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine, have profoundly disrupted global food systems, exposing vulnerabilities in food production, distribution, and supply chain resilience (Alabi & Ngwenyama, 2023; Hobbs, 2020). These disruptions have not only challenged how food is delivered but have also reshaped consumer attitudes and behaviors. Supply chain disruptions have influenced purchasing habits, while rising concerns about food safety, price increases, and environmental impacts have encouraged consumers to reconsider their food choices (Sharma et al., 2022). Sustainability is becoming more important in consumer behavior, impacting decisions across various aspects of daily life (Chen, 2024). As problems like climate change, resource shortages, and the environmental impact of traditional food production grow, many consumers are turning to more sustainable habits (Gil et al., 2024). This is especially clear in the food sector, where the meat industry—known for its high greenhouse gas emissions, deforestation, and water use—faces increasing criticism (Poore et al., 2008). Consumers are looking for healthier and more sustainable options and are becoming more thoughtful about what they eat. This marks a shift toward more pro-environmental consumption behavior (Ahn & Shamim, 2022).

When considering global health and sustainable food intake, Onwezen et al. (2021) state that one of the solutions lies in replacing daily meat consumption pattern by alternatives, such as insect-based foods. In fact, insect-based foods are one of the most promising alternatives (da Cunha et al., 2022). Insects have a low environmental footprint, are rich in protein, and require significantly less land, water, and feed compared to conventional livestock (van Huis, 2020). This makes them a viable option for reducing environmental pressure while addressing global food security challenges (van Huis et al., 2023). However, in Western countries, this solution faces reluctance and prejudice, preventing it from becoming a part of consumers' diets (Moruzzo et al., 2021). The idea of eating insects often evokes disgust, rooted in unfamiliarity and negative cultural associations. Overcoming these barriers requires a deeper understanding of the factors that influence consumer behavior.

Addressing these challenges, this study contributes to the global conversation on sustainable food consumption (UN SDGs, 2022). Promoting the acceptance and adoption of alternative food sources like insect-based foods can enhance food diversity and support a sustainable transition in supply chains, production, and consumption patterns. This shift not only advances sustainability but also contributes to

other Sustainable Development Goals, such as zero hunger, ending poverty, and good health and well-being (da Cunha et al., 2022). Setting the focus on consumer perspectives is highly relevant in order to transform food supply chains to more sustainable alternatives, e.g. through adapted Demand management approaches (Taylor & Fearn, 2009).

In this study, we focus on the barriers to adopting insect-based foods, which involve both emotional and cognitive challenges. A key factor influencing these barriers is disgust. Rozin et al. (2008) explain how feelings of disgust strongly influence food choices, particularly for unfamiliar options like insects. Even a small degree of disgust can significantly lower purchase intentions, creating a major obstacle for broader acceptance. This emotional reaction often outweighs the sustainability and health benefits of insect-based foods, making it harder for people to accept them.

However, awareness and familiarity can play a transformative role in overcoming these hurdles. The Mere Exposure Effect (Zajonc, 1968) suggests that repeated exposure to something unfamiliar can reduce discomfort and build positive associations. For instance, seeing insect-based foods in advertisements or on menus can normalize the idea over time, making it feel less strange and more acceptable (Koch et al., 2021). Similarly, Cognitive Dissonance Theory (Festinger, 1957) states that when consumers are repeatedly exposed to messages about for instance the environmental and nutritional benefits of insect-based foods, they may adjust their attitudes to reduce inner conflict, leading to greater acceptance.

Attitudes, in this case toward insect-based foods, play a central role in shaping purchase intentions. Ajzen & Fishbein (1980) highlight that positive attitudes are strong predictors of behavioral intentions. Social Cognition Theory (Bandura, 1986) emphasizes that awareness can reduce uncertainty and create favorable perceptions of unfamiliar products.

Social dynamics also play an important role in consumer behavior, particularly for unconventional products like insect-based foods. People often make purchasing decisions based on how they want to be perceived by others (Shukla, 2008). For some consumers, trying unconventional food like insect-based foods provides an opportunity to signal boldness, innovation, and environmental consciousness. These individuals might be more willing to overcome their initial disgust if it helps them stand out (Corneo & Jeanne, 1997) and show their commitment to sustainability (Hammad et al., 2019).

This study explores emotions, thoughts, and social factors to understand what affects people's acceptance of insect-based foods and how to encourage them to give these options a try.

Research Method

To explore these dynamics, a large-scale survey of 1.000 Dutch participants was conducted. Respondents, aged 18 to 88, were recruited through a market research bureau and represented all 12 provinces of the Netherlands. Validated scales measured key constructs, including disgust toward insect-based foods (La Barbera et al., 2020), attitude toward insect-based foods (Wang et al., 2019), purchase intention (Yazdanpanah & Forouzani, 2015), and social status (Eastman et al., 1999). Awareness of the existence of insect-based foods was assessed using a single-item question with responses indicating levels of familiarity. All items were rated on a 5-point Likert scale.

Results

Awareness emerged as a critical factor in promoting the acceptance of insect-based foods. Specifically, awareness indirectly influenced purchase intention through two key pathways: attitude and disgust. Participants who were more aware of the existence of insect-based foods tended to have a more positive attitude towards these products ($b = 0.26, p < .001$) which in turn enhanced their purchase intention ($b = 0.54, p < .001$). Additionally, respondents with a greater awareness of the existence of insect-based foods reported lower levels of disgust ($b = -0.44, p < .001$), and lower levels of disgust were associated with higher purchase intention ($b = -0.17, p < .001$). No direct effect of awareness on purchase intention was found.

The results also indicated that social status moderates the relationship between disgust and purchase intention (CI[-0.04, -0.002], $p < .05$). For individuals who highly value social status, the negative impact of disgust is weaker. These consumers are more likely to perceive insect-based foods as an opportunity to stand out or demonstrate their commitment to sustainability, even if they initially feel hesitant.

These findings show that consumer value preferences towards insect-based foods can bring important changes to our food systems and supply chains, addressing global challenges regarding food security and environmental sustainability. Highlighting the environmental and health benefits of insect-based foods can build positive attitudes and reduce resistance of both producers and consumers. Featuring these foods more often in the media or including them in familiar recipes can make the idea of eating insect-based foods more appealing. Additionally, marketing them as innovative and status-enhancing can attract individuals who value high social status. They may act as early adopters and influencers, paving the way for wider acceptance.

Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental

Bridging the competence gap for innovative and sustainable public procurement: The role of competence development

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Bridging the competence gap for innovative and sustainable public procurement: The role of competence development

Summary

As public procurement evolves to address complex societal challenges, the need for enhanced competences becomes critical to fostering innovative and sustainable outcomes. This study investigates the interplay between competence development mechanisms, individual competences, and their impact on innovation, sustainability and operational performance in public procurement. Drawing on survey data collected from 173 public procurement professionals in Finland and the Netherlands, the study provides empirical evidence of these relationships. The findings offer insights highlighting the importance of targeted programs to bridge the competence gap of innovative and sustainable procurement and to clarify the paths for competence improvement.

Keywords: Competence; Competence development; public procurement; innovation; sustainability; survey

Introduction

Public procurement has evolved into a strategic tool for governments to address pressing societal challenges (Grandia & Meehan, 2017). As these challenges grow increasingly complex, innovative approaches and solutions in public procurement become essential (Lenderink et al., 2022). The demand for innovation and sustainability in public procurement transcends traditional practices and requires the development of new competences to effectively address innovation challenges (Beske-Janssen et al., 2023). However, many public procurement employees often lack the necessary skills for strategic procurement (Uyarra et al., 2014), exposing a significant competence gap that limits their ability to harness procurement as a lever for societal change. These challenges highlight an urgent need for research and actionable strategies to build competences in public procurement.

This study investigates the role of individual competences, competence development and improving procurement outcomes in public organizations. Specifically, it seeks to address two key questions:

1. How do individual competence levels contribute to innovation, sustainability and cost performance in public procurement?
2. How do competence development mechanisms affect the competence levels of procurement professionals?

The study is based on a survey data collected from 173 Finnish and Dutch public buyer professionals. The analyses are conducted with PLS-SEM.

Literature background:

The shift of procurement from a cost-saving function to a strategic role has heightened the need for diverse competences among procurement professionals (Stek & Schiele, 2021). Inspired by the categorization proposed by (Spring & Araujo, 2014) and Holma et al., (2022), this study categorizes competences based on their role in enabling procurement performance:

- **Procedural competences:** Competences to perform key activities in procurement procedures, focus on process efficiency and compliance, such as procedural interaction competences, sustainability knowledge, and data analytics competences.
- **Relational competences:** Competences to collaborate and get activities done by suppliers and other stakeholders. Examples include networking, communication, and stakeholder management competences.
- **Enabling competences:** Competences to enable procedural and relational competences for performing activities. Examples include change management, creativity, leadership, and a results-oriented approach.

This categorization highlights how specific competences align with procurement activities to achieve innovation, sustainability and operational goals. Traditionally, the primary focus of public procurement has been on efficiency and cost-effectiveness. However, contemporary procurement practices aim to foster beyond cost and aims for innovation and sustainability (Malacina et al., 2022). This study also considers three types of performance outcomes: innovation in products and processes; operational performance, including cost efficiency, quality, and compliance; and procurement performance aligned with sustainability objectives.

Finally, we also investigate competence development within organizations. Compared to competence requirements, the perspective of developing competences has been much less present in the studies on public procurement competencies (Derwik & Hellström, 2017). Drawing on research emphasizing the role of networks in competence development (Momeni et al., 2023), we recognize that organizations either aim to internalize and own competences or collaborate with other actors to leverage external competences without ownership. Competence development in this survey can thus be categorized into two categories:

- Direct competence development: In these practices, organizations aim to internalize and own competences. These activities include trainings, mentoring programs and other internal competence development.
- Indirect competence development: In these practices, public organizations aim not to fully own but to leverage newly developed competence by collaborating with suppliers, public bodies, or intermediaries.

The proposed research model highlights the relationships among competence development, competences, and performance constructs. In the model, competence development influences the development of competences, which in turn affect performance outcomes. Additionally, enabling competences are shown to impact the other two competence categories, reflecting how this construct is defined as foundational to the overall framework.

Methodology

This study collected data through a survey of public procurement professionals in the Netherlands and Finland between March and October 2024. Out of 1,398 distributed surveys, 173 usable responses were received, reflecting a 12% response rate. The survey captured data on professionals' competencies, competence development methods, and perceptions of their organisations' operational, innovation, and sustainability performance, forming the basis for the analysis.

Constructs were measured using a multi-item questionnaire based on established scales, with responses captured on a five-point Likert scale (1 = "Strongly Disagree," 5 = "Strongly Agree"). This format, commonly used in PLS-SEM studies (Hair et al., 2011), balances granularity and simplicity, reducing cognitive load while maintaining reliability (Dawes, 2008) and minimise central tendency bias, enhancing result comparability (Hartley, 2014).

Data analysis utilised Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), suitable for predictive analysis and complex models with latent variables. Reliability and validity assessments followed established standards as indicator and internal consistency reliability, convergent and discriminant validity as proposed in guidelines by Hair et al., (2011) and later updated by Sarstedt et al., (2023).

Preliminary findings

The preliminary findings suggest that different competence development mechanisms have unique impacts. Indirect Competence Development seems to support Enabling Competencies, while Direct Competence Development focuses more on Procedural and Relational Competencies. Direct Competence Development also shows positive effects on Innovation, Sustainability, and Operational Performance. Indirect Competence Development adds to these performance areas too, but to a lesser extent.

After finalizing the analysis in the next steps of this working paper, we aim to identify novel contributions to the understanding and development of competences that enable innovative and sustainable public procurement practices.

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Paper topic

1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 13. Public procurement, 10. Purchasing innovation

Harnessing Artificial Intelligence for supply chain risk management: an Information Processing Perspective on providers and adopters

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This paper contributes to theory and practice by studying an under-investigated phenomenon that is relevant for companies, the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Supply Chain Risk Management (SCRM). This study found that SCRM is influenced by a high level of uncertainty and therefore is characterized by high information processing needs. Then, it identified the information processing capabilities needed for the SCRM process to answer those needs and explained how these capabilities can be enhanced by AI. In particular, the study reveals that AI can help to reach the fit between SCRM information processing needs and capabilities, improving the SCRM performance of companies and boosting overall SCRM outcomes.

Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience

Implementation of Performance Based Contracting: An explorative survey on the importance of fit

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Summary

This study empirically examines the critical role of strategy-structure fit in achieving success in implementing performance-based contracting (PBC). While PBC is a well-established concept within the field of purchasing and supply management (PSM), the notion of implementation success—particularly the organizational factors influencing it—requires further exploration. Drawing on the theory of fit, this research introduces a novel perspective to the study of PBC implementation. An exploratory survey investigating PBC practices in the German public sector highlights the significance of strategy-structure fit for successful PBC implementation. Furthermore, the findings demonstrate a positive correlation between effective PBC implementation and improved organizational procurement outcomes. The relationships tested within a structural equation model are statistically significant, underscoring the pivotal role of the fit construct in PBC success. Future research should explore the specific factors contributing to strategy-structure fit and employ methodologies involving larger and more diverse participant samples to validate and extend these findings.

Keywords or phrases: Performance-based Contracting, Structural Equation, Success factors, Fit

Submission category: Working paper (WP)

Introduction

Manufacturers of industrial equipment, such as plant and machinery builders, are increasingly offering integrated services such as maintenance, repair, and even operational management of their systems to

achieve competitive differentiation (Hypko et al. 2010; Töytäri et al. 2015). In academic literature, this transformation in the offering portfolios of traditional product manufacturers is commonly referred to as *servitization* (Vandermerwe und Rada 1988). Traditionally, so-called "Time, Cost, Material" contracts were used for providing these services, such as maintenance, repair, or spare parts supply (Guajardo et al. 2012). Since suppliers in these contracts are compensated based on the resources used (e.g., material costs, labour hours), and their profit is derived from the total effort, there is an incentive for them to deploy resources beyond what is necessary (Guajardo et al. 2012). In response to these inefficiencies, companies are increasingly adopting alternative contractual approaches that focus on performance outcomes rather than resource expenditures (Kim et al. 2007). Performance based contracting (PBC) is one of those contractual mechanisms aligning supplier remuneration with specific, measurable outcomes rather than dictating the methods for achieving them, and providing incentives for performance improvements (Selviaridis und Wynstra 2015).

While the shift toward service-oriented business models by manufacturers has been extensively explored, the challenges of adapting traditional procurement processes to accommodate complex performance solutions remain comparatively under-researched (Lewis und Roehrich 2010). The same applies to PBC: insights into the decision to and associated challenges with buying outcome-based service solutions remains limited (Schaefers et al. 2021; Selviaridis und Norrman 2015). PBC is predominantly classified as a contractual mechanism for shaping inter-organisational relationships between prime contractors and a buyers (Roehrich et al. 2020; Roehrich und Lewis 2014). Consequently, the implementation of PBC in individual projects or contracts has garnered considerable scholarly attention (e.g. Hou und Neely 2018; Selviaridis und Norrman 2015; Batista et al. 2017; Ng und Nudurupati 2010). However, as an expression of servitisation, it can also be viewed from a firm-level perspective as a strategic decision regarding service procurement or provision (Essig et al. 2016; Datta und Roy 2010; Glas et al. 2018).

PBC literature highlights that no single approach guarantees successful implementation; PBC is not a one-size-fits-all solution. Instead, it requires case-by-case decision-making (Sols et al. 2007). The approach can be implemented at different system levels, employing diverse contract forms and performance metrics (Holmbom et al. 2014). Thus, there is more than one way to successfully implement PBC in exchange relationships.

From a strategic perspective, PBC implementation in an organisation should follow a strategy implementation process. Strategy implementation is a topic that has received growing attention in strategic management, since it directly determines the success of strategic outcomes (Cândido und Santos 2019). A key concept in strategy implementation research is the so called *fit* between the strategy and organisational structures (Hill und Cuthbertson 2011). Fit in this context is defined as the degree of alignment between an organization's strategic objectives and its organisational characteristics, such as processes, systems, structures, and culture (Aleksić und Rašić Jelavić 2017; Chen et al. 2018). Achieving fit ensures that the organization's structure is optimally configured to support the implementation of its chosen strategy in certain environments (Chandler 1962; Schwartz und Davis 1981). Studies highlight the positive effects of proper fit between organizational characteristics and strategy on firm performance (e.g. Xu et al. 2006; Aleksić und Rašić Jelavić 2017).

However, research on strategy-structure fit primarily focuses on marketing and competitive strategy. The alignment of procurement strategies with purchasing structures has been addressed by only a few authors (e.g. Ateş et al. 2018). Existing contributions emphasize the link between purchasing strategies, such as offshore outsourcing (Tate und Ellram 2012) or global sourcing (Trautmann et al.

2009), and purchasing structures. Ateş et al. (2018) find that strategy-structure misfit negatively impacts purchasing performance across both cost and innovation strategies. Patrucco et al. (2023) demonstrate that the degree of environmental uncertainty influences the adoption of specific purchasing strategies. Since PBC is typically perceived as a contractual mechanism, the application of fit theory to PBC strategy is underexplored. Nonetheless, applying fit theory to PBC seems promising, as various approaches to PBC implementation exist. As with any procurement strategy, the fit between the organizational and external variables and the PBC strategy configuration is critical for determining its success.

Outlook

This research represents the first attempt to apply fit theory within the context of PBC. It aims to quantitatively evaluate the influence of organizational fit on the success of PBC implementation. While existing PBC research often focuses on individual projects and their outcomes, the relationship between PBC implementation success and broader organizational procurement performance remains largely unexplored.

An exploratory survey conducted between September and November 2024 highlights the critical role of fit in explaining PBC implementation success. The survey aimed to gain insights into the use of PBC in the German public sector, specifically targeting public procurement offices. It allowed for a distinction between public procurement bodies that have already adopted PBC and those that have not. The original objective was to investigate the impact of specific organizational and external characteristics on the adoption and extent of PBC strategies.

The survey retrieved 60 complete responses, up to now. Preliminary findings strongly support the importance of the fit concept itself. The relationship between fit and PBC implementation success was statistically significant. Furthermore, a second model demonstrated that successful PBC implementation positively and significantly impacts procurement performance.

These findings underscore the relevance of PBC not only as a contractual governance mechanism but also as a success relevant feature of procurement strategy. The initial results highlight the need for further exploration into the specific factors influencing successful PBC implementation. Expanding the survey sample size – until the conference or in future studies – will be essential to enhance the robustness and generalizability of the findings. Participation in IPSERA 2025 could refine the research methodology and provide valuable feedback on advancing the application of the fit construct to PBC.

Paper topic

13. Public procurement, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 2. PSM strategy

From a theoretical perspective: An explanation of strategic thinking in purchasing and supply management (PSM)

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

As purchasing and supply management (PSM) evolves into a strategic function, strategic thinking becomes increasingly important and is now recognized as a key competence for addressing future challenges. However, research on strategic thinking remains limited, revealing two key gaps: the absence of a commonly accepted understanding of strategic thinking and a lack of clarity regarding its functioning. Therefore, this working paper employs a theorization approach in the form of theory elaboration to elucidate strategic thinking from a triangulative perspective that incorporates organizational buying behavior (OBB), the resource-based view (RBV), and behavioral strategy theory (BST).

Paper topic

1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 2. PSM strategy, 15. PSM theory, methodology, education

Investor reactions to supplier exploitation: Threat or opportunity for buying firms?

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

Financial squeezing, abusing suppliers, or delaying payments are forms of supplier exploitation, which are not uncommon in supply chains. This study explores whether such misconduct toward suppliers is a threat or an opportunity for buying firms. An event study first reveals significant negative investor reactions to supplier misconduct. This effect intensifies with recent events and low media distraction but diminishes for highly profitable buyers. Then, an incentivized vignette experiment shows that investors prioritize profitability over ethical concerns in profitable firms. Overall, this study offers new insights into the impact of buyer misconduct toward suppliers on the buyer's market value.

Paper topic

12. Ethics, 17. Sustainability - social, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Adapting screening and signalling theory to advance supply market orientation in public procurement: A systematic literature review

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

A recent and prominent example of supplier-driven innovation in the public sector is Estonia's comprehensive e-government system, which has been largely developed through close collaboration with technology providers. This digital governance framework enables citizens to efficiently access nearly all public services online, including electronic voting (Donges, 2023; Kalvet, 2012). As a result, Estonia is recognized as a frontrunner in digital public services within the EU (e-Estonia, 2024). Similarly, Ukraine operates a platform, known as "Diia", aimed at enhancing efficiency, transparency, and resilience in public service delivery, particularly in response to the challenges posed by war (Kniazieva et al., 2023).

Particularly relevant in the context of procuring products and services from suppliers that boost public sector quality and efficiency is the concept of supply market orientation (SMO) in the pre-tender phase (Foerstl et al., 2020; Holma et al., 2022). SMO can be defined as the process of systematically collecting, analyzing, and disseminating information about supply markets and their development (Foerstl et al., 2020; Lorentz et al., 2020). The information gathering focuses on specific data and market intelligence relevant to procurement decisions (Handfield, 2010; Lorentz et al., 2020). These decisions include, for instance, the selection of potential suppliers, the determination of procurement strategies, and the definition of specific requirements for the procured solution. Moreover, it assists in preparing tender documents and determining which type of tendering procedure is most appropriate. The information collected includes, for example, data on suppliers' performance, reliability, and cost structures, price trends, supplier capacities, quality specifications, technological developments, supply chain risks, potential future suppliers, and regulations (Foerstl et al., 2020; Guida et al., 2023; Handfield, 2010; Song et al., 2009). This analysis enables informed decisions in public procurement management, optimizing costs, quality, risk management, and efficiency in the supply chain (Gray and Meister, 2006; Wondimu et al., 2016). For example, SMO strategies enable the identification of potential suppliers and their solutions through the information collected, aligning with a hybrid-governance interaction strategy (Kural and Alsac, 2006; Lenferink et al., 2012; Patrucco et al., 2017; Rokkan and Haugland, 2021). In addition, procurement strategies focused on identifying innovative, sustainable, and ethical supplier practices enhance public sector competitiveness and innovation (Uttam and Roos, 2015).

There is a significantly more evidence regarding procurement management and market exploration in the private sector compared to public procurement and its unique characteristics (Foerstl et al., 2020; Holma et al., 2022; Lorentz et al., 2020; Voda and Jobse, 2016; Wondimu et al., 2020). For instance, research in the private sector emphasizes the importance of up-to-date market information in the context of Industry 4.0 for effective procurement decisions (Tiwari, 2020). An example of this is the study by Lorentz et al. (2020), which highlights the critical role of accurate market information in mitigating risks, identifying technologies, and controlling costs in procurement. Additionally, research in this field has shown that leveraging modern technologies such as big data and artificial intelligence can significantly enhance the efficiency and accuracy of SMO. For example, Cui et al. (2022) underscore the potential of artificial intelligence in requests for proposals and its ability to gather and analyze supply market information. Furthermore, existing research findings indicate that SMO plays a key role in promoting sustainability within supply chains (Alhola et al., 2017; Cheng, 2020; Rainville, 2021; Uttam and Roos, 2015).

However, from a public procurement perspective, a systematization of SMO is missing. Existing research on SMO in public procurement is highly fragmented and, despite its critical importance for shaping procurement outcomes, remains limited (Holma et al., 2022; Voda and Jobse, 2016; Wondimu et al., 2020). Existing academic literature primarily focuses on critical success factors, objectives, advantages, and challenges in the SMO process, as well as various fragmented strategies that are employed (Farrell and Sunindijo, 2020; Gray and Meister, 2006; Voda and Jobse, 2016; Wondimu et al., 2016). Most identified studies emphasize the early involvement of suppliers in selected case examples, utilizing various terminologies related to SMO, mainly in the areas of infrastructure and construction projects within European countries (Antonsson et al., 2022; Eadie and Graham, 2014; Eriksson, 2017; Lenferink et al., 2012; Malvik et al., 2021; Plantinga et al., 2019; Rahman and Alhassan, 2012; Wondimu et al., 2020, 2018, 2016). However, Holma et al. (2022) note that the interaction between suppliers and buyers during the planning phase of public procurement procedures has largely been overlooked in research, which tends to adopt a general perspective centered on the public tendering process. This research gap highlights the need to develop a systematic approach to SMO in public procurement. This is particularly relevant given that various studies in the private sector demonstrate that supplier interaction and the utilization of accumulated external knowledge are essential factors for organizational innovation capacity (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990; Gemünden et al., 1996; Håkansson and Waluszewski, 2013; Harryson, 1997; Lamming et al., 2002; Lincoln et al., 1998; Liu et al., 2017; Pittaway et al., 2004; Ragatz et al., 1997; Rosell and Lakemond, 2012). Moreover, the literature on public procurement frequently suggests that the topic of SMO deserves greater attention (Holma et al., 2022; Plantinga et al., 2019; Rainville, 2016). Providing such a basis for future research is particularly relevant, as a lack of interaction by public buyers is considered one of the major innovation barriers for suppliers working with public organizations (Georghiou et al., 2014; Melander and Arvidsson, 2020; Uyarra et al., 2014). A survey by Uyarra et al. (2014) of 800 public sector suppliers in the United Kingdom shows that 43% of participants strongly disagreed with the statement that the public sector is generally open to unsolicited ideas (signals) from the market.

The identification of theoretical gaps and new theoretical perspectives through literature reviews is crucial to promote scientific progress (Craighead and Ketchen Jr., 2024). Hence, this study provides a comprehensive systematization of SMO within the context of public procurement by adopting a theoretical framework grounded in information economics, particularly signaling and screening theory. In doing so, it introduces new screening constructs in procurement and supply management (PSM) and applies existing constructs from other disciplines to PSM for the first time. This paper explores how public buyers can proactively address information asymmetries, which are especially prevalent in public

procurement due to factors such as the regulatory requirement to establish formal conditions for competitive tendering and imperfect competition - high entry barriers, constraints on engaging in long-term partnerships, and limited market transparency (Caldwell et al., 2005; Edwards, 1933). The theoretical lens allows generating actionable insights and recommendations to enhance SMO strategies, emphasizing their operational and strategic dimensions.

RQ : What is the current state of SMO in public procurement, and how can it be analyzed through the lens of information economics, particularly screening and signaling, to address information asymmetries and derive recommendations for its improvement?

The structure of the paper is organized as follows: Following the introduction, Section 2 outlines the conceptual framework, highlighting the relevance of signaling and screening theory to PSM. Section 3 explains the methodology, emphasizing the systematic literature review approach and its relevance to theorizing in underexplored domains like public procurement. Section 4 synthesizes findings from the literature, categorizing SMO activities and identifying research gaps. Section 5 presents a typology of SMO strategies and discusses their implications for public procurement. Finally, section 6 and 7 conclude by summarizing key insights, outlining limitations, and providing directions for future research.

This study examines SMO in public procurement through the lens of information economics, particularly using signaling and screening theories. The analysis reveals that SMO in public procurement is predominantly event-driven, focusing on narrow, short-term market analyses. The primary emphasis is on gathering information for immediate procurement needs, while the systematic dissemination and utilization of this information within public organizations remain largely absent. Long-term and continuous SMO strategies, such as those aimed at innovation scouting, technology monitoring, and strategic procurement alignment, are rarely implemented. A key finding is that suppliers actively use tailored signals to highlight their capabilities and alignment with buyer needs, whereas public buyers tend to take a reactive stance, limiting their ability to effectively screen, interpret, and leverage supplier information for strategic advantage. This reactive approach leads to an underutilization of SMO as a strategic capability in public procurement. To address these challenges, the study introduces a typology of SMO strategies, categorizing them into four approaches: Supply Market Exploration, Supply Market Analysis, Supply Market Observation, and Supply Market Forecasting (Types I and II). These strategies are structured along two dimensions: regularity (event-driven vs. continuous) and temporal focus (short-term vs. long-term). By integrating these approaches, public buyers can transition from reactive information gathering to proactive market engagement, utilizing market intelligence to enhance innovation, sustainability, and strategic procurement decision-making. The findings highlight the theoretical potential of signaling and screening theories in addressing information asymmetries in public procurement. However, the study identifies gaps in empirical validation, the limited consideration of supplier perspectives, and the absence of feedback loops and counter-signals, suggesting avenues for further research. Additionally, the applicability of findings to private-sector procurement remains an open question, given differing market dynamics and procurement practices.

Paper topic

13. Public procurement, 5. Supplier selection, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Supply Chain Integrity: A Systematic Literature Review, Definition, and Conceptual Framework

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Title: Supply Chain Integrity: A Systematic Literature Review, Definition, and Conceptual Framework

Summary: Supply Chain Integrity (SCI) emerged as a relevant yet inconsistently defined concept to meet consumers' demand for safe, qualitative, authentic, ethically and sustainably sourced products. This study embarks from a systematic literature review to propose a definition and conceptual framework for SCI to facilitate future research and its practical applications.

Keywords: Supply Chain Integrity, definition, framework

Submission category: Working paper (WP)

Main body of text

Over the past decades, companies from various industries initiated numerous efforts to provide consumers with more authentic, ethically, and sustainably sourced and manufactured products in a transparent and visible way (Carter and Liane Easton 2011; Carter, Hatton et al. 2019; Agrawal, Kumar et al. 2021). However, traditional reassurance mechanisms like brand reputation, country of origin labels, or certifications appear to lose credibility or suitability in documenting or controlling a product's origin and meeting the expectations of modern supply chain stakeholders (Montecchi, Plangger et al. 2019). Supply chain integrity (SCI) emerged to address these challenges (Castillo, Mollenkopf et al. 2018). Integrity proper is commonly used in specific industries, such as pharma and food, as a standard attribute of their supply chains.

Despite its importance, integrity often lacks a clear and consistent definition in academic literature and practice (Audi and Murphy 2006, Palazzo 2007, Becker 2009). This conceptual vagueness often hampers academic exploration and operationalization, presenting a significant challenge due to the concept's critical role across various sectors and its strategic and operational application (Palanski and Yammarino 2009; Robinson, Cadzow et al. 2018).

This study addresses this problem by analyzing how integrity in a supply chain context is conceptualized across different fields, looking for its theoretical foundations, proposing a comprehensive definition and using the findings to build and propose a new theoretical framework and model.

A systematic literature review, following the SPAR-4SLR protocol (Paul, Lim et al. 2021) to ensure rigor and minimizes bias and combining a content-based and bibliometric systematic literature review is employed. From the 786 and 1280 articles retrieved from the Web of Science and Scopus databases, covering academic journals, conference proceedings, and reputable non-academic sources until June 2023, 231 articles were filtered out, of which 189 were content analyzed. This extensive search ensures a comprehensive understanding of the existing literature on SCI, capturing its varied applications and interpretations across different fields and contexts.

The research, which to the best of our knowledge is the first one conducted across an extensive scope of fields, found diverse themes associated with SCI, such as blockchain, traceability, sustainability, transparency, and halal food, and classified the literature into distinct supply chain types: general, food, halal, pharmaceutical, ICT, and cold supply chains. Each of these types exhibits unique thematic emphases and SCI definitions.

One of the main observations of the study is that definitions of SCI vary significantly. Therefore, we propose a definition encompassing the multidimensional understanding of SCI, including structural and moral dimensions, transparency, traceability, and ethical behavior. Structural dimensions often relate to the physical integrity of products and the systems ensuring their consistent quality and safety. Moral dimensions, on the other hand, emphasize ethical practices within the supply chain, including fairness, honesty, and adherence to social and environmental standards. Transparency and traceability are critical for enabling stakeholders to verify the integrity of supply chains, ensuring that products are sourced, manufactured, and distributed in ways that meet established standards.

This study proposes a holistic definition of SCI that considers context, purpose, norms, analytic processes, and mechanisms for achieving, controlling, and maintaining delineated integrity. Context refers to the specific industry and supply chain type, recognizing that SCI must be tailored to different sectors' unique requirements and challenges. Purpose involves the intended outcomes of SCI, such as ensuring product safety, ethical sourcing, or compliance with regulatory standards. Norms encompass the standards and principles guiding SCI practices, while analytic processes involve the methods used to assess and verify integrity. Mechanisms for achieving SCI include technologies like blockchain, organizational practices, and policies.

This comprehensive definition is the foundation for developing a theoretical model of SCI, integrating principles of legitimacy to assess supply chain practices, social acceptability and desirability. Legitimacy involves evaluating whether supply chain practices align with societal expectations and norms, ensuring companies comply with regulations and meet broader ethical and social standards. This model emphasizes the importance of the product delivered by the supply chain and the necessary transparency, ensuring that all stakeholders can trust the integrity of the products and the processes behind them.

The definition and model developed in this study offer a new perspective and a solid basis for approaching supply chain integrity or implementing various aspects of integrity in a supply chain context. It provides a foundation for further research to refine the SCI concept and its practical

application and offers valuable insights for academics and practitioners to understand and enhance supply chain integrity and facilitate communication.

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Paper topic

12. Ethics, 2. PSM strategy, 15. PSM theory, methodology, education

Smart Contracting Design: A simulation-based evaluation of a decision logic for the design of contractual incentives

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Abstract

The purchasing and supply management area deploys contract incentives as a means of managing suppliers. Smart Contracting Design (SCD) is used to describe the automation of incentive design. In fact, SCD is a decision-making algorithm that enables the optimal design of contract incentives. In order to ascertain the usability in practice, conceptually developed algorithms such as the SCD must undergo a process of testing. Prior to implementation on a larger scale, it is essential to conduct a comprehensive testing to identify any inherent weaknesses in functionality and performance. This requires the operationalisation of the SCD concept as a prototype. The objective of this article is to employ action research to investigate the efficiency of the SCD prototype in designing optimal contract incentives. In particular, three simulation processes are conducted to facilitate a multi-stage evaluation of the SCD prototype by the research team. The result of this simulation-based evaluation is the formulation of recommendations for enhancing the SCD and ensuring its usability in practise.

Keywords: Algorithm, Contract Incentive Design, Supplier Management, Simulation Experiment, Prototype Evaluation

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Introduction

Contractual incentives are defined as financial and non-financial rewards and penalties that influence the motivational behaviour of suppliers (Selviaridis and Wynstra 2015). For this reason, the purchasing and supply management (PSM) contract literature advises that incentives should be optimized so that suppliers can be managed on a contractual basis (Jensen and Meckling 1976). Nevertheless, the process of incentive design is inherently complex and susceptible to error (Datta and Roy 2013; Zou et al. 2019). Digital tools provide a potential solution. Such tools contain algorithms that facilitate human decision-making by providing guidance through the application of pre-determined decision rules (Zweig 2018; Holtgrewe 1968). A significant number of procurement decisions are already supported by such algorithms in digital tools (Ates et al. 2024a). Examples of such tools include smart contracts for shipment tracking and transaction processing, chatbots to support supplier evaluation and selection, or digital twins for virtual delivery audits (Ates et al. 2024a; Mandl 2023). Despite the significance of contractual incentives for the alignment of interests in target-oriented supplier management, the process of incentive design is frequently undervalued (Aben et al. 2021; Steinbach et al. 2018; Eisenhardt 1989). Smart Contracting Design (SCD) addresses this gap by presenting a decision logic/algorithm for the optimal design of contract incentives (Ates et al. 2024b). SCD makes use of the capabilities of digital tools to identify and assess previously unidentified or challenging-to-understand correlations between ex-ante incentive conditions and their ex-post results (supplier behaviour), and to substantiate these with measures (Olsen and Tomlin 2020). In particular, this algorithm employs decision rules to ascertain an optimal incentive design (output variables) based on information pertaining to the procurement project (input variables) (Cormen 2013).

The objective of SCD is to address the tangible challenges inherent in supplier management, which are often the consequence of misaligned incentives. Such issues include over- or understocking, inaccurate forecasts and inadequate service quality (Narayanan and Raman 2004). Accordingly, the conceptual development of the SCD is insufficient; it must also be tested for applicability and practical suitability. This necessitates the operationalisation of the SCD concept as a prototype. In other words, the SCD concept must be operationalised (SCD prototype) so that it can then be tested, or more accurately, evaluated (Camburn et al. 2017; Christie et al. 2012). The authors Camburn et al. (2017) examined a total of 40 articles that dealt with the operationalisation of a concept as a prototype and its applicability test. The authors found that the majority of contributions primarily aimed to improve the concept. This article follows precisely this approach. The objective of this article is to employ the SCD prototype in a multi-stage evaluation process involving simulations. This approach enables the identification and elimination of any deficiencies in the logical functionality and efficient performance of the algorithm. As a result, recommendations can be formulated for enhancing the SCD prototype and ensuring its suitability for practical use. This will be achieved through the examination of the following research question: **What design recommendations can be derived from a simulation-based prototype evaluation of the SCD concept?**

The object of analysis is the SCD prototype, which is to be analysed using the action research method. The initial two action research cycles were dedicated to the parameterisation and calibration of SCD matrices, which map the core cause-and-effect relationships between SCD variables. These cycles have already been employed to refine the SCD concept (see Ates et al. in press). This article addresses action research cycle 3 and is based on an already developed SCD prototype. The research question will be addressed through a collaborative process, whereby the lead researcher will interact with teams of

experts from academic and practical backgrounds (Näslund et al. 2010; Saunders 2019). Three simulations are conducted for each of the three evaluation processes. To this end, the lead researcher prepares three case studies on procurement projects that are as realistic as possible. These case studies are used to demonstrate the SCD prototype, which is designed to create a set of optimal contract incentives for each case study. This enables an evaluation of the efficiency of the SCD prototype in a variety of procurement scenarios (Näslund et al. 2010). The results of the evaluation procedures provide insights that inform design recommendations for enhancing the SCD prototype.

This article's remainder is structured as follows: In the next section, the theoretical background is provided followed by the methodology. Subsequently, the findings of the simulation-based evaluation are presented and discussed. This study concludes with a discussion of the theoretical and practical implications of the findings, as well as suggestions for further research. The following section delineates the distinctive features of this study.

Advantages and relevance of the paper for the conference framework

The algorithms of digital tools are often not subjected to sufficient consideration and are even sometimes labelled as a 'black box'. Furthermore, contributions to software evaluation tend to prioritize aspects such as user-friendliness, speed, and user satisfaction. The focus is on the technical design of the human-software interface rather than on the logical structure and consistency of the underlying algorithm. The evaluation of the SCD prototype offers profound insights into the subject of algorithmic incentive design, which has not yet been investigated to such an extent. The novelty and complexity of the object of analysis therefore necessitates the involvement of experts to critically examine both the methodology and the findings of this paper. The IPSERA Conference 2025 provides a valuable opportunity to receive feedback and to gather new insights in the context of stimulating discussions, which are essential for the further optimisation of the SCD prototype.

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Paper topic

7. Negotiation and contracting, 11. Digital, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Toward post-growth supply chains: Prospective theorizing for alternative organizing and management principles

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Production growth—largely driven by the purpose of capital accumulation—continues to be widely perceived as desirable and positive despite its negative consequences for both humans and nature (Luzzini et al., 2024; Saito, 2022). Although critical voices have questioned the growth paradigm embedded in the current economic systems for many decades, the debate on alternative and potentially more sustainable economic models has recently intensified in the face of increasingly pressing crises, such as climate change (Fioramonti, 2024). Among the arguably most desirable alternatives for overcoming today's grand challenges is the 'post-growth economy', organized around principles that prioritize ecological resilience and social justice over economic growth for profit maximization and accumulation.

Despite the potential need for alternatives to dominant modes of production, perspectives challenging the growth paradigm are rare within the field of supply chain management (SCM; Luzzini et al., 2024). Although some scholars address sustainability aspects from more radical perspectives compared to the mainstream (e.g., Montabon et al., 2016), the field has largely failed to propose alternative forms of management that support aligning supply chains (SCs) with the principles of a post-growth economy. In fact, SCM research may have unwittingly reproduced insufficiently sustainable practices by replicating organizational and managerial models designed to achieve competitive advantage for profit maximization and continued growth, often at the expense of people and nature (Gold & Schleper, 2017).

Similar to other social science disciplines, the lack of post-growth alternatives in SCM may be attributed to the field's preference for describing and explaining the status quo rather than theorizing about desirable futures (Gümüşay & Reinecke, 2022, 2024). However, "the future is likely to be radically different from the present" (Gümüşay & Reinecke, 2024, p. 3), especially when it comes to a future that is socially just and truly environmentally sustainable. Such a post-growth future will likely require fundamentally different approaches to organizing society (Banerjee et al., 2020), including SCM (Luzzini et al., 2024).

Post-growth SCs would likely prioritize socio-ecological well-being, selective downscaling, and systems thinking (Luzzini et al., 2024). This approach represents a significant departure from today's focus on mass consumption, market penetration, and exploiting cost advantages that characterize many modern

SCs. However, given the scarcity of viable post-growth alternatives in the SCM literature, critical questions remain to be answered: How might post-growth SCs be organized? What specific methods of managing these SCs would be consistent with post-growth principles?

Our research seeks to explore alternative principles of organizing and governance, envisioning what post-growth SCs could look like and how they might be managed. To achieve this, we adopt the approach of ‘prospective theorizing’ (Gümüşay & Reinecke, 2024). Instead of mirroring and reproducing the empirical reality in a strictly objective way, prospective theorizing anticipates future possibilities with ‘speculative rigor’ (ibid.). We draw from existing literature on alternative forms of organizing and governance—such as workers’ cooperatives and social enterprises—that diverge from the current mainstream modes of production, which are largely organized based on the paradigm that considers growth in production and profits desirable or necessary. These alternative models offer valuable insights into how SCs could be restructured to bring social and environmental concerns to the forefront of production.

Despite their relatively small scale, various empirical examples illustrate what post-growth SCs might look like. Our ongoing analysis of the relevant literature has thus far identified four key principles:

- **Localization:** SC localization refers to the deliberate alignment of SCs with local markets, stakeholders, and societal needs (Smith et al., 2023). Instead of relying on extensive outsourcing and highly fragmented networks, localized SCs emphasize geographically concentrated production and sourcing. This approach promotes greater use of locally available resources and recycled materials while reinforcing closed-loop systems to reduce environmental impact (Nandi et al., 2021). Localization reconnects individuals and communities with the social and ecological consequences of production, countering the spatial disconnection typical of modern SCs. Currently, the exploitative impacts of production on nature and workers are often displaced to rural areas or the Global South, far removed from those who benefit most (Saito, 2022).
- **Democratic Participation:** Post-growth SCs may replace hierarchical governance structures—characterized by shareholder primacy and a lack of democratic control—with models emphasizing democratic decision-making and collective ownership (Karaosman et al., 2024). Traditional ownership structures often neglect the well-being of workers and local communities in favor of profit maximization and capital accumulation. In contrast, cooperative models allow workers to participate in decision-making processes, enabling them to address production’s social and environmental impacts as both workers and global citizens (Reinecke & Donaghey, 2021; Booth, 1995). Such democratic participation might facilitate the consideration of broader societal interests in SCM.
- **Design for longevity:** Post-growth SCs and their members may prioritize product designs that consider durability and reparability over planned obsolescence, which is typically driven by profit maximization. This principle promotes product longevity, reduces waste, and limits the consumption of energy and materials, aligning SCs with sustainable resource management (Froese et al., 2023). Companies like Patagonia and Fairphone exemplify this approach by focusing on sustainable materials, repairable designs, and modularity. However, even repair-focused models can create hierarchies and ‘assetization’ for maximizing profits and economic growth (Lloveras et al., 2023), which post-growth SCM must effectively address to avoid compromising overarching environmental and social concerns.
- **Commons innovations:** Post-growth SCs may emphasize open access to knowledge and collaborative technology development, prioritizing societal and environmental benefits over the competitive advantage and higher profits that can be realized through patents and private

protection (Roba et al., 2023). Examples include sharing life-saving technologies, such as seatbelt patents, and platforms like Wikipedia, which democratize knowledge. Moreover, social enterprises often embody this principle by fostering collaborative social innovations for the common good rather than for profit maximization (Longoni et al., 2019).

Our conceptual paper aims to make several contributions. First, it seeks to advance the emerging post-growth discourse within SCM (Luzzini et al., 2024) by synthesizing and extending existing perspectives on noncapitalist SCs (Safri, 2015). Specifically, it provides an overview of alternative organizing and management principles that challenge the latent growth paradigm prevalent in the SCM literature. By engaging in prospective theorizing, the paper envisions how these principles could inform the organization and governance of post-growth SCs. Finally, the research ultimately aims to present a theoretical framework that incorporates these principles and offers a potential blueprint for managing SCs in a post-growth economy. This framework is intended to guide future research and practice toward supporting the transition to a potentially more sustainable and socially just society.

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Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social

136

Supply base complexity in times of crisis: Moderating the negative impact of the Russia-Ukraine war

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

Supply chains are crucial to global business but are vulnerable to mega-disruptions like the Russia-Ukraine war. Analyzing 837 automotive firms headquartered in 41 countries, we reveal that automotive firms experience negative market reactions following the outbreak of the war, which is propagated to their customers in other industries. The negative impact was worsened for firms with high horizontal complexity but mitigated for those with high vertical complexity. Our study sheds light on the nuanced role of supply base complexity, emphasizing the importance of understanding its structural dimensions to develop effective resilience strategies during times of crisis.

Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience

Smart Sustainable Supply Chain Management: Shaping the way digital transformation is adopted for Sustainable Supply Chains

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The Smart Sustainable Supply Chain Management (3SCM) approach emphasizes the integration of digital strategies and sustainable practices in the supply chain context. However, the implementation of a 3SCM poses challenges, particularly in aligning operational and digital transformation strategies with sustainability goals. Our study aims to understand how companies implement 3SCM. To achieve this goal, we conducted qualitative research. We developed a theoretical framework for adopting 3SCM using Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and the Digital Transformation Level Model. Our 3SCM framework expands the CSR theory and develops an integrated, systematized, and simplified approach to digital transformation, CSR, sustainability, and supply chains. This simplification and systematization facilitate sustainability, innovation, and digital transformation in an integrated manner, enabling companies to shape their supply chains strategies. Our primary contribution is that our 3SCM framework not only facilitates 3SCM but also smart social and green supply chain management.

Paper topic

11. Digital, 16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social

Stakeholder engagement to enhance sustainable procurement in developing countries Case studies of multinational enterprises in Nigeria and Kenya

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Abstract

This working progress study aims to add understanding on sustainable procurement in developing countries. We focus specifically on multinational enterprises (MNEs) as buyers, and their interaction with the local stakeholders in promoting environmental sustainability. We apply sustainable supply chain management, stakeholder engagement, value creation and the IMP approach literature to investigate how the MNEs in developing countries engage with their focal stakeholders to enhance sustainable procurement, and what is the aim of the interaction. The empirical study is conducted as a qualitative case study of MNEs located in Nigeria and Kenya. The main data collection method is semi-structured interviews. The intended contribution relates to sustainable procurement literature in the context of developing countries.

Introduction

Multinational enterprises with businesses in developing countries have been criticized for not paying enough attention to sustainability when it comes to the impacts on local society and environment. There is a lack of knowledge about sustainable procurement in developing countries (Anin et al., 2023) and sustainability is indeed becoming an increasingly important characteristic of today's globalised supply chains (Masoumi et al., 2019). Consequently, stakeholders are exerting pressure on firms and their supply chain partners to become more sustainable (Boruchowitch and Morgane 2022). Sustainable procurement as captured in ISO 20400 is any purchase that considers criteria which aims at protecting the environment, promoting social progress, and enhancing economic development, while maintaining a balance between stakeholders (Boruchowitch and Morgane 2022).

Generally, the buyers in developing countries have less pressures to stimulate sustainable procurement than the buyers in developed countries (Tsoi, 2010). However, the criticism towards MNEs has made stakeholders such as governments, NGOs and consumers request MNEs to refocus their efforts away from short-term economic gain instead to long-term sustainable activity (Burritt *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, the empirical context of our study is developing countries and established MNE's efforts to enhance environmental sustainability in its businesses by engaging with the focal stakeholders. The key objective

of stakeholder engagement is to discover how business can be conducted in a profitable, socially and environmentally responsible manner (Aakhus and Bzdak 2015) which will lead to value creation. In general, value creation occurs whenever a corporation's activities satisfy its stakeholders' fundamental needs; and value creation essentially should go beyond dyadic value creation such as just creating value between the firm and their customers but be extended to other stakeholders both internal and external (Lüdeke-Freund et al.,2020). Companies often use value creation to show how they can co-create value with their customers (Ordanini and Pasini, 2008) and other stakeholders; which is a situation where stakeholders exchange resources and benefit from this exchange (Gronroos, 2008; Vargo et al., 2008). Value can be created when firms consider their environmental impacts and make improvements through improved material efficiency, renewable energy efficiency, and waste management (Ritala et al., 2018). There are various values that can be derived by both the MNCs and their stakeholder; Economic value can be in the form of revenue generation, environmental value, by product decarbonization and social value by job creation. Stakeholders are certainly capable of influencing a firm's social and environmental decisions (Parmigiani et al., 2011). It is impossible for organizations to achieve long-term success if they do not consider the needs and expectations of their stakeholders (Neely et al., 2002). It is therefore important for companies to be willing to take practical action with regards to dealing their stakeholders.

The theoretical framework of the study is built on stakeholder engagement, sustainable supply chain management literature, value creation and the IMP approach. Sustainable supply chain management aims to contribute to economic, social and environmental sustainability, including the management of material, information and capital flows (Khan et al., 2021). We investigate stakeholder engagement from the MNEs' supply chain management perspective. Suppliers are essential actors in this supply chain, however, there are other important stakeholders that have an influence and are influenced by the buyers' sustainability related activities. Thus, we turn to the stakeholder engagement literature, which derives from the stakeholder theory (Freeman 1984) and refers to the interaction among a firm and its stakeholders, for example, suppliers, governments, investors, political groups, customers, communities, employees and trade associations (Donaldson and Preston, 1995).

Stakeholder theory and the IMP business network approach have much in common. They both address business and non-business relationships; however, they are rarely discussed together (Esse, Szántó, and Wimmer 2012). An occasional exception is the study by Lindfelt and Törnroos (2006) which compared stakeholder theory and business networks in terms of their attitudes towards value creation and ethics. It is noted that, despite the similarities between stakeholder theory and industrial network theory, there is still a major difference between the two approaches; Stakeholder approaches view stakeholder and firm interests as opposing factors, whereas network approaches see a mutual interest stemming from each partner in the dyadic relationship (Lindfelt and Törnroos, 2006). Ivens and Pardo (2010) in their study argue that research on business networks can profit from an integration of the stakeholder perspective. The topics in which stakeholder relationships are most often discussed in the IMP literature address mainly sustainability and ethical issues (see e.g. Ritala and Salmi 2011). Thus, the combination of the sustainable supply chain management, stakeholder theory (more specifically stakeholder engagement), and the IMP network approach provide us a solid framework to investigate how MNCs engage with its various stakeholders to enhance social, environmental and economical sustainability in the developing countries. Therefore, building on stakeholder engagement, IMP interaction approach and sustainable supply chain literature, we aim to add understanding of sustainable procurement practices in developing countries by investigating how MNEs in Nigeria and Kenya engage with the focal stakeholders. We seek answers to the following questions:

- How MNEs interact with stakeholders in promoting environmental sustainability?
- How does stakeholder engagement enhance sustainable procurement?
- What are the values derived by the various stakeholders?

Methodology

This study is exploratory, qualitative, and adopts an embedded case study approach (Yin, 2011). Qualitative method is appropriate in investigating why people think or have certain perspective about an issue. Qualitative methods endeavor to describe an event thoroughly and give a holistic view of the issue, allowing flexibility in data collection and interaction with respondents in their own language (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012).

The empirical study is conducted among MNEs in the manufacturing sector in Nigeria and Kenya. Instead of focusing on a single case, this study endeavor to give a broader perspective, thus why a multiple case study approach is adopted.; comprising of different firms in the food and beverage (alcoholic and nonalcoholic) with proper supply chain structures and also with operations within different African countries. The choice of firms is based on accessibility.

Keywords – Sustainable Supply Chain Management, Stakeholder Engagement, Multinational Enterprises, IMP Approach, Developing Countries

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Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

Cyberattacks on Third-Party Logistics (3PL) Service Providers: A Ripple Effect on Global Supply Chains

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Supply chain partners are heavily dependent on a continuous flow of critical data to maintain efficient operations (Choy et al., 2008). The advent of Industry 4.0 technologies, including digital platforms, cloud computing, Internet of Things, blockchain, artificial intelligence and radio frequency identification, has facilitated the management of vast amounts of critical data, significantly improving the logistics industry's operational efficiency and transparency (Ugochukwu et al., 2022). These technologies facilitate supply chain optimization by enabling firms to share vital information through trust networks and interfaces (PWC, 2013).

The increasing reliance on digital technologies and centralized databases, coupled with the daily access to vast amounts of critical data, has made logistics and supply chain networks vulnerable to various cybersecurity threats (Ugochukwu et al., 2022). When one member of a supply chain has inadequate security, the vulnerability can spread like wildfire, affecting all other partners due to the interconnected nature of these systems (Li and Xu, 2021).

3PL service providers are the intermediaries that play an increasingly strategic role in today's global supply chains by connecting networks and ensuring efficient operations (Zacharia et al., 2011). As companies increasingly outsource logistics operations to 3PL service providers, who handle vast amounts of sensitive data from numerous stakeholders, they inadvertently transfer the risk of cyberattacks to these providers (Creazza et al., 2022; Ugochukwu et al., 2022). Over 60% of supply chain cyberattacks originate from suppliers or 3PL service providers (Simon and Omar, 2020). The NotPetya ransomware attack on AP Moller-Maersk in 2017 serves as a real-world example of the devastating impact of cyber threats (Cheung et al., 2021). Other organizations affected by the attacks include FedEx subsidiary TNT Express, Toll Group, and Hellman Global Worldwide Logistics. These real-world examples indicate that cybercriminals frequently target 3PL service providers and serve as a stark reminder of the vulnerability of critical infrastructure to cyber threats (Harju et al., 2024). These incidents underscore the urgent need for 3PL companies to implement robust cybersecurity measures (Schoenherr et al., 2023), as attacks on these providers can have far-reaching consequences, disrupting global operations and impacting all supply chain stakeholders beyond significant financial losses (Creazza et al., 2022).

Despite the central role of cybersecurity in logistics, there is a lack of in-depth studies focusing on the specific vulnerabilities of 3PL service providers and the broader impacts of cyberattacks on the supply chain. Research has concentrated either on general supply chain risks or cybersecurity, leaving a significant gap in understanding the unique challenges faced by 3PL service providers (Cheung et al., 2021). This study seeks to bridge this knowledge gap by investigating the potential ripple effects of cyberattacks on 3PL service providers throughout the supply chain. By examining how such attacks can compromise the security of the entire supply chain, from manufacturers to end consumers, we aim to highlight the significant risks posed by vulnerabilities in 3PL services.

This research aims to answer the following question: "How do cyberattacks on 3PL service providers affect the overall efficiency and resilience of the supply chain?". To gain a deeper understanding of the real-world implications of cyberattacks on 3PL services, semi-structured interviews were conducted. This method allows for flexibility in exploring specific areas of interest and capturing rich, qualitative data (Matthews and Ross, 2010).

The interviews were conducted with 18 participants representing various supply chain stakeholders, including 3PL service providers, ports, customs agencies, and manufacturers. The total duration of interviews was around 13 hours, with an average interview length of 44 minutes. The interviews were transcribed verbatim, resulting in over 400 pages. Content analysis was then applied to these transcriptions to identify patterns and insights (Weber, 1990). A multi-stage coding process was used, beginning with initial coding, followed by progressively more abstract categorization in subsequent coding levels to uncover deeper meanings and relationships within the data (Fawcett et al., 2014).

To understand the complex dynamics of supply chains, particularly in the face of cyber threats, this study utilized systems theory as its primary theoretical framework (Shi et al., 2009). By adopting a holistic perspective, systems theory enables us to recognize how cyberattacks can rapidly spread through the network, impacting multiple stakeholders and processes.

Preliminary findings suggest that cyberattacks significantly impact not only the operational efficiency of 3PL service providers but also the resilience of the entire supply chain. Notably, when an attack originates from a 3PL company, it affects the company itself and spreads throughout the supply chain with a domino effect, impacting all integrated stakeholders. Even in cases of lower integration, the supply chain remains vulnerable. While the risk of data leakage, system interruptions, or ransomware spreading to stakeholders may be reduced, operational processes remain indirectly affected due to the interconnected nature of the supply chain.

The initial findings reveal that a cyberattack can have both immediate and long-lasting consequences. In the short term, operations may be disrupted, data may be compromised, and communications may be hindered. Over the longer term, the impact can be even more severe, potentially leading to loss of customer trust, damaged business relationships, significant financial losses, extensive organizational restructuring, reputational damage, decreased sales, increased vulnerability to future attacks, higher operational costs, and persistent challenges in restoring trust.

Furthermore, the analysis indicated that a cyberattack on a 3PL service provider can trigger a chain reaction, potentially exposing numerous stakeholders to substantial risks. Importers and exporters may face increased costs, reduced trade volume, and damaged business relationships. More specifically, manufacturers may suffer from production line disruptions, product quality issues, and intellectual property theft, while suppliers may experience disrupted production planning, inventory management

challenges, delayed deliveries, and financial losses. Customs authorities may encounter delayed clearances and increased security risks. On the other hand, ports may experience operational disruptions, leading to container theft, misdirection, congestion and delays. On the other hand, retailers face stock shortages, decreased sales, and damaged brand reputation, while end users may experience delayed deliveries, product shortages, and compromised personal information.

This research, which examines how the cyberattacks on 3PL service providers affect multiple stakeholders and the resilience of the overall supply chain, is the first phase of an ongoing study. In the second phase, a focus group will be conducted to discuss the mitigation strategies for cyberattacks targeting 3PL service providers and explore how implementing these strategies influences the overall resilience, reliability, and efficiency of the supply chain.

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Paper topic

6. Outsourcing, offshoring, reshoring, 11. Digital, 18. Risk and resilience

Unpacking Customer Attractiveness Through the Lens of Proximity: A Conceptual Approach

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This conceptual article updates our understanding of attractiveness between buyers and suppliers—a central theme in procurement research. It delves into how firms navigate inter-organizational relationships by examining the interplay between proximity and attractiveness within client and supplier relations. It identifies institutional (i), organizational (ii), cognitive (iii), social (iv), and geographical (v) proximities as pivotal dimensions that enhance partner attractiveness (vi) by fostering collaboration, cultivating trust, and reducing coordination costs. The analysis argues that these proximities can be strategically managed to reinforce long-term relational value, offering a structured framework for integrating them into business models. In contrast, intangible relational elements like trust, while crucial, are less easily but are influenced by the actionable management of proximities, contributing to value creation in supply chain partnerships.

Paper topic

5. Supplier selection, 2. PSM strategy, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Investigating Public Procurement Officer's Preferences for Sustainable Procurement: A comparison in supplier selection decision-making between the Netherlands and Norway

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This study examines whether public procurement officers in the Netherlands and Norway prioritize sustainability differently in supplier selection decisions and examines the underlying factors contributing to differences or similarities. Both countries have regulatory frameworks or policies promoting sustainable public procurement, yet aligning employee practices with these regulations and policies still needs to be improved. Through institutional theory, the research examines decision-making and the prioritization of sustainability factors like environmental and social factors, as well as factors relative to price and quality. By doing this, the study explores the impact of institutional pressures shaping procurement preferences in both countries, using comparisons between Norway and the Netherlands. The study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining a conjoint experiment and qualitative interviews. The conjoint experiment systematically investigates whether sustainability is prioritized differently, while the interviews provide a contextual understanding of the factors influencing decision making. The findings are expected to reveal if and how institutional pressures influence decision-making, contributing to a better understanding of how sustainable public procurement strategies evolve.

Paper topic

13. Public procurement, 16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social

Artificial intelligence (AI) use cases in purchasing and supply management from the perspective of AI experts

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Artificial intelligence (AI) use cases in purchasing and supply management from the perspective of AI experts

Keywords or phrases: Artificial Intelligence, AI, PSM, Digitalization

Introduction

In the face of complex, global and uncertain supply chains, the ability to adapt to changing conditions is crucial (Pessot et al. 2023). The use of artificial intelligence (AI) is one of the emerging catalysts for a transformation of value chains, enabling companies to reinvent structures, make policies more flexible, innovate processes and offer novel improvements for value creation (Sharma et al. 2022, Ritchey et al. 2023). As a data-driven technology that can fulfil both assistive and autonomous roles in supply chain management, AI supports or performs both quantitative tasks to optimise performance indicators and qualitative activities such as contributing to decision-making processes (Hendriksen 2023, Allal-Chérif et al. 2021). In particular, the cross-functional nature of procurement and its involvement in upstream decisions with external stakeholders makes it possible to analyse large volumes of data, both across the organisation and between supply chain actors, and to apply AI to the various procurement tasks on this basis (Bienhaus and Haddid 2018; Allal-Chérif et al. 2021). Automation and autonomisation through the use of AI blur the boundary between machine and human activities and the use can primarily replace tasks and activities of procurement managers in tedious and operational tasks (Burger et al. 2023; Guida et al. 2023). This enables the purchasing and supply management (PSM) department to transform from a pure focus on low purchase prices in operational processes to a more strategic perspective with an increasingly internally integrated role as manager of the supply base and innovation facilitator (Meyer and Henke 2023, van Poucke et al. 2019).

AI in PSM is still at an early stage of maturity and potential use cases are currently an essential part of PSM research and business evaluation of their potential applications (e.g. Guida et al. 2023; Spreitzenbarth et al. 2024). Scientific publications and companies themselves are increasingly interested in identifying potential use cases, while the capabilities of the technology are constantly being developed internally and by established external service providers or start-ups (Guida et al. 2023). Within the publications, there are two main types of research into the topic: technical-oriented journals and management journals (Spreitzenbarth et al. 2024). Within the technical-oriented journals, individual activities in purchasing are examined from an isolated perspective with regard to the use of AI, using conceptual research methods or model building (e.g. Moosmayer et al. 2013; Abolbashari et al. 2018). In the management journals, this technological research is analyzed by literature reviews to create a holistic view of AI use cases and often combined with empirical data from companies, typically through case studies (e.g. Guida et al. 2023; Spreitzenbarth et al. 2024). The figure 1 visualises the state of research.

Figure 1 – State of research and resulting research gap

Nevertheless, this implies that solely the use cases that have already been developed or implemented are taken into account, whereas the broader potential of AI in the procurement process remains underexplored. This is mainly due to the fact that the perspective of AI experts does not yet play a major role in the data collection of publications in management journals. When AI experts were involved, they were often from the IT procurement department, providing only a limited interdisciplinary view. When IT experts outside PSM were involved, they were often only part of the evaluation, assessing the attractiveness of existing use cases against certain criteria (e.g. business value, ease of implementation) (Schulze-Horn et al. 2020, Spreitzenbarth et al. 2024).

However, this means that an important perspective on the possible current and, above all, future applications of AI in procurement and other use cases is lost. In addition, the wider involvement of AI experts can help describe the specific technical possibilities in more detail and pave the way for the targeted further research steps. This working paper addresses this research gap and identifies use cases through the perspective of AI experts to answer the following research question:

What use cases for applying AI in the steps of the purchasing process are being driven by AI experts?

Methodology

In order to answer the research question, qualitative empirical data collection using semi-structured guideline-based expert interviews is chosen to evaluate the existing use cases with AI experts (e.g. Lamarr Institute) and identify new possibilities in procurement (Miles et al. 2014). The advantage of this methodology in this research approach is that the researchers are able to make a structured reference to existing research and the already identified use of AI and, in turn, are granted the openness to evaluate these using their existing knowledge.

Beforehand, a literature review is used to develop a scientifically based interview guideline. This is based on existing assessments of AI and previous technologies in purchasing such as e-procurement (e.g. Gamal 2010; Vaidya and Campbell 2014). In the interview guide, the experts are first introduced to PSM in order to reach a common consensus on the tasks and responsibilities of PSM (van Weele 2018). In the second part, the experts then assess the technological application potential in the activities within the extended purchasing process. In the third part, they are given an overview of existing use cases and in this way expand the existing business and scientific perspectives.

Conclusion

The interview guide is currently in the final stages of development, and preliminary interviews will be conducted shortly, after which data collection will begin. The data will be analysed using MAXQDA, using qualitative content analysis according to Mayring (2014).

The perspective of AI experts expands the possibilities and considerations and addresses requirements and potential from a technological perspective. In this way, the primary descriptive use cases identified in current scientific publications from the perspective of PSM or service providers can be expanded to include future application potential, from which operational options for action can be derived. From a scientific point of view, the researchers can use this as a basis to investigate the incentives for implementing AI use cases and to conduct a scientific conceptualisation of the evaluation of use cases in purchasing in order to operationalise the process and the indicators of the assessment of the use of AI in PSM.

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Paper topic

11. Digital, 10. Purchasing innovation, 2. PSM strategy

The use of public contract data in public procurement research: A systematic literature review

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The use of public contract data in public procurement research: A systematic literature review

Purpose: The purpose of this working paper is to assess how researchers are using public contract data to advance knowledge about buyer and supplier behaviour and outcomes. The advent of e-procurement has meant that large tranches of numeric and text data on live and awarded public contracts are now available to access and download. This forms part of a wider trend towards “open data1” in public administration. Researchers are taking advantage of supranational databases like Tenders Electronic Daily (TED), federal databases like Federal Procurement Data System (FDPS) and national or regional databases like Contracts Finder to obtain quantitative and qualitative indicators of public procurement. Papers that mine such data are becoming more common. Topics analysed to date include the effects of dividing contracts into lots on SME participation and success in contract competitions (Zimmerman, 2017; Glas and Essig, 2018; Hoekman and Tas, 2022), the form and extent of sustainability elements in tender evaluation criteria (Grandia and Kruyen, 2020; Zheng and Wen, 2024) and the prevalence of corruption practices in public contract competitions (Bauhr et al. 2020; Fazekas and Kocsis, 2020).

The results of these and other studies have provided new, evidence-based insights into some of the key issues affecting public procurement, with implications for both scholarship and practice. Public contract data has the potential to be transformative for public procurement research, not only in addressing outstanding questions but also in increasing the sophistication of research designs and analytical approaches e.g., using public contract data from TED to undertake longitudinal and cross-national studies. For these reasons, it is desirable that the purchasing and supply management (PSM) community has a complete picture of how public contract data is used in studies, the meaning and significance of the results it has generated, and the potential for future research discoveries as more of it starts to become available e.g., the EU’s Public Procurement Data Space (PPDS). This is the motivation for the working paper.

Method: A systematic review of research that uses public contract data is the preferred methodological approach for this paper. The paper will follow established protocols for conducting systematic reviews in the PSM field (see, for example, Hoejmose and Adrien-Kirby, 2012; Seuring and Gold, 2012; Giunipero et

al. 2019). The review is limited to papers published in peer-reviewed journals and written in English. To start, a keyword search (KWS) of EBSCO and ABI Inform databases will be performed to identify relevant papers. The KWS will be supplemented with a cross-reference paper search (CRP) to ensure that all relevant papers are included in the final sample. Papers must have used public contract data that is openly available to be eligible for inclusion.

The review, conducted by two researchers to support the validity and reliability of the process, will proceed in two stages. The first stage is a bibliometric analysis of the final sample of papers using a deductive coding approach. The purpose of bibliometric analysis is to capture metrics on the frequency of publications, the source of publications e.g., journal/field and the research context of publications e.g., EU public contracts, US public contracts, Chinese public contracts, etcetera. The second stage is a categorization of papers based on their research aim. This part of the analysis will be inductive in nature. It is intended to identify how public contract data has been used in research, whether this is to do with the attributes of contracts e.g., evaluation criteria, the outcomes of suppliers e.g., SME win rates, the features of competitions e.g., number of bidders, the spatial distribution of contract awards e.g., local sourcing, or something else. The categorization of papers will, when complete, lead to the creation of an organizing framework concerning public contract data in public procurement research.

Anticipated results: the analysis is not yet complete, and no results are available to report at the time of writing. However, we anticipate the following based on initial screening (i) a substantial number of studies that use public contract data originate outside of the PSM field. Specifically, finance and economics scholars are drawing on public contract data as part of econometric studies into the corporate performance effects of winning tenders and (ii) while many studies use public contracts as their sole data source, others combine it with data related to supplier financial performance, the characteristics of the purchasing organisation or the demographics of the area in which the purchasing organisation is based. In other words, researchers are not only interested in the basic attributes of public contracts but in the factors that determine, or are determined by, public contract awards.

Expected contributions: This paper contributes to PSM scholarship and practice as follows. First, it collates and interprets the various published papers that have utilized public contract data. Doing so allows the PSM community to see how public contract data has been employed for research purposes, what the analysis reveals about public buyers, suppliers and the procurement system, and where there are opportunities for future research. Second, it puts forward an organizing framework that explains the relationship of public contract data studies to public procurement research. No such framework currently exists and the collection of papers that use public contract data is siloed and inter disciplinary. Third, it helps to advance scholarship on public procurement by advocating for greater awareness and understanding of public contract data and how it can be exploited to advance the PSM field. Fourth, it highlights lessons for policymakers, public sector managers and suppliers that have already emerged from the body of scholarship on public contract data. For example, the evidence suggests that splitting contracts into lots does not necessarily lead to greater SME involvement and success in contract competitions, even though policymakers assume that it is beneficial (Zimmerman, 2017; Glas and Essig, 2018; Hoekman and Tas, 2022).

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Paper topic

13. Public procurement, 15. PSM theory, methodology, education, 11. Digital

146

Circular supply chains: Push and pull factors in multi-industry networks

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

In today's society, there is much focus on increased sustainability, where circularity is one way to reduce the footprint of manufacturing companies. Companies are transforming their supply chains to be circular, enabling take-back of products as well as providing used material in their production, thus moving from a linear supply chain to a circular supply chain. This paper focuses on which key actors and activities enable circular supply chains as well as which push and pull factors that influence circularity across diverse industries. The study takes a qualitative approach through a multiple case study of companies with circular supply chains. The findings identify a range of internal and external actors who enable circularity as well as multiple activities that are needed for enabling circular supply chains.

Paper topic

15. PSM theory, methodology, education, 2. PSM strategy, 16. Sustainability - environmental

An analysis of the underrepresentation of procurement skills in senior managers in the construction and housebuilding industries

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Summary

This paper seeks to assess the level of skills and expertise in the construction sectors procurement function and examine the perception on the advantage of adopting these procurement skills in senior management positions.

The research hypothesises

1. Procurement based roles and skills are absent from senior jobs within construction.
2. Instead high-level jobs have a background in finance or quantity surveying.

And strives to:

1. Define which roles, skills and experience are more prevalent at senior or director level in housebuilding.
2. Investigate whether procurement-based roles and skills are absent from senior or director level in housebuilding.

Construction procurement

Historically purchasing functions within organisations have been perceived as administrative in nature and have therefore tended not to be a key component of organisational strategy development. (Lyson & Farrington, 2020) As a result, these procurement functions had often operated independently of border operational decisions. This created limitation on the understanding of strategic sourcing and hindered the benefits that can be realised from an integrated procurement function (Yu et al, 2020)

In recent years, larger corporations have increasingly recognized procurement as a critical component of operational development. (Benton, 2020). The impacts of Brexit, Covid and Russia-Ukraine war has made the global connectivity of modern supply chains more prominent and has underscored the strategic importance of a pro-active procurement function. (Oyegoke et al, 2024) Consequently, the

function has gained prominence as a core component within organisational strategy (Shivajee, et al 2023)

This integrative approach to procurement is reshaping perceptions of procurement professionals and the skills they require. For example, Chartered Institute of Procurement and Supply (CIPS) Salary guide (2023) note that the perception of procurement as a strategic function have grown over the last 12 months. With 69% of those surveyed suggesting that the heads of other departments understand the value of procurement can offer and 61% feel valued within the organisation. The cross functional approach has helped show the value of integrated procurement in making decisions for the long-term business strategy and has helped the function gain credibility within businesses.

As perceptions of procurement evolve, the ideal skill set for procurement professionals will also need to adapt to align with these changing demands and requires senior management to understand the role and skills needed for supporting procurement development. (Paulraj, 2006; Changalima, 2021) The future procurement professional requires the managers of the future to acquire training on strategic skills. If procurement is seen to operate more strategically this requires employment of skills and abilities to maximise the contribution to the long-term strategy (Giunipero and Percy 2006).

However this uptake within construction has been limited (Robertson et al, 2024) Procurement activities are still seen as transactional with limited scope over strategic decisions (Lou et al, 2023) Contextualized within private housebuilding, 33% percent of developers have admitted that they had no known supply chain strategy and half of respondents suggesting that have no formal supply chain performance measures. (Barker & Naim, 2008) and while opportunities have presented themselves for the sector to innovate its procurement frameworks, these have yet to be capitalised upon. (Costin et al, 2019)

These housebuilding and construction purchasing functions have focused on playing to the market in order to achieve short term transactional cost savings limiting the ability to make long term value driven decisions. (Robertson et al, 2024) The skills currently employed in these procurement functions are predominantly centred around contracting and tendering processes. (CBI, 2020) As a result, procurement decisions are often made by quantity surveyors, with a primary focus on selecting tenders and contracts based on the lowest cost criteria often lacking strategic priority.(Pryke, 2018) Hiring for these procurement roles, key criteria remain unrefined with only a limited number of these organizations applying standardized approaches to their supply chain processes, highlighting a critical gap in practice (Behera et al., 2015) that is misaligned with established academic procurement frameworks. CIPS salary guide (2023) found these procurement roles currently lack sector specific skills (at 52%), soft skills (34%) and technical procurement experience (45%). This limited commercial and technical understanding of strategic supply chain within construction and consequently has mean the sector is not capable of meeting the future of supply chain challenges and urgently requires a fundamental behaviour change in how it manages the procurement function.

To achieve this shift, there is need for internal education on strategic procurement. (Robertson et al, 2024). Successful procurement teams require well trained and well-educated employees. (Asiedu et al, 2023) The level of education and training of specialist procurement professionals has been on the decrease. Gartner (2023) now says Only 14% of procurement leaders have adequate talent to meet future needs of their function

The rationale for further research into this area is supported by an initial analysis of 10 job advertisements (taken from the Indeed website job board), taken from a range of job titles (Construction Director, Construction Project Manager, Site Manager, Multi-Site Manager), with the tendency to refer to general activities across the supply chain, such as “coordinate with subcontractors, suppliers and other stakeholders”, “working closely with the onsite team including subcontractors, engineers, management” or very general in terms of the procurement focus, e.g., “advising upon the procurement of resources”. Therefore, a more nuanced understanding of the specific procurement-related skills is needed and in this study we look at what job roles construction currently considers to be critical to develop a high-level board and search if supply chain-based roles are missing from senior management positions.

Method

The first part of this study will involve a fuller analysis of job advertisements (following the approach of Klézl et al., 2022; Kelly et al., 2024) in which skills are categorised according to different senior job role levels and possible differences between sub-sectors within the wider construction industry. It will then survey senior managers within construction to assess the understanding of procurement and supply chain roles within senior construction & housebuilding positions. Data collection includes information around age, gender, and personal work experience which will be quantitatively analysed to assess the prevalence of certain experience and backgrounds in developing senior leaders within procurement and supply chain. This includes the information on gender, age, education, and experience.

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Paper topic

1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

Herding Under Pressure: Behavioral Parallels Between Asset Management and Supply Chain Management During Crises

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This study investigates the transposition of herding—a phenomenon traditionally studied in the context of asset management—into supply chain management (SCM) during the COVID-19 pandemic. Herding, defined as the tendency of decision-makers to imitate others' actions while disregarding private information, frequently emerges in uncertain and volatile environments (Choi & Skiba, 2015). The research addresses the core question: "To what extent can the phenomenon of herding typically observed in asset management be transposed to SCM in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic?"

The pandemic created a perfect storm of conditions conducive to herding behavior: extreme uncertainty, asymmetric information, low-quality data, and intense decision-making pressure (Bikhchandani & Sharma, 2000). These conditions, coupled with the unparalleled disruption to global supply chains, necessitated swift strategic decision-making among SCM executives. This study utilizes a qualitative methodology, including semi-structured interviews with top-level supply chain executives in the European automotive industry, to examine whether these conditions fostered behaviors analogous to herding.

Research Philosophy and Approach

Adopting an interpretivist research philosophy, this study prioritizes the subjective meanings that decision-makers assign to their actions (Schwandt, 1994). Interpretivism aligns with the objective of understanding the lived experiences of supply chain managers during the crisis, allowing for a deeper exploration of the behavioral and contextual factors influencing decision-making. The qualitative approach further supports this objective by focusing on non-numerical, context-rich data (Fossey et al., 2002). This approach was particularly relevant given the study's goal of identifying nuanced decision-making behaviors that may not be evident through quantitative data alone, as seen in prior research on herding within asset management (Spyrou, 2013).

Methodology and Sampling Strategy

A case study design was employed to contextualize herding within SCM during the pandemic (Stake, 1995). Data were collected through semi-structured interviews with eight supply chain executives from European automotive companies. Purposive sampling ensured the inclusion of participants with extensive experience in managing SCM challenges during COVID-19. Selection criteria required executives to have held their positions for at least six years, providing both pre-pandemic and pandemic perspectives. Furthermore, participants were drawn exclusively from final manufacturers within the automotive industry to maintain focus and consistency, avoiding variability introduced by cross-industry comparisons (Pujawan & Bah, 2021). Snowball sampling and direct outreach facilitated participant recruitment, emphasizing voluntary participation and confidentiality (Arifin, 2018).

Data Collection and Analysis

Semi-structured interviews allowed for a balance between consistency and flexibility, enabling the researcher to probe deeper into participants' experiences. Interviews explored themes such as the drivers of decision-making during the pandemic, observed patterns of behavior, and explicit accounts of herding. Interviews were conducted via Microsoft Teams to ensure uniformity, and recordings were transcribed in a summarized format to address participant privacy concerns (Archibald et al., 2019). Summaries were shared with participants for validation to minimize researcher bias and ensure accurate representation of their narratives (Probst & Berenson, 2014).

Data were analyzed using thematic analysis, following Braun and Clarke's six-step model (Braun & Clarke, 2013). This method enabled the systematic identification and interpretation of patterns in the data, grounded in an inductive coding process. Themes such as decision uniformity, reliance on external signals, and reputational concerns emerged as indicators of herding behavior within SCM. Coding was conducted using MAXQDA 24 software to organize data and facilitate pattern recognition.

Findings and Discussion

The findings reveal strong behavioral parallels between herding in asset management and decision-making in SCM during the pandemic. Key characteristics of herding, including diminished confidence in private information, uniformity in strategic decisions, and observable information cascades, were evident. Participants reported adopting localization strategies, diversifying suppliers, and mimicking industry trends in response to perceived actions of peers. For instance, executives cited the widespread push toward nearshoring and supplier diversification, even in cases where these strategies did not align with their company's unique needs or empirical data. These behaviors align with intentional herding, where actions are guided by the assumption that others possess superior information or analytic capabilities (Bikhchandani et al., 1992).

Reputational herding emerged as a significant driver. Executives expressed concerns about appearing inactive or indecisive in the face of stakeholder scrutiny, leading them to emulate competitors' strategies to maintain credibility. This aligns with research in asset management, where reputational pressures amplify herding during crises (Popescu & Xu, 2014). Participants also acknowledged the role of information cascades, describing how early decisions by influential market players shaped industry-wide responses. This phenomenon was particularly pronounced in the context of localization, where prominent firms' publicized shifts toward nearshoring influenced others to follow suit, even in the absence of clear cost-benefit analyses.

The study also highlights the contextual factors unique to SCM that influence herding. Unlike asset management, where decisions and outcomes are closely aligned, SCM decisions often involve temporal disconnects, further complicating the identification of causality. Despite these differences, the core behavioral mechanisms underlying herding—such as reliance on social proof and the aversion to deviating from consensus—remain consistent across contexts.

Implications for Theory and Practice

This research contributes to academic discourse by demonstrating that herding is not confined to financial markets but can manifest in operational contexts under similar environmental conditions. By identifying herding behaviors in SCM, the study extends the applicability of behavioral theories to new domains, suggesting that existing decision-making models should account for these biases to better reflect real-world practices.

Practically, the findings underscore the need for training programs to help supply chain managers recognize and mitigate herding tendencies. Developing critical thinking and evidence-based decision-making skills could reduce reliance on mimetic behaviors, enabling managers to devise strategies tailored to their organizations' unique circumstances. Furthermore, scenario-based contingency planning could help firms navigate future crises more effectively, minimizing the adverse effects of herding on market stability and organizational performance.

Conclusion

The transposition of herding from asset management to SCM underscores the universality of behavioral biases in decision-making under uncertainty. By examining the pandemic's impact on supply chains, this study provides valuable insights into how crises shape organizational behavior, highlighting the need for interdisciplinary approaches to understanding complex phenomena. These findings pave the way for future research to explore the drivers and consequences of herding in other operational contexts, contributing to the broader effort to enhance resilience and adaptability in global supply chains.

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Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience, 6. Outsourcing, offshoring, reshoring, 15. PSM theory, methodology, education

Procurement Marketplaces - Panacea or Problem for meeting the Buyer-Provider ecosystem challenge

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Introduction

Procurement marketplaces rose to prominence initially in the 2000s as a catalogue-based efficiency enhancing approach to the buying and selling challenge between the public sector and potential providers. Governments and public sector organizations began exploring the capabilities of e-procurement systems while scholars reflected on what was driving the uptake of e-procurement tools and practices ([Allen et al., 2001](#); [MacManus, 2002](#); [Moon, 2002, 2005](#); [Neef, 2001](#)). Technological advancement promised the automation of rudimentary tasks and the streamlining of procurement processes.

In order to realize the full potential of e-procurement and e-marketplaces, there were many obstacles. Technological infrastructure was lacking, and organizations were constrained by inadequate technological resources ([Bulut and Yen, 2013](#); [Vaidya et al., 2006](#)). Basic requirements such as high-speed internet connectivity and compatible hardware and software systems had yet to become ubiquitous. The technology infrastructure was a problem but also organizational inertia, marked by a resistance to change ([Brandon-Jones and Kauppi, 2018](#); [Croom and Brandon-Jones, 2005](#)). Procurement operations in the public sector were manual and repetitive but certain, and as a result, staff members accustomed to these processes were often skeptical and even resistant to the technological innovations presented by digital procurement ([Henriksen and Mahnke, 2005](#)). This internal inertia would require technological adaptation and a cultural shift within organizations. Protecting sensitive data and concerns about unauthorized access and data breaches were issues from the outset and have grown substantially with the evolution of AI; the robustness of these systems has always been problematic and have impacted the perceived benefits of digital procurement ([Gani and Fernando, 2021](#); [Vaidyanathan et al., 2012](#)).

Many aspects of the human element have been studied, such as a lack of necessary digital skills and expertise among public sector procurement professionals ([MacManus, 2002](#); [Vaidya et al., 2006](#)). While the technology was advancing rapidly, there was often a skills gap among those responsible for its implementation. In the public sector, procurement officers and other professionals had to quickly adapt

to new tools and methods, a challenge that was approached with targeted training and development programs ([Williams and Hardy, 2007](#)).

Developing marketplaces around the world have had significant scholarly interest as technological solutions to the problems SMEs face when attempting to win business from the public sector ([Allal-Chérif and Babai, 2012](#); [Escobar, 2008](#)). The hope was marketplaces improve tendering capabilities ([Flynn, 2017](#)) and may counter entrenched networks ([Bates, 2001](#)). More recently the adoption of innovative technologies such as blockchain is having influence with respect to consumer trust and transparency in transactions, especially noticeable in tightly connected, closed-loop supply chains ([Ma et al., 2024](#)).

For SMEs aiming to compete in digital economies, having presence in online marketplaces can enhance their visibility and reach buyers, such as government organizations, buyers that could be critical to their success ([Dallocchio, 2024](#); [Nugroho, 2024](#)). SMEs can avoid huge outlays in sales platforms by using marketplaces which may have a role in democratizing access to wider markets ([Purwanto, 2024](#)). Creating loyalty and trust between buyers and sellers may lead to repeat contracts for those organizations able to establish themselves through the marketplace ([Ellitan, 2024](#); [Wen, 2024](#)). For the public sector buyer trust enables faster and more efficient deployment of mechanisms that can accomplish policy objectives.

From a central governmental agency perspective, marketplaces seem to improve the overall procurement process as they generally involve pre-qualification leading to potential shorter secondary processes. At least theoretically, leveraging data analytics, agencies may be able to gain insights into their SME supplier procurement practices, which may in turn lead to improved supplier selection and contract management. However, in an e-procurement marketplace, this is only if SMEs are capable of using the marketplace. We know that e-marketplaces tend to under-emphasize the nature of the public buyer and the characteristics of the traded goods and services in terms of the number of awarded contracts to SMEs ([Albano et al., 2015](#)). Lack of marketplaces can have huge negative consequences in times of crisis, where established suppliers are not easily accessible and new suppliers impossible to reach in a short time frame ([Cohen and Rodgers, 2020](#)).

Approach and Research Strategy

The motivation for this paper stems from the lack of evaluation and understanding with respect to public sector e-procurement platforms and whether they are meeting their policy objectives, as well as the public management questions as to whether they are efficient and effective mechanisms in and of themselves.

Consequently, this research explores the performance of the New Zealand public sector e-marketplace against its objectives to link businesses that offer services and products with government agencies that wish to buy them. To this point, we are using e-procurement marketplaces, marketplaces, digital platforms, e-commerce, e-enabled procurement, and the many titles and concepts scattered across the literature, interchangeably. Part of the work will involve identifying and carefully defining our main construct supported by the literature. The mechanism being explored 'is' clear for the purposes of moving forward - the New Zealand government's Pae Hokohoko-Marketplace. In due course we aim to compare New Zealand's marketplace with other systems such as the Australian Digital Marketplace and the United Kingdom Digital Marketplace, and/or other appropriate systems.

The fundamental theoretical question is whether e-marketplaces reduce transaction cost complexity making e-marketplaces effective for both the public sector purchaser and the private sector provider. Transaction cost-based theory underpins the key foundations of e-marketplaces, by reducing the cost and time resource involved in the procurement process, public sector efficiency and value-for-money will be improved. An adapted transaction cost approach drawing on Schmidt and Wagner (2019) provides the framework for analysis. As Coase (1937), Williamson (1975) and others laid out the foundational ideas, the theory came to be well established in purchasing, supply management, and operations scholarly research (Ellram *et al.*, 2008; Grover and Malhotra, 2003; Herold *et al.*, 2022; Wynstra *et al.*, 2018). In the cross-over with public policy, public economics and public management there is also much scholarly work (Ancarani *et al.*, 2019; Chen and Thurmaier, 2008; Parker and Hartley, 2003; Prasad and Shivarajan, 2015; Tan and Zhao, 2021). The assumptions in this model, of bounded rationality and opportunism, loom large with respect to arguments for e-marketplaces. The factors of asset specificity, transaction frequency, environmental uncertainty and behavioural uncertainty point the way to understanding whether transaction costs determine whether the governance costs and structure - relatedly the policies and mechanisms - make marketplaces worthwhile efforts to accomplish public objectives.

Data collection and expected findings

This is a two-part empirical study utilizing a survey of SMEs that are on the NZ marketplace to establish their own experiences of use of the platform, and secondly a series of interviews with firms who agree to talk further about their experience. There are approximately 400 businesses on the marketplace. We expect the survey response rate to be typical of business surveys (10-30%), so a single survey instrument will not be enough to establish reliability or lack of bias. We will use a number of mechanisms to address the low response rate (Shiyab *et al.*, 2023). In the New Zealand environment, with a small market, personal connections are often far more useful, thus both through identification in the survey, and through personal connections, we will interview organizational representatives to create a full picture of the marketplace system, including interviews of government officials where possible.

While this will be a small study in compared to what could be gathered in other jurisdictions (such as the UK or the US), New Zealand is often viewed as a 'social laboratory' for the world (Allen, 2021; Berman and Karacaoglu, 2020; Boston, 1996; Boston and Gill, 2017) and thus can provide an important and interesting example. The overall study ultimately aims to contribute to the international literature on procurement platforms and their role in enhancing and ensuring accountability in public spending. We also intend to contribute to the important literature on the relationships between SMEs and government in the procurement space - which looks beyond efficiency to the possibility of improving environmental performance and enhancing broader outcomes.

Note: Full reference list available, but will not fit in the 1500 words

Paper topic

3. Purchasing organisation, 11. Digital, 13. Public procurement

A systematic literature review of the use of AI in negotiation activities

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Summary

This systematic literature review explores how Artificial Intelligence has been used in the activities and processes of negotiation activities within the Purchasing and Supply Management field. AI technologies, such as machine learning and natural language processing, enhance efficiency and decision-making in supplier selection, demand forecasting, and contract management. The review identifies key trends, including predictive models, human-AI interaction, ethical considerations, and the integration of AI with other technologies like IoT and Blockchain. Despite significant advancements, the review highlights the need for further empirical studies and ethical considerations to fully leverage AI's potential in PSM negotiations.

Keywords: Negotiation, artificial intelligence systematic literature review, multidisciplinary

Submission category: Working Paper

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a concept dates from 1955 with the definition of the scientific procedures of machine learning as a simple theory of human intelligence being exhibited by machines (Bina, 2018) and involves the computerisation of intelligence to perform human tasks, make decisions and solve problems (Broussard et al., 2019). Although the field lacks a fully agreed-upon definition, AI can be seen as a: "...collective term for applications that can solve tasks which previously required human intervention (Zhang and Lu, 2021). AI technologies can now evaluate large data sets, make online purchase recommendations and detect fraud (Helm et al., 2020) and its usage can now be seen in a wide range of operational processes, often functioning behind the scenes.

The integration of AI in Purchasing and Supply Management (PSM) has started to gather significant attention in recent years. AI technologies, including machine learning, natural language processing, and robotics, have the potential to revolutionise PSM by enhancing efficiency, accuracy, and decision-making

capabilities. The adoption of AI in these areas can lead to improved supplier selection, demand forecasting, inventory management, and contract management. In addition, the use of AI in negotiation activities, i.e., when individuals, acting as representatives of buying and selling organisations, negotiate to match supply and demand factors to achieve their objectives, is a growing area of industrial focus. However, despite a growing body of research, there remains a need for a systematic review to consolidate findings and identify areas that require further investigation. Therefore, this systematic and multidisciplinary literature review, which follows the methodology developed by Denyer and Tranfield et al. (2009), aims to synthesise existing research on the application of AI in negotiation activities to identify current trends and areas of focus, as well as to highlight possible research gaps in the literature.

Methodology

The methodology of this paper follows the often-used approach of Tranfield et al. (2003), which involves a structured approach to identify, evaluate, and synthesise the relevant research on negotiation tactics. A full discussion of the different stages will be shown in the full paper, but in summary:

1. An over-arching research question was developed as follows: “What are the trends and activities that have been identified by the extant literature in researching into the application of AI in a negotiation context?”
2. A search of the Web of Science database using the search terms "artificial intelligence" OR "machine learning" OR "deep learning" OR "neural network" OR "natural language process" AND "negotiation" in the abstracts of English language papers from 2014-2024 (to reflect the rapid technological development of the field) identified 331 papers. As the purpose of this research is multidisciplinary in nature, all papers in this set were reviewed and confirmed as being relevant for the study aims. As noted by Subramanian and Gunasekaran (2015), using a previous medical study from Guo et al. (2004), a sample size of 100 has less than a 5% margin of error at a 95% confidence interval and this is above that figure.
3. The papers were extracted into an Excel spreadsheet and the following descriptive characteristics were identified and then collated: a. trajectory of research b. academic field of study. The key AI-driven negotiation activities were then identified and grouped into thematically-based areas.

Initial Findings

Trajectory of the extant research

As expected with the introduction of new technologies, the research on the use of AI in negotiation activities and processes has increased significantly within the last decade.

Field of study

An analysis of the publication titles (i.e., journal or conference) was undertaken to establish the number of papers that were from sources outside of the “traditional” Operations and Supply Chain Management boundaries. This figure was 97% which shows that there is considerable work being undertaken in other fields that could be used by PSM researchers. In addition, the percentage of conference/symposium/meeting papers was calculated, with this being 20%, which suggests that there are opportunities for more journal papers.

Thematic analysis

An initial set of themes have emerged as follows from the analysis of the papers and these will be explored more fully in the full paper:

1. The use of predictive models to predict negotiation outcomes more effectively, as well as hybrid models that combine expert knowledge with machine learning and also how these compare to other models such as linear regression and decision trees. These can analyse large datasets from past negotiations to predict future outcomes and identify patterns that can inform negotiation strategies. The real-time analysis of large datasets from past negotiations can also be used to predict future outcomes and identify patterns that can inform negotiation strategies.
2. Understanding human emotions and behaviours during negotiations to improve the interaction between humans and AI agents.
3. Ethical and social considerations associated with the minimisation of biases and enhance fairness in decision-making and also ensuring that the use of AI systems in negotiations is transparent and their decisions are explainable to human users.
4. How AI can be integrated with other technologies such as the Internet of Things and Blockchain to enhance negotiation processes, particularly in decentralised environments.
5. Affective AI systems that recognise and respond to human emotions during negotiations and can analyse facial expressions, voice tones, and body language to better understand the emotional state of the negotiators and therefore adapt their negotiation strategies based on the detected emotions of their human counterparts to create more favourable outcomes.
6. Personalisation and adaptation through the use of customised and tailored negotiation strategies that relate to individual preferences and past behaviours and aim to make the negotiation process more efficient and effective.
7. AI systems are being developed to handle negotiations involving the complexity of multiple parties, each with their own interests and objectives and ensure that all voices are heard and that agreements are reached efficiently.

Conclusions

This systematic literature review highlights the significant potential of AI in transforming PSM, i.e., Business-to-Business/buyer-supplier, negotiation. While the existing research provides valuable insights, there are notable gaps that need to be addressed. Future research should focus on empirical studies, long-term impacts, and ethical considerations to fully understand and leverage the benefits of AI in these domains.

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Paper topic

7. Negotiation and contracting, 11. Digital, 10. Purchasing innovation

The Supplier Side of Private Label Manufacturing: Exploring Transactional Costs and Conflicts

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The Supplier Side of Private Label Manufacturing: Exploring Transactional Costs and Conflicts

Summary

Private branding, also known as private label or store brand, refers to products that are entirely owned, controlled, and exclusively sold by the retailer (Ailawadi & Keller, 2004). Therefore, this study's purpose is to scrutinize the complex mechanisms of transaction costs and conflicts involved within private label networks, especially in supplier-retailer dynamics.

The research adopts the views of Transaction Cost Economics (TCE) (Williamson, 1985) and Conflict Theory (Rosenberg & Stern, 1970). Existing studies often adopt a retailer-centric perspective, frequently overlooking suppliers' transaction costs and viewpoints. This study aims to highlight suppliers' hidden costs in transactions, related conflicts, and motivations for engaging in private manufacturing.

Keywords: *Private Label Manufacturing, Transaction Cost Economics, Conflict Theory,*

Supplier & Retailer Dynamics, Conflicts

Submission category: Working Paper (WP)

Theoretical Background

Transaction cost theory provides a valuable framework for understanding the economic rationale behind private branding and how retailers can mitigate transaction costs to improve their profitability and competitiveness (Semeijn et al., 2004; Williamson, 1985). Private branding allows retailers to exercise more control over supply chains with better coordination; hence, transactional inefficiencies can be minimized (Ailawadi & Farris, 2017).

Meanwhile, such private branding would mean compliance with transaction costs, quality control, and reduced operational flexibility for suppliers (Banterle & Stranieri, 2013). Complementary to TCE, Conflict Theory describes how these power asymmetries and the interests of retailers and suppliers can be a source of conflict regarding prices, resources, or supply chain governance (Rosenberg & Stern, 1970). Since retailers and suppliers may have different goals, interests, or viewpoints (Argüelles, and Álvarez-González, 2005), the transactional expenses associated with the private label production process may give rise to disputes between suppliers and retailers (Herstein et al., 2017).

Method

Case studies are designed to explore new or poorly understood phenomena (Hartley, 1994). This study aims to shed light on private branding conflicts stemming from incurred transaction costs, an area that has been largely undervalued. In this regard, a case study approach was employed using semi-structured expert interviews with senior managers and owners of 8 private-label supplier firms in different sectors such as cosmetics, cleaning products, and aerosols. Due to having a specific focus, we utilized snowball sampling for the data-gathering process. Sampling continued until data saturation was reached.

Moreover, as secondary data sources, we reviewed industry reports, company documents, and invoices to elaborate more on the phenomenon. The analysis incorporated abductive reasoning and dynamic coding to explore and enhance the theoretical underpinnings of the phenomenon through theory matching (Kovács, and Spens, 2005), with themes emerging iteratively and grounded in empirical evidence. Initially, we developed a provisional coding framework based on our research questions and theoretical background. Then, we continuously updated our codes to reflect the nuances and complexities of the data.

Findings

By identifying and categorizing the transactional costs borne by suppliers, this study sheds light on suppliers' economic and operational challenges in private branding networks. Findings indicated several reasons motivating suppliers towards private label production: the ability to guarantee bulk sales, decreased operational costs, easier regulatory compliance, and access to new sales channels. Such motives make apparent the economic benefits of private branding, such as enhanced capacity utilization and reduced marketing expenses. These benefits, however, could be impeded by significant challenges, transactional costs, and conflicts.

The findings show that transactional costs lead to conflicts between suppliers and retailers. For suppliers, the most relevant upfront costs are those incurred for monitoring, enforcing, transferring, and switching, which mostly result from contract management, quality assurance, and retailer requirements (Semeijn et al., 2004). They include monitoring expenses on certification and audits.

Such costs directly breed operational conflicts over inventory standards and production standards. Transfer costs ranging from warehousing to transportation, and inventory management contribute to operational conflicts whenever these logistical inefficiencies and delays disrupt production planning or inventory flow. These issues often lead to serious economic conflicts, particularly when material wastage happens during unsold or expired materials, or when unmet demand causes financial stress for both suppliers and retailers. Non-compliance penalty enforcement costs lead to economic conflicts over profit sharing and price disputes (Herstein et al., 2017). Switching costs, mostly caused by such transitions between suppliers, lead to relational conflicts through their disturbance to trust and collaboration (Blut et al., 2016). Therefore, there arises a need for these costs to be brought forward in strategic interventions aimed at reducing power asymmetries and aligning supplier-retailer objectives.

Implications

Insights from Transaction Cost Economics and Conflict Theory provide a holistic understanding and management framework for supplier-retailer dynamics. This study expands TCE with the argument that asset specificity, such as a customized packaging investment, increases enforcement costs and creates new vulnerabilities to opportunism at retail (Williamson, 1985). Conflict Theory extends to defining disputes in economic, operational, and relational terms, enhancing the understanding of how power asymmetries and misaligned goals deepen tension in the supplier-retailer dynamic (Rosenberg & Stern, 1970). These insights show that conflicts have an uncanny ability to act as triggers for innovation or realigning strategy, pointing to the functionality. Hence, this perspective challenges us to further nuance our understanding of the contradictory image of conflicts as both barriers and new opportunities in supply chain management.

The study also brings practical lessons to practitioners about dealing with the complexities of private label production. Proactive conflict resolution mechanisms, such as increasing transparency and aligning long-range goals, and cooperation forecasting models are crucial for minimizing disputes (Anderson & Narus, 1990). The digital tools could also hasten monitoring and enforcement activity and reduce transaction inefficiencies while increasing operational efficiency (Banterle & Stranieri, 2013). The findings also highlight the importance of developing collaborative partnerships built on mutual trust and equitable power relationships. Such partnerships maximize mutual benefits and minimize the risks associated with transactional inefficiencies and conflicts. Establishing trust grounds in partnerships and a fair power balance may also contribute to the steadying and profit-making relationship between supplier and retailer. Lastly, findings indicate that suppliers focusing on differentiation, offer greater potential for innovation, higher margins, and a reduced likelihood of conflict.

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Paper topic

6. Outsourcing, offshoring, reshoring, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

EU-ESG Legislation: Purchasing with CS3D

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

EU-ESG Legislation: Purchasing with CS3D

Summary: This paper examines the transition to the EU's new Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CS3D) focusing on procurement. It highlights the shift from voluntary corporate social responsibility (CSR) to legally mandated environmental, social, and governance (ESG) obligations. The forthcoming CS3D includes climate risks, data accuracy, and stakeholder collaboration, significantly increasing compliance demands. Consequently, procurement departments will face challenges in managing extensive reporting, ensuring data accuracy, fostering supplier partnerships, etc. This research explores the CS3D's implications for procurement amid evolving sustainability, human rights, labour, and compliance responsibilities.

Keywords: Corporate Governance; Due Diligence; Sustainable Procurement; Supply Chain Transparency; Regulatory Compliance.

Main body of text:

Introduction:

Situation: In 2021, European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen stated, "*Doing business around the world,, global trade – all that is good and necessary. But this can never be done at the expense of people's dignity and freedom. (...) So we will propose a ban on products in our market that*

have been made by forced labour. Human rights are not for sale – at any price" (European Commission, 2021). This statement reflects the EU's long-standing commitment to advancing sustainability, human rights, and labour standards globally. Initiatives like the Green Deal and numerous EU policies promoting decent work globally by addressing the worldwide supply chains through the inclusion of due diligence obligations, social disclosure standards, and provisions for transparency and information on product sustainability to enable consumers to make informed choices highlight this commitment (European Commission, 2022). The Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CS3D) embodies another intra-European policy effort, imposing ESG requirements on companies with EU-based supply chains.

Complication: Unlike preceding voluntary or country-specific measures, the CS3D standardises ESG obligations across the EU, applying to companies worldwide, and certain elements of the downstream supply chain, addressing not only environmental standards but also social issues such as forced labour and governance reforms (Rendtorff, 2024). These extensive requirements present novel compliance challenges and engender queries regarding their operational impact.

Question: What implications do these developments have for procurement? In what ways must procurement teams modify their practices to meet CS3D obligations?

Answer: This paper provides an overview of the CS3D, focussing on its ESG framework and procurement implications. It examines the ways in which procurement departments can navigate these requirements, balance compliance with operational efficiency, and support sustainability goals.

The CS3D as a Purchasing Requirement

Expanding Regulatory ESG Obligations

As indicated, the CS3D represents a significant change in the regulatory ESG framework for companies operating in the EU and beyond (Komba et al., 2023). The Directive, negotiated for transposition into the national laws of EU Member States (cf. Art. 288 TFEU), applies to both EU and non-EU companies with significant EU-based operations, whereby for non-EU companies, a substantial portion of their turnover must be generated within the Union (cf. Art. 2 CS3D). The CS3D entered into force on 25 July 2024, marking a new era of corporate accountability and transparency.

Nevertheless, the Directive is not entirely new in legally targeting supply chain transparency; it builds on existing frameworks adopted with varying degrees of intensity by some EU Member States. Germany's *Lieferkettensorgfaltspflichtgesetz* and France's 2017 *Loi de Vigilance* are examples of national legislation addressing human rights and environmental standards in supply chains (Godt, 2023).

However, the CS3D significantly expands these obligations by incorporating climate risks, data accuracy, and collaboration into its compliance structure (cf. Art. 17, 19, 20, 28(3) CS3D).

Environmental Compliance: Supporting the 1.5°C Goal

A key aspect of the CS3D is its alignment with environmental regulations aimed at supporting the global goal of limiting temperature increases to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels (Feigerlovd, 2024). The preamble of the CS3D outlines the requirement for companies to meet minimum environmental standards throughout their supply chains, increasing transparency in sustainability reporting to meet, especially, Paris Agreement goals on climate change, resource scarcity, and biodiversity loss (cf. Recital 10 following CS3D). By prioritising sustainable practices, CS3D mandates companies to decarbonise their supply chains, which typically account for the majority of greenhouse gas emissions (Bodie, 2024).

Social Requirements: Respect for Human Rights

Additionally, the CS3D places significant emphasis on social requirements, including the protection of human rights due diligence as set out, for example, in the MNE Guidelines and the UN Guiding Principles (cf. Recital 4 following CS3D). Companies are required to conduct due diligence on human rights standards in their supply chains, extending beyond first-tier suppliers to all levels (Velluti, 2024). This extension requires a comprehensive approach to monitoring and addressing potential human rights abuses globally. CS3D therefore advocates for collaboration with suppliers to address underlying risks, rather than simply checking compliance, which aims to create synergy between public authorities and private entities, recognising sustainability – including human rights, environmental, and climate considerations – requires the active participation of all market players (Ruggeri, 2024).

Governance: Restructuring for Accountability

The CS3D also calls for changes in governance structures to ensure accountability and effective implementation of its requirements (cf. Recital 6 following CS3D). Companies are expected to integrate sustainability considerations into their corporate governance frameworks, aligning business strategies with environmental and social objectives, potentially leading to a "more inclusive trade" environment (Velluti, 2024). This may involve restructuring corporate governance models to facilitate better oversight and decision-making processes related to sustainability initiatives.

Enforcement Mechanisms

To ensure compliance, the CS3D includes several enforcement mechanisms to hold companies accountable. For example, according to Article 24 CS3D, each Member State shall designate one or more supervisory authorities to monitor compliance with the provisions of the CS3D. Other mechanisms may include penalties for non-compliance or incentives for those who demonstrate leadership in sustainable

practices (Lafarre, 2023). These enforcement mechanisms highlight the Directive's emphasis on synergy between public authorities and private entities in achieving sustainable development goals (Ruggeri, 2024).

Procurement Implications

For those tasked with the procurement of goods and services, the introduction of CS3D presents both challenges and opportunities. As companies navigate this evolving regulatory landscape, procurement professionals must balance compliance with operational efficiency amidst increasing demands for sustainability-driven strategies. Procurement departments play a critical role as the first point of contact with suppliers and are responsible for ensuring that supply chain partners comply with environmental and social standards.

Especially for German-based companies, the transition from LkSG to CS3D represents a paradigm shift that is intertwined with existing policies such as the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) and other domestic laws. CS3D introduces a requirement to consult with suppliers – a departure from previous compliance-focused approaches under the LkSG. In accordance with LkSG, the responsibility was already incumbent upon them to ensure that first-tier suppliers complied with human rights and environmental standards. Consequently, they are now required to extend their oversight beyond first-tier suppliers to encompass climate-related risks across all levels of the supply chain.

Consequently, companies are encouraged to work with suppliers to develop action plans that promote sustainable practices, while actively monitoring improvements over time. Procurement teams will need to allocate additional time, resources, expertise and potentially new technologies such as AI to effectively manage the associated risks at all levels of the supply chain.

Summarised, procurement departments are at a crossroad as they adapt to the CS3D. By proactively embracing the changes connected to the CS3D – balancing compliance requirements with strategic objectives – they can make a significant contribution to achieving long-term sustainability goals while supporting overall business success in an increasingly complex global market environment.

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Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social, 21. Special track: Regulations in shaping sustainable ecosystem change

Quantifying green levers

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The paper introduces "green levers," a systematic tool designed to enhance sustainability in supply chains while reducing costs. Using design science methodology, the research identifies 39 green sourcing tactics through world cafés, interviews, and case studies across multiple countries and industries. A survey with 204 participants yielded a prioritisation of the most feasible levers. These levers integrate sustainability goals into purchasing strategies, addressing the tension between environmental compliance and cost efficiency. Pilot applications in logistics and manufacturing achieved significant cost savings (up to 12%) and reduced environmental impacts. The paper highlights the feasibility of harmonizing sustainability and profitability, supporting the Porter Hypothesis, and provides actionable insights for sustainable supply chain management.

Paper topic

4. Category management, 16. Sustainability - environmental

The Role of Supply Chain Digitalisation in Achieving Operational Excellence and Supplier Satisfaction - A pre and post intervention-based quasi experiment

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

Emerging technologies have driven supply chains to be more digitalised than ever before. Digital technologies such as IOT, cloud computing, block chain, big data, and many others have shown positive improvements in supply chain performance through increased efficiency and transparency achieved in cooperation with supply chain partners. This study analyses how such technologies contribute to improvements in supply chain relationships, focusing on metrics of operational excellence, including forecast, ordering process, quality of process, and payment, as well as the level of satisfaction among suppliers using such digital systems. This study analyses survey data collected over a period of two years, with 291 responses collected prior to and 204 responses collected after the introduction of a digital supply chain collaboration tool from suppliers of a focal firm to assess the effectiveness of digitalisation initiatives. Findings suggest that digitalising the supply chain not only improves several metrics of operational excellence, but also contributes towards maintaining the supplier satisfaction level. These findings highlight the essential role of digital supply chain transformation in improving supplier relationships and offer valuable insights for practitioners aiming to enhance their operational strategies. This study is the first to examine the impact of supply chain digitalisation on different metrics of operational excellence and supplier satisfaction using a pre- and post-intervention quasi-experimental approach in a field context.

Paper topic

11. Digital, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 2. PSM strategy

159

Sustainable procurement: An exploratory study of the importance to purchasing agents of their privately held and publicly traded suppliers' corporate social responsibility practices.

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Summary

This study examines purchasing agents perceptions of their suppliers corporate social responsibility (CSR) practices when making procurement decisions in business-to-business (B2B) exchanges. The theoretical framework centers on transaction costs, which are known to decrease with supplier trust. A total of 79 experienced purchasing agents employed by privately held and publicly traded firms were surveyed. This study reveals a strong correlation between the importance a purchasing agent assigns to a supplier's corporate social responsibility record and the purchasing agents perceptions that the supplier is trustworthy. This study also reveals, however, that a suppliers' willingness to provide its CSR record (i.e., to be transparent) has no effect on the correlation between a supplier firm's CSR record and trustworthiness, raising questions about what drives a purchasing agent's perceptions. Quotations that lend insight to the respondents position on the importance of sustainable procurement are provided, as well as how they assess supplier practices.

Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social, 2. PSM strategy

I'm not rude, I'm Dutch. The influence of cultural dimensions on the perception of opportunistic behavior in strategic buyer-supplier relationships

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Practitioner Paper

Abstract/summary

With globalization and intercultural collaboration, business relationships are increasingly influenced by cultural differences. These differences can present in international business contexts in varying ways (e.g., communication styles), and can lead to misunderstandings due to varying cultural perceptions (Meyer, 2014; Ribbink, 2010; Weiss, 2006). This is especially true in buyer-supplier relationships across national borders (Murphy, Gölgeci & Johnston, 2020). Globalization has increased the complexity of supply chains, which confronts organizations with cultural challenges in their relationships (Gong and Zhang, 2011; Hsuan et al., 2007).

In strategic buyer-supplier relationships where cooperation is based on trust and commitment, parties cannot afford to behave opportunistically (Gelderman et al., 2020). Opportunism implies a choice of self-interest *with guile* at the expense of the partner (Williamson, 1975). Such opportunistic pursuit of self-interest at the expense of the partner can be detrimental to cooperation, as strategic cooperation requires mutual dependence and a balance of power (Gelderman et al., 2021; Raassens et al., 2012). However, opportunism is a socially-constructed concept, and is hence open to interpretation as to when an incidence is considered "opportunistic", which cultural has the potential to influence (Williamson, 1993; Chen et al., 2002; Gelderman et al., 2020). For example, what is perceived as an opportunistic incident in one context or culture, might be considered of as a normal practice from another cultural perspective. However, little empirical evidence exists to demonstrate how this manifests in the perception of opportunism in buyer-supplier relationships (Ribbink et al., 2014; Skowronski et al., 2022).

To fill this gap, in this research we consider how Hofstede's 6-D model on cultural dimensions influence the perception of opportunistic behavior in buyer-supplier relationships. Hofstede's model is one of the most widely applied and studied models to examine cultural differences (Beugelsdijk et al., 2017), and has been widely used to examine the role of culture within management-related issues (Griffith et al., 2021). The 6-D model offers insight into different cultural values and norms that may influence the behavior of individuals in different societies. The six dimensions include: 1) power distance, 2)

individualism versus collectivism, 3) masculinity versus femininity, 4) uncertainty avoidance, 5) long-term versus short-term orientation, and 6) permissiveness versus restraint (Hofstede, 1980). These cultural dimensions are relevant to understanding how culture and trust can influence opportunistic behavior, especially in the context of international business relationships (Chen et al., 2002; Ribbink, 2010; Ketkar et al., 2012; Hadley & Angst, 2015).

To further our understanding of the influence of culture on whether incidences are perceived as opportunistic in international buyer-supplier relationships, an inductive, qualitative approach was applied. Such an approach is particularly suited to explore the contextual nature of business relationships and the complexity of cultural influences, as it provides a dynamic and flexible research perspective in exploring the topic and answering the research question (Lillis & Tian, 2010; Saunders et al., 2019). Extending the Critical Incident Technique (Gelderman et al., 2016, 2020; Janssens et al., 2023), hypothetical incidents were developed to evoke discussions on whether the incident is perceived as opportunistic given differing norms between cultural dimensions. Based on a purchasing portfolio approach (Caniëls and Gelderman, 2007), specific focus was set on scenarios including cases of strategic buyer-supplier relationships, as these convey specific characteristics in terms of mutual power and interdependence, that are believed to influence the negotiation process between both parties. Incidents were used as interviewing aides. Data was collected through semi-structured with interviewees involved in strategic buyer-supplier relationships with one focal international firm. A sample of interviewees were chosen to represent variation of Hofstede's cultural dimensions. The sample consisted of interviewees from China, Vietnam, the Netherlands, and Norway. Semi-structured interviews provide flexibility and depth in analyzing perceptions and experiences of procurement professionals from different cultures (Bryman, 2016; King & Horrocks, 2010). Data was analyzed using a combination of deductive and inductive methods to identify themes and categories (Schreier, 2012). This structured process ensures reliability and validity, leading to valuable insights into the influence of culture on opportunistic behavior in buyer-supplier relationships (Schreier, 2012).

The findings of this research have practical and theoretical contributions for understanding the influence of culture in the perception of opportunism in buyer-supplier relationships. The operationalization of Hofstede's cultural dimensions in buyer-supplier scenarios in this research extends the Critical Incident Technique (Gelderman et al., 2016, 2020; Janssens et al., 2023) for exploratory research involving norm transgression. These scenarios can be used to measure the strength of cultural influences in future studies. The results of this study are congruent with results of similar studies demonstrating a clear manifestation of Hofstede's cultural dimensions in international buyer-supplier contexts (Chen et al., 2002; Ribbink, 2010; Ketkar et al., 2012; Hadley & Angst, 2015). Important validity issues for future quantitative studies have been raised in our findings, including the tendency of international purchasing and supply chain professionals to represent multiple cultures (i.e., culture of origin, work culture, culture of residence, etc.). Furthering our understandings of how cultural dimensions influence the perception of norms (and norm transgression, i.e., opportunism) in international business contexts is vital to improve the ability of firms and individuals to build trust and subsequently foster strategic buyer-supplier relationships.

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Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Cultivating Accountability: Sustainability Performance Management in Alternative Food Networks

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This study explores how alternative food networks (AFNs) navigate sustainability performance management (SPM) while maintaining their transformative essence. Using a multi-case qualitative approach, the study examines 11 AFNs to unveil how they deal with the paradoxes of SPM. The findings reveal that AFNs struggle with tensions between grassroots authenticity and external legitimacy, informal governance and formal processes, and traditional knowledge and technical expertise. Rather than seeking one-size-fits-all solutions, AFNs manage paradoxes through acceptance, contextualization and resolution. Using paradox theory, the study shows how AFNs transform tensions into strategic advantages and thus contribute to the discourse on sustainable governance.

Paper topic

17. Sustainability - social, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

The Impact of the Buyer's Purchasing & R&D Involvement on the Supplier's Perception of Innovation Potential, Support and Involvement

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Research context and Hypotheses

Over the last decade, a lot of research has been conducted on preferential resource allocation of suppliers, supplier satisfaction, and their antecedents (Piechota, Glas, & Essig, 2021; Pulles, Schiele, Veldman, & Hüttinger, 2016; F. G. S. Vos, Van der Lelij, Schiele, & Praas, 2021). This is relevant, as supplier satisfaction and preferential resource allocation have a long-term strategic impact on the competitive advantage of a company (Frederik G. S. Vos, Schiele, & Hüttinger, 2016). Research already found that the perceived innovation potential, support and involvement of the buyer influence the overall satisfaction of the supplier with the relationship (Hüttinger, Schiele, & Schröer, 2014). All these antecedents also relate directly to the ability of the supplier to innovate and collaborate with the buying firm. When it comes to these types of collaborations, purchasing has a boundary spanning role by simultaneously managing the internal organization (e.g. R&D) and external environment (e.g. the suppliers) (Schmelzle & Tate, 2022). While research has been conducted on the antecedents of supplier satisfaction in different contexts, the explicit role of the purchasing function's involvement in the buyer-supplier relationship has been overlooked. Purchasing involvement in buyer-supplier relationships management has already been found to have a positive operational impact for quality, delivery, flexibility and innovation (Nair, Jayaram, & Das, 2015), as well as overall business performance measured in commercial and financial performance (González-Benito, 2007). However, how the involvement of purchasing is perceived by the suppliers, especially regarding its influence on resource allocation is not yet known. This study assesses how purchasing and R&D involvement might influence perceived innovation potential, support and involvement of the supplier.

Regarding the concepts of innovation potential, support and involvement, firstly, Innovation potential refers to the perception of "the supplier's opportunity to generate innovations in the exchange relationship due to the buying firm's innovative capabilities and its contribution in joint innovation processes (Hüttinger et al., 2014, p. 703). Secondly, support is defined as the perception the supplier has regarding the effort and assistance of a buyer to improve the supplier's performance and/or capabilities (Hüttinger et al., 2014; Krause & Ellram, 1997). Finally, involvement refers to the supplier's

perception of “degree to which the supplier’s staff participates directly in the customer’s product development team and is entrusted with developing product ideas (Hüttinger et al., 2014).

The role of R&D and purchasing in innovation projects has been discussed by multiple papers with differing results. For example, Melander and Lakemond (2014) conclude that mainly contributes by solving problems related to the supplier’s strategy, the relationship, and commitment issues. However, to solve these problems, purchasing has not to be a member of the NPD team. Furthermore, Picaud-Bello, Johnsen, Calvi, and Giannakis (2019) defines a more elaborate role for purchasing by proposing several purchasing practices to lead innovation projects. In addition, Delgado-Verde and Díez-Vial (2024) found that R&D collaboration with supporting organizations increases NPD efficiency but does not lead to effectiveness. Here, the results indicate that specific knowledge from supporting organization increases speed and reduces costs, but does not improve the commercial expectations and others aspects related to the market (Delgado-Verde & Díez-Vial, 2024). Moreover, former research has found that early purchasing involvement drives the proactivity of the purchasers leading to effectiveness measured in value creation and supply risk reduction (Van Poucke, Matthyssens, van Weele, & Van Bockhaven, 2019). Consequently, both functions (R&D and purchasing) may have different interests when it comes to managing the relation with the supplier. We study in how far the intensity of involvement of either or both functions in a buyer-supplier relationship might enhance or reduce the supplier’s perceived innovation potential, support and involvement. We hypothesize that both functions contribute to a better perception of innovation potential, support and involvement when they are engaging stronger in a specific buyer-supplier relationship.

Additionally, this study aims to assess in how far involving the two functions might lead to better goal congruence between the two, eventually also influencing the perceptions of innovation potential, support and involvement. We define goal congruence as degree to which the supplier perceives that both purchasing and R&D share the same goals and objectives in the relationship with the supplier, which is adapted from similar definitions of goal congruence for other functions (Jap, 1999; Patrucco, Moretto, Luzzini, & Glas, 2020). Hence, it refers to the degree to which the supplier thinks that both functions align with each other. In this study, goal congruence is expected to be a mediator between involvement of the two functions and innovation potential, support and involvement.

Method

The hypotheses were tested via structural equations model. For this, data was collected via a survey sent to the suppliers of a large Brazilian company. The suitability of respondents as key informants was assured by selecting only respondents with enough experience in the focal buyer-supplier relationship and knowledge on the matter. In total, 286 valid responses have been collected and, at the time of writing this abstract, data collection is still ongoing. Regarding the survey questions, most items and measurements in the model were derived from validated scales. Purchasing involvement and R&D involvement were developed and added as new scales adapting and adjusting the measures of by Song, Cadeaux, and Yu (2016) for the context of this study.

Regarding data quality, all measured showed good reliability and validity (i.e, AVE, Fornell-Larcker, composite reliability, HTMT etc.). Both the CFA and the structural model had acceptable model fit indices. We still need to assess non-response bias, common method bias, test for endogeneity etc. in future, yet the initial assessments of data look promising. We will add more quality criteria and analysis in the future, and are also planning to add control variables to the model.

Results

So, far the analysis has resulted in several interesting results. At first, when testing the model without goal congruence as a mediator, both R&D and purchasing involvement have a positive impact on innovation potential, support and involvement, hence supporting our initial hypotheses. Then, when adding goal congruence as a mediator between R&D/purchasing involvement and the three satisfaction dimensions, the results show that goal congruence is positively influenced by both purchasing, and R&D involvement. In turn, goal, congruence has a positive impact on innovation potential, support and involvement. Furthermore, it was found that innovation potential and supplier involvement has a positive effect on preferential resource allocation. However, the effect for support was not confirmed in our research.

Interestingly, although purchasing involvement still remained a positive direct influence on all three satisfaction dimensions, R&D involvement lost its direct impact on support when we added goal congruence to the model. An additional mediation test supported the finding that the R&D involvement's impact on support was significantly mediated by goal congruence. When looking at the different paths of the model, we found that the impact of purchasing involvement was structurally stronger for all relationships compared to R&D involvement.

In a nutshell, these findings support the assumption that both R&D and purchasing involvement in buyer-supplier relationships are beneficial for the supplier's perceptions of innovation potential, support and involvement, leading to preferential resource allocation. An important underlying mechanism seems to be goal congruence which has an effect on purchasing and R&D involvement as well as on the three satisfaction dimensions (i.e., innovation potential, support and involvement).

Interpretation of the findings, contributions and Future research

The intended contributions of this paper are twofold. On the one hand, this paper adds empirical insights on the consequences of purchasing involvement. To our knowledge, only Van Poucke, Matthyssens, and Weeren (2016) tested the effect of purchasing involvement on stakeholder satisfaction and found no effect of purchasing involvement on internal customers' satisfaction. However, based on the results, we argue that how purchasing involvement affects the satisfaction of the

supplier is just as crucial as the internal customers, as this influences the buyer-supplier relationship and can have long-term competitive consequences.

On the other hand, we were also able to find an underlying mechanism through which R&D and purchasing involvement increase satisfaction. Apart from the direct benefits of R&D and purchasing involvement, we expected that goal congruence might be increased by involving both, thereby also increasing preferential resource allocation. In support of this assumption, the results show that R&D and purchasing involvement do not only affect directly the three satisfaction dimensions, but also increased goal congruence and, in turn, increased innovation potential, support and involvement.

Practical implications are that purchasing involvement should be facilitated, especially when R&D is already heavily involved in a relationship, as this increases the goal congruence between the different functions regarding interactions with a supplier and improves the innovation potential, support and involvement perceived by the supplier, eventually leading to preferential resource allocation.

Regarding future research, we provide initial insights into the relevance of purchasing involvement in achieving goal alignment and motivate scholars to study in more depth the mechanisms that are underlying the positive impact of purchasing involvement of buyer-supplier relationships, for example contingencies and other performance criteria.

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 10. Purchasing innovation

Improving procurement in small to medium-sized enterprises (SMEs): a systematic literature review providing insights and trends

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

ABSTRACT (1470 words)

Improving Procurement in Small to Medium-sized Enterprises - a systematic literature Review providing Insights and Trends.

Introduction

Over the last decades, research has made great strides in procurement related to large organisations. A rough estimate is that there are 20,000+ relevant academic articles.

At the same time, publications related procurement in SMEs are limited to probably 500-1000 academic articles. However as Welsch & White stated in the Harvard Business Review: *A small business is not a little big business*. Procurement in SMEs is an under-researched domain in both procurement and SME literature. This working paper will analyse extant research on procurement improvement in SMEs.

Small to Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs)

SMEs play a vital role in the global economy. They represent over 90% of all businesses worldwide and generate over 60% of employment. They are also responsible for the Scope 3 environmental impact of many large buying organisations. Countries tend to define SMEs differently. For example within the EU, SMEs have 1–250 staff; in Canada and the US, SMEs have up to 500 staff. Other countries define SMEs as having max 20, or 50 or 100 staff. Additionally, there is some confusion about the terminology. Some authors or institutions prefer the term SME(s), others prefer terms like micro, small or medium (sized) business, company or firm. By far most of all SMEs (90%) have less than 5-10 staff. A common trait is that they are managed by the SME-owner.

Whereas large enterprises often pursue growth strategies, SME-owners generally pursue lifestyle or survival strategies. They can have a less complex of informal organisation, although some SMEs are known to have more formal organisational models.

In smaller enterprises the SME-owner will work in the company, and their personal characteristics will impact how they approach suppliers. In larger enterprises the SME-owner will organise (lead, manage) their team and the organisation. Procurement is then often the responsibility of a staff member.

Studies show that procurement in SMEs typically represents 40-80% of their total expenses, accounting for their largest single category of spending. Due to inherent limitations, SMEs depend on external resources. The quality or the importance of procurement can vary greatly across SMEs or industries. SMEs are generally scarce on specialised resources, negotiation power, and lack management skills. This generally hampers their procurement performance.

Objective and Research Questions

The objective in this study is to identify insights and trends on procurement improvement among SMEs. Hence the team defined the following research questions:

***RQ1:** What are reported types of SME procurement improvement?*

***RQ2:** What are reported effects of procurement improvement on SME performance?*

***RQ3:** What are reported key drivers and barriers for realising procurement improvement in SMEs?*

***RQ4:** What are reported key best practices, key trends, and key suggestions for further research?*

Research Design

The team conducted a systematic literature review to address the research questions. It identified three concepts: 1) procurement; 2) improvement; and 3) SMEs. For each concept it used search strings with synonyms and related words. It used the SCOPUS database, used the search strings in the title, abstract and keywords. It initially identified 1875 records published between 2000–2024. Following a PRISMA flow diagram, the team selected 181 peer-reviewed articles for further analysis.

The data were subsequently analysed using bibliometric techniques and content analysis. To reduce selector bias, the team used a double-blind approach. Furthermore, findings will be validated through expert interviews to ensure the robustness and accuracy of the results. These experts are academics selected from the 181 articles.

Analysis / Discussion of (interim) Results

RQ1: What are reported types of SME procurement improvement?

Our review identified several key strategies to improve procurement practices among SMEs. These include the use of purchasing consortiums, third-party group purchasing, and inbound supplier flexibility. Notably, a "triple A" strategy - comprising Agility, Adaptability, and Alignment - emerged as a best practice.

From the perspective of SMEs' size band, the team identified several types of procurement improvement. For example, micro and small-sized enterprises (< 50 employees) mostly use purchasing consortia and optimise their (superficial) use of ICT. Purchasing consortia help these micro or small enterprises to improve their buying power by pooling resources to obtain better pricing and terms from suppliers. The optimisation of ICT helps SMEs in their communication, knowledge sharing and supplier evaluation.

For medium-sized enterprises (50-250 employees), strategic purchasing practices can help build long-term suppliers relationships and improve overall supply chain resilience. In addition, these medium-sized enterprises also apply third-party group purchasing such as collaborating or forming non-profit organisations to manage their purchasing activities. This helps in achieving economic-of-scale, and reducing procurement costs.

In general, the types of procurement improvement can be categorised into three strategies: inbound supplier flexibility, external supplier flexibility, and cost savings through joint replenishment.

RQ2: What are reported effects of procurement improvement on SME performance?

Our initial findings highlight both positive and negative effects that SMEs may experience when improving procurement practices. The primary effect identified is costs. Several studies observed that any procurement improvement requires an initial financial investment, which can impact SMEs in the short term. Nevertheless, improvements can generate benefits in the long run, e.g. by reducing the overall expenditure on procurement.

Moreover, procurement improvements have been found to positively and proportionately influence the growth and competitiveness of SMEs. On the other hand, there is an associated risk, as these

improvements may challenge the financial stability and organisational culture of SMEs. This risk is particularly significant because changes in procurement practices can introduce uncertainties and disruptions that affect employees, the company structure, its supplier relations and its culture.

RQ3: What are reported key drivers and barriers for realising procurement improvement in SMEs?

The key drivers of procurement improvement in SMEs include technological advancements, sustainability goals, supplier collaboration, access to new markets, and meeting customer expectations. These factors encourage SMEs to adopt streamlined processes, modern tools, and sustainable practices, enhancing their growth and competitiveness.

However, SMEs face key barriers such as financial constraints, lack of expertise, resistance to change, technological challenges, supplier dependence, risk aversion, and limited resources. Overcoming these barriers can realise long-term benefits for SMEs.

RQ4: What are reported key best practices, key trends, and key suggestions for further research?

Based on our initial observations, there is a strong possibility that SMEs can leverage technological advancements to improve their procurement practices. Emerging technologies as e-procurement systems, social media platforms, generative artificial intelligence (genAI), and cloud-based platforms can help SMEs to streamline processes, improve decision-making, and increase procurement performance. By adopting these technologies, SMEs can not only reduce costs but also strengthen supplier relationships and gain a competitive edge in the market.

Additionally, the literature reveals a growing trend toward integrating sustainability into the procurement processes of SMEs. Their sustainable procurement practices focus on minimising environmental impact, promoting ethical sourcing, and adhering to social responsibility standards. This is driven by increasing awareness of environmental concerns, regulatory pressures, and customer demands for sustainable products and services. Together, these trends highlight significant opportunities for SMEs to modernise their procurement while aligning with global sustainability goals.

(Interim) conclusions

Our preliminary findings indicate a significant upward trend in this research domain, with the number of articles almost doubled over the past five years. Our research will generate findings for the industry and future research.

(Anticipated) limitations of the Research

This study is limited by its focus on search strings in the title, abstract and keywords, and by a limited number of search terms related to “improvement”. If an author used a different term, or used a term selected by the team but in the main text, this article was excluded from the corpus. The study also focused on the procurement context, although articles could discuss relevant improvements in a supply chain or customer context. Finally, also referring to the variety of SMEs, extant research that was related to a specific company or industry context may not be generalisable to other contexts.

(Anticipated) key Suggestions for the Industry

For SMEs: They could integrate sustainability into their procurement practices, considering environmentally-friendly and socially-responsible sourcing as a long-term strategy to improve their brand reputation and meet regulatory requirements.

For Suppliers of SMEs: Suppliers could provide flexible procurement options to SMEs, such as dynamic pricing, just-in-time delivery, and scalable order sizes to accommodate the unique needs of smaller enterprises.

(Anticipated) key Suggestions for further Research

Given that our findings emphasise the potential contributions of technology, particularly AI, and the critical importance of sustainability, the team recommends further in-depth investigation into these key areas. Future research could explore how these elements can be more effectively leveraged to optimise the procurement performance of SMEs.

Originality, and Contribution (Relevance) of this Research

This ongoing research aims to fill a persistent and relevant knowledge gap. It aims to identify best practices on improving procurement in SMEs, while also identifying potential future research trends.

***Key Words:** improvement; procurement; small to medium-sized enterprises; systematic literature review; expert interviews.*

Paper topic

1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 3. Purchasing organisation, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Sustainable supply chains: the microfoundation of data sharing

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Sustainable supply chains: the microfoundation of data sharing

Abstract

The global supply chain landscape faces growing pressures to enhance sustainability amidst increasing environmental, social, and governance (ESG) demands. Data sharing is a complex phenomenon that underpins the development of sustainability and the circular economy (Kristoffersen et al., 2020). Yet, data-sharing potential is frequently underutilized due to cognitive barriers. Our research adopts a micro foundation perspective (Barney and Felin, 2013) and develops a conceptual framework that explicates how information and data sharing are either hindered or facilitated within an industry context. We focus on the role of shifting mental models, which often constrain data sharing by perpetuating risk aversion, competitive secrecy, and siloed thinking, toward mental models that prioritize transparency, trust, and collaboration. Through an analysis of the garment, chemical, and automotive supply chains, we explore how individuals' cognitive schemas influence their willingness to share information, uncovering pathways for fostering sustainable transformations through the reorientation of mental models.

Keywords: data sharing, sustainability, supply chain, microfoundations

Introduction and Literature

The sustainability of supply chains is a critical issue in today's global economy, driven by mounting ESG pressures. Organizations are increasingly recognizing that sustainability requires coordination across supply chain networks. Among the most critical enablers of this coordination is data sharing, which facilitates transparency, traceability, and informed decision-making to achieve sustainability goals.

However, the potential of data sharing remains underutilized, as organizational and cognitive barriers frequently hinder its effective implementation.

This study aims to investigate the factors hindering and favoring the emergence of data sharing in supply chains. For this we adopt a microfoundation perspective (Barney & Felin, 2013), which emphasizes the role of individual and organizational-level interactions in shaping broader macro-level phenomena. The microfoundation perspective considers individual-level factors in understanding larger phenomenon by studying the relations amongst both macro and micro factors. In their review of the microfoundation perspective, Barney and Felin (2013, p. 149) suggest that it is well suited to study how information is aggregated within and across organization: *“Many questions remain about how factors such as incentives affect the identification of appropriate sources of knowledge and the aggregation of dispersed information and the evolution of capabilities.”*

This perspective led us to explore the cognitive dynamics that govern data sharing, focusing on how micro and macro factors interact to influence sustainability outcomes. By examining data-sharing initiatives in the **garment, chemical, and automotive sectors**, we explore the interplay of cognitive and systemic factors influencing data-sharing practices.

Specifically, this research seeks to answer the following questions:

1. **What data should be shared?** Identifying different types of data critical for enabling sustainable supply chains.
2. **For what purpose?** Understanding how shared data contributes to sustainability objectives.
3. **With whom?** Understanding the dynamics of inter-organizational data sharing and the role of trust in data sharing.
4. **Why is there resistance to data sharing?** Investigating the cognitive, barriers that inhibit data sharing.
5. **What solutions have been adopted?** Exploring how successful initiatives have addressed data-sharing challenges and foster a culture of collaboration and sustainability.

By addressing these questions, this paper contributes a nuanced understanding of the cognitive factors that impact data sharing. In doing so, we provide insights into the pathways through which supply chains can transition toward more sustainable practices. Specifically, we aim to identify actionable strategies that align mental models with the broader goals of transparency, collaboration, and systemic transformation.

Research Design

Our goal is to develop a conceptual framework describing how, within an industry, data sharing occurs and enables the emergence of more sustainable supply chains. We anchor the conceptual development in a qualitative, multiple case study approach. The cases were selected following a purposeful sampling logic and using a set of criteria consistent with our research intent (Moser et Korstjens; 2018). We selected three data-sharing initiatives, one each in the chemical, automotive and garment industry. We performed 35 interviews and collected primary data on these initiatives. We interviewed CEO, CSCO, CPO and sustainability and digital specialists of different actors, some who participate in the data-sharing initiatives and some who have not yet decided to join. We also collected data from representatives involved in policy discussions related to policy initiatives on supply chain data sharing. Table one describes our data collection process.

Firms who are part the data-sharing initiatives

Chemical sector: 9 interviews, 6 public presentations recorded in videos. Press releases, organization websites and guidelines.

Automotive sector: 9 interviews, 12 public presentations recorded in videos, Press releases, organization websites and guidelines.

Garment sector : 17 interviews 5 workshops, organization websites and guidelines.

Table 1: data collection

Findings

Data sharing in supply chains is governed by a complex interplay of cognitive and structural factors that influence the willingness of individuals and organizations to share information. These dynamics reflect how perceived benefits, competitive risks, costs, and data control concerns shape decision-making, and how macro-level industry mechanisms interact with micro-level cognitive frames to either enable or inhibit sustainable outcomes. Below, we examine the key findings regarding these dynamics.

The perceived benefits of data sharing are unevenly distributed, creating both motivation and concerns among supply chain stakeholders. Data sharing is seen as a mechanism that drives standardization, improves efficiency, and facilitates compliance with sustainability regulations within the industry. The benefits, however, vary significantly depending on the firm's size and position within the supply chain, its capacity to leverage shared data, and its existing technological infrastructure. This asymmetry of value distribution results in a cautious approach to data sharing, particularly when the direct value to a firm's operations remains unclear.

One of the most significant barriers to data sharing is the perception of competitive risk. Many organizations regard their data as a source of competitive advantage and are concerned about the

potential misuse of shared information. The ambiguity of industry change including evolving regulations or new competitive dynamics, further deters data sharing.

The cost of data sharing represents another barrier. Establishing and maintaining systems for data sharing requires investment. These costs are particularly burdensome for smaller firms, which often lack the resources to adapt to diverse client systems. Furthermore, the multiplicity of systems and standards across supply chains exacerbates these challenges, creating inefficiencies that deter firms from engaging in data-sharing initiatives.

Concerns about losing control over data also remain a pervasive cognitive barrier. The fear of cybersecurity threats, data breaches, and the potential misuse of sensitive information leads many firms to adopt defensive stances. This apprehension is strong in industries handling sensitive or proprietary data.

Macro-Level Mechanisms Shaping Cognitive Frames

Organizations often manage risks associated with data sharing by adopting selective sharing practices and limiting information access to trusted partners, excluding broader networks. While this mitigates competitive concerns, it restricts the benefits of transparency and collaboration across supply chains.

Alleviating these fears requires the presence of independent intermediaries or the adoption of suitable technologies. The use of anonymization protocols and secure platforms, such as data spaces, help manage these risks effectively. These solutions instill greater confidence in data sharing by ensuring traceability and accountability while minimizing exposure to potential misuse.

Industry standards and regulatory compliance are crucial in shaping the cognitive frames that influence data sharing. Standardization reduces ambiguity and simplifies the adoption of data-sharing practices, while regulatory requirements for sustainability reporting and traceability can compel firms to reconsider their reluctance, reframing data sharing as a necessary strategy for compliance.

Social norms and peer dynamics within industries also influence cognitive frames. Firms that see competitors or partners successfully implementing data-sharing initiatives may feel compelled to participate to avoid reputational or operational disadvantages. Such normative pressures, coupled with publicized success stories, can shift organizational mental models toward recognizing the collective benefits of transparency.

Finally, technological advancements play a role in reshaping cognitive barriers to data sharing. Tools that allow organizations to control access to information and monitor its use alleviate fears of data misuse. Technologies can simplify the process of sharing data and reduce the cognitive and administrative burden on decision-makers.

Micro and Macro Interactions in Data Sharing

The interaction between micro-level cognitive frames and macro-level structural factors significantly impacts data-sharing practices. When independent organizations, industry standards and proper use of technology demonstrate the feasibility and benefits of data sharing, individual cognitive frames often shift toward trust and optimism. Conversely, the absence of alignment or clear guidance at the macro level can reinforce micro-level fears, entrenching resistance and stalling progress.

Conclusion

The cognitive dynamics governing data sharing in supply chains reflect a delicate balance of perceived benefits and concerns. By addressing these factors through technological, regulatory, and normative mechanisms, it is possible to reframe organizational mental models to prioritize transparency, trust, and collaboration ultimately fostering more sustainable supply chains.

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Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental

Digital Product Passports: Transforming Consumer Awareness and Driving Sustainable Supply Chains: A Quantitative Analysis

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

During the last years, the European Union (EU) due to the increasing global concern about the integration of sustainability in the supply chains, has decided to develop specific measures such as the Green Deal which has the Digital Product Passport (DPP) as one of its key components (Virkkunen, 2024). The DPP is a new instrument developed to promote traceability and transparency as well as the right choice at every stage of a product's life cycle towards the creation of a circular economy while minimizing environmental hazards. As outlined in the EU Green Deal, the objectives set forth to proceed towards sustainability are straightforward and base on waste reduction, and resource efficiency and curb suppression on the supply chain of the production processes and practices in general (Eckert & Kovalevska, 2021). DPP is crucial for those objectives because it is a database that is dedicated to each product and contains information on the raw materials used, the production technology, the environmental effects, how to recycle the product, and post-consumer product management. Retailers can use DPP to meet the high levels of consumer needs for authenticity, sustainability, and compliance by giving a clear and consistent method for tracking and verifying product content information (Saleheen & Afrid, 2023).

Even though they have great potential, the large scale of DPP adoption rests on the resolution of several key barriers; lack of consumers awareness, technology intricacies, and poor engagement among the involved parties (Shehu, 2024). This research is based on previous research, which was focused on the integration and combination of blockchain technology and global data standards in DPP operationalization processes (Papadakis et al., 2023). The goal is to bring these issues to a consumer basis. Therefore, the study is aiming to identify the ways in which DPP can be used as a tool, in order to drive purchasing behavior, securing trust and loyalty while enhancing environmental sustainability.

The focus of this paper is consistent with its aims and seeks to understand and promote the target awareness of consumers of DPP and their prospects of encouraging responsible consumption among them. So, researchers are going to:

- Investigate at what extent consumers understand the concepts of sustainability and DPP.
- Evaluate at what extent the impact of DPP integration will influence their purchasing decisions and their brand loyalty.

Therefore, the main key research questions that researchers developed, are:

- To what extent are consumers aware of the environmental and social impacts of their purchasing choices?
- How can DPP, supported by blockchain and standardized data exchange, address consumer concerns about authenticity, traceability, and sustainability?

So, the study employs a mixed-method approach, combining a literature review of existing frameworks with empirical data gathered through a structured consumer questionnaire, based on the quantitative analysis. The questionnaire that was developed, was presented to a specific demographically sample, that of young consumers (Gen-Z mostly), who are going to be the next generation of environmentally conscious buyers (Ghouse et al., 2024).

The first findings of the research show a significant difference in consumer awareness of sustainability and DPP. The participants of the survey were truly aware of environmental issues, but they were not about DPP, as a concept and as a new EU approach. So, when researchers explained the full potential of DPP concept, participants recognized that dynamic to influence their purchasing mindset and decision-making, based on the fact that the information will be accessible and transparent.

So, the survey come to a great conclusion, that of transparency could increase the consumer trust. Moreover, the new generation of consumer expressed their support for brands that are going to adopt DPP policies, indicating that they are going to be more aware of environmental issues and be more sustainable-driven consumers.

Trust emerged as a critical factor in DPP adoption. The decentralized and unchangeable nature of Blockchain technology was considered to be a distinct advantage by maintaining data integrity and limiting the possibilities of false claims (Oliveira et al., 2024). On the other hand, some authors were concerned with data privacy issues, technical difficulties and potential increase of costs, which emphasize the need for DPP technologies that are both effective and safe for users.

The participants expressed their desire that DPP should be incorporated into existing technologies that consumers already use, such as smartphone apps or QR codes. It was believed that making product information available in such a simple way would facilitate mass adoption of the DPP. Moreover, participants highlighted that sustainable focused campaigns could decrease the level of consumers awareness, promoting the benefits that derived from the use of DPP for both consumers and the environment.

The findings of the quantitative analysis indicate that DPP is going to offer significant potential to the consumer behavior and lead to specific sustainable market practices. However, the successful implementation will depend on collaborative efforts among society and all the involved stakeholders:

- Companies should invest in DPP policies into their supply chains, using blockchain technology in order to increase their transparency and trust towards the consumers. Clear communication of DPP benefits can enhance brand differentiation and customer loyalty (Legardeur & Ospital, 2024).
- On the other hand, government and policymakers must establish specific regulatory frameworks that incentivize DPP adoption while ensuring data privacy and accessibility, in order to increase the sustainable impact inside the supply chain and achieve the sustainable goals (Götz et al.,

2022). Public awareness campaigns can play a pivotal role in normalizing DPP usage and educating consumers about their environmental impact.

In conclusion, this research highlights the importance of integrated the concept of DPP within the EU Green Deal framework in order to increase the sustainable impact of the supply chain management. By addressing these issues, that of consumer awareness and the technological adoption of blockchain technology, this research provides both practitioners and academics with a roadmap for investigating and analyzing the full potential of DPP, leading to a more transparent, ethical, and circular economy.

Subsequent research should focus on the investigation of DPP in practice, using DPP pilot projects and longitudinal studies that examine how consumer behavior and supply chain relationships can be altered. Additionally, a future research should include greater demographic sample which will be able to provide deeper insights of consumer awareness.

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Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social, 11. Digital

Revisiting Sustainability Disclosure in Fast Fashion Supply Chains: 2013 vs 2023

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Background

Despite many efforts and initiatives that are introduced by companies and industry organizations to improve sustainability performance, fast fashion industry has been maintaining its position under the spotlight for sustainability criticism. Rana Plaza Crash in 2013 which caused the death of thousands of garment workers who worked for the supply chains of many globally well-known fashion brands, is considered the worst ever industrial accident that hit the clothing industry. The causes behind this incident were scrutinized in detail and led to the exposure of these brands to public criticism for neglecting their supply chains or structuring their supply chains in a way that led to this disaster (CleanClothes, 2024). The industry is not short on scandals since then. Recently revealed greenwashing practices (Forbes, 2022), incineration of excess stock to preserve brand value (BBCEarth, 2023) or water pollution from garment processing are some examples from a longer list. More regulations are on the way, such as extended producer responsibility (ZeroWasteEurope, 2022) and the waste export bans from the EU (EC, 2024).

Fast fashion is not only an industry, but also a business model. It is based on a value proposition that promises high-end fashion at the lowest possible cost and value generation in this business model is dependent on the speed of operations. Although the industry continues to make pledges for sustainability, this business model hinders the path to sustainable development of the industry. Furthermore, the industry is not getting any smaller. Together with effective use of social media communication channels, data analytics and artificial intelligence, even faster versions of fast fashion companies take the lead every day. The Chinese fashion company Shein has outperformed the largest fast fashion brands by extremely lower prices and faster response time to trend changes (Olcott and Eley, 2021).

Purpose

10 years ago, Turker and Altuntas (2014) have investigated the public disclosure of 9 European fashion companies operating under fast fashion principles. They applied the sustainable supply chain management framework (Seuring and Mueller, 2008) to the sustainability reports published by the

selected companies to map how sustainability was implemented in their supply chains. The purpose of this paper is to revisit the map by analysing the GRI reports from the same companies after 10 years have passed to monitor the development and illustrate the change.

The paper builds further on the current discourse on sustainability and fast fashion and critically discusses it in relation to supply chain management principles. Such discourse includes consumer responsibility and activism, circular economy, textile waste, degrowth and omni-channel retailing.

Theoretical framework-revisited

In their seminal paper, Seuring and Mueller (2008) borrow from Bowen et al.'s (2001) 'greening the supply process' and 'product-based green supply' to suggest their two norm strategies. The model can simply be described in two parts: (1) the product and (2) the supply chain. The former part focuses on the product itself, its life-cycle impacts, how it is developed together with the suppliers, what type of criteria is imposed to the suppliers for the production and delivery of this generic product. The latter part deals with the supply chain and the supply process where the focus is on managing the triple bottom-line risks in the supply chain while optimizing the performance. The two norm strategies are very generic by nature but they are informed by the management standards that define the code of conduct in specific industries, the reporting guidelines and the dominant pressures.

Methodology

The methodology of this paper is divided into two stages.

Part 1: Revisiting the theoretical model

During this first part we followed the steps of a tertiary SLR which is similar to a secondary literature review where the goal is to analyze the primary studies within a certain field and synthesize their findings (Centobelli et al., 2022). Rather than synthesizing the findings from former reviews, the purpose here is to discover the new dimensions of a generic SSCM model that were not included in the 2008 model that was developed by Seuring and Mueller (2008), match them with the categories of the original model while inductively building inferences to other higher-order categories at the same time and map them alongside the two norm strategies in the original model.

Although the goal is different than common SLRs, a systematic approach after Durach et al. (2017) and particularly the content analysis-based approach by Seuring and Gold (2012) was followed to assure rigor in the refinement of the model. A total of 196 papers were selected for the final analysis which resulted in 11 new components: circularity, collaborations, CSR, stakeholders, technology, governance mechanism, government, Resource-based view, employees, innovation, covid-19.

Part 2: Analyzing sustainability disclosure of fast fashion companies

Sample selection and data collection

The population of study is composed of fast fashion companies operating in Europe. In order to ensure the replicability of methodological approach in the study of Turker and Altuntas (2014), the same set of companies were considered as the sample. In the original study, these companies were selected as a

comparable data set since they prepared their sustainability/corporate social responsibility (CSR) reports according to the framework of Global Reporting Initiative (GRI).

Analysis method

The collected data on nine companies was analyzed through content analysis by deriving meaningful inferences from a text by considering their context of use in the report (Krippendorff, 2004, 18). The revisited theoretical model of Seuring and Muller (2008) provided the analytical framework of current study.

Preliminary Findings: Components and Linkages

The result of analysis reveals that the theoretical model has changed over years by the emergence of new components (the illustration of old and new maps/models could not be uploaded due to the submission format). Similar to the results in 2014, companies' management systems are still at the heart of SSCM and operationalized via codes of conduct.

Although the previous study found that these codes for suppliers were generated based on the international, national or sectoral standards, regulations, or agreements etc. (Oeko-Tex Standard 100, UN Global Compact, Universal Declaration of Human Rights, UN Rights of the Child, ILO Convention, ETI, the Framework Agreement with IndustriALL, Global Union, FWF's Code of Conduct etc.), the scope and meaning of these frameworks have significantly changed over time and they surrounded the management systems. As a newly emerged component, collaborations have illustrated at the outer layer and refers to the stakeholder engagement for SSCM. While these collaborations mostly aimed at improving suppliers, there are many collaborations with the local organizations across supplier countries. For example, while C&A collaborated with MUDEM, *"a non-governmental organization with specific expertise for the situation of Syrian refugees in Turkey"* on *"the investigation and remediation of complaints concerning production units of C&A suppliers"* though an online grievance mechanism together, H&M attempted to include *"the marginalised populations in our supply chains and continued to work with various stakeholders focused on our commitment with TENT to support the ethical recruitment of refugees in Türkiye"*, Moreover, while H&M also explained its commitment to *"the Ready Made Garment Sustainability Council (RSC) in Bangladesh"*, the company tried to engage with *"local stakeholders"* through an alliance for ware stewardship program in the same country.

The findings also show how and where the new components appear in the revised model. All components are embedded into digital technologies in some ways. For example, PUMA adopted *"a comprehensive suite of supply chain analytics [ELEVATE intelligence (EIQ)]... to assess our supply chain risks by geography, commodity and issue... manage risks that are material for each supplier, factory or site"* or initiated a *"customised e-learning on Social Standards, to support existing and new suppliers with understanding PUMA's expectations"*. While *"circularity"* gains a lot of attention among companies, it has been linked with *"innovation"* component. For example, Mango started to collaborate an Indian company, Materra, to design *"solutions for the cultivation and supply of regenerative cotton with the aim of creating a positive impact on the territory"* and *"provide complete traceability of the cotton"*

supply chain from its cultivation to the garment”. In a similar vein, H&M showed how circularity is linked with innovation below:

“Our Circular Innovation Lab worked with Ioniqa Technologies BV and polyester suppliers to evaluate advanced recycled polyester. This includes Sysav’s automatic sorting of post- consumer textiles and Ioniqa’s recycling process to obtain high-purity polyester fibres, through to successfully producing virgin-quality 100% recycled yarn.”

The findings also reveal that while social risk and performance were aligned with an increasing focus on suppliers’ employees, environmental risk and performance were integrated along the theme of traceability/transparency. For the former dimension, companies explained how they reduce the risks on workers’ health, safety, and wellbeing and provide the level of progress as the indicators of their social performance. Traceability/transparency, which can be linked with the increasing concern for developing a well-functioning governance mechanism, has emerged as one of the most important components in the model. Most companies mentioned them as the objective of SSCM and integrate their approach on both risk and performance management components.

Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

The new paradoxical role of the purchasing function: Innovating!

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Why this paper topic for IPSERA 2025?

The identification of paradoxes within an organization is essential for optimizing talent management. By understanding and navigating these tensions, organizations can create environments conducive to performance, innovation, and employee fulfillment. Managing paradoxes thus becomes a strategic lever to maximize the potential of talent while ensuring organizational sustainability.

Summary

Purchasing can find itself torn between arbitration to innovation while working on its historical activities, which leads to tensions. Thus, easing purchasing function contribution by identifying those tensions appears important to help companies to reach their innovation goals. In this paper, we examine purchasing innovation organizations tensions from the angle of paradox theory from Smith and Lewis (2011). We use a qualitative research method with a single case study at Schneider Electric and semi structured interviews. We identified four paradoxes and their representation per purchasing innovation structures. We reveal the predominance of performing paradoxes.

Keywords or phrases: Purchasing and Supply Management; Paradox theory; Purchasing innovation

Submission category: working paper abstract

ABSTRACT

Some authors argue that suppliers are one of the most important sources of innovation (Un et al., 2010; Pihlajamaa et al., 2017). Consequently, purchasing, which is historically known as a means of managing costs and suppliers, is also now expected to contribute to innovation. Thus, purchasing contribution to firm innovation can be detailed “in terms of the proportion of new product ideas generated by purchasing, the extent to which purchasing promotes standardization and simplification of parts/components between products, whether purchasing determines the timing and modes of supplier involvement in NPD, and the activities of scouting for new suppliers and new technologies for the sake of NPD or process innovation” (Castaldi et al., 2011, p.7).

By intensifying its role in innovation, the purchasing function must work simultaneously on short-term (reduction of costs) and long term (innovation) logics. As Kim Godwin, CPO of Barclay emphasizes in an interview (Gonzalez Padron et al., 2008, p.1), this is a simultaneous activity “It is not one (reduce costs) or the other (drive innovation), it is about maintaining a broad and balanced agenda on costs, innovation, supplier management, corporate social responsibility (CSR), systems, compliance and so on”. Eventually, purchasing organizations can find themselves torn between arbitration to innovation while working on their historical activities, which leads to tensions.

Those tensions can be felt differently according to purchasing innovation activities in New Product Development (NPD) or in Fuzzy Front End (FFE). In NPD, on incremental innovation activities, the tensions remain rather low because it is often a question of working in co-development with known suppliers for example (Maniak, Midler et al. 2008). However, in FFE, the accumulation of novelties can become a source of tensions. The more the buyer leaves his historical competences quality-cost-delay (Aljian, 1984; Andersen, Ellegaard et al. 2020), to go towards innovation activities such as the scouting of concepts and ideas (in contrast to mature technologies), the identification of new and distant sectorial partners (Ben Mahmoud-Jouini and Charue-Duboc, 2018), the search for new solutions neither identified nor solicited, for example, for a poorly defined problem with unknown suppliers (Ben Mahmoud Jouini et al. 2019), the more these innovation buyers are subject to tensions. Managing those tensions appears to be vital for purchasing organizations and companies because not managing the tensions inherent to the job of purchasing involved in innovation means that the company risks depriving oneself of a real source of innovations that are the suppliers (Un et al., 2010).

We propose to examine our object namely purchasing organizations tensions, from the lens of paradox theory. The theory of paradoxes would provide a more global approach to framing tensions (Beech, Burns et al. 2004; Lewis 2000; Gotsi, Andriopoulos et al. 2010). A paradox is defined as a contradictory yet interdependent element which exists simultaneously and is persistent over time (Smith and Lewis, 2011). This definition leads us to consider underlying tensions - that is to say, elements that seem logical individually but incoherent and even absurd when they are juxtaposed (Lewis, 2000). Some of the tensions experienced by purchasers when contributing to innovation can be considered as paradoxical since they are contradictory, simultaneous and persistent over time.

In that context, our research question is: What are the paradoxical tensions that purchasing innovation teams are facing when they contribute to innovation?

Research methodology

We decided to follow the single case study approach advocated by Dyer and Wilkins (1991) and Dubois and Araujo (2007) that pays more attention to the context and the story than to construct development and empirical generalization. Declining the paradoxical tensions concept into the attributes of interdependence-simultaneity, persistence and contradiction made it easier to identify empirical occurrences of the concepts. Our data were structured using the GIOA approach.

Our field research focuses on Schneider Electric, a multinational company that provides energy and automation digital solutions for efficiency and sustainability and has shown excellence in innovation and purchasing innovation. We have done 28 semi structured interviews and one observation.

Research results

First, the research allows us to see how the contribution of purchasing to innovation is organized in a company that is emblematic in the world of innovation. This work shows a contribution through four different purchasing organizations: OCP BU Energy Management an organization dedicated to innovation which focuses on NPD, Purchasing & Innovation BU within Energy Management that is dedicated to Fuzzy Front-End innovation, Category Management organization that deals through ad hoc resources on both NPD and FEE and finally a support function organized with dedicated and ad hoc resources that intervenes in FFE innovation. In addition, we discover the stages through which these purchasing organizations have passed to become what they are today.

Apart from showing which purchasing innovation organizations associated with innovation steps processes along with resources allocation can support purchasing contribution in innovation, we reveal that not all purchasing innovation teams are facing paradoxes. But the more the purchasing teams focus on FFE and are with ad hoc or with mixed resources allocation the more likely they will live paradoxes.

High interest has been placed so far in the exploitation-exploration tensions that innovation purchasers face (Constant et al, 2020). Consequently, the concept of Purchasing ambidexterity arises as "the extent to which a purchasing function simultaneously pursues exploratory and exploitative activities within supply networks" (Gualandris et al., 2018, p. 667; Constant et al, 2020). This work sheds light on paradoxes other than exploration-exploitation tension, proposing to better size the whole spectrum of tensions. Conversely, we reveal the paradoxical tensions that certain purchasing innovations teams are facing, and which are "Innovate without taking risks", "Innovate and be competitive", "Structure and be creative" and "scale up with startups with over solicited resources". In addition, we note the predominance of 'innovate without taking risk paradox' as well as performing paradox category. We show that tensions faced by purchasing innovation teams are first and foremost linked to the inner contradictions in objectives within Schneider goals and not at individual level. Our work highlights the importance of risk related paradox within Schneider organization.

Contribution to the literature

We contribute to the purchasing literature by showing how different combinations of purchasing innovation organizations, innovation steps processes and resource allocation can support purchasing contribution in innovation and reveal that not all purchasing innovation teams are facing paradoxes.

In addition, our work contributes to paradox literature by generating knowledge around the identification of paradoxes that purchasing and innovation organizations experience, providing further empirical illustrations. Contributing to the paradox literature, we propose a method to operationalize the persistence 'attribute' of identified paradoxes. We recommended operationalizing the persistence "attribute" by reconstituting interviewees professional trajectory.

We contribute to the purchasing literature and the innovation literature by showing evidence of the similarities of paradoxes between purchaser innovation and "traditional" actors from innovation, thus positioning purchaser's innovation as true enabler of company's innovation agenda.

Managerial contributions

This paper brings insights at the managerial level. First, for companies wishing to make their purchasing department contribute to innovation, it allows to understand how to organize the purchasing for innovation from an organization, resources and innovation process standpoint. It also helps practitioners

to understand certain stages in the evolution of the function towards innovation. In addition, it permits to detect paradoxes and to integrate the management of paradoxes as an important factor. Indeed, recognizing paradoxes allows not to be surprised or even abandon the innovation purchasing initiatives because of the multitude of paradoxes to manage.

Finally, for companies that have left the innovative purchasing process, the idea is to allow them to have feedback and to put into words the tensions that they may have experienced and that they may not have been able to identify and even manage. Because of the prevailing importance of risk related paradox, we provide visibility on this aspect, but we also recommend prioritizing risk related paradoxes management to support innovation efforts.

Paper topic

1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 3. Purchasing organisation, 10. Purchasing innovation

Demystifying Circular Purchasing: Toward a New Procurement Paradigm

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Demystifying Circular Purchasing: Toward a New Procurement Paradigm

Introduction

The concept of a circular economy (CE) has gained prominence in academic and policy discussions as a pathway toward sustainable development. Unlike traditional linear systems of production and consumption, CE focuses on creating a regenerative cycle where materials are reused, repurposed, and recycled, enhancing both environmental and economic resilience (e.g., Ghisellini et al., 2016). While circular principles are increasingly integrated into business models (e.g., Geissdoerfer et al., 2020), applying them at the organizational level demands substantial changes in management and operational practices. Purchasing and supply chain functions, which interact with various organizational partners (e.g., Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2023), are particularly affected by this transition.

Despite the growing body of research on sustainable and green purchasing, literature focusing on circular purchasing is still nascent. Early studies draw on the broader discussion around sustainable procurement and circular business models, highlighting the transformative potential of CE (e.g., Geissdoerfer et al., 2017; Ghisellini et al., 2016). Within the purchasing domain, circularity introduces additional layers of complexity due to the need for collaborative innovation, extended supplier engagement, and alignment with CE principles.

Sönnichsen & Clement (2020) and Xu et al. (2020) review green, sustainable, and circular practices in public procurement. However, their work relies heavily on sustainable practices due to the limited literature on circular practices. Although it is valuable, it lacks a clear conceptual distinction (see e.g., Geissdoerfer et al., 2017 for the differences between sustainability and circularity) between sustainable and circular practices. At times, they conflate these terms, and it remains unclear how their examples connect to circular practices.

In light of this, one might argue that the literature on circular purchasing begins with the work of Neessen et al. (2021a, 2021b), who call attention to the critical role purchasers play in implementing CE principles through, for example, innovative product design, strategic networking, and organizational

citizenship behaviors. However, while this work points to the importance of the purchaser's role in translating CE principles into practice, much of the existing research still blurs the lines between circular purchasing and broader notions of sustainable procurement. As a result, we lack a clear framework to differentiate circular purchasing from other sustainability-driven approaches, making it difficult to identify which activities genuinely advance CE principles and in what contexts they do so.

To clarify this conceptual ambiguity, this study examines the nature and scope of circular purchasing, asking:

1. What types of products and services can be considered circular purchases, and in which settings?
2. How can these products and services be categorized in terms of their complexity and suppliers' business models?

By addressing these questions, we aim to establish a more precise understanding of circular purchasing practices, thereby helping practitioners and scholars recognize when, where, and how purchasers can best support circularity.

Methodology

This study employs an exploratory qualitative approach, relying on semi-structured interviews with purchasers and suppliers from the construction industry. The selection of this industry is deliberate, given its high resource intensity and significant environmental impact. Globally, the construction sector accounts for more than 30% of natural resource extraction and produces approximately 25% of solid waste (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2021), with only 20-30% of construction and demolition waste either recycled or reused (European Commission, 2020).

The interview guide is informed by extant literature and preliminary fieldwork, focusing on the types of purchases made, how CE principles are integrated, and the associated challenges. Participants represent a wide range of organizational roles, including strategic decision-makers and operational buyers, helping us capture a comprehensive view of circular purchasing practices. Data will be analyzed using NVivo, with thematic coding based on the literature and refined through iterative team discussions to ensure reliability.

Preliminary findings and conclusion

Based on existing literature and preliminary interviews in the construction industry, it is clear while general awareness of circular economy concepts exists, buyers often struggle to understand how these concepts affect their daily life. Moreover, the results indicate a wide spectrum of "circular purchasing," making it difficult to generalize without stating what is being purchased or assessing the success of these efforts.

Sometimes a simple adjustment can add circularity to an existing product or service—for example, switching from disposable to reusable packaging. In other cases, circularity involves completely new and previously unpurchased categories, such as acquiring charging infrastructure for battery-powered construction vehicles. In addition, some suppliers may shift their business models—typically, but not limited, toward servitization—which can further influence the purchasing process and even alter the level at which the purchasing decision is made (e.g., from a regular buyer to a category manager).

In the full version of this paper, we aim to categorize the “circular purchasing” products and services, offering a framework that reflects their characteristics. We hope this will help buyers and managers better understand their processes and allow them to purchase more items in a circular manner, while also contributing to the growing body of literature by empirically grounding the concept of circular purchasing.

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Interview Guide - Circular Procurement in the Construction Industry

Thank you for agreeing to do this interview about sharing knowledge in circular procurement. The interview will take approximately 60 minutes and we don't anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to stop the interview or withdraw from the research at any time.

Just to get started our definition of circular purchasing is:

“Circular procurement occurs when the buyer purchases products or services that follow the principles of the circular economy, supporting the assessment of designing, making, selling, reusing and recycling products to determine how to get the maximum value from them, both in use and at the end of their life” (UNEP, 2021)”

Section 1: Introduction: can you tell me something about yourself? What is your current position, your work & education background? Can you tell me something about your company? What is the history in brief, and what does it do?

Section 2: Circular practices in general: How does your company integrate the principles of circular economy into its business operations and product lifecycle? Are there any circular economy activities currently developed at your company? If yes, for how long? Does your company plan to continue these activities, or develop more? Does your company educate the workforce on circular economy, and are some frameworks used (e.g., 3Rs, 7Rs, the butterfly diagram)?

Section 3: Circular practices in purchasing: How does your company embed circular principles into its procurement activities? (if not forthcoming then suggested prompts are: what decisions do you take about the products you buy, i.e., reusable, repairable, bio-sourced, recycled/recyclable, how do you evaluate a supplier's ability to how are procurement involved in the design process, how is value evaluated, how are wider supply chain implications assessed).

Section 4: Level of circular activities/change in business models: On what level are those activities devised (company level, function/department level/individual level)? How much do they change your current business model/structure? Is there a strategy to develop them, or are they created ad-hoc?

Section 5: Circular purchasing/selling: for these activities, do these activities lead to changes in purchased products or product categories? Do they lead to changes in suppliers, or are extant suppliers able to modify their offerings? If there are changes in end product offered by the company, is there a difference in customer segmentation?

Section 6: Additional remarks: Is there anything you feel we haven't covered and you'd like to add?

Paper topic

14. Project procurement, 16. Sustainability - environmental, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

Exploring the diffusion of energy-efficient technological innovations for decarbonizing supply chain operations

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Introduction

Decarbonization of supply chains through energy-efficient practices is a topic that has gained recent attention. For instance, industrial carbon emission growth remains a great challenge to overcome, yet there is enormous potential that the diffusion of green innovations can attain (Kannan et al., 2022; Kim et al., 2024; Onat and Kucukvar, 2020, IEA 2024). Research on the optimization of energy efficiency in the industry has depicted the increase of green practices in supply chain management as response to the enhanced demand for sustainably-produced and manufactured products alongside patterns of increased monitoring among supply chain actors of the implementation of energy-efficient strategies (Gawusu et al., 2022; Green et al., 2012; Marchi and Zanoni, 2017). The deployment of energy-efficient technologies in manufacturing, and operating processes, albeit complex, is milestone to achieving not only individual but collective economic, and environmental sustainability (Anser et al., 2020; Costantini et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2016; Patterson et al., 2003).

However, previous studies have vastly overlooked the potential to identify opportunities in supply chains that consider the harmonization of aligned energy-efficient strategies (Marchi and Zanoni, 2017). It is therefore crucial that the adoption of technological innovations is orchestrated to align SC actors' specific needs by recognizing the opportunities of technological attributes and attractiveness such as practicality, investment return, cultural, and social compatibility, among others, that accentuate the value and application of technological innovations (Fang et al., 2023; Schniederjans, 2017; Wu et al., 2013). Research in Supply Chain Management employs various grand theories like Resource-based View, Transaction Cost Theory, Resource-dependency Theory – among others – to a great extent (Feng et al., 2022; Gligor et al., 2019; Touboullic and Walker, 2015). At the same time, SCM scholars acknowledge the need and importance to expand the interdisciplinary scope of the theoretical underpinning in explaining supply chain activities (Gligor et al., 2019; Spina et al., 2016). Consequently, the adoption and diffusion of innovations is a theoretically underdeveloped area in SCM alongside the lack of empirical research that shows the roles of technological attributes in supply chain activities (Wu et al., 2013).

To address these matters, we seek to examine the diffusion of technological innovations in supply chains through the lens of Diffusion of Innovations Theory (Rogers, 1983), namely, within the domain of perceived characteristics of the innovation. The DoI provides fundamental groundwork to measure

determinants of the intention of potential adopters to accept innovations solely based on the characteristics in a technological context (Lai et al., 2018; Schniederjans, 2017); identifying technology adoption in the supply chain context entails huge potential for SCM improvement (Agi and Jha, 2022). The theory enables an understanding of the extent to and circumstances under which supply chain actors are inclined to forming attitudes and intentions to accept energy-efficient technological innovations in their supply chain applications (Wu et al., 2013). Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to theoretically and empirically identify and validate technological innovation specific attributes alongside their impact and interdependence in diffusion of innovations in supply chains and will be guided by the following research question: *What technological factors shape the intention to adopt energy-efficient technological innovations in supply chains?* Ultimately, this research will endorse the enhancement of energy efficiency in supply chains by bringing the ecological and economic benefits associated with the diffusion of technological innovations as a mechanism to reducing carbon emissions across supply chains. Additionally, it will unfold the direction and the extent to which technological factors influence the intention of supply chain actors to adopt energy-efficient technological innovations. Lastly, it will extend Roger's Diffusion of Innovations framework at a newly applied context and approach SCM with a different theoretical lens from what previous research proceeded.

Diffusion of Innovations

Diffusion of Innovations is rather a process that determines the speed and rate of the innovation adoption; it is an information seeking and processing system that leads to reduced uncertainties about a certain innovation (García-Avilés, 2020). Innovation, according to Rogers, is "an idea, practice, or object that is perceived as new by an individual or other unit of adoption." (Rogers, 1983, p.11) Likewise, technological innovation according to Vaughan, is rather an intertwined concept among technology, new technology, and innovation, albeit not used interchangeably (2013). The newness of innovation is not as important as the perception on the newness of the idea; if one has not seen, heard, or known about an idea, one might still perceive it as innovation (Rogers, 1983). Consequently, energy-efficient technologies, including the corresponding technological innovations, can be defined as technologies that endorse the efficient use of energy in products, processes, and systems (Kim et al., 2024). Energy-efficient technologies limit the environmental impact by reducing carbon footprint and ultimately emissions while reducing costs, improving product and process quality and safety, and enhancing productivity and growth (Martin et al., 2000; Wang et al., 2024). In line with the DoI, the five main stages of innovation diffusion include 1) knowledge acquisition, 2) persuasion stage, i.e., forming an attitude with the aim of reducing the uncertainties about the outcomes of the innovation, 3) decision, 4) implementation, i.e., institutionalizing the innovation to practice, and 5) confirmation (García-Avilés, 2020; Rogers, 1983).

Diffusion of energy-efficient technological innovations in supply chains

The adoption and diffusion of energy-efficient technological innovations bridges the transformation of supply chain processes by simplifying operational processes, minimizing uncertainties, and the associated risks, and improving overall energy efficiency performance (Carmagnac and Naoui-Outini, 2022; Rauniyar et al., 2023). The diffusion of innovations for the advancement of SC performance is an enabling factor to driving economic, environmental, and social growth (Jiang et al., 2024; Rauniyar et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022).

Literature recognizes that the application of the DoI in the SCM discipline is crucial and well-suitable to understand the adoption of energy-efficient solutions in supply chains (Giunipero and Eltantawy, 2022; Lin et al., 2020; Sarkis et al., 2011; Swanson et al., 2017). The purpose of diffusion of innovations is rather to streamline the innovation along different categories of adopters in supply chain that best

satisfy the needs and requirements of supply chain actors. Identifying the role of the attributes of innovation has the predicting power to determine the success or failure to adopt these technologies (Feng et al., 2022). Fang et al., highlight that the adoption of technology is means to promoting and enhancing supply chain activities that drive strategic agility and value creation among SC actors (Fang et al., 2023).

In line with Rogers' persuasion enablers of the innovation adoption rate, this study focuses on the five perceived attributes of the innovation, i.e., i) relative advantage – the degree to which a technological innovation advantage is perceived better than the alternative innovations, ii) compatibility – the level of consistency and conformity of the innovation with one's values, culture, norms, needs, and practices, iii) complexity – how easy or difficult innovation is perceived to be used, iv) trialability – the opportunity for an innovation to be tried or experimented with, and v) observability – how visible the results of the innovation are to the potential adopters (Lin et al., 2020; Rogers, 1983; Schniederjans, 2017).

Methodology

The data will be collected through a survey with actors in manufacturing supply chains. More specifically, this study will investigate supply chain actors' intention to adopt energy-efficient technological innovations in the manufacturing industry, namely in the dairy, pulp and paper, and beverage sectors in Finland and Sweden. The manufacturing industry has an enormous impact on the generation of carbon emissions and is among the most challenging industries with complex SCs, to decarbonize. Likewise, the dairy and paper and pulp sectors are EU's biggest manufacturing sectors, with the highest energy intensive operations and production capacities (Richie et al., 2024; Sundaramoorthy et al., 2023; Wei et al., 2019). Data will be analysed using factor analysis, structural equation modelling (SEM), and multiple regression models.

Research Model & Expected Results

This study will empirically investigate the causal relationships between the independent variables), i.e., relative advantages, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability, and the influence that they have on the intention of the potential adopters to accept energy-efficient technological innovations as a base model. The study will additionally analyze the extent and the conditions under which certain factors explain the others in terms of innovation attributes. This specific model predicts that observability will explain relative advantages, considering it measures the extent to which the benefits of the innovation are visible and communicated. Similarly, trialability to experiment with innovation eases the rate of the adoption of innovations. Given the insufficiency to prove consistency results due to the diversity and polarization of technological context, the model predicts that it will add to the complexity and therefore perceive the intention to adopt technological innovations negatively.

Conclusively, this research will bring a cross-disciplinary theoretical underpinning to the SCM field, by laying groundwork for scholars in SC decarbonization to approach the diffusion of innovations in SCs as a means towards betterment of ecological and economic performance of supply chains. It will do so by bringing an empirical study that investigates the sole technological factors affecting the intention to adopt energy-efficient technological innovations.

Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 10. Purchasing innovation, 15. PSM theory, methodology, education

Supply chain resilience and the role of contracting: Insights from the UK medicine supply system

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Purpose

We explore how contracting influences supply chain resilience and its various forms. Disruptions such as the COVID-19 pandemic created a sense of urgency internationally to improve resilience of critical supply chains, including health and medicine ones (Harland et al., 2021). Our research setting is the UK medicine supply system. Medicine shortages have been a pressing problem even before COVID-19, with significant negative effects on patients' welfare and care costs. The pandemic exacerbated these challenges, triggering various government interventions (de Vries et al., 2021). Alongside measures to build medicine stockpiles and reshore manufacturing, countries including the UK started rethinking the way they procure medicines for use in public hospitals.

Research on supply chain resilience has identified several strategies and underpinning capabilities such as those based on redundancy and flexibility (Ali et al., 2017). The literature stresses two diverse perspectives (Wieland and Durach, 2021): (a) an engineering view, which emphasises the ability of organisations to bounce back to a steady state following a disruption, and to resist or absorb shocks, and (b) a social-ecological view, stressing flexible responses to unforeseen events and the ability of focal firms to adapt and transform their supply chains in the face of change. Building on this distinction, Wieland et al. (2023) stress three resilience forms: *persistence*, *adaptation*, and *transformation*. Persistence is related to robustness and redundancy principles. Adaptation and transformation are based on flexibility and the ability to effect radical changes, respectively.

Research at the intersection between procurement and supply chain resilience highlights both redundancy and flexibility strategies: while some studies focus on *buffering* practices such as expanding the size and geographical footprint of the supply base (Pereira et al., 2014; Silva and Ruel, 2022), others show that *bridging* practices promoting supplier collaboration and adaptations are more effective, especially in the immediate aftermath of a disruption (Küffner et al., 2022; Spieske et al., 2022).

Although contracting plays a central role in procurement, little is known about how contract design and management contribute towards supply chain resilience. Contracting decisions, both before a contract is agreed (e.g., design of tenders and payment mechanism) and during contract execution can influence supplier behaviour and supply market dynamics (Jia and Zhao, 2017). And yet, prior research has underplayed the role of contracting: the few relevant studies analyse contracts as a tool alongside many others, including relational governance mechanisms (Faruquee et al., 2023; Gu et al., 2023; Li et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2023). They treat contracting for resilience decisions as driven by contingency factors (e.g., Merzifonluoglu, 2024) and largely neglect the tensions underlying and influencing those decisions. They also do not distinguish contracting effects on different types of resilience. We seek to extend the literature by asking: *How does contracting shape different forms supply chain resilience?*

Method

We adopted a single case design to explore how contracting may enable different forms of supply chain resilience, and any barriers and associated tensions involved in making contracting decisions. We used a criterion sampling approach and chose to study the UK medicine supply system because, following Brexit and the pandemic emergency, the Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC) and NHS England launched a review of tendering and contracting in secondary care with a stated aim to boost resilience of medicine supply chains. This offered a timely opportunity to study contracting practices and related decisions, for instance regarding the design of contractual provisions.

We collected data through 42 semi-structured interviews with all relevant stakeholders including representatives from DHSC, NHS England, manufacturers, and NHS hospitals. We triangulated our interview data by analysing 90 documents, notably a sample of tenders and contracts. We also organised four workshops and discussed with policymakers and practitioners how contracting interventions address medicine shortages. Data analysis focused on how tendering and contracting practices influence supply chain resilience.

Findings

The findings show that NHS tendering and contracting practices emphasise *persistence* based on redundancy of stock and suppliers, in line with an engineering resilience view. A key feature is that contracts embed supplier obligations to hold 8-weeks of buffer stock in UK soil. NHS tender design follows a supply diversity logic: tendering frequency and contract durations vary and lotting (regional contract awards) applies to foster competition and enable multiple sourcing.

Although the emphasis is on contracting for persistence, some NHS initiatives seem to stress the *adaptation* form of resilience, largely based on lessons learned from COVID-19: for example, designing bespoke tenders to increase supply flexibility by luring back into the market suppliers with dormant licenses and manufacturing capacities. In addition, contracts include provisions for supplier data sharing (e.g., on stock volumes), which the NHS medicine procurement agency can use to model inventory levels and anticipate supply issues.

We also uncovered tensions that limit the contribution of contracting, especially in relation to the *adaptation* and *transformation* forms of resilience. These tensions include:

1. Affordability vs. availability goals – despite recent calls within the NHS to transform medicine procurement by adopting a “value-based” approach, a lowest-cost principle persists. Currently, contract award criteria do not include any supply security considerations and there are no rewards (e.g., price increases) for resilient suppliers.
2. Lack of commitments in contracts vs. supplier collaboration – the prominence of framework contracts means that the NHS makes no purchase or volume commitments as bidders awarded a framework contract have a “potential supplier” status. This hurts supplier collaboration and flexibility; the NHS intends to introduce minimum volumes in bespoke tenders designed to increase supply flexibility.
3. Buffer stock contractual obligations vs. supply diversity – a portion of suppliers do not fully comply with these obligations. Besides NHS’s contract management capacity constraints, there are concerns that strict contract enforcement would push some suppliers out of the UK market, given low prices.

Contribution

We contribute to the supply chain resilience literature by offering insights regarding the role of contracting. We show how tendering and contracting practices can contribute to the persistence and adaptation forms of resilience. We also extend research on resilience-oriented procurement, including the few studies that partly address the role of contracts, by elucidating the tensions involved when developing sourcing strategies for resilience. We demonstrate how these underlying tensions shape decisions regarding the design of tenders and contracts.

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Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience, 7. Negotiation and contracting, 13. Public procurement

Managing the paradox of supplier sustainability: The case of cost leaders

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Increasingly, companies are making substantial commitments to enhance their environmental sustainability performance. For many companies, much of the environmental impact stretches beyond the scope of individual companies and direct operations (Hettler & Graf-Vlachy, 2024). As a result, companies are often setting voluntary greenhouse gas (GHG) emission targets for their supply chain (scope 3) to assess and reduce their environmental impact and strive towards carbon neutrality for a more sustainable future. Companies must ensure that their suppliers can handle this requirement if they want to reach their climate targets, including getting suppliers to report on emissions, take accountability and take action to realise reductions (Ellram & Tate, 2024; Zhang et al., 2024).

Many companies aiming to improve their environmental sustainability have historically emphasised economic performance and profitability goals. This traditional focus on cost leadership, optimisation and efficiency as the source of competitive advantage has led to the creation of complex global supply chains (Linton et al., 2007), often characterised by low levels of sustainability performance and widespread unsustainable behaviours of companies and their suppliers (Hoejmose et al., 2013). This suggests an inherent trade-off between economic and sustainable performance, frequently addressed in the sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) literature (Wu & Pagell, 2011). That is, companies must prioritise one or the other of these seemingly opposing objectives. However, companies are increasingly faced with demands to achieve both opposing objectives simultaneously. In particular, cost-leader companies must cope with the need to maintain the lowest possible costs to uphold their sales levels, but simultaneously, they must manage their supply chains to lower their environmental strain, often as a response to stakeholder demand.

Such sustainability management exceeds the scope of supplier engagement, focused on information sharing for GHG emission transparency, which has characterised several SSCM scope 3 studies (e.g., Lintukangas et al., 2023; Tidy et al., 2016). Rather, it suggests a costly performance improvement that requires high initial investments from buyers (Zhang et al., 2022) and costly involvement from suppliers (Chen et al., 2019). Frequently, this also implies a more costly product, for instance, through the

development of new products or production processes but also supplier training, information sharing, capability development or other collaborative efforts (Viera et al., 2024; Plambeck, 2012). In other words, it necessitates sustainable supplier development (SSD) efforts, which are broadly defined as any initiatives aimed at improving supplier sustainability performance or capability (Yawar & Seuring, 2018; Busse et al., 2016). In particular, direct SSD involvement, including elements such as supplier training and education, management involvement, or financial investments (Jia et al., 2021).

As a result, many cost-leader companies are faced with a paradoxical management task of meeting contradictory objectives of improving scope 3 sustainability while keeping their costs low (Lewis & Smith, 2014). That is, these companies face a paradox between environmental sustainability goals and a cost-leader business strategy. This paradox becomes salient as a cost-leader company attempts to tackle its negative environmental supply chain impact, for example, through the commitment to GHG emission reduction targets, demanding action and change across many levels and interactions within a short timeframe and with the risk of failure to meet targets.

With this study, we use paradox theory (Lewis, 2000) as our theoretical lens as it allows us to increase knowledge on how companies cope with and make sense of the overarching cost-sustainability paradox and the tensions it creates in the complex system comprising the buying company in connection to its many direct suppliers, who are ultimately subject to this demand. In other words, a paradox lens enables us to explore the existence and acceptance of tensions stemming from a contradictory but interdependent focal paradox by unpacking the tensions as they unfold and teasing out managerial responses, including the potential for novel and creative outcomes to meet performance demands for both environmental sustainability and cost-focus (Schad et al., 2016).

We believe this theoretical perspective has the potential to enrich the growing literature on SSCM and SSD (Jia et al., 2021; Rodriguez et al., 2016), by providing an understanding of how a company makes sense of and copes with a seemingly conflicting situation that necessitates SSD. Therefore, we seek to answer the following research question: *How do companies with a history of a cost leadership strategy cope with the paradoxical demands for low-cost and environmental sustainability performance of their global suppliers?*

To answer our research question, we focus on gaining deep insights explored over time in an in-depth single case study setting (Dubois & Araujo, 2007) across levels of analysis (Lewis & Smith, 2014). This includes interviews, documents, and observations involving managers from a buying company and its suppliers. The focal case company, Retailer X, has historically operated its global supply chain from a highly cost-focused perspective but has now signed up for the Science Based Targets initiative, demanding costly action to report on and reduce their scope 3 GHG emissions within a bounded period of 5-10 years.

We expect to contribute to the literature on SSCM and SSD by creating in-depth insights into this complex task, where the focal paradox generates a series of tensions across the vertical and horizontal internal organisation and spreads to the suppliers, who are ultimately responsible for the production and logistics processes that create the emissions. For instance, managers with supply responsibilities may be pulled in different directions as they balance a historical emphasis on cost reductions and sustainability in their purchasing actions and supplier management with varying sense-making and responses to such tension (Lewis & Smith, 2014). Likewise, suppliers may be in a similar contradictory setting, having to increase their sustainable performance and simultaneously provide cost reductions. Moreover, there may be internal tensions and varying responses between departments, teams, or individuals as they work under competing forces of sustainable and economic performance.

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Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 2. PSM strategy

The role of not-for-profit research centres in the reshoring of manufacturing

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This study examines how not-for-profit research centres influence the reshoring initiatives of for-profit firms. Using the UK's High Value Manufacturing Catapult (HVMC) as a case study, it explores how government-funded organisations provide essential infrastructure, expertise, and incentives to encourage manufacturers to bring back production. Data was collected through 35 semi-structured interviews from the seven innovation centres within the HVMC network. Dunning's eclectic paradigm serves as the theoretical framework to assess whether not-for-profit innovation catapults can enhance location attractiveness and positively impact the relocation decisions of for-profit firms. The findings inform a framework that helps managers navigate the barriers encountered during the various stages of reshoring.

Paper topic

6. Outsourcing, offshoring, reshoring

Critical Raw Materials, Geosciences, and Supply Chain Management: Towards an Integrated Approach

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Critical Raw Materials (CRM) have been listed by the European Union (EU) as materials with high economic importance and a high supply risk. These materials, vital for future based technologies like batteries, permanent magnets, semiconductors and renewable energy are obtained through primary (geological sources, mining, and refining) and secondary (mine tailings, recycling, and urban mining) sources. The demand for these materials is expected to at least quadruple by 2024, to meet the directives of the Paris Agreement. This trend is evident with countries escalating their efforts to secure these minerals with regulations like the new Critical Raw Materials Act in the EU and the Inflation Reduction Act in the USA. CRMs are essential for a circular and sustainable future.

Supply Chains of CRMs are complex to manage, due to the interactions between key factors from geological and processing constraints and supply chain management practices. Geologically, CRMs are constrained at the source by limited and specific depositional environments, feasibility to extract and in some cases climatic conditions. Furthermore, refining expertise and infrastructure are restrained to specific countries, increasing supply chain vulnerability. End consumers are based in different locations than producers, increasing dependencies. As an example, in the case of the battery industry where Lithium (Li) and Cobalt (Co) are used, primary production is focused on South America, Africa and Oceania and consumption is largely based in USA, EU, China, making an imbalance evident. Mining activities are driven by investments and exploration, which in turn are influenced by its demand from the supply chain manufactures and end users. The demand and therefore the price of these minerals often determines the feasibility for primary production of these minerals. Limited exploration due to lack of investments, declining ore grades, by-production and the need for sustainable mining further affect security of supply.

From a supply chain perspective, traditional mitigation techniques like stockpiling, diversification and supply redundancy are restricted by geological and refining limitations of CRMs. Alternatives and substitutes to these minerals are few, due to their physical and chemical properties. Besides this, supply chain managers are tasked with making procurement decisions, many without the required knowledge of the upstream supply chain of these minerals. This contributes to overmining and price volatility or, alternatively, price drops and closures of mines. Supply chains resilience is impacted further by

geological limitations like location specificity of minerals, by-production and exhaustion of mineral reserves, among others. Geographical specificity of processing knowledge and infrastructure leads to disruptions and uncertainty. These point towards a complex interdependent cause-effect relationship between geological constraints and supply chain decisions, whose exact structure seems to be currently unknown.

Nonetheless, developing resilient and robust CRM supply chains is a critical nexus for the future, given the relevance that those products have for key industries that have strong societal implications. Thus, understanding the structure and interactions between the geological and supply chain components has strong implications in securing supply chains whose products are at the backbone of the energy transition, as well as inform policy development in this field. This requires a view into the supply chain and transparency in the sourcing, production, manufacturing, and procurement of these materials. It is unclear which variables factor into this relationship, nor how do these variables interrelate with each other. Moreover, most literature in both supply chain management and geosciences is largely siloed, with limited overlap and acknowledgment of respective findings. This calls for an exploratory approach, revolving around the question:

How do geological factors interrelate with supply chain management decisions within the context of CRM supply chains?

We address these questions through an exploratory setting aimed at providing a conceptual base for grounding the practical issue of CRM management in existing knowledge on both supply chain management and geoscience, supporting further explorations. We aim at conducting a set of exploratory interviews with stakeholders knowledgeable of both supply chain management and the geological aspects of CRMs. Ultimately, our work aims at producing a theoretical framework that illustrate the complexity and interrelation between factors that play a role in CRMs management, supporting further validation and empirical research in this field.

We aim at exploring the role of supply chain transparency and mapping, identify stakeholders and understand their motivations, interactions, and priorities between them. This has strong implications, both theoretically and from a societal perspective. Theoretically, such a framework can support more integrated and unified knowledge development efforts on both the supply chain and geoscience sides. From a societal perspective, this framework can help build momentum towards developing CRM supply chains in an equitable, socio-environmental conscious and sustainable direction. This framework will also form the bases for further empirical research as part of a PhD study focused on understanding the causality between geoscience and supply chain management, bridging the gap between the two disciplines.

Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 18. Risk and resilience, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Integration of Artificial Intelligence in Supply Chain Risk and Disruption Management: Analysis and Concept Development of a LLM-Based Event Identification System

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Abstract

The increasing complexity and vulnerability of global supply chains, particularly in the automotive industry, have prompted significant concerns regarding supply stability. Recent disruptions, exemplified by the Covid-19 pandemic and the Suez Canal blockade, have underscored the critical need for effective supply chain risk management (SCRM) practices. This paper addresses the existing gap in leveraging diverse data sources to enhance supply chain visibility and resilience.

Introduction

The globalization of the manufacturing industry has led to increasingly complex and vulnerable supply chains, particularly in the automotive sector (Ahmad et al., 2024). Recent disruptions, such as the Covid-19 pandemic and the Suez Canal blockade, have highlighted the dependence of industries on international goods flow and the unpredictability of external factors affecting supply stability. This growing concern has elevated the importance of Supply Chain Risk Management (SCRM) practices, especially in automotive supply chains (Rezki and Mansouri, 2023). However, a significant gap remains in leveraging information from diverse sources to enhance supply chain visibility and resilience. Our research focuses on the initial identification and analysis of supply risks and disruptions, aiming to reduce the time needed for threat identification and the timely implementation of mitigation strategies.

Methodology

To ensure scientific rigor, we conducted a comprehensive literature analysis to identify existing propositions in supply chain disruption and risk management, as well as the methodological approaches utilized to examine and validate relevant concepts. The conducted review contains the steps identification, screening, eligibility and inclusion of scientific literature (see Sharma et al., 2022,

Bhattacharya et al., 2024). Therefore, based on the content-related objective of our analysis, we define search terms, collect and filter the results and perform a content analysis on the identified articles. The search of academic literature focuses on recent developments in AI applications in supply chain contexts and derives a gap in event based, AI-integrated risk management tools for real time risk management.

Based on our analysis we propose an innovative event-based supply chain risk identification system that integrates commercially available Large Language Models (LLMs) with both external news data and internal supply chain information. By relying on pre-trained, market-available LLMs rather than developing custom models, the system ensures continuous access to state-of-the-art advancements in AI technology. This approach minimizes development overhead while enabling the system to benefit from the rapid evolution of LLM capabilities, thereby providing a scalable and future-proof solution for supply chain risk identification.

The objectives are to streamline the identification of supply risks and disruptions and to facilitate timely mitigation strategies. Through the comprehensive literature analysis, we examine current propositions, methodological approaches and identify the potential of LLMs in processing unstructured text data for risk identification. Our proposed framework aims to enhance the operational value of AI applications by combining automated news extraction with internal logistics databases. The concept includes a news feed, a logistics database, a LLM, and a user-friendly graphical interface. As seen in Nyqvist et al. (2024), we plan to empirically validate this framework through case studies in the automotive sector, enabling quantitative and qualitative assessments of its effectiveness. Our research aims to provide actionable insights for supply chain disruption managers and contribute to the theoretical discourse on AI applications in supply chain management. Future studies will extend this framework to other industries, enhancing its applicability and robustness in various contexts.

Supply Chain Risk and Disruption Management

Supply Chain Risk Management (SCRM) is a multifaceted discipline encompassing the identification, evaluation, mitigation, and continuous monitoring of supply risks (Fan and Stevenson, 2018). It is complementary to Supply Chain Disruption Management (SCDM), which becomes relevant once a disruption has occurred. As proposed by Behdani et al. (2012), both concepts are unified in a framework termed Supply Chain Disruption and Risk Management (SCDRM). Identifying risks and disruptions quickly is crucial for minimizing their negative impacts on supply stability (Macdonald and Corsi, 2013). The complexity of global supply networks therefore necessitates an efficient disruption management system to handle unexpected events effectively.

Previous Applications of AI in Supply Chain Risk Management

Our structured literature analysis reveals that previous studies predominantly focus on specific aspects of risk and disruption management using AI, particularly Natural Language Processing (NLP). Existing research lacks a comprehensive approach to integrating external information and internal company data for the practical identification and assessment of external disruptions. Instead, previous publications have used NLP for subtasks within the risk identification process, such as analyzing patterns in internal supplier-related data to predict the likelihood of future supply disruptions caused by a particular supplier company (see e.g. Rezki and Mansouri, 2024). Extensive model training and fine-tuning have often hindered real-world implementation, limiting the practical utility of these approaches for dynamic and time-sensitive disruption management.

Event Identification Application Concept

We propose a Large Language Model (LLM)-based event identification system comprising several components: news-feeds, such as RSS, a logistics database for internal supply chain data, a pre-trained commercial LLM, and a graphical user interface (GUI) for user interaction. News-feeds will deliver unstructured text data from reliable sources in a structured and timely manner, while the logistics database will supply essential supply chain information to improve the precision and relevance of event identification. The LLM will serve as an agent to evaluate the relevance of news articles and perform preliminary cause analyses based on the combined data. The proposed components of the application concept which shall be orchestrated to a web based application are:

- **News-Feeds:** This component retrieves unstructured text data from reliable news sources through RSS or Atom feeds, using predefined keywords related to potential supply chain disruptions. By leveraging a diverse range of trusted news outlets, the system ensures efficient and timely identification of relevant events.
- **Logistics Database:** Incorporating specific supply chain data, such as supplier information and transportation times, enhances the precision of risk identification by providing detailed context. This integration enables targeted cause analysis of affected products and suppliers.
- **Large Language Model:** The core of the system is the commercial pre-trained LLM, which evaluates the relevance of news articles to the supply chain. To further optimize event identification, the system incorporates Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG). This approach enables the Large Language Model (LLM) to retrieve relevant supply chain data dynamically from the logistics database during the analysis of external disruptions, ensuring more context-aware and accurate insights. Furthermore, incorporating reinforcement learning from human feedback has shown positive effects on LLM output quality in previous empirical research and thus further refines the event identification process by leveraging user input during operations, particularly when integrated into the Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) Layer to dynamically combine external and internal data (Aboutorab et al., 2023 Zhu and Vuppalapati, 2024).
- **Graphical User Interface:** A user-friendly interface is designed to assist disruption managers in navigating identified risks. The GUI enables users to view relevant alerts, analyze potential impacts, and engage with the LLM for additional insights.

Course of Evaluation

To assess the operational value of our proposed concept, we will conduct case studies in real life business context in the automotive sector, utilizing both quantitative and qualitative evaluation methods. Based on the analysis of previous studies, performance measures will include precision, accuracy, F1-score and RMSE. Additionally, qualitative interviews with disruption managers will provide insights into the system's strengths and weaknesses, informing potential improvements (Nyqvist et al., 2024).

Summary and Outlook

This study addresses the rising importance of SCRM and SCDM in response to external influences on supply stability. By leveraging NLP algorithms, we aim to fill the existing gap in the application of LLMs for risk and disruption management. Our proposed concept integrates external news sources with internal supply chain data to enhance operational insights. Future research will expand the applicability

of this concept to other industries, such as construction, to validate its effectiveness across different contexts. Ultimately, our work aims to provide a practical, accessible framework for disruption managers to utilize LLMs in identifying and assessing supply chain disruptions and also risks effectively.

Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience

183

Organization design of socially oriented public-private collaborations

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

How should public-private collaborations (PPCs) be organized for social value creation, given the inherent tensions of cross-sector initiatives? We conduct an inductive multi-case study on social value creation in urban public spaces and find that the plural nature of social value generates operational complexities and multitask agency problems that the organization design must address. Design choices depend on: the PPC's specification abilities; the comparative capabilities of available actors; and their interest alignment. A broadened transaction cost economics framework therefore best explains PPCs' design choices, considering both incentive conflicts and adaptation needs in response to operational complexity.

Paper topic

13. Public procurement

184

Demand curve approach, an award method to choose the most suitable tender

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Practitioner Paper

Abstract/summary

This article describes how the often-used linear weighted factor method can be adapted to 'play' with the intersection of the production cost curves and the demand curve. The PQ-area is divided into two parts via a demand curve: below the demand curve the supply of extra quality points is encouraged, above it discouraged. In this way the contracting authority communicates its preference for quality and costs.

Paper topic

1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 13. Public procurement, 5. Supplier selection

Pulling Whom?: The (Heterogeneous) Demand-Pull Effect of Green Public Procurement

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Green Public Procurement (GPP) is considered as a demand-pull instrument to stimulate the green transition of the supply market. We investigate the effects of GPP wins across subgroups of manufacturing firms. GPP contracts are awarded more often to larger and greener firms, while the effect of GPP is stronger among pollution-intensive firms that face high competition. After the first GPP win, firms win more GPP contracts while reducing their pollution in following years, which suggests that firms grow into the green procurement market. Our findings provide suggestive evidence that GPP creates or shapes markets.

Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental

The role of the procurement function in a Circular Economy

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Introduction

The transition to a circular economy is crucial for addressing environmental crises. The European Commission has made this transition a key part of its Green Deal strategy, and some companies have developed successful business models around it. However, the transition is challenging, especially for established companies due to path dependencies.

The procurement function is vital in this transition, acting as a "gatekeeper" to the supply chain and identifying new innovations and partners. It can identify new materials and suppliers to enable circular material flows. Additionally, procurement can play a role in "closing the loop" by managing the return and reuse of resources. This function faces challenges in managing diverse resource flows and establishing strong supplier partnerships.

Because of this important role the procurement function can play in the transition, we investigate the following research question in our study:

What is the current and future role of the procurement function in the transition to a circular economy?

Literature and theoretical background

The circular economy (CE) is defined as a restorative or regenerative system (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013) and as an economic system that replaces the 'end-of-life' concept with reducing, reusing, recycling, and recovering materials to achieve sustainable development (Kirchherr et al., 2017). Bocken et al. (2016) introduce three principles for circular energy and material flows: closing, slowing, and narrowing the loops. To encompass the diverse opportunities, Geissdoerfer et al. (2018) add intensifying and dematerializing loops:

1. **Closing the loops:** This involves recycling and remanufacturing to reuse materials, creating a system that minimizes waste and reduces reliance on virgin materials. Examples include recycling plastic bottles.

2. **Slowing the loops:** This principle extends the life of products through robust design, repair, maintenance, and refurbishment. For instance, a repairable smartphone can significantly extend its useful life, reducing waste and the need for a new product for a longer time.
3. **Intensifying loops:** Introduced by Geissdoerfer et al. (2018), this focuses on shared use of products, as seen in the sharing economy (e.g., car-sharing services), maximizing utility and reducing the need for personal ownership.
4. **Narrowing the loops:** This aims to optimize resource use per product unit by improving production methods and design, such as using lightweight materials or energy-efficient techniques.
5. **Dematerializing the loops:** This concept replaces physical products with services, shifting from product ownership to product-service systems, like using car-sharing services instead of owning a car, thus reducing resource use.

Pollice and Batocchio (2018) highlight the new role of procurement in a circular economy, emphasizing mindset changes and systemic tasks. While prior studies have explored sustainable procurement, the systemic and holistic role of procurement in enabling circular economy transitions remains underexplored. Sönnichsen and Clement (2021) explore sustainable public procurement patterns for circular economy implementation. Definitions vary, with Quazi and Appoloni (2022) describing circular procurement as integrating circularity into procurement to purchase regenerated materials and close supply chain loops. However, this definition may not fully capture procurement's holistic and systemic role in a circular economy.

CE is currently in a dynamically developing state. New inventions and business models lead to opportunities and threats to which companies need to adapt rapidly. For such business environments, Teece et al. (2007) suggest Dynamic Capabilities (DC) as the theoretical lens. We apply DC to understand the role of procurement to sensing, seizing and reconfiguring (Teece et al., 2007) the internal business processes and strategies and influence the external business environment.

Methodology

The world café method, used in procurement research (Schiele et al., 2022; Beske-Janssen et al., 2023), involves expert groups discussing topics at different "café tables." Moderators guide discussions and take visible notes. Groups rotate, building on previous discussions to explore new phenomena and research paths. After several rounds, participants vote on the most relevant results. This method allows for dynamic discussions and iterative development of insights particular in a novel research area.

We conducted two World Cafés to gather preliminary results for later in-depth interviews. The first World Café was broader in scope including not only circular procurement, but other topics related to sustainable procurement, such as sustainable innovation, as well. Based on the results of the first World Café, we conducted a second one with a distinct focus on circular procurement and three identified roles from the first World Café.

Preliminary results

Preliminary findings highlight procurement's role in closing, slowing, and narrowing resource loops, with challenges in material quality, supplier collaboration, and cross-sector resource integration. The study identifies three key roles for procurement—investigation, facilitation, and implementation—aligned with dynamic capabilities theory. Participants highlighted recycling as a key aspect for circularity,

focusing on using recycled materials or ensuring their products are fully recyclable to avoid landfill. However, challenges with recycled materials, such as quality concerns, were also discussed.

Slowing the loops involves procurement sourcing technologies that support repair or reuse. The proactive role of procurement in challenging suppliers to create more circular products was emphasized. This includes design to extend product lifespans and raising awareness within the procurement team.

Intensifying the loops, like sharing products, is less established, with few examples mentioned. Narrowing the loops involves finding more circular materials, with procurement being involved in the product design process. Dematerializing the loops was briefly mentioned, focusing on services for own use rather than offering services themselves.

Based on the results of the world cafés we propose to distinguish the procurement function into an internal and external part, where it can enable a transition to CE in three different roles. Based on the first world café we identified investigation, facilitation and implementation which we translated into the micro foundations laid out by Teece et. al (2007) for the second World Café. Sensing (investigating) includes, for example, the acquisition of new knowledge. Seizing (facilitating) would include involvement in product development or internal-external alignment of requirements. Finally, reconfiguring (implementing), entails internal education or implementing new tender criteria related to CE.

Preliminary Discussion and Conclusion

We can clearly see the relevance of the procurement function for the transition to a CE. This role is characterized by a stronger involvement of sensing opportunities, seizing the relevant ones aiding in their implementation through reconfiguring. However, it is also obvious that there is not a general answer to the research question due to differences in industries, business model approaches or also closeness of companies to the final consumers.

Further, while there is already a well-established understanding of the potential for the procurement function in a CE, the implementation is only starting. Additionally, the perception of procurements role seems to be rooted in the linear economy. Participants are seeing the function mainly related to the upstream side of their supply chain. Considering the downstream part of their supply chains as future resource streams, i.e. truly closing the loop, has not come up. A stronger emphasis on the potential of circular nature might be necessary to fill this gap. Additionally, participants often focus on their core industries when it comes to connecting resource streams. The discussion about using cross-sector resources, e.g. from so far unrelated industries as a possible resource providers is only gearing up slowly.

This suggests that much potential is still dormant. The study underscores the need for procurement to adopt a more strategic and systemic approach, transitioning from a linear to a circular mindset. This includes fostering cross-sector collaboration and redefining procurement as a resource management function.

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Paper topic

2. PSM strategy, 10. Purchasing innovation, 16. Sustainability - environmental

Market stewarding's design principles in public procurement: A case study reflection and systems dynamics modelling approach – providing qualitative and analytic arguments.

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This paper examines how market stewarding design principles, inspired by Ostrom's design principles for managing common-pool resources can address inefficiencies in public procurement. Using case studies from the Netherlands, Slovakia, and Thailand, it identifies systemic governance issues such as information asymmetry, supplier collusion, and biased tendering. Regarding analyses, first, we reflect on Ostrom's principles for adaptable interventions, and second, we develop a System Dynamics Model (SDM) to simulate the impact of information asymmetry for the Dutch case. Findings show that targeted interventions can stabilize markets and lower costs, providing a robust framework for enacting stewarding.

Paper topic

13. Public procurement

Competition in Software Procurement: Exploring the Influence of Software Requirement Specifications on Sourcing Dynamics

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, purchasing and supply management literature has explored various factors influencing supplier behavior and selection. However, the critical role of requirement specifications is notably absent from these discussions. While software requirement specifications were extensively studied in engineering contexts (Franch et al., 2023), their significance within procurement processes remains underrepresented. This research aims to address this gap by investigating how the properties of requirement specifications impact the sourcing process of open tenders, particularly in the inherently complex context of software development, emphasizing relevant implications for research and practice.

Software has become fundamentally ingrained in the operations and products of firms. With the ongoing digital transformation, the demand for software has massively grown. In the next five years, a rise in revenue of 30.35 % in the global software market is forecasted, reaching 858 billion US dollars in 2028 (Statista, 2023). In response to this trend, information technology (IT) governance has emerged as a growing subfield of the classic governance mechanisms literature. IT governance focuses on how organizations align their IT investments with their strategic goals, while managing risks and delivering value. According to Weill (2004), *“IT governance represents the framework for decision rights and accountabilities to encourage desirable behavior in the use of IT”*, where *“governance is about systemically determining who makes each type of decision (a decision right), who has input to a decision (an input right) and how these people (or groups) are held accountable for their role”* (p. 3). Within IT governance, different decision-making frameworks, including accountability structures and performance metrics, are proposed to balance the demands of technical teams and business priorities (Brown and Grant, 2005). While these frameworks contribute to organizational alignment, challenges persist at the intersection of technical and procurement functions. Research and development departments often prioritize technical feasibility and operational effectiveness (Haines, 2009), whereas procurement aims to achieve cost efficiency and risk mitigation (Van Weele and Van Raaij, 2014). These misalignments can lead to inefficiencies in the sourcing process, strained interdepartmental relations, and reduced coordination (Melander and Tell, 2019). Central to this tension is the software requirement specification document (SRS) as the central instrument used in software development to formalize the sourcing requirements. The SRS serves as a critical link between business stakeholders and technical teams,

outlining functional and non-functional elements to align stakeholders and provide a clear reference for development, testing, documentation, and future changes. The dominant stakeholder is the technical department. Procurement often plays a subordinate role and has limited influence in the SRS creation. The literature states that hardware requirement specifications are usually very precise, yet SRS show fuzziness, with many failing to specify budgets, implementation timelines and detailed evaluation criteria (Nguyen et al., 2022). Flexible requirement specifications, focusing on desired outcome rather than specific tools and methods, foster innovation and competition among suppliers. However, vague requirements may be exploited to create lock-in situations (Johansson and Lahtinen, 2013).

A review of the literature reveals extensive research on IT governance mechanisms and interdepartmental dynamics. Still, a gap remains in connecting these findings to the nuanced impact of SRS documents on supplier behavior and competition in sourcing events. Building on this observation, we emphasize the importance of analyzing the influence of technical interests on procurement preconditions. Therefore, this paper asks the following research question: *How do software requirement specifications influence the procurement process of open tenders, particularly regarding supplier behavior and competition?*

EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

The empirical analysis is based on a comprehensive dataset of software-related sourcing projects conducted between 2020 and 2024 at a German automotive Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM). Data from different internal systems were merged to create the basis for this research. The final dataset encompasses 556 multiple-bidder projects, filtered from an initial pool of 2,649 by excluding tenders submitted to a single supplier. These projects span a diverse range of software types, from standard licenses to customized platforms, and focus on domains such as automotive security, infotainment, smart mobility, driver assistance, connectivity, and embedded software services. Each project is represented by an entry containing detailed information about the tender, the suppliers, the offers, and the financial metrics together with the associated textual SRS documents. On average, 17.5 bids were submitted per sourcing project, with the number of bids ranging from 2 to 125 per sourcing. We combined numerical and categorical information from each sourcing project with textual information from the corresponding SRS documentation. Numerical and categorical information is derived from the internal systems. The textual information is extracted using a text mining approach, which will focus on three underlying methods to perform the text mining. These include automated feature extraction based on existing libraries for extracting formal properties (Merrouni et al., 2020), which are based on methods established in existing SRS literature (Kummler, 2019). In addition, software domain specific feature extraction rules are derived from expert interviews and are semi automatically extracted from the requirement documents. Finally, large language models are used to extract complex features, such as functional dependencies, requirement ambiguity and semantic meaning (Xu et al., 2024). To address the research question, a linear model with multi-way fixed effects is used (Verdier, 2020). The SRS-specific variables generated serve as the independent variables in this study's statistical model. The dependent variables represent supplier behavior and the overall level of competition in each sourcing project. Supplier behavior is quantified as the ratio of submitted bids to the total number of suppliers invited to bid. To accurately reflect the true level of competition, this variable is further refined by considering the proportion of technically acceptable offers. The fixed effects are based on suppliers, intra-firm purchasing groups, and software segments while keeping the control variables contract type, contract duration and sourcing budget constant.

CONTRIBUTION

Following the call of Althabatah et al. (2023), who emphasize the transformative potential of big data analytics to enhance procurement processes, we adopted a methodological design that combined the quantitative analysis of secondary data with advanced text mining techniques. This study aims to demonstrate that nuanced features of SRS, such as complexity, flexibility and semantic coherence, significantly influence supplier participation rates and the technical viability of sourcing projects. The findings contribute to our theoretical understanding of how internal IT governance influences external competitive dynamics in procurement. Managerial implications include strategies to optimize supplier engagement and foster inter-departmental collaboration.

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Paper topic

5. Supplier selection, 2. PSM strategy, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

191

The Evolving Risks of Defense Supply Chains: A Longitudinal Perspective on Resilience

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The paper examines how major defense companies have managed internal, supply-side, and demand risks over the past decade by analyzing annual reports (with the help of AI) from seven defense firms . It finds that while demand risks have stabilized with steady defense budgets, internal and supply risks have grown more complex due to technological challenges and various geopolitical disruptions. Companies have responded by diversifying suppliers, bolstering digital operations, and engaging more closely with government stakeholders.

Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience

Fostering Learning Skills Through Game-Based Learning: Scenario Exploration System Approach at Supply Chain Management Course

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

With this research, we provide evidence of the adaptation and integration of a serious game, based on the Scenario Exploration System, into the field of Operations and Supply Chain Management to develop skills in bachelor-level studies. Through an interactive and participatory process in the Supply Chain Management course, the game enables participants to acquire and share knowledge and explore the interests, motivations, and strategies of different societal actors. The adapted version targeted specifically the supply chain problems and challenges and motivated students to think holistically about the supply chains. Based on the field experiment with a cohort of third-year bachelor students, an improvement in change management, stakeholder management, creativity and creative problem-solving skills, communication and relationship management, strategy and analytics, and holistic supply chain thinking skills have been demonstrated. The study lays out the perspectives and limitations for future implementations and developments.

Paper topic

15. PSM theory, methodology, education

Can Sustainable Practices mitigate supply risk of Critical Raw Materials? Evidence from the automotive industry

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Keywords: Critical Raw Materials, Supply Chain Resilience, Supply risk, Sustainability performance, Automotive industry

Context: The European Commission has defined the “criticality” of materials based on two key indicators, namely their economic importance and their potential supply risks (European Commission, 2023). In particular, Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) possess unique physical and chemical properties, making them essential for the digital and green transition and in key industries, such as aerospace and defense. As a result, securing access to CRMs is imperative for the European Union (EU) in order to strengthen competitiveness, stimulate innovation and facilitate the transition to a sustainable, low-carbon economy.

Demand for CRMs is growing as a result of multiple factors. First, EU’s ambitious net-zero carbon targets for 2050, along with initiatives aimed at accelerating electrification and promoting economic growth in emerging markets (Liu et al., 2019; Wiebe et al., 2012). Next, escalation of military tensions further intensifies this demand, as CRMs are integral to the development of modern defense systems (National Research Council, 2008). Against this backdrop, questions persist regarding the sufficiency of global supply to meet these needs (Draghi, 2024) and the uncertain availability of CRMs has become a central concern for the competitiveness of the European manufacturing sector (Draghi, 2024). The current overreliance on external CRM sources can cause significant disruption to supply chains, thereby underscoring supply risks as a second indicator in the EU’s criticality assessment (Løvik et al., 2018; European Commission, 2023). In fact, the availability of CRMs is uncertain and susceptible to dynamic and unpredictable disruptions due to their inherent scarcity and geographical concentration. The limited concentration of CRMs in few countries, which are responsible for most of the extraction and refining processes, not only endangers the stability of global supply chains due to the reliance on politically sensitive regions, but also increases the probability of disruptions resulting from policy shifts and operational failures. In recent years, trade restrictions on CRMs have proliferated, complicating logistics, increasing price volatility, and reinforcing monopolistic structures (Ediriweera and Wiewiora, 2021). This vulnerability extends to manufacturing, where supply disruptions can lead to delays and increased costs,

further exacerbated by price fluctuations (Draghi, 2024; Løvik et al., 2018). Moreover, while recycling CRMs from end-of-life products presents an alternative supply opportunity, current technologies are often inefficient and costly (Dominiguez et al., 2019). These challenges, alongside improper disposal of CRM-containing products, threaten supply continuity and pose sustainability concerns (Sauer and Seuring, 2019). Hence, CRM-reliant industries are among the most polluting and generate a considerable amount of waste, contributing to the emission of greenhouse gases, the degradation of ecosystems, and the loss of biodiversity. The resulting decline in these ecosystems raises concerns about the potential health and safety risks to local communities with whom these industries interact. Additionally, labor exploitation and conflicts in mining regions pose ethical concerns and threaten supply chain stability through protests and disruptions (Herrington and Gordon, 2024). This, in turn, has resulted in a further strain on supply chains, as both customers and regulatory frameworks require a heightened level of commitment to ethical conduct and sustainability (Sauer and Seuring, 2019).

To overcome these challenge, recent literature has suggested the potential of sustainable practices aimed at addressing CRM supply risk. Multiple studies suggest that sustainable practices for CRM management, including those practices associated with eco-design and circular economy, can offer alternative and more sustainable sources of supply, thereby mitigating risks traditionally associated with non-sustainable sourcing while fostering supply chain resilience and other benefits such as job creation, economic growth and environmentally friendly products and processes (Ferro et al., 2020; Gaustad et al., 2023; Hagelüken and Goldmann, 2022).

Purpose: While extant literature extensively explores the challenges posed by CRM supply risks, particularly in CRM-intensive industries, a significant gap in understanding the role of sustainable practices in mitigating these risks remains. Specifically, few studies have empirically examined how sustainable practices might impact supply risk exposure and influence supply chain resilience as well as sustainability performance (e.g., Gardner and Colwill, 2016; Van den Brink et al., 2020). This study aims to fill this gap by empirically investigating how sustainable practices affect supply risk exposure and contribute to building resilient supply chains, alongside fostering improved sustainability performance in CRM-intensive manufacturing industries.

Methodology: To achieve these goals, empirical research will target decision-makers and supply chain managers within the automotive industry, a CRM-intensive field particularly susceptible to supply risks (Ortego et al., 2020). The study will focus on automotive manufacturing companies located in Germany and Italy, two leading nations in this industry characterized by advanced industrial capabilities and distinct policy frameworks (Dechezleprêtre et al., 2023). This context is ideal for investigating how sustainable practices mediate the relationship between CRM-related supply risk exposure and supply chain resilience and sustainability performance. Data collection will draw on validated frameworks and new constructs developed from a comprehensive literature review to ensure robustness and relevance. The interview protocol will explore key constructs, including the adoption of sustainable practices (e.g., circular economy, material substitution), the level of CRM-related risk exposure (e.g., geopolitical, market, and technological risks), and metrics for sustainability performance and resilience (e.g., resource efficiency, adaptive capacity). Appropriate analytical approaches will be applied to analyze the intricate relationships among the involved constructs and explore their interconnections as outlined in the conceptual framework.

Expected outcomes: The expected outcomes of this study are multi-faceted. First, the research aims at developing a theoretical framework that describes the relationships between sustainable practices, supply risk exposure, sustainability performance, and resilience in the automotive manufacturing

industry. This framework will provide a holistic understanding of how sustainability-driven practices can mitigate CRM-related supply risks and enhance environmental, economic, and social performance of supply chains. Second, findings are expected to offer actionable insights for the industry, thus helping automotive companies adopt targeted practices that reduce their vulnerability to CRM-related supply risks and improve their resilience. Third, this study will contribute to policy discussions by highlighting the importance of sustainable practices in fostering resilient and sustainable manufacturing industries, thus fostering alignment with EU objectives.

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Paper topic

20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.), 18. Risk and resilience, 16.

Sustainability - environmental

Maverick buying: Reveal, Regulate, and Reduce

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

Maverick buying refers to procurement activities that do not align with procurement governance. The literature distinguishes between different types of maverick buying; however, it remains unclear whether there are any potential positive aspects beyond its negative effects, particularly the lack of transparency within an organisation. This research addresses this ambiguity by applying supply holobiont theory to frame the overarching issues of supply base transparency, accessibility, and symbiotic collaboration with suppliers. Based on this framework, the study contrasts two primary effects of maverick buying: (1) its impact on supply transparency and (2) its influence on collaboration, specifically supplier fit and supplier symbiosis. Using a sample of 307 questionnaire responses, a structural equation model was developed to compare the effects of these constructs. The findings indicate that maverick buying has solely negative consequences for performance and as such is in line with previous research. Even its indirect effects on procurement performance are detrimental. In contrast, the results highlight that performance is driven by transparency and collaboration (supplier fit and symbiosis). The implications of this study underscore the need to raise further awareness of the negative effects of maverick buying. At the same time, the research calls for a deeper examination of organisational openness and the interplay between competition and collaboration in purchasing and supply management.

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 13. Public procurement, 15. PSM theory, methodology, education

Biases in medical test procurement

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Introduction

Medical diagnostic testing is the cornerstone of healthcare management. These “health condition measurements” help with timely and correct diagnosis of illnesses, thus enabling medical professionals to craft more effective personalized treatment plans for individual patients (Badric and Bowling, 2023). However, despite this pivotal role, rarely do healthcare systems have sufficient resources to perform as many tests as otherwise desired. This is especially true for screening tests in which a large number of tests are needed, and expensive tests which can strain the constrained budget of healthcare systems (Subramanian et al. 2010). An example in case is the recent cuts in the proposed cuts in screening test budgets in Finland (Yle, 2024).

As a result, certain compromises have to be made in healthcare procurement when deciding the number of each test to be bought within a given budget. Moreover, adding to the complexity of such decisions, diagnostic tests are often available with different prices and qualities relating to inaccuracy rates in terms of false positives (e.g. Streiner, 2016) and false negative rates. For simplicity, we exclude the conditions under which some tests may become scarce –e.g., due to a pandemic (Drakopoulos and Randhawa, 2021).

Therefore, compromises in allocation of resources of the healthcare system to the purchase of stocks of different diagnostic tests are inevitable. However, human decision-makers (e.g., procurement managers of healthcare systems) rather than algorithms, often decide diagnostic test portfolios. Human decision-makers are prone to such judgmental biases as status quo bias (Samuelson and Zeckhauser, 1988), anchoring bias (e.g., Lieder et al., 2018; Ly et al., 2023) and confirmation bias (Oswald and Grosjean, 2004) while also suffering from limited cognitive capacity leading to bounded rationality (Conlisk, 1996) further fueling the biases. That is, we expect diagnostic test purchasing decisions to be at least sub-optimal and likely also biased in certain directions.

In addition to these and similar judgmental biases, a agency problem may further affect such healthcare procurement decisions. While the procurement manager may be perceived to be an agent (the principal being the healthcare system), the healthcare system as a whole may also be perceived to be an agent

(the principal being the target population that the system should serve). While the consequences of the former agency problem are well-studied (Matinheikki et al. 2024), those of the latter are not –being the main focus of the present work.

The mission of any sound healthcare system should be to maximize welfare of its target population through provision of healthcare services within its constrained budget. Hence, in the first look, an agency problem should not occur as a conflict of interest does not exist. However, two causes, one largely specific to medical diagnostic tests, give rise to agency problems. First, healthcare systems tend to be more aware of costs incurred than value provided (Qaseem et al. 2012; Hood and Weinberger, 2012)–partly because costs are more explicit and measurable (Matinheikki et al. 2024). The cost function then likely includes the actual costs for the healthcare system, including both testing and treatment costs (NCI, 2024). On the other hand, it often overlooks the costs beared by the patients including their share of medical expenses and home-care supplies –by extension also including the nonmonetary cost of pain and discomfort (Yeh, 2017).

Second, it is even less likely that the costs of lost opportunities for the patients be taken into account in the procurement decision making efforts of the healthcare system. This is a cost largely associated with inaccuracy rates of medical diagnostic tests. For example, the cost of a false positive result for the healthcare system often equals *only* the cost of unnecessary medicine and doctor visits. For the patients, however, it equals their share of medical expenses plus the lost opportunity cost of the time spent on treatment and potentially quarantine. As yet another example, the cost of false negative inaccuracy for the healthcare system often equals the cost difference of timely (early) treatment versus late treatment. For the patient, the cost function includes the lost opportunity costs of lowered quality of life and life expectancy. While these patient-side costs of diagnostic test inaccuracy are sometimes studied for the benefit of public (Drakopoulos and Randhawa, 2021) seldom they are considered in budgeting and diagnostic test purchasing efforts.

Research questions

The main research questions we aim to address is as follows: What determines healthcare spend allocation decisions about portfolio selection of diagnostic tests for a target population? Determining this portfolio entails decisions on the number of each test to be bought and making accuracy-price compromises. Hence the first sub-question is: What determines healthcare buyers' decisions on number and accuracy of tests to be ordered? Further, to see how human biases affect such decisions, we ask the second sub-question: How do such decisions compare against optimal decisions? Finally, we are specifically interested in seeing whether any observed bias can be linked to a potential agency problem (with healthcare system considered as the agent for the community it serves), hence the final sub-question would be: How the difference in costs of test inaccuracies for patients vs. healthcare system affects the biases in test portfolio decisions?

Conceptual design of studies

We study how the portfolio of tests for a target population as well as the quality (accuracy) of them is decided using a sample of potential medical procurement decision-makers (real healthcare

professionals). As we were interested in establishing a causal relation between several independent variables (e.g., prevalence, error rates, costs, etc.) and certain dependent variables (each being an aspect of portfolio decision), we used an experimental procedure involving individually crafted simultaneous manipulations of model variables. In each of the three studies planned, we follow this procedure: (a) Rational test purchasing behavior is simulated, (b) Real behavior is obtained through an experiment, and (c) Real behavior is contrasted against simulated behavior, inferences are made especially with regard to the agency problem mentioned earlier.

Study 1: The base effect on portfolio decision

The goal is to study the basic effect of agency problem on portfolio decisions for accurate tests. The agency problem arises from the differing costs of not getting tested (test unavailability due to portfolio structure) for patients versus healthcare system.

Study 2: Making quality-price compromises

A step forward, here we investigate how choice of test quality/price (for inaccurate tests) is affected by model parameters, especially the differing costs of inaccuracies for patients versus the healthcare system.

Study 3: The increasing cost function of false negative

Finally, in study 3 we acknowledge the fact that for a truly existing medical condition, the cost of false negative results will likely increase by time. That is, the medical condition gets more severe/ difficult to treat because of the inaction that follows a false negative result. We study how such a cost function – also different for patients versus healthcare system– would change the test portfolio decisions of healthcare procurement managers.

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Paper topic

3. Purchasing organisation, 13. Public procurement, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

Unveiling the carbon credit supply chain

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This paper critically examines the carbon credit market through a supply network lens, addressing its structural flaws, governance inefficiencies, and informational asymmetries. It explores compliance and voluntary markets, highlighting challenges such as bounded rationality, opportunism, and fragmented standards. Employing global value chains and complex adaptive systems as theoretical frameworks, the study reveals systemic imbalances that disadvantage smaller actors while favouring dominant intermediaries. While integrating digital technologies promises traceability, persistent governance gaps undermine market trust. This analysis underscores the urgent need for harmonised standards, equitable participation, and interdisciplinary solutions to ensure the market's credibility and scalability.

Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience, 16. Sustainability - environmental, 11. Digital

Adoption of additive manufacturing services by urban production centres: implications for companies in terms of social impact

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The research explores the role of urban production centres offering 3D printing services to firms in improving their social impacts. Through a literature review and nine case studies, the research identifies key services provided by urban production centres that enable companies to access 3D printing. Moreover, it maps the impacts of AM adoption on multiple stakeholders: workers, consumers, local communities, value chain actors, and society. Based on these results, we formulate 9 propositions. The results support centres and companies in choosing sustainability-oriented actions through knowledge of the impacts they generate by offering/adopting AM through the urban manufacturing model.

Paper topic

17. Sustainability - social, 11. Digital

Forging a Responsible Future: Navigating Due Diligence Challenges in SME Metal Supply Chains

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This study investigates how small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the metals sector adapt to sustainability regulations, particularly the European Union's Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD). Researchers combined interviews with SME managers, industry experts, and secondary data through an embedded case design to examine due diligence practices and barriers. Findings reveal that leadership commitment, collaboration, and robust performance management drive successful supply chain sustainability. Resource constraints and limited awareness hinder progress. The paper concludes that proactive strategies, strong governance, and multi-tier transparency enable SMEs to meet evolving regulatory demands and enhance competitive advantage.

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 21. Special track: Regulations in shaping sustainable ecosystem change, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

Upstream cascading makes sense: leveraging prospective sensemaking for Sustainable Supply Chains

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This study examines how procurement professionals leverage prospective sensemaking to cascade sustainability practices across multi-tier supply chains. Through narrative interviews, surveys, and netnography, it identifies three conceptual frameworks—business-case, paradoxical, and convincing—that procurement professionals employ to manage systemic tensions between profitability and sustainability. Findings highlight the critical role of clear role definitions, strategic foresight tools, targeted training, and cross-functional alignment. Although limited by sample size and qualitative approach, the study provides actionable insights aligning procurement strategies with regulatory contexts (e.g., EU's CSRD and CSDDD), positioning procurement as a strategic driver of sustainability.

Paper topic

7. Negotiation and contracting, 17. Sustainability - social, 1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences

Operating in multi-party networks: A party for the C-suite or should purchasing also be invited?

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Purpose

Addressing grand societal challenges, such as the digital, the circular and the energy transitions, requires coordinated efforts among a diverse array of stakeholders operating in multi-party networks that unite public and private entities. Working in networks to address these challenges requires a system thinking approach rather than an individualistic approach (Di Mauro et al., 2024), leaving traditional, hierarchical governance models often insufficient. Operating in multi-party networks is hence expected to have (major) implications for Purchasing & Supply Management (PSM), for example, in terms of governing their inter-organisational relationships. Also, changing roles and responsibilities of the public and private stakeholders involved may have implications in terms of who they need to collaborate with and how, suggesting changes in, or additions to, PSM competences.

This paper explores to what extent and how operating in multi-party networks affects PSM professionals' capacity to act, also known as purchasing agency. We aim to investigate whether such settings have implications for agency in terms of how PSM professionals govern their relationships with direct suppliers, and the extent to which they deal with indirect relationships in their network and in what ways. In this working paper, we limit ourselves to three aspects in which multi-party networks fundamentally differ from conventional purchasing settings: scoping, governance, and execution & monitoring. This more or less corresponds to Roehrich et al.'s (2023) network orchestration phases: creating connections, governing networks, and monitoring progress.

Looking at the *scoping*, networks cannot be reduced to a set of inter-organisational alliances, or a group of dyadic relationships. While network members may or may not have alliances among themselves, it is their alignment that is critical to realise the value proposition. As such, networks typically do not rely on hierarchical or arm's-length relationships. Purchasing will thus have to expand its focus from direct and hierarchical relationships to include also indirect relationships with a multitude of other stakeholders for which one cannot rely on hierarchy. Practitioners and academics alike should, hence, move beyond issues of connectedness (i.e. optimising ties with direct partners to enable seamless operations), and instead focus on the interconnectedness of current issues (Harland, 2021). For example, climate change cannot be stopped by one organisation or supply network, a whole sector is needed. This aligns well

with PSM's shift toward networked models where organisations must manage interconnected relationships and shared resources to fulfil broader goals.

Zooming in on *governance*, the notion of network governance involves a paradigm that addresses the challenges inherent in multi-party networks, where governance must balance coordination, cooperation, and adaptive mechanisms across interconnected actors—vis-à-vis traditional, market-based relationships that underlie transactions and that traditionally are the domain of PSM. Additionally, operating in multi-party networks with indirect ties involves dealing with structural holes, something that may most effectively be addressed by specific (relational) governance mechanisms. To effectively manage this different type of governance, it is important to re-analyse, and perhaps revise, the existing frameworks regarding PSM competences.

Finally, regarding the *execution & monitoring*, networks face specific challenges in terms of coordination of activities, goal alignment, and performance monitoring and management. One thing to consider is what type of agreements are most conducive for coordination and collaboration, and what mix of behaviour-based and/or outcome-based controls may meaningfully support this. These agreements should motivate network members to optimise the public value to be achieved, rather than optimising their individual gains. Since the creation of public value can be considered a cornerstone of multi-party network collaborations, it urges PSM professionals to adopt a broader, societal perspective in their decision-making processes. As such, we seek to understand whether the switch to multi-party networks entails expanding the existing roles of individual purchasers so that they are better equipped to help manage multi-party collaborations (in addition to their organisations' traditional collaborations) or that it entails the design of a new role besides the role of purchaser (e.g. the creation of 'network relationship managers' that specialise in multi-party network).

To investigate these three aspects, we draw on three case studies of multi-party networks to illustrate and substantiate the impact on PSM we (fore)see. Our case studies were designed with other research objectives in mind; hence, our "evidence" can at best be considered anecdotal. Nevertheless, we hope to convince readers of the need for challenging and broadening current thinking about PSM and particularly the intrapreneurial character of the PSM function in organisations and multi-party networks (see also Knight et al. (2022)).

Methodology

We draw on three existing case studies to illustrate the phenomenon in focus and explore how the PSM function is affected by the multi-party network setting. As the cases (and the related data) have been used in other studies, we consider the original case descriptions and the data on which they are built as archival data. We re-analysed the data from all three cases to explore new theory about potential role of PSM in multi-party network settings and the specific competences that are needed for these types of collaborations.

Our first case study concerned a multi-party network in the infrastructure sector that aimed to source and implement a federated software platform to digitally connect the software systems of each organisation involved, leading to a radical digital transformation. The second case study concerned a multi-party network in the electricity sector that aimed to roll out smart electricity meters and use the smart meter data to provide useful insights to end consumers and support the ongoing energy

transition. The third case study concerned a multi-party network transitioning to a circular or at least more sustainable variant of a specific type of construction material, used in civil engineering projects.

Preliminary results

The first case revealed institution-related and socio-cultural challenges that prevented the successful sourcing and implementation of a digital technology. For example, apart from a memorandum of understanding, the collaborating organisations did not have formal governance mechanisms nor structures in place. The findings also showed that trust and focusing on the joint goal (rather than pursuing individual goals) play a pivotal role in keeping the collaboration on track, which constituted a major shift from the way the involved organisations traditionally managed their inter-organisational relationships.

The second case revealed market-related and socio-cultural challenges that prevented the successful usage of smart meter data. For example, there was not a clear business case for the appointed organisations that were supposed to provide information from smart meter data to end consumers. Moreover, a covenant was initiated with several outcome-based agreements that ultimately did not support the overall goal that was set out.

The third case revealed barriers to circular transitions that are market- or institution-related, or socio-cultural or technical in nature, and that procurement is affected by all these types of barriers. Examples include the lack of a business case and clear sustainability requirements, which leaves purchasing to continue to rely on rather conventional selection and award criteria, and conservative decision-making approaches. The findings also clearly point at the need for collaborative innovation and risk-sharing approaches as ways to overcome barriers.

In terms of purchasing competences, the findings in all three cases allude to the need for increased technical (e.g. innovation sourcing), inter-personal (e.g. deal with ambiguity), and strategic business skills (e.g. risk management and holistic supply chain thinking). Interestingly enough, discussions between the various partners of the multi-party networks in our cases are mostly conducted by either employees working in the policy departments (acting as substitutes for higher management) or employees in other strategic positions, while the purchasing departments were hardly involved.

Contributions

This paper advances PSM scholarship by exploring the PSM function within multi-party networks, moving beyond traditional dyadic relationships to focus on multi-stakeholder systems. Academically, it provides a framework for studying multi-party networks and exploring whether and what such settings imply for PSM. For example, the shift from isolated transactions to interdependent networks highlights the limitations of traditional governance models in complex, multi-actor systems, advocating for governance structures that enable resilience and collective action across diverse sets of interconnected stakeholders. For PSM professionals, such understanding emphasizes the role of PSM in addressing societal challenges, positioning PSM as a key enabler of public value creation. Additionally, the importance of aligning network-level goals with individual objectives is underscored, suggesting that incentives, role clarity and information-sharing mechanisms can help address collaboration challenges.

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Paper topic

1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 13. Public procurement, 15. PSM theory, methodology, education

Strategic relocations: case studies unravelling motivations and performance in outsourced reshoring decisions

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

Global supply chains, shaped by globalization and offshoring for cost efficiency, are now shifting due to rising complexities, geopolitical tensions, sustainability concerns, and disruptions. This study examines the underexplored topic of outsourced reshoring, where companies transition from international to domestic suppliers to reduce dependency and enhance resilience. Focusing on Italy's machinery manufacturing sector, it analyses six case studies to uncover drivers, challenges, and benefits of outsourced reshoring. Key themes include regulatory impacts, sustainability, and Industry 4.0 advancements. The research highlights relocations as a strategy for risk mitigation, sustainability, and innovation, offering insights for adapting to the evolving business landscape.

Paper topic

6. Outsourcing, offshoring, reshoring

Micro-company Buyer Behaviour: An Exploratory Study

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CTU, Prague, Czech Republic

Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

1. Introduction

Micro-companies, defined as enterprises with fewer than ten employees and an annual turnover of less than 2 million euros, are a fundamental part of the economic landscape. In the Czech Republic, they constitute 95.6% of all companies, employ 50% of the workforce, and contribute 36% of the national GDP. Despite their economic relevance, the buyer behaviour of micro-companies remains an underexplored domain.

Anecdotic evidence suggests that these companies exhibit purchasing behaviour combining business-to-business (B2B) and business-to-consumer (B2C) buying patterns. However, little is known about which facets of B2B and B2C buyer behaviour prevail and why. This study addresses this important research gap with theoretical implications (a hybrid model of buyer behaviour) and practical implications (way forward in micro-companies purchasing professionalization).

2. Literature Review

The theoretical foundation of this study is rooted in two main streams of literature: micro-company purchasing and buyer behaviour.

Micro-Company Purchasing: Previous studies, particularly Ellegaard (2006), have highlighted the barriers that micro-companies face in purchasing. These include limited access to suppliers, lack of negotiation power, and insufficient expertise. While these challenges are well-documented, little is known about how micro-companies perform purchasing activities. The motivations, processes, decision criteria, and underlying logic remain opaque. Ellegaard's work focuses on barriers but does not sufficiently explain the behavioural mechanisms underlying micro-company purchasing decisions.

Buyer Behaviour Theory: Buyer behaviour literature distinguishes between B2B and B2C purchasing. Organizational buying (B2B) is generally characterized by formal decision-making processes, multiple stakeholders, and rational evaluation of suppliers. Consumer buying (B2C), on the other hand, is typically informal, emotional, and relationship-driven. Contributions by Wilson (2000) or van Weele (2020) have established frameworks for understanding the fundamental differences between B2B and B2C behaviour. However, to the best of our knowledge, no established model has yet addressed the unique position of micro-companies, which may borrow elements from both domains, e.g. micro-

companies, often run by owner-managers with limited capacity, may exhibit the emotions and informality typical of consumers but still leverage some aspects of organizational purchasing, such as established purchasing process, price inelasticity or good supply market knowledge.

3. Research question

Building on this conceptual background, a critical research question is formulated: What characterizes the buyer behaviour of micro-companies?

4. Research Design and Methodology

An exploratory qualitative study involved 47 semi-structured interviews with micro-companies in the Czech Republic. This approach was chosen to gain a more profound, context-specific understanding of the mechanisms underpinning micro-company purchasing. The study sample was purposefully diverse, ensuring representation from various industries and turnover levels (an average of €150,000). Interviews lasted between 20 and 50 minutes and were guided by a semi-structured protocol designed to capture key aspects of the procurement process and specific

Data were analyzed using thematic analysis, with two independent researchers serving as coders. A rigorous coding process ensured that recurring themes and differences were captured, enabling a nuanced understanding of buyer behaviour patterns.

5. Results

The findings of the study reveal that the purchasing behaviour of micro-companies is neither fully B2B nor fully B2C but instead represents a hybrid buyer behaviour. Several key patterns characterize this hybrid nature:

B2C-Like Features

Simplified procurement process: Unlike formal B2B purchasing, which involves extensive evaluation, documentation, and multiple decision-makers, micro-companies often make rapid, informal decisions led by a single owner-manager.

Relationship-based purchasing: Personal networks and long-term relationships with suppliers are central. This aspect resembles consumer buying, where familiarity, trust, and loyalty are primary decision factors.

Limited supplier pool: Many micro-companies rely on a narrow range of suppliers, often regional or local, as opposed to the broader supplier base typically seen in B2B purchasing.

B2B-Like Features:

Rational decision-making elements: While emotional and relationship-driven elements are prominent, certain micro-companies exhibit rational decision-making similar to B2B firms. For instance, the evaluation of price, quality, and delivery times often takes place, albeit less formally.

Elastic demand: Purchases by micro-companies are influenced by their end customers. When demand changes (for example, due to fluctuations in customer orders), micro-companies adjust their procurement, reflecting the demand-driven logic of B2B buyer behaviour.

Market knowledge and situational awareness: Owner-managers often demonstrate deep awareness of market conditions, pricing trends, and supplier dynamics. This level of knowledge mirrors, to a degree, the strategic sourcing decisions seen in larger organizations.

Price inelasticity is typically driven by their own customer price inelasticity, which micro-companies have to pass on to their sub-suppliers.

6 . Theoretical Implications

This study introduces the concept of hybrid buyer behaviour in micro-companies. Current literature positions B2B and B2C purchasing as distinct modes of behaviour, but the findings from this research reveal a fluid and hybrid approach. This insight calls for an extension of buyer behaviour theory to include micro-companies as a distinct category of purchasers. The theoretical contribution lies in challenging the binary view of B2B and B2C purchasing by identifying a third mode of behaviour, hybrid purchasing, which reflects the unique operating constraints of micro-companies.

7. Managerial Implications

The findings of this study have significant practical implications for suppliers, policymakers, and micro-companies themselves.

Suppliers: Suppliers seeking to engage with micro-companies should recognize that traditional B2B sales strategies may not be effective. Given micro-companies' preference for local suppliers, regional suppliers can leverage proximity as a competitive advantage.

Professionalization of Micro-Company Purchasing: While micro-companies are unlikely to adopt complex procurement systems like larger firms, there is potential to professionalize their weakest points. For example, tools that support price transparency, supplier comparison, or simple procurement tracking may help micro-companies make better purchasing decisions. However, such tools should be simple, intuitive, and reflect the time constraints of owner-managers, who often have limited bandwidth for administrative tasks.

Public Policy and SME Support: Policymakers should consider supporting micro-companies through simplified procurement systems tailored to their needs. Efforts to support the digitalization of procurement may focus on tools that combine the speed and simplicity of consumer platforms (like e-commerce) with the price comparability and evaluation logic of B2B platforms.

8. Conclusion

This study is one of the first to investigate micro-company buyer behaviour in detail. The concept of hybrid buyer behaviour offers a useful lens for further exploration, providing a foundation for future research and practical development.

Paper topic

20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.), 3. Purchasing organisation

207

Crisis management governance in the supply chain of a food franchise network

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This article examines the governance of crisis management in the supply chains of food franchise networks. Using resource theory, it highlights the importance of relational and organisational skills in building resilience. A qualitative methodology (interviews, longitudinal observations) reveals the challenges of coordination. A collaborative governance model is proposed, incorporating a structured crisis unit, transparent communication and systematic feedback.

Paper topic

18. Risk and resilience, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.), 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

208

Supplier satisfaction as a driver of platform adoption: a study of European SMEs through preferred customer theory and platform strategy

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

Summary: This study integrates procurement and platform strategy literature insights to investigate how supplier satisfaction influences online platform adoption. By analyzing survey data from 764 European manufacturing SMEs, we examine how growth opportunity, profitability, operative excellence, and reliability affect initial platform adoption and continued engagement decisions. The findings demonstrate that while non-adopters consider all satisfaction dimensions when evaluating the opportunity of joining a platform, adopters prioritize realized growth and profitability. The research advances the understanding of supplier behavior in digital platforms and provides practical guidance for platform managers on evolving their strategies as relationships mature.

Paper topic

11. Digital, 10. Purchasing innovation, 2. PSM strategy

Who holds the power? Unpacking AI adoption in buyer-supplier negotiations in the Kraljic matrix: a power-dependence perspective

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

Buyer-supplier negotiations are crucial to procurement, and artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly shaping this domain. However, AI adoption in negotiations varies significantly depending on contextual factors that remain underexplored. This study applies power-dependence theory to interpret the Kraljic matrix, analyzing AI adoption across negotiation phases and examining how different levels of human-machine collaboration emerge within distinct product portfolio configurations. Through expert interviews with multiple actors we find that AI is predominantly used for augmentation in high-power supplier contexts, whereas automation prevails in buyer-dominated negotiations. The study provides actionable insights on aligning AI solutions with product categories to maximize negotiation efficiency.

Paper topic

7. Negotiation and contracting, 11. Digital, 4. Category management

212

Misalignments in multi-tier supply chain: An Agency Theory perspective

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This study investigates transitional triads in an automotive semiconductor supply chain, exploring how attempts to address existing misalignments create new ones. Focusing on multi-tier relationships - specifically, an automotive OEM, its Tier-1 suppliers, and Tier-2 suppliers - the research examines connections within two such triads. Drawing on agency theory, it reveals how conflicting interests and information asymmetry lead to persistent misalignments that undermine coordination and performance. By analysing empirical data from all three tiers, this study highlights the complexity of managing multi-tier supply chains, contributing to a deeper understanding of how triadic structures can shape, and hinder, alignment.

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Interorganisational innovation for the circular economy: a longitudinal case study of eco-park evolution

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Introduction

The circular economy (CE) is nothing new. Despite a tsunami of research on the topic of circularising the economy and supply chains over the last 10 years, the idea of obtaining value from discarded materials and energy has been a guiding principle for centuries and much longer in natural systems relying on symbiotic relationships, e.g. between trees and mycorrhizal fungus (Anthony *et al.*, 2022). In sum, as the old adage states “where there is muck there is brass” (Rays, 1678), so making money from waste has been around for a long time. In this research, we take a longitudinal perspective on circular economy change. We attempt to show how CE has evolved over time and can be seen as an exemplar of innovation at the systems level. Such developments take time and rely, for the most part, on effective interorganisational relationships that need to be nurtured not only between individual firms, but also at the business ecosystem level within localities, regions and beyond (Kühl *et al.*, 2022).

Theoretical framing

Sustainable purchasing and supply management (Miemczyk *et al.*, 2012) has become mainstream for companies to answer the current global environmental challenge. One of the levers for sustainable supply chain management is the adoption of systems thinking, which involves recognising the social embeddedness of supply networks, the interdependence of local stakeholders and the engagement in non-usual or small-scale collaborations (Luzzini *et al.*, 2024). With this in mind, the introduction of loops in local supply networks is seen as a possible way forward - commonly known as industrial symbiosis or industrial ecology – frequently manifested as eco-parks (Chertow, 2000). However, these industrial developments require time, investment and trial and error to determine which loops and collaborations are the most relevant from an economic, social and environmental point of view (Sudusinghe and Seuring, 2022).

We propose an ecosystem perspective for studying this phenomenon for two reasons. First, eco-parks are examples of the more general concept of industrial symbiosis and therefore follow principles related to the natural systems ecosystem metaphor (Chertow, 2000; Parida *et al.*, 2019). Second, the innovation

literature has also used the ecosystem metaphor to explain the interorganisational knowledge exchange processes within innovation networks (Aarikka-Stenroos and Ritala, 2017). Innovation within the context of ecosystems for the circular economy is driven by a number of factors including changing customer demands, public procurement (Alhola *et al.*, 2018) and institutional drivers such as regulations. This leads to the development of new flows of materials and energy and the redesign material and immaterial processes (Sudusinghe and Seuring, 2022), requiring new interorganisational relationships (Brown *et al.*, 2021; Köhler *et al.*, 2022). Due to these characteristics such ecosystems can be seen as systemic innovations as they show complementarity between innovations in different firms, local or regional governance structures supporting innovations, societal laws and norms enabling ecological sustainability, collaboration between multiple actors and finally evidence of how people engage in systemic thinking and action (Midgley and Lindhult, 2021).

While frameworks exist explaining the development of these new interorganisational relationships, with some insights into the time dimension (Brown *et al.*, 2021; Parida *et al.*, 2019), how these eco-systems persist over time has not been extensively studied. Even the most famous examples, the 60-year old Kalundborg eco-park in Denmark has faced local challenges (BBC, 2024), so continued success is not a given. Hence this research aims to demonstrate how, over time, innovations in the service of the circular economy evolve by taking a systemic innovations perspective, while combining both ecosystem and industrial symbiosis viewpoints. With this framing we propose to specifically examine the impact on, and of, interorganisational relationships over the duration of the eco-park.

Method and research context

This article focuses on the local-level and adopts the perspective of the network through a single in-depth and longitudinal case study of an eco-park organised around a biorefinery in the North-East of France in operation since 1983. The eco-park comprises eight companies' in a system including processing wheat and sugar beet products and by products inputs for food, chemical, cosmetics, pharmaceutical and combustible industries outputs. An additional feature of the system lies in the intellectual resources in circulation for synergies set up via a research centre built jointly in 2012 between academic bodies and the members of the eco-park with the support of local public authorities (Alhola *et al.*, 2019). This approach fosters proximity between the actors of the territory and ensures a sustainable supply of raw materials. The research builds on previous studies of the eco-system development and supplements with new qualitative data to build a case history of how this collaborative interorganisational system, with circular economy aims, has evolved for nearly 40 years.

The data collection to date includes five interviews with the following: founder and former CEO, (agriculture cooperative of 2000 farmers); operations director (industrial gases and chemistry supplier); R&D director (cosmetic ingredients manufacturer); site director (biomass fuel manufacturer) and the association director (professional association coordinating the eco-park). Additional interviews are planned to complete the study.

Initial findings and contribution

The core of the case is the development and optimisation of industrial processes and exploration of practical ways of transforming and adding value to plant-based raw materials. While the eco-park has already been the subject of discussions on the evolution of industrial processes implied by the implementation of symbioses (Allais *et al.*, 2021), this study focuses on the interorganisational changes related to the elaboration and operationalisation of material and immaterial loops in a cross-sector,

cross-industry initiative at the scale of a territory. The knowledge generated on the skills mobilised during the collaborative process of developing a mature industrial symbiosis will be valuable for researchers with a view to expanding the circular economy model and to practitioners for insights into the diffusion of practices. Key insights into the enablers of systemic innovation in this context include the roles of a variety of actors, including a strong leader, continuous adaptation to changes in the institutional environment, the important social connections between local actors and the trial and error approach to developing new processes and flows.

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Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 10. Purchasing innovation

Sustainability standards for fostering sustainable agriculture and improving rural livelihoods: a research study in the cocoa supply chain in Ecuador

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This research investigates the impact of sustainability standards on sustainable agriculture and rural livelihoods in the cocoa supply chain in Ecuador. It explores how the tensions faced by farmers and supply chain actors in adopting certification standards can be managed to generate positive environmental and social impacts. The study employs a mixed-method nested case study, analyzing the supply chain of a large international cocoa trader, including conventional, Rainforest Alliance-certified, and organic farmers. Preliminary results suggest that certified farmers, especially those with non-agricultural income, have better access to financial services. Deeper qualitative analysis is needed to understand the full impact of certifications on sustainable agriculture and rural livelihoods.

Paper topic

17. Sustainability - social, 16. Sustainability - environmental, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

216

Food Solidarity Purchasing Groups in Italy and Türkiye: Understanding Participation, Sustainability Priorities, and Satisfaction

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This study investigates the dynamics of solidarity purchasing groups (SPGs) in Italy and Türkiye, focusing on sociodemographics, sustainability priorities and satisfaction. A systematic literature review and a survey were conducted, reaching 419 respondents involving current, former and non-participants of SPGs. The descriptive statistics revealed the differences between the respondent groups in terms of sociodemographic characteristics and participation, while regression analyses showed the drivers of participation in SPGs and satisfaction with SPGs and MMRs. These findings provide insights into designing effective strategies to enhance member engagement in SPGs and challenge existing assumptions about these networks.

Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

Enabling Supply Chain Social Sustainability Through Innovation: A cross case analysis

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

As the social dimension of [sustainability](#) in supply chains grows in importance within both academic and industrial communities, The necessity to understand how this dimension is incorporated into the daily operations of organizations rises. This is particularly relevant in the context of emerging economies. Sustainable operations in this context require a commitment to addressing the social issues and conditions affecting underserved populations, with a focus on promoting inclusivity and equality. Building on recent studies exploring how social dimension has been incorporated in supply chain management, this study attempts to establish a link between social sustainability antecedents, social innovation capabilities and social innovations outcomes. NVIVO is used to cross-analyze the content of ten cases where social innovations were applied successfully within the food industry in Egypt. The results provide evidence of six main outcomes of social innovation initiatives namely; welfare, safety, equity, wellbeing of the community, health and training education and learning. Each of the outcomes has its own particular sets of social innovation capabilities and antecedents. Industry and researchers alike can use the study to develop the decision-support systems guiding social-oriented sustainable innovations within their supply chains.

Keywords: Social sustainability, Frugal innovation, Inclusive innovation, Technological innovation, Cross-Case analysis, Capability based view

Paper topic

17. Sustainability - social, 12. Ethics, 10. Purchasing innovation

Moving Beyond Pragmatism: The Authenticity of Sustainable Supply Chain Legitimacy

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

With a history spanning over three decades as a pioneer in sustainability initiatives and reporting, the International Business Machines Corporation (IBM) should be acknowledged as a leader in sustainability performance. Still, stakeholders may question the legitimacy of its sustainability initiatives. Utilizing data from over two decades of IBM's corporate sustainability reports, this research analyzes IBM's efforts to establish its commitment to sustainability and secure moral, cognitive, and pragmatic sustainability legitimacy in the eyes of its stakeholders. Adopting a template analysis approach and building upon prior research on corporate sustainability reporting, this research examines the temporal shifts in IBM's sustainability commitments, focusing on its sustainable supply chain practices. The evolution of IBM's sustainability policies and practices provides valuable insights into the organization's journey toward achieving sustainable supply chain legitimacy. This research advances comprehension of legitimacy theory through theory elaboration by navigating the intersection of empirical data and existing literature. It posits that the construct of authenticity is a pivotal link between organizations seeking to establish legitimacy and those striving for credibility in sustainable supply chain management. Sustainability must be a deeply ingrained organizational value that permeates every facet of a firm's operations and resonates throughout its entire network.

Paper topic

2. PSM strategy, 16. Sustainability - environmental, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Visualizing value creation and value capture beyond the buyer-supplier relation

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

While societal challenges can best be solved when buyers and suppliers collaborate, this does not indicate that each actor also strives for the same values. Our study aims at visualizing values across buyers, suppliers and other stakeholders that are involved in a Dutch dike enforcement project. The findings show how value creation and capture is perceived differently by actors and that certain values seem to be captured by the ecosystem instead of the organizations directly involved in the buyer-supplier relation. This indicates that value visualisation contributes to explicating systemic business relations that develop around a single buyer-supplier relation.

Paper topic

20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.), 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 13. Public procurement

Searching for excellence in the integration of ESG into purchasing

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Abstract

One of the primary goals of contemporary enterprises is to build resilience to crises, among others to the risk related to climate change and climate crisis (Adana et al., 2023; Thomas, 2023; Nnaji et al., 2024). Both creation and operationalization of sustainable development strategies are currently based on the ESG concept. It assumes three pillars Environmental, Social and Governance, which include groups of ESG factors (aspects). The acronym ESG was used for the first time in the report “Who Cares Wins. Connecting Financial Markets to a Changing World” (United Nations, The Global Compact, 2004). Based on the results of the systematic literature review, Agrawal et al. (2024) reported that the ESG concept has prominently emerged from the corporate to academic field in 2018. Although the ESG concept is currently associated mainly with reporting related to sustainable development, it is not only a performance measurement system, but it provides strategic value for companies prioritizing sustainable development as their primary strategy for growth (Truant et al., 2024). The debate on ESG aspects has been dominated by a general approach to strategies or business models transformation so far. It should be noted that there is an essential need to investigate how the strategic ESG goals can be operationalized in business functions, processes and relationships.

The ESG-driven business strategies stress the great importance of end-to-end supply chain management for the sustainable development of enterprises in the era of climate crisis. Purchasing as a business function as well as a business process plays a strategic role in this perspective. The maturity of purchasing is defined as the ability to influence the achievement of strategic goals or increasing results, and therefore competitive advantage and value of the enterprise. Many authors confirmed that business effects and value increase as the purchasing function matures (Burt, Starling, 2018; Chick, Handfield, 2015; Provines, 2017; Schiele, 2007; Van Weele, 2018). The previously published academic and business studies revealed different aspects of purchasing maturity determining to the greatest extent its evolutionary development at several subsequent levels or stages. The key elements of the purchasing maturity can be systemized as follows: (1) strategic approach, (2) position in the organisational structure, (3) internal integration in the enterprise, (4) external integration in the supply chain, (5) performance measurement and key performance metrics (KPIs), (6) use of technology.

The main purpose of the paper is to investigate how the ESG aspects can be integrated into purchasing management in the light of the elements of its maturity. The author presents research findings and conclusions derived from the three-year research project entitled “The quality of management of ESG aspects vs resilience to crisis. Enterprises - financial institutions - local government units” led between 2022 and 2024. The following research methods were applied: in-depth individual interviews (IDI), Focus Group Interviews (FGI) and survey.

Table 1 outlines some examples of practices that will be presented in the paper based on the case studies. The more integrated and holistic scope of considering ESG aspects in purchasing management, the higher the ability of the purchasing function to influence the achievement of sustainable strategic goals and results, and therefore the resilience of the company against the climate crisis.

Table 1. Incorporation of ESG aspects into purchasing management

Source: author’s own elaboration.

The paper contributes to research on the sustainable supply chain phenomenon and sustainable purchasing management in several important ways. First, the author answers the question of how ESG aspects can be integrated into the elements of the purchasing maturity. Second, by exploiting case studies, the author add value to a deeper understanding of the rules and mechanisms relevant to ESG-driven transition of supply chains. Next, the paper provides “real life” lessons learned clarifying that the sustainable and scalable development of ESG-driven purchasing management requires the orchestration of supplier ecosystems. Third, it extends the literature on supplier development and early supplier involvement that can play the role of game-changers in the perspective of sustainable purchasing in the times of climate crisis. Additionally, considering the challenge in the context of the small and medium sized companies, the findings of the research reveal how to bring less powerful actors into the mainstream economy.

Keywords: supply chain, purchasing, supplier management, sustainable development, ESG

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Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 21. Special track: Regulations in shaping sustainable ecosystem change, 1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences

Towards Innovation Performance with Public Customer and Tender Attractiveness: A Social Capital Perspective

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This paper explores the role of social capital, customer attractiveness, and tender attractiveness in driving innovation performance in public procurement. PLS-SEM was used to analyze data from 182 suppliers of public organizations. The results were verified with a sample of suppliers of a private company. The study reveals that social capital exhibits limited direct impact in public procurement. Cognitive capital, which emphasizes shared values and goals, is the only social capital dimension that positively influences tender attractiveness. Tender attractiveness emerges as a distinct and significant construct, particularly in the public sector. The findings underline the public procurement emphasis on tender clarity and procedural excellence to foster innovation, in contrast to the relational and long-term collaboration mechanisms prevalent in private procurement. This research challenges assumptions about universal procurement strategies, offering valuable insights into sector-specific approaches for enhancing innovation.

Paper topic

2. PSM strategy, 13. Public procurement, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Assessing the Current Status of Circular Economy Practices in Procurement and Supply Chain Management on Big Companies in Brazil

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Title: Assessing the Current Status of Circular Economy Practices in Procurement and Supply Chain Management on Big Companies in Brazil

Summary

Transition to a Circular Economy (CE) is seen as a critical point for addressing environmental challenges and fostering sustainable economic development. This study aims to assess the current state of CE practices as implemented by large enterprises operating in Brazil and impacts on procurement, examining their awareness, current initiatives, and future plans to adopt circular models, grounded in theoretical frameworks and reviews.

Research will employ a structured quantitative and qualitative survey targeting a stratified sample of companies across different sectors and dimensions.

Findings are to contribute to future researches and business development providing a comprehensive overview of CE practices in Brazil.

Keywords or phrases:

- Circular Economy
- Sustainability
- Supply Chain Management
- Purchasing and supply management
- Sustainable Supply Chain Management

Introduction/Context

The concept of the Circular Economy (CE) and its increasing relevance to either global economy and emerging markets offer significant opportunities. The urgency of implementing a Circular Economy system is increasingly viewed as essential to fostering a new economy. This system prioritizes circularity,

i.e., a novel production approach aimed at minimizing environmental impacts across multiple dimensions. Such a transition is gaining academic and social attention, as noted by researchers (Korhonen et al., 2018) and institutions such as the Ellen MacArthur Foundation (EMAF, 2012). The system seeks to move beyond the linear economy model of “extract-produce-use-dispose” (Frosch and Gallopoulos, 1989, apud Korhonen et al., 2018).

The ultimate goal is to create a production system where consumer goods generate minimal waste and have a net-zero CO2 impact. Although the concept of CE is widely contested (Korhonen et al., 2018) and subject to various interpretations (Kirchherr et al., 2017), recent updated paper produced by Kirchherr et al. (2023), analysed 364 articles, and so provides an updated definition. This definition positions CE as a “**regenerative system demanding a paradigm shift** to replace the “end-of-life” concept. It promotes reducing, reusing, recycling, and recovering materials across the supply chain, aiming to sustain value and ensure sustainable development while delivering environmental quality, economic growth, and social equity for current and future generations. It is enabled by an alliance of stakeholders (industry, consumers, policymakers, academia) and their technological innovations and capabilities”.

This definition also emphasizes that CE is enabled through collaboration among stakeholders (industry, consumers, public entities, and academia) and their technological innovations and capabilities. The updated framework by Kirchherr et al. (Kirchherr et al., 2023) integrates key principles, objectives, and enablers of CE, providing a comprehensive basis for academic and practical discussions.

This definition also emphasizes that CE is enabled through collaboration among stakeholders (industry, consumers, public entities, and academia) and their technological innovations and capabilities. The updated framework by Kirchherr et al. (Kirchherr et al., 2023) integrates key principles, objectives, and enablers of CE, providing a comprehensive basis for academic and practical discussions.

A more pragmatic approach, previously presented by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2013), defines CE as an **industrial system intentionally designed to be restorative or regenerative**. This system replaces “end-of-life” with restoration, transitions toward renewable energy, and aims to eliminate harmful chemicals that impede reuse. It also focuses on minimizing waste through refined material, product, and business model design.

As illustrated in the 2023 and 2024 World Economic Forum surveys, the top four perceived risks for the next ten years are primarily environmental, driven by the impacts of economic activities (Figure 01). However, for the short term (two years), only one environmental risk ranks among the top four in 2024—extreme weather events. In 2023, two environmental risks were highlighted for the short term: natural disasters and extreme weather events (2nd place) and failure to mitigate climate change (4th place).

This gap between short-term and long-term risk awareness suggests procrastination in addressing environmental challenges. Consequently, actions required to mitigate these risks—such as transitioning from a linear economy (Kirchherr et al., 2023) to a circular economy—are often deferred.

By the framework proposed (Braz & Mello, 2023), it is expected to understand circular supply chain management strategies and even to try to capture a forward step of integrated supply chain strategies in more complex structures of ecosystem or circular economy supply network.

Design/Methodology/Approach

Key dimensions to be analysed include resource efficiency (narrowing resource loops), product lifecycle extension (slowing resource loops), waste reutilization (closing resource loops), and environmental regeneration (regenerating resource loops), as well their impacts on procurement (Bocken and Geradts, 2022).

Evolution, actions and plans, to business models of Circular Economy and innovation (Ferasso et al. 2020) as well strategies, types and tactics adopted or to be adopted on supply chain (Braz and Mello, 2023) are to be included. This assessment will also explore barriers, enablers, and motivations for CE adoption, alongside the maturity of supply chains transitioning towards circular ecosystems.

Moving forward, important is also include in this assessment topics in order to capture status of evolution from sustainable/circular business models and circular supply chain to circular business ecosystems (Kanda et al., 2021) considering the expressive impact this evolution would be in procurement and supply chain management and relations between supplier and client. This evolution is key on effectiveness to move beyond the linear economy model of “extract-produce-use-dispose” (Korhonen et al., 2018).

Findings

The research question for this study seeks to evaluate the current status of Circular Economy initiatives among companies operating in Brazil, looking for following findings:

- Provide insights about companies’ awareness about CE practices
- Practices been adopted or to be adopted
- Barriers and enablers
- Subsidies for general companies approaches and associations
- Subsidies for public policies to be adopted in the future
- Assess their plans for the future.

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Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 2. PSM strategy, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Exploring the potential of Artificial intelligence as an Enabler of Process Innovation in Purchasing

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Introduction

Nowadays, as companies face fierce competition, the continuous search for innovations becomes increasingly important to improve the overall performance of organizations. Among the different types of innovation, process innovation clearly marks its presence. Process innovation can be defined as carrying out business activities in a new way to achieve visible and spectacular results in order to achieve business objectives (Davenport, 1993).

Technologies, and increasingly nowadays, information technologies (IT), often play a crucial role as enablers of process innovation. Research shows that technological tools transform organizational processes by improving their efficiency, opening up new possibilities or revolutionizing existing work methods. Some technologies act as efficiency drivers, enabling the streamlining of processes, improving communication, reducing organizational silos (Chege et al., 2020), and giving rise to a radical workflow reengineering (Davenport, 1993). This transformation is further driven by Industry 4.0, where connected technologies reshape production processes (Narayan et al., 2025). IT plays a pivotal role in integrating systems and data, facilitating the transformation of organizational processes. For example, these technologies integrate previously siloed functions, offering a global view of operations and optimizing value chains (Rajapathirana and Hui, 2018). This integration fosters new processes driven by real-time analytics and improved strategic decision-making (Chege et al., 2020). Additionally, digital tools such as cloud systems, collaborative platforms, and robotic automation reconfigure working methods, making them more agile and adaptable. For example, in a production environment, IT enables intelligent systems that adapt processes to real-time needs (Prajogo, 2016). IT also fosters collaboration between internal and external stakeholders through shared digital platforms, facilitating the co-creation of processes previously unattainable. This capability enhances integration, transforming existing processes and leads to new organizational configurations (Najafi-Tavani et al., 2018).

However, the adoption of IT or technologies does not inherently ensure process innovation. Their potential relies on how effectively organizations align them with strategic objectives. This highlights the need to position IT as a strategic driver rather than merely a set of supporting tools (Vargo et al., 2015).

Process innovation and its scope are prominent in many industries, and the procurement sector is no exception. Although purchasing processes are located at a strategic crossroads at the heart of organizational operations, they are among those that have lagged furthest behind in terms of innovation (Spreitzenbarth et al., 2024).

However, in hindsight, we can see traces of process innovation in purchasing. For example, the introduction of the Kraljic matrix transformed purchasing by segmenting approaches, reducing repetitive and operational tasks from buyers to strategic partners. Similarly, models such as Vendor-Managed Inventory (VMI), Supplier relationship management (SRM) and digital tools (e-sourcing, e-procurement...), have replaced classic processes with centralized, collaborative approaches focused on supervision and analysis. These innovations shift administrative tasks to strategic activities, making purchasing a lever for efficiency and resilience, while redefining buyers' activities.

More recently, artificial intelligence (AI) technologies have taken off considerably in all areas of business activity. The literature has explored AI in fields such as entrepreneurial decision-making, finance, strategic performance, and sustainable supply chain management, but its application in purchasing departments remains very little studied (Allal-Chérif et al., 2021; Spreitzenbarth et al., 2024). AI is a technology that uses algorithms to simulate human intelligence and behavior (Russell and Norvig, 2010) to reproduce cognitive processes such as learning, reasoning, and decision-making.

AI in purchasing is justified by the exploitation of massive data generated by the players in the sector (Handfield et al., 2019), offering a strong potential for added value that is still underexploited (Brinch, 2018; Spreitzenbarth et al., 2024). In this sense, AI makes it possible to analyze and structure data to optimize processes and strengthen the effectiveness of strategic decisions.

Research on AI in purchasing mainly focuses on enhancing performance, supporting strategic decisions, and addressing ethical and sustainability challenges. Studies target process automation via technologies like Robotic Process Automation (Maldareanu et al., 2024) and AI applications in procurement, emphasizing improved performance and decision-making (Spreitzenbarth et al., 2024; Srivastava and Roy, 2024). Other research examines AI's role in negotiation optimization (Schulze-Horn et al., 2020) or ethical considerations (Voeth et al., 2023). Despite these advances, the role of AI as an enabler of process innovation remains underexplored.

This observation forms the basis of our research question, which seeks to address this gap and explore the strategic role of AI in transforming business processes

How can artificial intelligence be considered as a process innovation enabler in purchasing practices?

And the sub-questions are :

-What is the role of artificial intelligence in transforming purchasing processes?

-What conditions are necessary to effectively integrate artificial intelligence into purchasing processes?

Research Method

To understand how AI can be an enabler of process innovation in purchasing, we opted for an exploratory study of a qualitative nature in order to obtain an in-depth interpretation of the phenomena

in their natural context (Denzin and Lincoln,2017).The method used in this research is based on semi-structured interviews with eight experts in the field of purchasing who have significant experience ranging from 5 to 18 years.They are responsible for purchasing in sectors such as Transport, Agri-Food and Automotive in France.

For the data analysis, we followed the approach of Corbin and Strauss (2008).The aim was theorization by highlighting relationships between different conceptual levels, in accordance with the objective of the research.We used two strategies of questioning and comparison to identify and link concepts.With open coding, the data were decomposed and the concepts were categorized.Then with the comparative analysis the similar codes were merged, and with the axial coding they were linked, revealing interactions between the factors that contribute to highlighting the role of AI in the modification of purchasing practices.This analysis is still in progress and the results demonstrated here do not reflect a completely finished analysis.

Fisrt Results

Through the first data analysis, we highlighted four main areas of perception regarding the integration of AI in purchasing practices: improving efficiency and automation, concerns related to the reliability and ethics of AI in purchasing, the conditions necessary for successful integration and the implications for process transformation, while highlighting the importance of strategic alignment between the implementation of AI, the performance strategy of companies and the expectations of buyers.

According to the results, AI is considered an important lever for efficiency and automation.Participants highlighted its ability to reduce repetitive and time-consuming tasks, such as the analysis of calls for tenders and the centralization of supplier data, while improving the speed and accuracy of decisions.By freeing purchasing staff from transactional activities, AI allows a better allocation of resources towards strategic activities, such as negotiation or innovation in sourcing, thus contributing to organizational objectives of competitiveness and performance.This aspect highlights a concordance between the use of AI and the strategic priorities of companies.Despite its benefits, participants raised concerns about AI's reliability and ethics, emphasizing the need for quality data to avoid errors and biases.

Concerns about data security were also raised, reflecting the need for rigorous management to ensure trust in the use of these tools.These concerns, although technical, are intrinsically linked to the ability of organizations to align purchasing practices with their strategic and ethical requirements.

For successful integration, several organizational and operational conditions were highlighted, including training purchasing teams, accessing reliable databases, and establishing clear frameworks to align AI with business objectives.These elements reinforce the idea that the involvement of AI in procurement can only be effective if the implementation is carried out in an environment that ensures consistency with buyers' expectations and the strategic priorities of organizations.Finally, the implications for process transformation were discussed, although most participants currently perceive AI as a tool for optimizing tasks rather than a driver of fundamental change.However, its capabilities in predictive modeling and advanced analytics are recognized as having the potential to better align purchasing practices with long-term organizational objectives. This therefore makes it possible to promote rapid decisions while meeting buyers' operational expectations.The results show that AI integration in purchasing is not only viewed as a tool for automation and efficiency but also as a strategic enabler, aligning with organizational goals and professional needs to drive a coherent and effective transformation of purchasing processes.

Conclusion

The objective of this research is to explore the integration of AI in purchasing, with a particular focus on the role of this technology as a process innovation enabler. The results highlight the promise of AI to improve efficiency and support decision-making, while revealing challenges related to data reliability, ethical concerns, and the balance between automation and human intervention.

Given the nascent state of AI research in purchasing, this study's originality lies in exploring how AI enables the redefinition of purchasing processes and drives process innovation, an understudied area. It also offers fresh insights into the interplay between technological integration and organizational objectives, providing a novel perspective on process innovation in purchasing.

Regarding managerial contributions, this research offers concrete avenues for effective AI integration, emphasizing organizational readiness, data quality, and training. It highlights the importance of aligning AI adoption with broader strategic objectives to enhance efficiency, adaptability, and innovation. By addressing both technical and human dimensions, this study provides managers with a framework to responsibly and effectively leverage AI in purchasing practices.

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Paper topic

10. Purchasing innovation, 11. Digital

Balancing Stability and Flexibility in Transportation Procurement: A Dual-Channel Sourcing Approach Under Uncertainty

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Balancing Stability and Flexibility in Transportation Procurement: A Dual-Channel Sourcing Approach Under Uncertainty

Effective transportation management requires companies to implement robust capacity management strategies. Efficient capacity management influences overall performance and ensures uninterrupted service to customers. This process involves two key stakeholders: the shipper and the carrier. While the shipper assumes the role of the service purchaser, the carrier acts as the supplier.

Transportation purchasing decisions involve a variety of objectives, including cost minimization, performance maximization and risk management (Agatz et al., 2024). These decisions are shaped by factors such as market dynamics, supplier performance, and the company's strategic goals. In markets characterized by seasonal fluctuations in transportation prices, risk management becomes particularly critical for shippers. One of the key challenges in managing supplier relationships in such market conditions is balancing efficiency and flexibility. To address this, shippers can adopt one of two approaches: long-term contracts, typically annual, for transportation services, or vehicle procurement through the spot market (Wang et al., 2021).

Annual agreements involve long-term commitments between the parties, usually valid for one year, providing stability and predictability for both shippers and carriers. Such agreements require mutual trust and cooperation between the parties, which forms the basis for long-term business relationships (Acocella and Caplice, 2023). However, they also introduce challenges, particularly in terms of flexibility during market fluctuations. In particular, errors in demand forecasting or sudden market changes can reduce the effectiveness of annual agreements. Spot markets, on the other hand, offer flexibility and allow shippers to purchase as needed, based on current market conditions (Houghton and Amini, (2024). In the spot market, prices are determined by equipment supply and demand and therefore trading in the spot market can lead to cost savings in low seasons, but higher costs in peak seasons. However, the spot market carries inherent risks, such as the lack of guaranteed equipment availability during high-demand periods.

Long-term contracts with carriers often provide stability and predictability, but they may also limit a shipper's ability to respond quickly to changes in demand or market conditions. Controversially, reliance on spot markets can offer flexibility but introduces risks such as price volatility and supply uncertainty (Kleindorfer and Wu, 2023). Dual channel sourcing is recognized as an effective strategy for shippers, offering advantages in cost and flexibility against market fluctuations (Xing et al., 2014). However, this strategy also presents challenges, particularly when cost increases or changing market conditions impact equipment supply. To mitigate such risks, shippers may allocate fixed large quantities for long-term contracts to ensure supply during peak seasons. By this way, the shipper guarantees the equipment availability, but may lose the trust of the supplier when the shipper requests less than the contracted amount during the normal seasons (Yang et al., 2017). Consequently, the shipper may run the potential risk of equipment shortages during peak periods due to strained relationships with carriers. Such an opportunistic behavior may also be possible as the dark-side of long-term supplier relationships (Vilenna et al., 2011). An opportunist shipper may abuse long-term agreements by allocating the demand to fixed-price contracts during high cost periods, and resorting to spot markets during low-cost periods, further exacerbating supply imbalances. Such opportunism is one of the most common ethical problems between the parties in the supply chain and these behaviors often undermine the trust between the parties (Grandinetti, 2017). Mir et al, (2017) suggests that violation of psychological contracts or loss of trust in these contracts are the main factors that trigger switching behavior, and even contract termination.

Optimization of purchasing processes typically involves methods such as cost-effectiveness analyses, supplier evaluations, and risk management strategies. Quantitative modeling in transportation sourcing is essential in supply chain management, enabling businesses to make informed supplier selection decisions, optimize costs, and may improve operational efficiency. However, studies addressing the dual channel sourcing, particularly those considering behavioral aspects such as risk-taking tendencies, remain limited.

In this context, this research investigates long-term contracting decisions in an uncertain transportation market with seasonal effects, supplemented by spot market supply. The study examines how businesses can strike a balance between these two approaches by utilizing hybrid models that combine the benefits of long-term contracts with the flexibility of spot markets. To this purpose, two mathematical models are developed to analyze supplier decisions under different conditions.

The first model examines the pure opportunistic behavior of shippers with two objectives: minimizing cost and maximizing suppliers' performance without considering equipment shortages during peak periods. This model ignores the risk of equipment shortages during peak periods. The second model considers three objectives: minimizing cost, maximizing supplier performance, and minimizing losses based on prospect theory. In Prospect Theory, individuals' behaviors when facing risks diverge from what classical economics predicts and states that people differently react to gains and losses. From the shipper's perspective, fixed price contracts might be considered as a win when prices escalate in the market, but viewed as loss when prices drop in the market. Hence, the model adopts a piecewise utility function, linking the probability of vehicle availability to goodwill losses, and incorporates spot market uncertainty, accounting for loss aversion and diminishing sensitivity beyond a certain loss threshold.

The models are applied to hypothetical companies—opportunistic and risk-averse—under various scenarios, including homogeneous and heterogeneous supplier bases, pronounced seasonal differences, and varying levels of risk aversion.

The preliminary analysis results show that opportunistic carriers tend to over-contract, which may lead to a loss of trust between shippers and carriers. In contrast, loss aversion tends to reduce the number of long-term contracts in all scenarios, which reduces the loss of goodwill and makes the cooperation sustainable, hence decreasing the risk of equipment shortages. When the risk perception is decreased, the tendency towards opportunism is observed. These findings demonstrate that a Prospect Theory-based model can provide a foundation for dual-channel sourcing strategies, integrating long-term contracts with spot markets.

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Paper topic

5. Supplier selection, 12. Ethics, 18. Risk and resilience

Drivers, Barriers and Interventions for Green Hydrogen Supply Chains:A Multi-Actor Framework

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

Green hydrogen supply chains (GHSC) must scale rapidly to support decarbonization. This study develops a framework to identify drivers, barriers, and interventions for actors in GHSCs using an exploratory multiple case study with 12 cases. The framework categorizes drivers and barriers into five areas: demand, economics, technology, actor dynamics, and policy. Interventions occur at three levels: actors, supply chains, and markets. While GHSC opportunities are recognized, economic uncertainties, high costs, and regulatory ambiguity hinder progress. Proactive collaboration is essential for viable business models, investment de-risking, and competitive GHSCs, emphasizing the need for stable policies and market-aligned interventions.

Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

Procurement for carbon reduction in the infrastructure sector – organizational and institutional perspectives

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Background and aim

The infrastructure construction sector is increasingly recognized as a major source of carbon emissions and, therefore, has a significant role in meeting national and international carbon reduction targets. Measures to achieve carbon reduction include a wide range of activities: new construction materials, optimizing designs to reduce volumes of construction material (primarily cement, asphalt and steel) and energy use over the life cycle, coordinating use of masses within and between projects, and minimizing emissions from transport and site operations. Since construction is a demand-led sector, public infrastructure clients have begun to use procurement requirements intended to mitigate carbon emissions.

Procurement for carbon reduction in construction projects is however a new and complex field where practices vary and are developing. Firstly, there are different types of requirements, including award criteria (rewarding supplier competence or carbon footprint); specific requirements for material, fuel or vehicles; specific requirements for organizational competences and resources, and reduction requirements or bonuses relating to the carbon footprint. Further, procurement routes and payment principles are important: suppliers can be involved early or later in the process and procured based on lowest price or for a collaborative alliance. All procurement models are associated with transaction costs, and buyers are generally dependent on supplier competence and preferences to secure bids. Accordingly, research has shown that implementing new procurement requirements is a long-term process, based in interaction between developments at institutional, organizational and project levels (Kadefors et al., 2021). Often, environmental functions are driving development, while purchasing departments and project managers are more reluctant. There is also a need for broad knowledge development. Thus, new procurement requirements are preceded by lengthy processes of legitimization and capability building.

Furthermore, many national policies for carbon reduction rely on stepwise sharpening of goals, typically percentage reductions relation to 2030, 2045 or 2055. Translating these to contract requirements means that risks increase accordingly. Contextual changes are also important: developments in

standardization, new materials and regulations may open for new solutions. Hence, what is the optimal procurement model will vary over time. Therefore, it is important to understand the actors, processes and organizational context that shape procurement requirements and strategies and adjust them over time to changing circumstances.

This working paper follows the introduction and development of new procurement requirements for carbon reduction in the Swedish Transport Administration (STA) over more than a decade. It uses the lense of institutional work and entrepreneurship (Battilana et al., 2009; Micelotta et al., 2017), and focuses on actors and how their strategies have been designed and modified over time.

Method

The case study is based on results from two reviews, performed by the consultancy company WSP for the STA to follow up the implementation and effects of the requirements, as well as on documents and a complementary (still ongoing) interview study. The first review project, Control Station 2018, was based on interviews with 80 persons from 16 companies (STA representatives, contractors, consultants and material suppliers) and the second, Control station 2023, was based on 15 interviews with representatives for larger projects and a questionnaire survey to smaller projects with 384 responses. In the complementary part, one workshop has been held and 6-7 interviews are planned.

Preliminary results

Sweden has a long tradition of ambitious environmental politics with the aim to be a forerunner to inspire other countries to follow. In 1991 Sweden was one of the first countries to introduce a carbon dioxide tax on fossil fuels, and today the climate goal states that Sweden will have net zero emissions by 2045 and strive for “negative net emissions” of carbon from 2045 onwards (compared to 1990). Since 2018, a Climate Act requires the Swedish Government to present an implementation plan every fourth year to demonstrate how the climate goals will be reached.

The Swedish Transport Administration is responsible for planning, building and operation of state roads and railways, and stands for around 30 per cent of the market for infrastructure construction. Since 2016, the STA has implemented procurement requirements for the mitigation of carbon in the construction, operation and maintenance of transport infrastructure. The STA was however not formally required to introduce such requirements by the Swedish Government. Instead, the driver has been the national climate goals.

Procurement models and their background

The STA procurement requirements differ for large and small infrastructure projects. Projects with a total budget over 5 million Euro have a carbon reduction target relating to the carbon footprint. Reduction is verified against a project baseline, calculated by the tool Klimatkalkyl, provided by STA. For design-build contracts with an estimated operation start between 2020 and 2024 the target was 15% carbon reduction. Projects estimated to be finalised 2025-2030 are required to achieve a 30% reduction compared to the baseline. If the targets are exceeded, a bonus can be awarded, and if requirements are not met, there are sanctions. For smaller projects, specific requirements are used. Maximum carbon emission levels are stipulated for reinforcement steel and concrete, and at least 20 per cent of the

energy used for construction equipment and vehicles must be based on renewable fuel, or on electricity from renewable sources.

Several previous developments have influenced the design of the model. Firstly, the LCA-based international EPD (Environmental Product Declarations) system was developed by the Swedish Environmental Management Council in the mid-1990s. Further, the STA has been inspired by requirements by the EU Commission on CO₂ emissions from vehicles. These had a long-term perspective, letting the industry know future requirements in advance. Another goal was to be technology neutral, by requiring a CO₂-emission performance level instead of specific technical solutions, and to stimulate the most cost-efficient solutions. This model further aligns with another general STA policy, introduced in 2010, to be a “pure client” and place responsibility for design innovation on the supplier side.

Experiences

In general, interviewees have been positive about the requirements. In the study performed in 2018, many examples of measures to reduce carbon without increased cost were identified. However, many of these were hard to distinguish from regular procedures for optimising material use and logistics. Further, many interviewees reported that much time was spent on revising and recalculating baselines as the project scope changed over time. Since time and competence was scarce, there could be a conflict between performing calculations vs finding and implementing reduction measures. Further, the functional reduction requirements had not yet propagated through the supply chain to the suppliers of, for example, cement, concrete and steel products, who had so far seen no demand for low-carbon alternatives in infrastructure projects. In general, suppliers requested more guidance for how to work systematically with carbon management, and perceived specific requirements such as in the smaller projects to be more efficient. It was suggested that STA should specify expected meetings, roles and processes for carbon management, to help consultants and contractors make realistic estimations of the resources needed and price them more correctly in the tender. Suppliers also said that STA project management did not always prioritize carbon measures. Another view was that there is a need for more and stronger collaboration in the supply chain to reach more substantial carbon reductions.

In the study from 2023, many of these experiences remained, and the recommendations were largely similar between the two reports. However, knowledge is more widespread, and many practices have developed. The use of low-carbon concrete is not questioned as it was in 2018, but when facing higher requirements some suppliers have found it less expensive to pay sanctions fees than to meet reduction goals.

Overall, the interviews show that the STA's climate requirements play an important role by signalling to the industry that the climate change issue is important. As the requirements are well known, they are perceived to contribute to creating long-term guidance for the industry. They also align with suppliers' own policies, and thus have high legitimacy.

Discussion

The discussion will centre around the role of the environmental units in STA acting as institutional entrepreneurs in preparing for carbon requirements over many years, forming communities of practice with external competencies. Another question is why there has been such a strong focus on reduction requirements, despite the suppliers' preference for collaborative contracts and specific requirements.

Also, the current organizational context, which will be shaping requirements for the future, is described and discussed.

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Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 3. Purchasing organisation, 10. Purchasing innovation

Designing an inflation management tool for souring

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The paper presents a comprehensive approach to addressing inflation challenges within strategic sourcing. Recognising that traditional sourcing models inadequately address inflation, the authors develop an actionable inflation management framework informed by literature reviews and expert interviews. The study identifies key levers, such as assessing cost-passing capabilities, utilising inflation heat maps, and integrating supply-side and demand-side inflation strategies. Using the design science research framework, the paper refines its conceptual model through empirical validation with industry stakeholders. This model bridges theoretical insights with practical applications, offering manufacturing organisations a systematic tool for mitigating inflation risks and optimising sourcing strategies. The findings contribute to academia and industry, enhancing sourcing strategies in inflationary contexts.

Paper topic

2. PSM strategy, 18. Risk and resilience, 19. Supply chain finance

Improving ESG performance via circular supply chains: Moderation of stakeholder engagement and digitalization

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Summary: ESG reporting has become a prominent framework for measuring responsible business practices, and supply chain networks are closely associated with buyer companies' ESG scores. Particularly, inserting circularity principles into supply chains is likely to yield positive sustainability outcomes. This study aims to investigate the impact of circular supply chains (CSC) on corporate ESG performance and to test the moderating roles of stakeholder engagement and digitalization in this relationship. A panel data analysis of 397 Standards&Poor's companies reveals that all proposed effects are significant. While CSC improves overall ESG performance, both stakeholder engagement and digitalization applications strengthen this influence.

Keywords: ESG performance, circular economy, circular supply chain, stakeholder engagement, suppliers, digitalization

Theoretical Framework

ESG Performance and Supply Chain Circularity

Circular supply chain management (CSCM) has gained increasing attention during the last decades among business organizations. In their recent sustainability report, Swedish fast fashion giant, H&M explains the interconnected areas of its circular ecosystem focus as 'circular products', 'circular customer journey', and 'circular supply chain', which encompasses the former two components by "building scalable systems that circulate products and materials for repair, reuse, remake and recycling and that use lower- impact production processes — such as dyeing, printing and finishing" (H&M, 2024). While the concept can be defined as "the integration of circular thinking into the management of the supply chain and its surrounding industrial and natural ecosystems" (Farooque et al., 2019: 884), the increasing number of studies explore its antecedents and consequences; yet, there are still some questions that must be addressed in the literature (Lahane et al., 2020). As one of these critical questions, we need to understand to what extent CSCM can contribute to a company's environmental, social, and governance (ESG) performance.

ESG framework comprises the prioritization of ESG issues in investment decisions (Seow, 2023). Many studies have attempted to explore and discuss the key antecedents of improved ESG performance. For instance, institutional pressures (e.g. state, financial markets), corporate governance, audit quality, media exposure, CEO and board characteristics, ownership structure, organizational culture, leadership style, digital transformation, and R&D capability have been listed among the determinants of ESG performance across national, organizational, and individual levels. Despite its increasing importance, a few studies connect ESG performance with circularity (e.g. Patil et al., 2021; Lawrence, 2025) and none of them specifically focuses on the impact of CSCM on ESG performance. However, CSCM has been the major area where circularity transforms all the dynamics of product, process, relationship in an interorganizational level. Therefore, the integration of circular thinking in SCM can enhance ESG performance in organizations. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Improving CSC positively affects the ESG performance.

According to Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2023), CSC requires ‘distributed and interconnected networks’ to enable the collaboration among the local and global stakeholders, “multidirectional flows of information, goods, and money to enable data” and “ability to capture and deliver value by keeping products and materials in use”. The current study particularly focuses on the former two dimensions as the moderators that strengthen the link between CSC and ESG performance; while the first one points out how well a company engages its stakeholders; the second dimension requires having a capacity to manage all these flows of data – which leads many companies towards digitalization.

Stakeholder Engagement and Digitalization

Stakeholder engagement can be described as the process in which firms involve stakeholders in their business decisions and practices (Greenwood, 2007) to achieve agreed-upon outcomes (Leopizzi, 2023). Besides significant impacts on value creation, innovation, and strategic decision-making, successful stakeholder engagement has a positive connection to ESG performance (Dobele et al. 2014). It was found that investor activism that focuses on environmental and social issues induces ESG score adjustments via compliance with relevant stakeholder demands (Barko et al. 2022). In line with these findings, we argue that engaging stakeholders in sustainable business practices will enhance the effect of CSC on firm ESG performance as they constantly monitor, scrutinize, and support the implementation of circularity principles across the supply chain.

H2: Engaging stakeholders in sustainability practices moderates the link between CSC and ESG performance.

Digitalization is another major issue that transforms the traditional ways of doing business and relationships among chain actors. Considering its pervasiveness across industries, digital technologies can also channel circularity efforts at SCM into ESG-related outcomes. For instance, many industries, which are characterized by long and very complexity supply chain structure have difficulties to trace the materials used for products throughout its life cycle. As of 2024, European Union (EU) started to implement a regulation for the use of digital product passport (DPP) as part of its “ecodesign for sustainable products regulations” “to enhance transparency across product value chains by providing comprehensive information about each product’s origin, materials, environmental impact, and disposal recommendations” (EU, 2024). By reducing information asymmetry, supply chain digitalization significantly enhances the ESG performance of corporations (Chen et al., 2024). Firms must back up their circularity efforts on supply chain with digital technologies when addressing the social and

environmental concerns as well as strengthening the governance mechanism. Therefore, the following hypotheses can be provided as:

H3: Using digital technologies in sustainability practices moderates the link between CSC and ESG performance.

Methodology

Sample and Data Collection

To empirically test the relationship between variables, the sample size of this paper was derived from Standards & Poor's (S&P) 500 indexed companies. The stock market index known as the S&P 500 is based on the performance of the stocks representing the 500 biggest firms traded on US exchanges. Considering the direct impact of sectors on supply chain circularity, the sectors to be sampled were Consumer Discretionary, Consumer Staples, Energy, Health Care, Industrials, Materials, and Utilities. In data collection, it is important that these companies publish ESG or sustainability reports and have an ESG score. Therefore, in this index, 397 companies that meet the conditions within the scope of the study were selected as the final sampled companies over the year 2016-2021. In total, a sample with the 2279 observations was analysed by using panel regression analysis for 6 years. Data on the ESG performance of the sampled companies were collected through the ESG score calculated by S&P. Data for the independent and moderator variables of this study were collected through published ESG or Sustainability reports of the sampled companies based on the specified word count frequency. Lastly, data on financial indicators collected through the financial reports of sampled companies.

Measures

This paper is grounded on testing how ESG performance improved through CSC regarding the moderator role of stakeholder engagement and digitalization. To do so, this study used various measures. Total ESG performance is measured by ESG score provided by S&P, which is the dependent variable of this paper. To proxy ESG performance, independent and moderator variables were considered. CSC is the independent variable of this study, measured by the determined word count frequency in published ESG or sustainability report. This study also has two moderator variables that are stakeholder engagement and digitalization, which were measured by considering determined word count frequency in published ESG or sustainability report. Lastly, return on assets, total assets, and financial leverage ratio was issued as control variables of this paper.

Data Analysis

Initially, descriptive statistics, correlation and multicollinearity test is addressed. Then, depending on the Hausman test statistics, we checked whether the fixed or random regression model is appropriate to the nature of the data. Random effect panel regression analysis is used to test the relationship between the hypothesized variables. Moreover, to deal with possible endogeneity, the generalized method of moments (GMM) is used. The following models were tested;

Baseline Model

In this baseline model, the impact of CSC on ESG performance is tested with and without control variables, considering year and industry effects.

$$\text{ESG} = \text{CSC} + \text{Year} + \text{Industry} + e \text{ (Model 1)}$$

$$\text{ESG} = \text{CSC} + \text{ROA} + \text{FinancialLeverage} + \text{Size} + \text{Year} + \text{Industry} + e \text{ (Model 2)}$$

Moderating Model

In this moderating model, this time, the impact of CSC on ESG performance is tested through moderating role of stakeholder engagement and digitalization. The year and industry effect are also included. In this model, the coefficients CSC, CSCxStakeholder Engagement, and CSCxDigitalization is expected to be positive.

$$\text{ESG} = \text{CSC} + \text{Digitalization} + \text{StakeholderEngagement} + \text{CSCxDigitalization} + \text{CSCxStakeholderEngagement} + \text{ROA} + \text{FinancialLeverage} + \text{Size} + \text{Year} + \text{Industry} + e$$

(Model 3)

Results

The results of model 1 indicates that there is a positive and significant relationship between CSC and ESG. In model 2, a positive and significant relationship is existed between CSC and ESG. Considering the control variables, ROA and Size is positively and significantly related to ESG at 1 percent, while Financial Leverage is at 5 percent. Among these control variables, Size has the highest coefficient. Model 3 reveals that CSC has a statistically significant and positive impact on ESG at 1 percent. Moreover, in this relationship, Digitalization and Stakeholder Engagement has moderating effect at 5 percent significance level. Considering the control variables for Model 3, ROA, FinancialLeverage, and Size positively and significantly affect ESG at 1, 10, and 1 percent level respectively.

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social

Exploring the relationship between sustainability practices, organisations' affiliations, and financial performance of the UK fashion industry.

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Sustainability as a concept has garnered increased attention over the last 2 decades owing to several factors, including ecological, environmental, and societal factors, steered by different stakeholders' interests. This is quite pertinent within the fashion industry which is characterised by a lot of issues. For instance, as well as been the third biggest manufacturing industry in the world (Zhang, Zhang & Zhou, 2021), the fashion industry is the second largest polluting industry globally, after the oil and gas industry (Papasolomou et al., 2023). The fashion industry is also criticised for unethical practices relating to unsafe working conditions and child labour (Arduini et al., 2024). These issues of climate crisis and human right scandals are becoming more visible, resulting in increased consumer awareness and demand for a more sustainable and ethically produced fashion. From an organisational perspective, sustainability practices include the three pillars of environmental, social and governance. Wherein to address environmental concerns, organisations are expected to adopt a more circular approach of *'take-make-distribute-use-recover'* instead than a linear approach of *'take-make-waste'* thereby mitigating climate change and pollution crisis. To address social concerns, organisations are expected to adopt ethical practices, like improving employees' working conditions, respecting employees' human rights and promoting equal opportunities, whilst to address governance concerns, organisations should have in place systems to ensure the previous targets are met as well as promoting a good corporate culture where the organisations, its employees, partners, and the community thrive (Arduini et al., 2024). Similarly, Pedersen et al. (2018) also suggested that adopting a sustainable business model, using organic and environmentally friendly materials, ensuring fair working conditions, ensuring traceability and certification are examples of sustainability practices.

Although, there have been efforts by the fashion industry to move towards a more sustainable processes in responses to these demands (Arduini et al., 2024; International Labour Organisation, 2023; Medcalfe & Miralles Miro, 2022), the fashion industry has remained largely linear in nature creating a lot of waste, which has severe environmental consequences (Abbate et al., 2024; Saha et al., 2024). Arduini et al. (2024) has also stressed that the fashion industry is one of the industries that have widely adopted the Social Accountability 8000 (SA8000) certification, yet it is highly characterised with human rights and poor working conditions of employees' issues. This somehow imply that these

certifications are either poorly implemented or not effective. This situation has led to the introduction of new policies and/or regulations, such as, the Eco-design for sustainable product regulations (ESPR), Digital Markets, Competition and Consumers Act 2024 to influence and promote the uptake of sustainable practices in the fashion industry. There are also other factors influencing the uptake of sustainability practices, like organisational resources, technological innovation, market conditions, as well as the impact such practices have on organisational performance, i.e. environmental, social, and financial performance (Prieto-Sandoval et al., 2018; Saha et al., 2022).

Traditionally, organisations' performance is primarily measured from the financial performance perspective, relegating environmental and social performances to the bottom of organisations' priority. However, this has changed with many arguing that sustainability practices can lead to competitive advantage, with many studies proving a positive relationship between sustainability practices and financial performance (Li et al., 2017; Medcalfe & Miralles Miro, 2022; Surroca et al., 2010; Trumpp & Guenther, 2017). However, a recent study focusing on the fashion industry established mixed findings between sustainability practices and financial performance. For instance, in Arduini et al. (2024) whilst a significant positive relationship was found between organisations' sustainability practices and stock prices, implying investors consider sustainability performance in their investment decisions, no statistically significant relationship was found between environmental performance and corporate profitability. This finding contradicts the study of Medcalfe & Miralles Miro (2022) which found significant positive relationship between sustainability practices and financial performances in the fashion industry. These mixed findings hinder the genuine uptake of sustainability practices, which in turn leads to more GHG emissions, water usage, use of hazardous chemicals, use of unsustainable fibres and poor waste management within the sector.

Notwithstanding the preceding arguments, the State of Fashion 2024 report by McKinsey & Company (2024) stressed the views of fashion executives who continue to prioritise sustainability and are poised to building more sustainable businesses across the fashion industry. Whilst this is laudable, understanding the relationship between sustainability practices and profitability, especially the role of certifications and affiliations is crucial to help organisations within this industry identify the most significant sustainability practices driving profitability, therefore make strategic decisions based on these. This is specifically vital considering the varied practices, certifications and affiliations linked to sustainability. A recent study by Arduini et al. (2024) stressed the need for more exploration into the relationship between sustainability practices and corporate profitability within the fashion industry. Also, addressing the growing demand on the fashion industry to improve its operations by implementing sustainability practices (Hiller-Connell et al., 2017; Jestratijevic et al., 2020; Medcalfe & Miralles Miro, 2022), will require strong justifications of how such practices impact on the financial performance of organisations instead of mixed evidence.

So far, there is limited empirical evidence exclusively examining the relationship between sustainability practices of the UK fashion industry from a broad spectrum of environmental, social and governance perspective on corporate profitability. Unlike, the work of Arduini et al. (2024), our study focusses on a broader spectrum of practices, certifications, and affiliations, to determine the extent to which these

variables impact on organisations' corporate profitability, especially within the UK. Focusing on the UK context would provide better and richer understanding of the relationship between the research variables taking into consideration the contextual nature of implementing sustainability practices. Considering the above, the following research questions are proposed:

RQ1: What is the impact of implementing sustainability practices on the profitability of UK fashion organisations?

RQ2: What impact does UK fashion organisations' certifications and affiliations have on their profitability?

To answer the proposed research questions, the study collected relevant secondary data relating to the sustainability practices (i.e., responsible production processes, eco-efficient distribution, carbon emissions, ethical labour practice, sourcing sustainable materials, water usage, waste generation) of fashion brands operating in the UK, information about their certifications and affiliations as well as their financial reports. Multiple regression analysis will be undertaken using Stata to determine the relationship between the research variable.

Keywords: Fashion industry, sustainability practices, environmental performance, social performance, financial performance.

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Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social, 20. Sector/industry studies (e.g., healthcare, fashion, etc.)

233

Governance structure and TCE attributes

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Selecting an appropriate governance structure remains a critical decision in supply chain management. This decision has been addressed through transaction cost economics (TCE) for several years, yet challenges still seem to exist in terms of the operationalization and measurement of the theory's key concepts. To address some of this challenge, this paper develops a novel TCE quantification method for operationalizing TCE attributes and trust. The study collected data through survey interviews from two manufacturing companies to empirically test the method. The method introduced in the study provided a coherent and analytical approach to navigating the complexities of the selection process.

Paper topic

2. PSM strategy, 6. Outsourcing, offshoring, reshoring, 15. PSM theory, methodology, education

A systematic analysis of industrial symbiosis relationships

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

In contemporary society, climate change is recognized as one of the most urgent challenges (Ghisellini and Ulgiati, 2020). Although variations in climate have been a part of Earth's history, the rate of warming experienced over the past 150 years is unparalleled, largely due to human activities (Enel - Green Power, 2024). Since the onset of the Industrial Revolution, human actions have resulted in the emission of billions of tons of greenhouse gases, particularly carbon dioxide (CO₂), leading to levels that are now twice as high as the lowest recorded values over the last 700,000 years (Enel - Green Power, 2024). This scenario presents significant environmental concerns, as well as economic, socio-political, and health challenges that necessitate a unified and concerted global response. To effectively address this crisis, the European Union has introduced the Green Deal, an action plan designed to attain climate neutrality by 2050, making Europe the first carbon-neutral continent. Simultaneously, the Action Plan for the Circular Economy aims to shift the economic framework from a linear model characterized by extraction, production, and disposal to a circular model that emphasizes the optimization of resource use and the reduction of waste throughout the supply chain. According to the FAO, roughly one-third of the world's food is lost or wasted every year, amounting to 30 percent of total production. Food waste occurs at various stages of the supply chain, including primary production, industrial processing, and distribution, and also results from the amount wasted by end consumers (Cattaneo et al., 2024). The traditional linear economic model, which is focused around the processes of extraction, processing, consumption, and waste generation, is increasingly recognized as unsustainable in light of current environmental conditions (Cooney et al., 2023). In contrast, the circular economy offers a framework for optimized resource management that prioritizes waste reduction and the reuse of by-products (Aït-Kaddour et al., 2024). Ghisellini et al. (2016) pointed out that the circular economy seeks to create a balance among economic, environmental, and social dimensions by reducing the consumption of natural resources and minimizing pollution. The circular economy presents significant environmental and social benefits, including the preservation of ecosystems, a decrease in greenhouse gas emissions, and the protection of biodiversity (Cristoni and Tonelli, 2018). Effectively managing waste and by-products across various industries presents significant challenges, primarily due to the high levels of resource consumption and the consequent environmental pollution they generate. Industrial symbiosis is a fundamental strategy within the circular economy framework (Fraccascia et al., 2019). This approach facilitates collaboration among companies across sectors to share resources, energy, and by-products. It reduces operational costs and enhances the efficient use of resources, contributing to sustainable

business practices. Industrial symbiosis offers a strategic and innovative solution to these issues by facilitating the collaborative use of waste materials. Through Industrial symbiosis, companies can transform their by-products into valuable resources for other businesses, creating a network of shared benefits. This approach enhances sustainability by minimizing waste, reducing environmental impact, and maximizing value for all stakeholders involved in the interconnected supply chains. In this way, industrial symbiosis helps to foster a circular economy, where waste is reimagined as a resource, promoting economic efficiency and ecological responsibility. Indeed, Industrial symbiosis establishes strategic connections among enterprises across various sectors to enhance resource efficiency, reduce reliance on virgin raw materials, and optimize the recovery of waste by-products that would otherwise be discarded. This approach supports advancing a circular economy by facilitating the exchange of resources and waste among companies. Such collaboration creates new market opportunities, improves operational efficiency, and mitigating environmental impact, thereby promoting sustainable practices within the business landscape. However, implementing Industrial symbiosis requires the development of collaborative competencies among purchasing and supply management.

This study conducts a comprehensive and systematic literature review to identify the barriers preventing industrial symbiosis development, which entails collaboration among industries to effectively utilize one another's by-products and resources. The systematic literature review has identified the primary barriers to implementing industrial symbiosis and classified these barriers into five macro-categories: economic, technical, regulatory, social, and communication. Among the critical issues identified are high startup costs, insufficient infrastructure, and inadequate integration of logistics systems among companies. The review further examines essential factors such as the level of trust among partners and the significance of digital platforms in facilitating the exchange of information. Additionally, the study introduces a detailed taxonomy of development configurations that illustrate various scenarios or evolutionary models of industrial symbiosis in practice. The study emphasizes the capabilities necessary for each configuration presented to facilitate and enhance collaboration across different sectors. It delineates the fundamental capabilities organizations must develop to address technical, managerial, and operational challenges effectively. These capabilities are essential for cultivating an environment helpful to achieving shared objectives. Finally, this paper proposes a taxonomy of Industrial symbiosis development configurations. This taxonomy delineates a progression from basic internal by-product recovery methods to more sophisticated network structures, including Eco-Industrial Parks (EIPs). Each configuration is characterized by the operational and dynamic capabilities necessary to manage cross-sector collaboration while effectively addressing specific challenges. The proposed evolutionary model offers a theoretical framework for organizations seeking to implement Industrial symbiosis and serves as a practical roadmap to inform their decision-making processes. Organizations can effectively navigate challenges such as mistrust, fragmented information, and logistical inefficiencies by focusing on key capabilities. By prioritizing these areas, they can foster collaboration and streamline operations for improved overall performance. By adopting this thorough approach, the study aims to provide valuable insights into effective strategies that can mitigate the identified barriers and promote successful cooperation and synergy in the implementation of industrial symbiosis initiatives, ultimately contributing to enhanced sustainability and resource efficiency in industrial operations.

In addition, we conducted a Delphi study that engaged a panel of experts through a structured evaluation and consensus-building process, to develop the final framework. This method ensured a comprehensive assessment and integration of expert perspectives, enhancing the framework's reliability and applicability. This comprehensive strategy is essential for successfully implementing industrial symbiosis within various production contexts. It offers critical guidance on effectively managing and developing the requisite capabilities.

By emphasizing collaborative efforts among different industries, this approach enhances operational efficiency and promotes sustainable practices across the board. The findings of this study are of significant relevance to industry stakeholders, particularly those involved in policymaking. As these individuals seek to devise comprehensive strategies, the insights presented can serve as a resource for enhancing waste management practices. Additionally, this research supports the objectives of Agenda 2030 and the associated Sustainable Development Goals, which strive to create a more sustainable and equitable global future. By effectively addressing the challenges related to waste management, policymakers have the opportunity to foster environmental sustainability and improve community well-being.

Keywords: Delphi study; industrial symbiosis; supply chain management; waste valorization

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Paper topic

16. Sustainability – environmental

E-auction research in the era of industry 4.0 and AI: A systematic review and research agenda

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

In Purchasing and Supply Management (PSM), electronic auctions (e-auctions) are vital tools for cost savings, efficiency, and transforming supplier-buyer relationships. This paper offers a comprehensive literature review on e-auctions in SCM, highlighting future research calls over the past two decades and the potential impacts of Industry 4.0, AI, and Blockchain. By reviewing historical and contemporary e-auctions research on antecedents, consequences, and design recommendations, this study identifies existing knowledge and research gaps. It underscores the transformative potential of e-auctions, particularly with Industry 4.0, AI, and blockchain, and complements a recent review of e-auctions in marketing.

Paper topic

7. Negotiation and contracting, 2. PSM strategy, 10. Purchasing innovation

Framing supply chain sustainability misconducts:-

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

Sustainability-related misconduct in upstream supply chains often impacts both social and environmental sustainability. Consequently, the same misconduct can be reported as 'social' or 'environmental' issue, depending on the perspective adopted. In the business-to-business context, buyers may respond differently depending on the framing. This study, through a scenario-based experiment involving 219 buyers, provides empirical evidence of such differences. Results reveal that buyers' purchase intentions toward the first-tier supplier decline significantly when first-tier supplier misconduct is framed as 'environmental' rather than 'social.' Similarly, buyers' attitudes toward the first-tier supplier decrease when lower-tier suppliers' misconduct is framed as 'environmental' rather than 'social.'

Paper topic

16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social

From Micro to Macro: The Role of Microfoundations of capabilities in overcoming barrier to Circular Procurement

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Circular procurement (CP) is a key enabler of the circular economy (CE), yet its adoption remains limited due to persistent barriers across procurement processes. This study explores the dynamic capabilities (DCs) and their microfoundations that enable firms to overcome these barriers. Using a multiple-case study of Italian manufacturing firms, we identify five key DCs—demand intelligence, market intelligence, strategic design, supplier selection reconfiguration, and contract reconfiguration. Our findings contribute to CP literature by integrating DC theory, providing managerial insights on supplier engagement, procurement strategy, and contract adaptation to accelerate CE transitions.

Paper topic

1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 16. Sustainability - environmental, 10. Purchasing innovation

240

Circular supply chains: A systematic literature review on integration mechanisms

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Summary

Supply chain integration (SCI) has been studied as a concept to overcome barriers in the transition towards circular supply chains (CSCs), which is especially crucial to companies operating in technology-oriented industries, as they aim to recover valuable products and materials. This paper investigates which integration mechanisms could be implemented within the CSCs of these companies through a systematic literature review (SLR). Sev-enty-six integration mechanisms were identified across four SCI dimensions: sharing in-formation, developing collaborative approaches, joint decision-making and system cou-pling. The results contribute to a systematic understanding and show that future research should focus on mechanisms for reverse flows.

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 16. Sustainability - environmental, 2. PSM strategy

The Role of Individual Factors in Supplier Selection Decisions

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

How much do the individual attributes of purchasing managers influence business decisions? Many firms are focusing on sustainability as a strategic priority and implementing socially and environmentally responsible procurement (SERP) practices. SERP is the focus on sustainability—or the equal balancing of ESG (environmental, social, and governance) priorities (Elkington & Rowlands, 1999; Escrig-Olmedo et al., 2019; Henriques & Richardson, 2004; Hoejmose & Kirby, 2012)—in procurement decisions. To achieve success in implementing sustainability within an organization, sustainability must permeate every part of an organization, especially within the supply chain (Carter & Rogers, 2008; Kasemsap, 2017). While sustainability encompasses environmental, social, and governance aspects, environmental sustainability—especially carbon emissions—has consistently been a salient issue in supply chain management.

With the recent Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) ruling on Scope 1 & 2 emissions reporting, large firms operating in the United States must now measure and report their environmental impact in terms of their emissions (U.S. SEC, 2024). However, the ruling does not regulate or require the reporting of Scope 3 emissions. There are two perspectives on measuring and reporting Scope 3 emissions. On one side, Scope 3 emissions are challenging to measure accurately, and the responsibility to reduce these emissions typically falls on customer-facing firms in the downstream supply chain. On the other hand, Scope 3 emissions are the supply chain emissions, which means each firm is responsible for ensuring the sustainability of its supply chain—only then can businesses create systemic change on the sustainability front.

With these differing perspectives also come varying organizational strategies when it comes to taking responsibility for emissions in their supply chain. Many firms require their tier-one suppliers to report their Scope 1 and Scope 2 emissions and implement a plan to reduce them actively. Other firms require additional actions from their supply chain partners, requiring measuring and reporting of emissions at multiple tiers in the upstream supply chain. However, it is typically individual purchasing managers who make supplier selection decisions that ultimately impact the sustainability of their firm's supply chain (Davis-Sramek et al., 2018; Davis-Sramek et al., 2020; Thomas et al., 2016; Thomas et al., 2021).

The behavioral economics literature has established that each individual is inherently more risk-seeking, risk-averse, or risk-neutral, which is exhibited in their decision-making behaviors (Kahneman & Tversky,

2013). Because of the challenges of accurate measurements and chances of double counting, there are risks associated with reporting emissions, and some may perceive greater risks related to reporting Scope 3 emissions. Thus, more risk-averse purchasing managers may not select suppliers reporting all emissions.

In addition, purchasing managers may have strong beliefs about sustainable business practices that may not necessarily align with the organization's sustainability objectives. Previous research has found that managers can act as change agents within their organizations—integrating their personal beliefs and views into their business decisions (Hemingway & Maclagan, 2004). Purchasing managers may strongly believe in taking responsibility for the sustainability of the supply chain and choose suppliers that report all emissions.

This research considers the differences between individual decision-makers (such as risk preferences and sustainability beliefs). With the introduction of individual decision-makers in these sustainable supply chain decisions, specific attributes and biases of these individuals also emerge, as well as room for interpretation. Applying signaling theory, this research seeks to understand how purchasing managers interpret their suppliers' sustainability signals and their organization's sustainability priorities (Connelly et al., 2011).

Through scenario-based experiments, this research seeks to understand the individual factors that drive purchasing managers to select some suppliers over others in a sustainable supply chain context. In a series of vignette experiments, this research manipulates supplier attributes in a supplier selection decision—specifically whether the supplier reports Scope 1 & 2 emissions, all emission types, or does not report emissions at all. This research also manipulates the importance of sustainability on the purchasing manager's supplier scorecard as well as the impact of the supplier's sustainability initiatives. Finally, this research measures various individual factors that may influence supplier selection decisions, such as environmental orientation and risk aversion (Falk et al., 2023; Polonsky et al., 2014).

Our study demonstrates how managers balance the tensions between their corporation's sustainability strategies and their personal sustainability views. Specifically, we seek to understand how purchasing managers perceive signals from their firms on their commitment to sustainability in the supply chain and how these managers interpret signals on the sustainability of their suppliers. Are all scopes of emissions treated equally, or do personal attributes of decision-makers influence their perception of emission reporting from suppliers?

One of the practical implications of this research is that our study analyzes how corporate sustainability directives are translated into operational decisions, such as in purchasing decisions and buyer-supplier relationship management. This research provides insight into the importance of reporting emissions and whether organizations perceive firms reporting Scope 3 emissions as more sustainable. On the other hand, this research also provides a greater understanding of whether greater risks are perceived with Scope 3 emissions reporting. Finally, this research will provide additional knowledge on whether individual attributes of purchasing managers significantly influence supplier selection decisions. Through the application of signaling theory, this research demonstrates how individuals interpret and act upon sustainability signals from their organization and their suppliers.

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Paper topic

5. Supplier selection, 9. Supplier relationships/performance/development, 16. Sustainability - environmental

Learning to fly: tracking how capabilities for innovative public procurement evolve in three municipalities

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Abstract

In this paper, we examine the role of public procurement in fostering innovation within municipalities, with a specific focus on the development of internal capabilities. Previous research presented at IPSERA has identified capabilities (and their antecedents), building on empirical research carried out in municipalities. The present paper expands this research, building on data from municipalities over time. Through an analysis of three distinct procurement cases, we explore how municipalities navigate and respond to changing conditions, leveraging and evolving their capabilities to address complex challenges. Drawing on the classification of capabilities by Grimbert et al. (2024) and Karttunen et al. (2023) emphasizing the mechanisms and capabilities required in digital procurement processes, we investigate how these capabilities evolve in response to the complexities of municipal procurement. Additionally, Schulze and Bals' (2020) framework on general purchasing capabilities in a sustainability context is applied to understand the temporal development of these capabilities within municipalities, offering insight into how municipalities learn and change their strategy over time.

The selected cases provide a nuanced understanding of the strategic development of procurement practices. Exemplifying the learning processes through which municipalities enhance and transform their practices. Our study also highlights the importance of collaboration, both within municipal organizations and with external stakeholders (e.g. suppliers and other municipalities) in promoting innovation and driving systemic change. By examining how dynamic capabilities in public procurement address emerging challenges, this paper underscores its potential as a powerful tool for public adaptation, capacity building, and long-term resilience.

Ultimately, this study contributes to the growing body of literature on public procurement as a driver of innovation and systemic transformation, by contextualizing and conceptualizing the evolving nature of how the capabilities are used over time in dynamic contexts. The paper also offers practical insights for municipalities aiming to leverage procurement as a strategic instrument for achieving innovative outcomes.

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Paper topic

10. Purchasing innovation, 13. Public procurement, 1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences

Acceleration of Digital Procurement Transformation (*work in progress*)

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Practitioner Paper

Abstract/summary

Abstract: Acceleration of Digital Procurement transformation (work-in-progress-interviews)

The business world is experiencing profound changes driven by geopolitical shifts, market fluctuations, and rapid digitalization. Within this context, positioning procurement as a core business function is crucial and enables companies to swiftly adapt to the ever-evolving global landscape (Chick & Handfield, 2015). Digital technology offers the potential for a procurement revolution. Surveys by Deloitte, PwC, and EFFSO underscore the significance of digital procurement, yet many procurement leaders grapple with defining clear digital strategies and visions (Schnellbaecher & Weise, 2020).

The adoption of advanced digital tools in procurement remains limited across companies (Herold, Heller & Rozemeijer, 2023).

Methods

The methodology for this research, included sub-research questions derived from literature and our main research questions. A digital procurement survey was conducted with questions aligned to the sub-research questions. The respondents were from more than 64 different companies in several European countries and primarily CEOs, CPOs, and category managers. Answers were categorized by procurement maturity and innovation readiness, into our model's four quadrants. Follow-up interviews were conducted with selected respondents from each quadrant and with special in-depth interviews on the digital procurement transformation leaders (with high Procurement maturity and high Innovation readiness).

Research Questions and Survey Answers

Our project aims to explore the transformative potential of new technologies in accelerating procurement transformation for sustained competitiveness in a dynamic environment. We have framed two primary research questions:

RQ1:What opportunities do emerging technologies offer for advancing procurement maturity?

RQ2:What managerial strategies and approaches are necessary to effectively leverage these opportunities?

To support the 2 research questions, we have identified several sub-research questions across the following four key areas:

A.Procurement Maturity Level

The distribution of companies across different procurement maturity levels was highlighted: this revealed that 53% of companies leaned towards a primarily commercial functional orientation, while 47% emphasized a cross-functional business orientation.

B.Level of Innovation Readiness and Cooperation in Eco-Systems

-Survey results shed light on the varying levels of innovation readiness, with 65% of respondents showcasing low levels of innovation readiness. However, the data revealed a notable correlation between procurement maturity and innovation readiness.

-The report showed a link between procurement maturity, innovation readiness, and cooperation with partners in ecosystems. While 83% were not currently cooperating, many planned to do so, showing an understanding of the relevance of working in ecosystems with suppliers.

C.Knowledge of New Technologies and Relevance for Procurement

-The survey highlighted a knowledge gap concerning emerging digital tools for procurement across all levels of procurement maturity, with 52% of respondents having little to no knowledge. The results also show the need for increased awareness and education regarding the potential benefits of these tools.

-Most participants (85%) state to have in place standard electronic tools to reduce time and automate transactional activities: P2P-solutions are and will remain a must. While the tools for improved data analysis and to support the decision-making are still not in the target of our respondents but are in the target ambitious plan for most of the companies.

Dike Benefits, Main Barriers, KPIs, and Impact of Digital Procurement Transformation.

-the survey remarks the main benefits resulting from digital procurement, which are in line with the literature research and can be summarized with 2 dimensions: (I) Higher efficiency as reduced time for operational activities and (ii) Higher effectiveness of the data analysis and the decision making.

-three main obstacles were identified by most of the companies,

-Challenges in system integration, which is relevant across all types of companies.

-Lack of understanding of the benefits: this barrier is particularly predominant for the procurement functions with lower level of maturity (about 50% of these companies)

-Limited budget for digital procurement initiatives: the limited budget prevails for the procurement functions with a low level of innovation.

Recommendations and Managerial Implications

Based on findings from our survey, interviews, and literature research, we recommend procurement leaders to create a Roadmap for their digital procurement journey, focusing on business transformation. We have extrapolated the following recommendations for CPOs planning a Digital Procurement transformation Roadmap:

(i) Ensure found key success factors are included: stakeholder involvement, integration of digital technologies into the IT system, and adaptation of procurement processes.
(ii) Recruit procurement staff with prioritized skills in strategic and analytical thinking for new PSM roles.
(iii) Plan for new PSM-roles with major impact (data analyst, master data manager, process automation manager).

(iv) Focus on recruiting innovators for change in the new PSM-roles.
(v) Assess the starting point and maturity of master data as the foundation for data-driven transformation, and allocate necessary resources, skills and leadership.

(vi) Develop augmented roles where humans and AI collaborate to enhance procurement productivity.
(vii) Implement a proactive change strategy with chosen innovators, balancing technical and social innovation to ensure successful transformation and productivity gains.

RQ1: What opportunities do emerging technologies offer for advancing procurement maturity?

Based on our findings we propose a framework model showing how emerging technologies can impact procurement activities (operational, tactical, and strategic) by enabling automation and augmentation, leading to increased efficiency and effectiveness.

- **Procurement Efficiency** results from automating repetitive activities, digitized procurement, also named digitalization of procurement. The two key digital options are automation, where technology handles tasks with human oversight, and automation, where machines independently manage simple, repetitive tasks.

- **Procurement Effectiveness** primarily reflects the improvement of tactical and strategic procurement processes.

Digital procurement transformation uses emerging technologies to transform procurement organization and potentially the entire organization. It goes beyond tool implementation, driving a business transformation that changes culture and capabilities.

RQ2: What managerial strategies and approaches are necessary to effectively leverage these opportunities?

To effectively leverage digital procurement opportunities, leaders need a clear roadmap for digital procurement transformation and valuable business impact. To address the second research question, **"What are the managerial implications of exploiting the opportunities of the new technologies?"** we have developed a model based on two key dimensions of the companies in our study.

1. Procurement maturity

2. Innovation readiness of the procurement function

This model helps assessing a company's procurement maturity and innovation readiness to implement a digital procurement transformation. It's a development model serving as both a starting point and a target to accelerate the transformation process.

I. High procurement – High Innovation: Accelerate procurement

A company with both high procurement maturity and high innovation readiness is positioned as a "procurement disruptor", ideal to embark on the digital procurement transformation journey, particularly to leverage Big Data and AI-tools for a competitive edge. Key design principles found for accelerating the digital procurement transformation is an agile organization and a collaborative culture:

Open & Flexible Systems: a Procurement technology ecosystem of interconnected tools

Companies should leverage advanced digital tools to address the data-intensive nature of procurement and the role of AI. For instance, an interconnected AI-Hub could be designed to include (Strummer et al, 2020):

- A P2P tool for automating procure-to-pay activities.
- Spend visibility and analytics tools for rapid spend analysis and future scenario modeling.
- A bot sourcing tool for RFP/RFQ-processes and an AI-based coach for sourcing strategies of a product category.

People in procurement

In a VUCA-world, procurement professionals must be creative and adaptable. They must manage complex projects, navigate uncertainties, and think strategically, requiring them to utilize both analytical and creative thinking. This "ambidexterity," where procurement professionals balance analytical and strategic skills, with creativity, intuition, and courage, enables them develop supplier partnerships, drive innovation, and advance sustainability. (Kearney, 2022)

ii.High Procurement – Low Innovation: Develop innovation first

"A New technology into an old system result in an expensive old system" (Iske, P., 2017). Leaders must address the imbalance between technological and social innovation—managing, organizing, and collaborating innovatively—by maintaining proficient procurement, while investing in innovation capabilities.

iii. Low procurement – High Innovation: Develop procurement first

In this scenario, procurement's innovativeness lacks real business impact. Leaders should prioritize enhancement of procurement by streamlining processes, negotiating key-supplier contracts, fostering cross-functional collaboration, and investing in procurement technology to support innovation.

iv. Low procurement – Low Innovation: Focus on continuous improvement

Managers should assess the company's strengths and weaknesses, set a three-year plan, and address gaps in both areas with gradual and continuous improvements, training, and culture change. Digitized procurement is essential to reduce time on repetitive tasks and instead focus on more value-added activities.

Merits and Conclusions

Based on literature research, survey answers and interviews this paper contributes

*(i) a model showing emerging different technologies supporting different procurement processes
(ii) a matrix model for CPOs to assess their starting point (procurement and innovation maturity)*

*and from this dependent actions for their digital transformation journey
(iii) success factors for the Roadmap to digital procurement.*

Digital procurement transformation is essential for enhancing efficiency and maintaining competitiveness. This report provides managerial guidance to empower procurement professionals in navigating this shift. As Professor Hermann Simon noted, "*Not everything can be digitized, but everything that can be, will be,*" and AI researcher Max Tegmark emphasized, "*Companies embracing AI will outperform those that do not.*"

Our concluding recommendation: develop a digital transformation roadmap for procurement and your organization, If you won't make it happen, it will happen to you.

Paper topic

3. Purchasing organisation, 11. Digital, 10. Purchasing innovation

Does accuracy matter? Formulation and measurement of environmental criteria for supplier selection in public procurement

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Does accuracy matter? Formulation and measurement of environmental criteria for supplier selection in public procurement

Summary: This paper examines the recent law changes in public procurement in Norway, introducing stricter rules for including and weighing environmental criteria in supplier selection. In 2023 alternative proposals for law changes have been announced, and feedback from various has been collected. We perform a content analysis of the 164 responses to identify the pros and cons related to each alternative, and their relevance for the new law. Further, we conduct a qualitative case study of a road de-icing service procurement to investigate law changes implications from the supplier and buyer perspectives using the paradox theory framework.

Keywords or phrases: public procurement, sustainability, supplier selection

Submission category: Working paper (WP)

Introduction

The Norwegian Public Procurement Law §7-9 introduced a new rule on the 1.January 2024, stating that “the buyer shall weigh climate and environment with at least 30%. Where the buyer presents award criteria in prioritized order, climate and environment ought to be among the three highest prioritized”.

These changes were made effective due to poor compliance (only 40% used environmental criteria in contract award) with existing guidelines to promote environmental procurement to support national climate policy. The Norwegian Agency for Public and Financial Management (DFØ), that has the overall responsibility for development and implementation of green public procurement, also showed that only 50% of public organizations have implemented any low emission and sustainability measures in their procurement activities in 2022.

Several barriers have been identified that prevent public procurers from implementing sustainable public procurement, such as financial constraints, lack of knowledge or motivation lack of accuracy in formulating specifications and criteria (Grandia & Kruyen, 2020). Research has also shown that green public procurement may lead to less competition among suppliers due to increased complexity of the qualification rules and selection criteria, and hence increased price and less effective usage of public resources (Lundberg & Marklund, 2015). It has also been discussed whether environmental criteria for contract award led to environmentally friendly solutions and to selection of the best suppliers, and that minimum environmental requirements for supplier qualification can be more beneficial in some cases. According to Igarashi et al (2015), the so-called environmental demands by public authorities in Norway was put forward through compulsory use of environmental labels, product declaration or other minimum performance standards, requirement for suppliers' certifications according to environmental management system and explicit environmental knowledge requirements. One of the most popular product declarations based on third party verification of life cycle analysis (LCA) is Environmental Product Declaration (EPD), that is created according to certain rules for which life cycle inventories and environmental impact categories, including emission, must be included for each product. Introduction of the new law may lead to a mandatory use of EPD for some purchases, and potential challenges related to emission measurement elaborated below.

Vieira et al (2024) identifies significant issues related to inconsistency and inaccuracy in measurement and management of emissions occurring from internal operations (scope 1 and 2) and sources not owned or controlled by the organisation (scope 3) that are taken for granted by the literature. Some of the challenges are related to the degree of the knowledge of the value chain to derive meaningful environmental measurements from. As Carter et al. (2015) have pointed out, the inability to determine the structure of the value chain and its boundaries is a limitation for elaborating on any related parameter. Despite existence of guidelines assisting in measuring emissions, it is still difficult to define the company's value chain and inventory boundaries for tiers and emission categories to be included, due to for example limited transparency beyond first-tier suppliers and dynamicity of supplier relationships (Vieira et al, 2024). It is not clear how the supply chain complexity, the size of buyer or supplier organization, knowledge level or power balance impacts the scope and accuracy of environmental criteria formulation and measurement. De Stefano and Montes-Sancho (2023) analysed the supply chain complexity and its impact on emission reduction ability, within the frame of organisational information processing theory, assuming that supply chain complexity may have a negative impact on performance. Their study showed that vertical and spatial complexity dimensions increased GHG emissions at the firm and supply chain level. Further, the authors argue that the introduction of written guidelines neutralises the negative effects of vertical complexity on firm and supply chain GHG emissions, however it is not sufficient in the presence of spatial complexity.

The other challenges identified by Vieira et al. (2024) are related to the emission data quality and consistency, as few companies use primary data from suppliers rather than estimations, relying on averaged secondary data and assumptions (such as LCA or emission factors from generic databases), making it also difficult to measure progress towards achieving emission reduction targets. Large volumes

of data for vast supplier bases and the need for continuous monitoring becomes resource-demanding and impractical task. It is not clear if all organizations have competencies and interest in using supplier selection process for formulating relevant environmental criteria and being able to evaluate the responses. Hence, a paradox exists in requirements to formulate and to use relevant selection criteria for the buyers and provision of accurate emissions information by the suppliers. In paradox theory tensions or trade-offs arise between two extremes of a paradox, which often appear incompatible when considered together (Dahlmann et al., 2023). Following the future research recommendations by Vieira et al. (2024), in this paper we aim contributing to the paradox theory: exploring the paradox between the achievement of sustainability goals and the reliability of the environmental criteria formulation (by buyer) and measurement (by supplier) (Dahlmann et al., 2023).

The main research question of this study is: how do the new legislation changes contribute to emission reduction and competition through supplier selection process in public procurement avoiding “greenwashing”? The following sub-questions are included: did the responses on alternative law proposals indicated new potential challenges for suppliers and buyers? What are the specific challenges of emission measurement related to supplier selection process for public buyer and supplier for a specific case after the new law introduction?

Empirical background: alternatives to the new law and responses

The three proposed law alternatives to Norwegian Public Procurement Law included:

1. The procurer shall strive to minimise the environmental burden and promote environmentally friendly solutions through procurement and use environmental requirements and criteria in the procurement process. The environmental criteria shall always weigh at least 30%.
2. Public procurers shall use environmental requirements or criteria in at least one of the following steps in the procurement process: a) qualification requirement; b) requirement specification; c) award criteria; d) terms of contract. In areas with not insignificant environmental impact, environmental considerations must always be weighted at least 30 percent.
3. The procurer must either use environmental performance requirements, or weigh environmental criteria with a minimum of 30 per cent. The use of environmental requirements and weighting of environmental criteria can also be combined.

The summary of the alternative preferences is presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1 Summary of preferences across all parties

Half of the responses supported alternative 3, mostly buyers arguing that stringent rules for weighing climate and environment was seen as potentially reducing the possibility to manage each procurement on its contextual merits. The responses also highlight the complexity of policy goals, technological development and relations to markets, and fear less flexibility. Some responses suggested

that the proposed regulations would be ineffectual unless new tools were developed to operationalize the new requirements into the procurement process.

We will further investigate the responses to identify:

- Barriers not mentioned in the previous research from the buyer and supplier perspective
- New alternatives and reasoning behind those

We'll first perform a review of the research literature and the recommended methods by Norwegian government for public supplier selection process at the tender phase with a focus on supply chain boundaries definitions and complexity parameters. Further, we'll analyse a case study of public service procurement of de-icing service to identify which parameters impact the environmental criteria formulation and measurement, and how.

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Paper topic

13. Public procurement, 5. Supplier selection, 16. Sustainability - environmental

Transition toward digital and sustainable supply chains: a bibliometric analysis

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

The supply chain is transitioning into a more complex and delicate structure because of increasing costs, competition, and fast worldwide technological development. This is one of the main drives for supply chains toward sustainability (Nasiri et al., 2020). In the last two decades, major technological shifts have been observed in the industry, immensely impacting supply chains. Organizations can shift towards digitalization with the help of emerging technologies to have an effective, sustainable supply chain concept and further improve its performance (Gillani et al., 2020). This attracts the researcher's attention in the area of digital and sustainable supply chains. Digital technologies help the transparency and traceability of information and product flow within the supply chain (Garay-Rondero et al., 2020). This research investigates how digital technologies lead to sustainable outcomes throughout the supply chain.

This paper opts for a bibliometric analysis to identify the trend and links between digital and sustainable supply chains by summarizing and mapping 383 Web of Science (WOS) articles until July 2024. Keywords were selected to best present the scenario using WOS. The standard setting was maintained for extracting the dataset, such as articles and English as a language. Only Q1 journal articles were selected to maintain the quality of the study. The study uses the four-stage method: data collection, analysis, visualization, and interpretation using biblioshiny software.

The study identifies blockchain, big data analytics, and additive manufacturing as the most discussed and used technologies in the literature. The descriptive analysis summarized the evolution of the research topic in leading scientific journals and highlighted the use of technologies and different sustainability practices. The publications have significantly increased after 2019. The results allow us to identify the main clusters that lead to in-depth discussion and critical perspectives for future research. Implementing digital technologies in the supply chain tends to improve visibility, information sharing, and processing of high volumes of data, leading to efficient decision-making toward sustainable development. This study shares significant implications for practitioners, suggesting the use of technologies to improve the efficiency and profitability of businesses. Implementing digital technologies helps track, control, and improve operations, which will result in sustainable economic, environmental, and social performance.

Keywords: Digital Transformation, Sustainable Supply Chain Management, Sustainable Performance.

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Paper topic

11. Digital, 16. Sustainability - environmental, 17. Sustainability - social

248

Making the most out of customer-supplier collaboration in the product development process

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Competitive Paper

Abstract/summary

This study examines the role of customer technical capability as a main driving force of two forms of customer-supplier collaboration—customer involvement and knowledge integration between suppliers and customers—and their impact on supplier innovation performance. Findings from an empirical survey of 216 supplier Swedish manufacturing firms reveal that both customer involvement and customer-supplier knowledge integration are driven by customer’s technical capability, and both exert positive influence on supplier innovation performance. Moreover, while the effect of customer technical capability on customer-supplier knowledge integration depends on the supplier’s technical capability, it remains unaffected in the case of customer involvement. This study highlights knowledge as a fundamental aspect of customer-supplier collaboration and emphasize the need for suppliers and customers to align their technical capabilities to maximize their innovation outcomes.

Paper topic

9. Supplier relationships/performance/development

Non-award and efficiency of public procurement procedures in the EU

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Summary

The Tenders Electronic Daily database provides an opportunity to explore the specificities of a variable that has been available and searchable since 2016. The characteristics of invalid LOTs of procedures are the subject of the study. If a LOT is unsuccessful, the contracting authority has administered the procedure unnecessarily and its needs have not been met and it has not been able to fulfil its tasks. Non-award is directly linked to efficiency and to ensuring competition. If the procedure fails, it is necessary to examine the reasons for the failure, which is a waste of resources and a lack of supply. This is what our study aims to contribute to, requiring the construction of a database of its own from a large amount of structured TED data. We expect that the context will also contribute to a clearer understanding and conditions for efficient public procurement.

Acknowledgement: This work was created on the basis of an NKFI commission under project K 137794.

Key words: efficiency, public procurement, competition

Submission category: Academic working paper

Literature review

In public procurement research, structured data analysis is becoming increasingly important for big data analysis (Fazekas and Sanchez, 2021; Prier et al, 2018; Zeisel, 2020). Namely, measuring the performance of public procurement (Flynn, 2018), investigating the specificities of pricing (Placek et al, 2019), analysing the causes of delays (Placek, 2020), and investigating the specificities of voluntary ex ante notices (Prier, 2021), understanding the reasons for the speed of decision (Prier, 2021), analysing the characteristics of year-end spending (McCue et al, 2021) are detailed questions that all contribute to

measuring the effectiveness of public procurement and understanding the conditions for successfully securing competition.

The studies also help to increase transparency (Soylu et al, 2022), as they often highlight data quality issues that would not be revealed without analysis, as data disclosure allows direct access to both the notices and the databases for all.

In this context, the study seeks to identify the causes and correlates of the failures in the process, which have received less attention from researchers to date.

Research method

The TED database contains EU public procurement procedures above the EU thresholds set by EU Directives. Data on these procedures are available in a structured format in two databases. One database contains the contract notices and the other database contains the information notices on the outcome of the procedure (contract award notices). In the course of the work, the two databases were linked, while the so-called long-term procurement methods (framework agreements, dynamic purchasing systems) were excluded. The reason for this is that these procedures have several procedure outcome notices which cannot be managed in the present data structure. Thus, we focus only on procedures that start with a contract notice and end with a contract award notice. Based on the Code Book, the following variable was examined:

INFO_ON_NON_AWARD

As described in the Code Book:

PROCUREMENT_UNSUCCESSFUL means that

"A contract is not awarded", because "No tenders or requests to participate were received or all were rejected"

PROCUREMENT_DISCONTINUED means that "A contract is not awarded" because of "Other reasons (discontinuation of procedure)"

In this research, we are looking for data links in the single database that will help us to understand why the proportion of unsuccessful lots is so high. Since causality cannot be assumed, it is expected that the data relationships will shed light on the more frequent cases of non-award, i.e. the lack of success of a particular part of the procedure.

Unsuccessful LOTS in EU Countries

Based on the TED database, we have data on failed LOTS from 2016. Since a procedure can consist of several LOTS, it is necessary to examine the data at the contract level. The figure below shows that in some countries the proportion of unsuccessful LOTS is very high, 20-30-40% of the total LOTS. This also indicates a high level of wasted resources (time, money, human activity).

Figure 1 – Role of CPBs in the EU (Source: TED database Contract Award Notices)

In fact, when looking at the types of procedures, most of the procedures are completely non-communicative, so that conclusions can be drawn directly between the type of procedures and the lack of success.

Figure 2 Different types or procedures in the EU (Source: TED database Contract Award Notices)

Likewise, the speed of procedures is also examined in relation to unsuccessful LOTs.

Figure 3 Accelerated procedures in the EU (Source: TED database Contract Award Notices)

The other variables that will be examined after the database is completed with 2024 data are:

- country-specific characteristics
- specific characteristics of the object of purchase (goods, works, services)
- contracting authority specific characteristics (classical contracting authority, public service contracting authority).

Conclusion

An effective procurement procedure is characterised by the contracting authority's attention in the preparation and management of the procedure to ensuring competition and the conclusion of a contract that is capable of ensuring successful performance in the future. If the procedure fails, it is necessary to examine the reasons for the failure, which is a waste of resources and a lack of supply. This is what our study aims to contribute to, requiring the construction of a database of its own from a large amount of structured TED data. After 2024, it is possible to examine 9 full years of data and explore the correlations with the failure rates. We expect that the context will also contribute to a clearer understanding and conditions for efficient public procurement.

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Paper topic

13. Public procurement

250

Procurement Performance in Private Equity Companies compared to Listed Companies

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

Abstract

Private equity (PE) ownership has gained prominence due to its focus on financial efficiency and value creation. This study examines whether procurement in PE-backed companies achieves better financial results compared to procurement organizations in publicly listed firms.

Through a structured survey of procurement professionals, with working experience in both fields, the research identifies key differences in procurement strategies, priorities, and success factors. The findings suggest that PE-backed firms emphasize cost efficiency, rapid decision-making, and financial-driven key performance indicators (KPIs), whereas listed firms prioritize long-term supplier relationships, compliance, and risk management.

While PE procurement practices lead to improved short-term financial outcomes, concerns remain about long-term sustainability and supplier stability. This study contributes to the academic dialogue by providing empirical insights into procurement priorities under different ownership structures and their potential impact on driving financial results.

Paper topic

1. Purchasing talent, skills, competences, 3. Purchasing organisation, 2. PSM strategy

251

Developing a perceptual scale for upstream supply chain complexity

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Paper type (competitive, practitioner, working)

Working Paper

Abstract/summary

This ongoing study aims to develop and validate a scale to measure upstream supply chain complexity. While existing studies highlight its importance—arising from supplier relationships and related uncertainties—there remains a lack of validated perceptual measures capturing how managers experience and respond to this complexity. We have defined supply chain complexity and begun generating measurement items. Expert interviews with academics and executives are underway, followed by Q-sorting for content validity. Future steps include pre-testing and large-scale validation. This research will bridge structural complexity indicators with managerial cognition, offering a robust assessment tool.

Paper topic

2. PSM strategy, 15. PSM theory, methodology, education